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Ichthyofauna of India (1758–2024): review, analysis, and annotated checklist

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Abstract

India is well-known for its abundant and varied fish species, a result of its great variety of aquatic environments. The earliest reference to fishes in Indian writing is found in Vedas and Puranas. The taxonomic knowledge on the fishes of India started with the father of taxonomy, Linnaeus in 1758, whose works included many fishes from Indian waters, although others are mistakenly tagged as ‘Habitat in India’. For this review, a total of 958 articles in the literature were used. The compilation of records and resulting analysis of the ichthyofauna of India yielded a total of 3,967 species of fishes belonging to 1,197 genera, 287 families, and 60 orders. Among the various states, Tamilnadu had the highest fish diversity with 1,919 species followed by the Andaman and Nicobar Islands with 1,544 species, and Kerala with 1,202 species. Of the 3,967 species, 2,173 species occur exclusively in marine

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habitats, plus 401 found in both marine and brackish water (and not in fresh water). Only 20 species are limited to brackish waters. In comparison, 1,026 species are restricted to freshwater habitats, plus 125 species found in both fresh and brackish-water habitats. In addition to these, 223 species of euryhaline fishes occupy all three habitats. Overall then, in marine waters a total of 2,797 species can be found; in brackish waters a total of 768 species can be found; and a total of 1,374 species occur in fresh waters. The most diverse fish family in India is Cyprinidae, with 337 species, followed by Gobiidae (250 species) and Sisoridae (148 species). A total of 59 families are monotypic and 204 families are represented by fewer than 10 species. Among the numerous new fish species described from India over more than 250 years of research, currently 1,561 species remain taxonomically valid as of July 2024. A complete list of Indian ichthyofaunal literature citations is presented at the end of the article.

INTRODUCTION

Biodiversity

Biodiversity, also referred to as biological diversity, plays a vital role in the essential processes that support all life on Earth. Biodiversity encompasses the entire range of biotic variation, from genetic diversity to the diversity of entire ecosystems, including humans (Purvis & Hector 2000, Maclaurin & Sterelny 2008). The significance of biodiversity in enabling ecosystem services and essential ecological processes is widely acknowledged (Diaz et al. 2006). The Earth, estimated to be about 4.54 billion years old, has hosted life for at least 3.5 billion years, with the earliest physical evidence of life dating back 3.7 billion years (Dalrymple 2001, Noffke et al. 2013), resulting in the evolution of countless species. Biodiversity's richness stems from genetic variation and encompasses the vast array of species, living forms, and their interactions, all organized in spatial patterns that extend from biological communities to ecosystems, geographic regions, and beyond (Colwell 2009). The Earth teems with an astonishing diversity of life, including millions of different species. Approximately 86% of global biomass exists on land, 13% in the deep subsurface, and only 1% in marine waters (Bar-On et al. 2018). Recent estimates suggest there are around 8.7 million (± 1.3 million) species of living organisms on Earth (Sweetlove 2011), with over 2.2 million (± 0.18 million) species found in marine environments (Mora et al. 2011). It has been estimated that over the past 250 years, about 1.2 million species have been described. Clearly, a huge number of species remain unidentified and undescribed, primarily small organisms and microbes. According to an estimate by Mora et al. (2011), 86% of Earth's species and 91% of marine species are yet to be described. Advances in predictive modelling have significantly narrowed the range of biodiversity estimates, which previously ranged widely from 3 million to 100 million species. This underscores the vast unexplored biodiversity still awaiting discovery (Sweetlove 2011, Catalog of Life 2022). Another contributor to the great variation in these estimates is the subjectivity in defining criteria for species status and the fluid nature of taxonomic classifications. Taxonomic revisions frequently lead to species being split or merged, complicating efforts to confirm total numbers. Additionally, certain taxonomic groups, especially insects, fungi, and microbes, pose significant challenges to any estimates due to their immense diversity, genetic heterogeneity, and limited collections. Bacteria and Archaea contribute significantly to this uncertainty, with estimates ranging from 1 to 6 billion species on Earth, with bacteria estimated as accounting for 70% to 90% of these species (Larsen et al. 2017). According to the State of Observed Species, the current rate of species descriptions is only about 17,000–20,000 new species each year, despite global efforts to catalogue new species (Banerjee et al. 2024).

As a tropical country, India is especially rich in biodiversity. Although it covers only 2.4% of the world's land area, India exhibits a vast range of ecosystems, species, and genetic diversity. India is one of the 18 "megadiverse" countries globally, following a construct by Dr. Russell Mittermeier which led to the independent creation of a "Like-minded Group of Megadiverse Countries" within the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), and is home to 4 of the world's 36 declared biodiversity hotspots (Venkataraman & Sivaperuman 2018): the Himalayas, Indo-Burma, the Western Ghats, and the Sundarbans. Additionally, India accounts for approximately 8% of the world's recorded plant species and 6.5% of its animal species. As of December, 2023, India has been documented to contain 104,561 animal species. From 2014 to 2023, 4,875 species have been discovered in Indian fauna, including 3,516 new species and 1,359 new records (Banerjee et al. 2024).

Global fish diversity

Fish are ectothermic aquatic vertebrates that occupy virtually all water habitats, such as oceans, rivers, lakes, canals, reservoirs, and estuaries. There are around 54,711 species of fish globally, making up more than half of all vertebrate species (Nelson 2006). The Catalog of Fishes enumerates 37,245 valid fish species worldwide, including 18,990 valid fish species with the tag ‘Habitat: freshwater’ (Fricke et al. 2025). Available taxonomic species names total 62,063 and genera count is 5,280 (Catalog of Fishes 2024).

Fishes have considerable importance to humans. For a long time, most societies have relied on them as a fundamental part of their food supply. However, excessive fishing has caused a great decrease in the population of many species, with the paradigm being the Atlantic Cod (*Gadus morhua*), which was on the verge of becoming commercially extinct in the Western North Atlantic. Fish products serve as a significant global protein source and provide essential elements, including long-chain omega-3 fatty acids and micronutrients relatively difficult to get from other dietary sources, such as iodine, selenium, calcium, iron, and zinc (FAO 2024). Currently, fishes comprise a major part of the economies of many countries, as well as offering substantial recreational and psychological benefits to naturalists, sportsmen, and home aquarists.

The vast majority of fish species are exclusively either freshwater or marine for their entire lifespan. Nevertheless, more than 225 species exhibit diadromy, a phenomenon in which they inhabit both freshwater and saltwater environments at different stages of life. Of these, most are anadromous, reproducing in freshwater but spending much of their life in the sea. A few fishes are catadromous, reproducing in the ocean but migrating back to their native freshwater habitats. Many fishes defy simple categorization as denizens of marine, diadromous, estuarine, or freshwater habitats. Higher order taxa can be heterogeneous, with some predominantly marine-fish families including species found only in freshwater habitats, or a variety of strategies, such as anadromous or catadromous species or those specializing in brackish-water habitats. Approximately 33% of the 555 fish families have at least one species that inhabits freshwater for a portion of its life cycle (Nelson et al. 2016).

The tropics have the greatest diversity of fish species, in both freshwater and marine habitats, with a steady decline towards polar regions. However, abundance does not follow the same pattern, with temperate fishes often exhibiting the greatest population size. For freshwater fishes, tropical Africa, Southeast Asia, and the Amazon Basin are by far the most diverse. Of the 85 orders and 536 families of fish according to the current categorization, around two-thirds of the species in the major families are freshwater, despite the fact that only about 43% of all species primarily live in freshwater habitats (Nelson et al. 2016). Freshwater ecosystems occupy a relatively tiny part of the Earth’s surface water, but have a disproportionately large number of species. The number of species in freshwater is greater than the number in marine waters, with roughly 15,200 species compared to around 14,800 species in marine habitats (Manel et al. 2020). Similarly, the most species of marine fishes are limited to coastal habitats less than 200 meters deep, which make up less than 1% of the total sea-surface area worldwide. In all cases, the number of species diminishes sharply as temperature declines on a wide regional scale. These numbers show that variation in ecosystem productivity, climatic and temperature conditions, and habitat connectivity and complexity interact to determine the number of fish species in any particular habitat or region (Manel et al. 2020).

Fish diversity in India

India is well known for its abundant and varied fish species, a result of its great diversity of aquatic environments. There are, in India’s rivers, lakes, ponds, reservoirs, and wetlands, around 2,443 species of fish. Some of these species are endemic to certain river systems or locations (Eschmeyer & Fong 2017). Significant biodiversity is found in major river systems such as the Ganges, Brahmaputra, Indus, Godavari, and Krishna rivers. The Western Ghats, which is considered one of the 8 areas with the highest biodiversity, have a significant number of endemic freshwater fish species. Thus far, there have been over 290 species identified, and more than 30% of them are found alone in this region (Dahanukar et al. 2011). India’s marine waters, which include the Arabian Sea, Bay of Bengal, and Indian Ocean, sustain a wide range of marine fish species. The waters have been found to have over 2,500 species of marine fish (CMFRI 2020). The marine biodiversity of the Andaman and Nicobar Islands and the Lakshadweep Archipelago is especially notable due to their coral reefs. Despite their lesser size compared to other coral reef systems worldwide, these reefs support a diverse array of fish species, including economically valuable ones like as groupers, snappers, and parrotfish. India’s estuary environments, including the Sundarbans, Chilika Lake, and the backwaters of Kerala, provide a substantial contribution to the country’s fish diversity. These

ecosystems include a combination of freshwater and marine organisms that have evolved to tolerate different degrees of salinity. Chilika Lake, the biggest brackish-water lagoon in Asia, has around 317 different kinds of fish (Mohanty et al. 2014). The Sunderbans, which is the biggest expanse of mangroves in the world, is home to around 414 species of fish (Sen & Sreeraj 2023).

Fishes in ancient Indian culture

Ancient cultural and many religious beliefs have emphasized and practiced conservation and protection of species and ecosystems. Ancient civilizations in India have respected nature in all its aspects. All of the sacred Hindu books like Mahabharata, Ramayana, Vedas, Upanishads, Bhagavad Gita, Puranas, and Smriti reflect on the conservation of the environment and the maintenance of ecological balance. The earliest reference to fishes in Indian writing is found in Vedas and Puranas. The belief of “Dashavatara”, i.e. the 10 incarnations of a primary Hindu god Vishnu, starts with the Matsya (Fish). In this incarnation, Lord Vishnu is believed to have saved the first human on Earth by warning him of the disastrous floods that were to follow (Gupta et al. 2016). In the Vedas and Puranas, the warrior fish slays the demon Hayagriva, who stole the Vedas and hid them in the ocean. The story follows the journey of a tiny carp from a small pot to the Ganges and eventually to the Ocean (Kumari et al. 2023). The cultural significance of fishes in the Indian context is underlined by first reference of sexual dimorphism comes from Panini (Bagchi & Jha 2011). References to the importance of fish as a source of food are found in Kautilya’s Arthashastra as early as 300 BC (Hora 1948). Notably, the edict on the second pillar of King Ashoka implies a prohibition on consumption of fish during a certain lunar period, which Hora (1950) interpreted as being based on principles of conservation of natural resources (Gopi & Mishra 2015). It is no surprise that in India, fish have been concurrently used as food, as talismans, as symbols of fortune, as subjects in art and sculpture, and as an integral part of literature and folksongs of traditional Indian culture.

REVIEW OF INDIAN ICHTHYOFAUNA

Early taxonomic studies on Indian fishes (1758–1899)

The taxonomic knowledge on the fishes of India started with the pioneer work of the “Father of Taxonomy” – Carolus Linnaeus. Some species described by Linnaeus (1758) were from Indian waters, although many of his listings are erroneously tagged with ‘Habitat in India’. Currently 9 species described by Linnaeus remain valid with a type locality from India. The work of Bloch & Schneider (1801) included many species from India, and, along with a few from the earlier work of M.E. Bloch (1786, 1787, 1790, 1792, 1793, 1794, 1795), added a number of additional species to the Indian ichthyofauna. The first comprehensive work focusing on Indian fishes was by Russell (1803), whose pioneering work included the description of 200 fishes from one ‘locality’, Vizagapatnam in India. Since his work on documenting species was not strictly conforming to binomial practice, most of his illustrations were later used by several other authors to describe many species (Gopi & Mishra 2015). The most significant early work on the taxonomy, using binomial nomenclature, of Indian fishes was by Francis Hamilton-Buchanan (1822) on the fishes of River Ganges and its branches, in which he included more than 300 fishes, and described as many as 235 species of marine, brackish, and freshwater fishes. To date, 172 species described in his work remain valid. Further additions to knowledge of fishes of the East Indian region were provided by the works of McClelland (1839, 1844). During the same period, Cuvier & Valenciennes (1835, 1844) discussed the natural history of many fish groups (in particular, scombroids, *Taenioides*, atherinids, and cyprinids) from various regions of India.

Heckel (1838) was the first to describe the fishes of the Indian Himalaya region, mainly from the Kashmir area. Colonel Sykes (1839) worked on the fishes of the Deccan, describing many new records from the tributaries of the rivers Krishna and Godavari. As many as 26 species described by him remain valid. Between 1828 and 1848, Valenciennes worked on the fishes of Indian waters, describing as many as 75 currently valid species. Jerdon (1849) catalogued many fishes, primarily carps, from southern India, specifically in the Carnatic, Mysore, and Malabar regions. As many as 25 species described by him remain valid.

The period from about 1825 to about 1895, especially the mid-1800s, was a time of the great worldwide marine expeditions by Europeans, by such ichthyologists as Cuvier and Valenciennes, Sir F. Day, and A.W. Alcock, producing high points in new marine-species descriptions. Cuvier & Valenciennes (1828–1849) described 70

nominal species of fish from the marine waters of Pondicherry, now known as Puducherry, according to Krishnan & Mishra (2004). *The Fishes of India by Day* (1875–77, 1888), a monumental treatise on fishes of the region, still continues to be a valuable reference work. Subsequently, Alcock (1889, 1890) described 162 new fish species from the seas of India.

Fish taxonomy studies in India in the last century (1900–1999)

Taxonomic studies in India from 1900 to 1999 yielded significant contributions to the understanding and classification of fish species, focusing both on freshwater and marine ecosystems. Some notable works on fishes, such as the series on *The Fishes of Indo-Australian Archipelago* (Weber & de Beaufort 1916–1936, de Beaufort 1940, de Beaufort & Chapman 1951, Koumans 1953, de Beaufort & Briggs 1962), have considerably strengthened our knowledge of these fishes.

The work done during 1900–1999 laid a strong foundation for modern fish taxonomy in India, and many of the findings during this period remain critical to understanding the country's aquatic biodiversity. The period also saw the establishment of important research institutions and the publication of reference texts that are fundamental to ecologists and ichthyologists today. Lloyd (1909) was the first major taxonomic study from the century, describing extensive deepsea fish collections by the Indian Marine Survey Ship *Investigator*, resulting in the description of 5 new genera and 19 new species of fishes. Another notable early contribution during this period is by Annandale, who, in 1912, described a number of new species of freshwater fishes from North India. This work was pivotal as it expanded the known diversity of Indian freshwater fish and provided essential descriptions providing a basis for future taxonomic research (Chaudhuri 1912). Notably, in addition to taxonomy, Annandale highlighted the ecological significance of these species. Around the same period, Jenkins (1910) also described new species of fishes from India and Persia, providing a comparative perspective on fish species across regional boundaries, emphasizing the interconnectedness of aquatic ecosystems in India and Persia. Subsequently, Chaudhuri (1913) in the “Abor expedition” described a new genus and three new species from the sub-Himalayan region. Sunder Lal Hora was one of the more prominent ichthyologists of this era and is known for his “Satpura Hypothesis”, which explained the distribution of fish species across the Indian subcontinent. His research primarily focused on freshwater fishes and were published over a long career between 1921 and 1950 (Hora 1921, 1938, 1950). In 1921, he published a notable work on Indian cyprinoid fishes of the genus *Garra*, providing detailed descriptions and notes on related species from other countries (Hora 1921). This project not only expanded the taxonomic coverage of Indian freshwater fishes but also facilitated comparisons with global patterns of diversity. In addition, his collaboration with Mukerji led to the identification of two new species of cyprinid fishes from Deolali, Nasik District, Bombay Presidency (Hora & Mukerji 1935). Such studies were critical to establishing a comprehensive inventory of regional fish species, essential for conservation and management decisions.

One of the notable contributions during this time was by Das, who published several important papers on the bionomics of air-breathing fishes in India, detailing the adaptations of certain freshwater fish species, such as *Heteropneustes fossilis*, which are known for their ability to breathe air and venture onto land (Das 1928). This research provided insights into the ecological roles of these species and their adaptations to varying environmental conditions, highlighting the importance of understanding fish biology in the context of their habitats. In 1934, he further explored the structural adaptations to air-breathing of the fish *Pseudapocryptes lanceolatus*, commonly found in the estuaries of the Ganges. His findings emphasized the evolutionary significance of adaptations for air-breathing, contributing to the understanding how fishes evolve to exploit diverse ecological niches (Das & MacBride 1934). A subsequent notable contribution is Koumans (1941, 1953), who described the lesser-known gobioid fauna from the Indian region.

A particularly important contribution during this period was the work of K.P. Jayaram, who has published extensively on the freshwater fishes of India over many decades. His comprehensive book, *The Freshwater Fishes of India*, first published in 1974 and revised and expanded multiple times since then, provided detailed descriptions of numerous species, including their distribution, ecology, and taxonomy. This book was initially instrumental in consolidating the knowledge at the time and continues to serve as a valuable reference for Indian ichthyology. His systematic approach helped clarify the classification of various fish species and contributed to the identification of new taxa.

Later studies on soles and stonefish by Rama Rao reviewed these taxa in India (Rama-Rao 1967, Eschmeyer & Rama Rao 1973). P.K. Talwar, another eminent researcher during the last part of the century, is remembered for his notable contributions, including as a coauthor of *Francis Day (1829–1889) and His Collections of Indian Fishes*, published in 1979, which highlights the historical significance of Francis Day's work for Indian ichthyology. Talwar (1972) additionally contributed insights on sciaenids of India in his article *A neotype and 2 topotypes for *Bola chaptis* Hamilton, 1822 (Pisces, Sciaenidae)*, which provided critical taxonomic insights into the family Sciaenidae by identifying and classifying the well-preserved specimens collected from the Hooghly Estuary, contributing to a better understanding of the species' distribution and taxonomy. Talwar (1973, 1974, 1976, 1981), Talwar & Sathiarajan (1975), Talwar & Mukherjee (1977), Talwar & Kacker (1984) are some of his important contributions.

The early 20th century also saw the establishment of institutions dedicated to the study of natural history, which played a crucial role in advancing fish taxonomy. The Zoological Survey of India, founded in 1916, became a key institution for conducting systematic studies on the country's fauna, including the fishes. This institution facilitated the collection and classification of fish specimens, contributing to a comprehensive database of Indian fish species (Nair & Kumar 2018). The Central Marine Fisheries Research Institute (CMFRI), established in 1947, has played a key role in this area (Pillai 2003). The establishment of the Central Institute of Fisheries Technology (CIFT) in 1957 and the continued support of the Zoological Survey of India has subsequently played a vital role in advancing research on fisheries and fish taxonomy (Jones 1968). More recently, the establishment of the National Bureau of Fish Genetic Resources (NBFGR) in 1983 marked a significant milestone in the conservation and management of fish diversity in India. The aim of the NBFGR was to document and preserve genetic resources of Indian fishes, facilitating research on biodiversity and contributing to sustainable fisheries management (Das & Chidamparam 1989).

The modern era of fish taxonomy in India (2000–2024)

The decade from 2000 to 2010 was pivotal for advancements in the study of fish diversity and taxonomy in India, focusing primarily on the freshwater fauna. This period witnessed an intensive effort to document the rich ichthyofauna across various states and regions, particularly in biodiversity hotspots such as the Western Ghats and the Ganga basin. One of the key contributions during this period was made by Dahanukar et al. (2003), who provided a comprehensive overview of the distribution, degree of endemism, and status of threats for the freshwater fishes of the Western Ghats. Their study underscored the region's exceptional biodiversity, highlighting the presence of numerous vulnerable endemic species that are increasingly threatened by habitat degradation and anthropogenic pressures. This work emphasized the necessity of targeted conservation efforts to preserve the unique ichthyological heritage of the area.

Raghavan et al. (2008) documented the fish fauna of the Chalakudy River, assessing species richness and the threats faced by these fish populations. Their findings contributed to the broader discourse on biodiversity conservation in freshwater ecosystems, elucidating the role of habitat integrity in shaping fish diversity and community dynamics. Further enriching the taxonomic knowledge for northeastern India, Kar & Sen (2007) compiled a systematic list and reported the distribution of fishes in the region. Their documentation of the ichthyofauna of Mizoram, Tripura, and the Barak drainage highlighted the diversity present in these less-studied areas, establishing baseline data critical for guiding future research and conservation efforts. Sarkar et al. (2009) assessed the biodiversity and conservation priorities for the Gomti River, a tributary of the Ganga, emphasizing the urgent need for conservation strategies to protect these aquatic resources from pollution and habitat loss, particularly in light of India's growing challenges related to freshwater resource management. Lakra et al. (2010) focused on the fish diversity and habitat ecology of the River Betwa, revealing a rich assemblage of fish species. Their findings emphasized the correlation between fish species richness and hydrological attributes, crucial for effective management and conservation strategies. Bhat (2005) studied the eco-morphological correlates for tropical stream fishes of southern India, emphasizing the relationships between fish morphology and habitat utilization, providing valuable insights into how environmental gradients influence fish diversity and community structure, essential for effective conservation measures. Aditya et al. (2010) studied fish species assemblages in rice fields in West Bengal revealing the high diversity of fish species in these agro-ecosystems and underscoring

the importance of rice fields as habitats for various fish species, suggesting that agricultural practices can play a role in supporting fish diversity and supporting the integration of biodiversity conservation with agricultural policies and practices. Mohapatra et al. (2007) explored fisheries enhancements and biodiversity in the Chilika Lagoon, demonstrating the interconnectedness of hydrological interventions and fish diversity, including new records of fish species following hydrological changes, underscoring the dynamic nature of aquatic ecosystems and the importance of adaptive management strategies. For saltwater fishes, Ramakrishna et al. (2010) reported as many as 83 species of coral reef fishes recorded for the first time from India. This was the first report of such a large number of fishes from the coral-reef environment from India. Throughout this decade, several prominent ichthyologists, including Arunkumar Laifrakpam, Vishwanath Waikhom, Laishram Kosygin, Heok Hee Ng, and Muthukumarasamy Arunachalam, made substantial contributions to the understanding of freshwater ichthyofaunal diversity in India. Their collective efforts have played a crucial role in advancing the field and addressing the challenges faced by freshwater ecosystems (Director 2010, Ramakrishna 2009).

Between 2011 and 2020, the study of fish diversity and taxonomy in India witnessed significant advancements, driven by the contributions of various researchers. This period was marked by the discovery of numerous new species and the documentation of previously unrecorded fish populations. A combination of traditional taxonomic studies, molecular techniques such as DNA barcoding, and ecological assessments, collectively enhanced the understanding of India's rich ichthyofauna. One of the notable contributions during this period was the work by Lakra et al. (2015) on DNA barcoding of Indian freshwater fishes. This study provided a systematic approach to species identification and revealed cryptic diversity among fish populations. He documented 157 species of freshwater fishes, significantly improving taxonomic resolution and facilitating the identification of species that were previously misclassified or unknown. The molecular approach employed in this research has become increasingly important in fish taxonomy, allowing for more accurate species identification and the contributing to the discovery of new species. Biswas et al. (2014) studied fish assemblages along the Kalpakkam coast of Tamil Nadu, documenting a total of 244 fish species, including 11 new records for the Tamil Nadu coast, and revealed the influence of monsoonal patterns on species richness and distribution. Singh et al. (2014) investigated the impacts of invasive-fish species on the fishery dynamics of the Yamuna River revealing declines in native fish populations and underscoring the need for management strategies to mitigate these impacts. Nagpure et al. (2012) established the Fish Barcode Information System (FBIS), developing a comprehensive DNA-barcode database that facilitates the identification of fish species and is essential for tracking species diversity and implementing effective conservation measures. Kumar et al. (2018) reported 4 new species of deep-sea chondrichthyans from Andaman waters and updated the checklist of chondrichthyans, including species that had not been previously recorded in the Indian Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ). Chakraborty et al. (2020) studied the ichthyofauna of the Sunderbans, documenting 62 species of fishes and emphasizing the relationship between hydrological features and fish diversity and exploring how environmental factors influence fish assemblages in this ecologically sensitive region, highlighting the need for integrated management approaches that consider both biodiversity and habitat conservation. Hoque et al. (2023) documented a total of 45 fish species in the River Padma at Murshidabad, West Bengal, including many Cypriniformes, and emphasized the urgent need for conservation efforts due to threats posed by habitat degradation and pollution. Rose & Rathore (2023) identified 32 fish species in Ana Sagar Lake in Ajmer, Rajasthan, including commercially important species such as Catla (*Catla catla*) and *Oreochromis mossambicus*, providing valuable insights into the dynamics of fish populations in the lake and underscored the importance of sustainable management practices and implementing effective conservation strategies. Parmar et al. (2022) recorded 78 fish species along the Sikka Coast in the Gulf of Kachchh, Gujarat, and emphasized the ecological significance of mixed-stock fisheries, which can help mitigate the risks of over-exploitation of target stocks. Durairaja et al. (2022) provided an annotated checklist of the ichthyofauna in the Potamon zone of the Thamirabarani River in South India, documenting 56 fish species, with 72% categorized as Least Concern and 5% classified as Endangered on the IUCN Red List, highlighting the conservation challenges in freshwater ecosystems. Ray et al. (2023) studied the stock status of small indigenous fish species in the River Ganga, one of India's most important river systems, revealing that the river supports a diverse ecosystem with 190 species of finfish, of which 42 are significant for commercial use. Karthik & Rajakumar (2023) identified 66 fish species along the Nagapattinam Coast in Tamil Nadu, emphasizing the importance of fish diversity management in coastal environments. Sreeraj & Sen (2021), Sreeraj et al. (2022, 2023) and Ragul et al. (2024) documented several new

records of gobioid fishes from Indian waters, increasing the known gobioid diversity along the Indian coast.

During the modern era of ichthyological research in India, most studies have been based on non-targeted collections or accidental findings. There has been relatively few researcher groups or laboratories who focus on particular groups of fishes. Among these, the renowned fish taxonomist this decade is Anil Mahapatra and team, who have specialized in the study of eels (Anguilliformes) in India, contributing significantly to the understanding of eel biodiversity, taxonomy, and conservation (Chandra et al. 2021, Banerjee et al. 2022, 2023, 2024). Sreeraj C.R. and team have focused mainly on coral-reef and mangrove fishes, reporting more than 135 new records for India, while Vishwanath, W. and team from northeast India have focused mainly on freshwater fishes in the region. Many other researchers have recently made significant contributions to the field, including well-known freshwater ichthyologists such as Heok Hee Ng, Ralf Britz, Achom Darshan, Yumnam Lokeshwor, Laishram Kosygin, Mathews Plamoottil, Lalram liana, Neelesh Dahanukar, J D, Marcus Knight, and marine ichthyologists including Akhilesh K.V., Bineesh K.K., Praveenraj, J., Subhrendu Sekhar Mishra, Dipanjan Ray, Barman R.P., Rajan P.T., Ragul and Kodeeswaran Paramasivam (Chandra et al. 2021, Banerjee et al. 2022, 2023, 2024).

The contributions of many researchers during 2000–2024 have significantly advanced the understanding of fish diversity and taxonomy in India. Through systematic documentation, ecological assessments, and molecular techniques, these studies have laid the groundwork for ongoing efforts to protect and manage the country's diverse fish populations. The collaborative nature of this research underscores the importance of interdisciplinary approaches in addressing the challenges facing freshwater and marine ecosystems in India.

Prior reviews of the fish diversity of India

Day (1889) was the pioneer in compiling a comprehensive listing in his *Fishes of British India*, documenting 1,418 species in 342 genera, encompassing both freshwater and marine fishes. For the specific region Lakshadweep, *Fishes of the Laccadive Archipelago* by Jones & Kumaran (1980) is highly regarded for its extensive focus on marine-fish species in the waters surrounding these islands. Talwar & Kacker (1984) contributed significantly to the knowledge of important food fishes with their illustrated account *Commercial Sea Fishes of India*, covering 548 species within 89 families. The *FAO Species-Identification Sheets for Fishery Purposes—Western Indian Ocean* (Fischer & Bianchi 1984) also serves as an excellent resource for marine-fish studies and fisheries professionals. For freshwater fishes, *Inland Fishes of India and Adjacent Countries* by Talwar & Jhingran (1992), and A.G.K. Menon's *Check List—Fresh Water Fishes of India* (Menon 1999) and Jayaram's (2010) *The Freshwater Fishes of the Indian Region* (Jayaram 2010) are invaluable resources for taxonomists, ecologists, conservationists, and policymakers concerned with freshwater aquatic biodiversity, conservation, and fisheries management. The comprehensive coverage of inland-fish species, coupled with detailed ecological and economic analyses, makes these foundational texts for understanding the complexities of freshwater ecosystems in South Asia. These books not only serve as references for identification and classification, but also a call to action for sustainable management and conservation of these vital aquatic resources (Talwar & Jhingran 1992, Menon 1999, Jayaram 2010).

The Zoological Survey of India published the *State Fauna Series*, based on extensive surveys and literature reviews, listing fish species found throughout the marine and estuarine waters of various Indian maritime states. These include Lakshadweep (Rao 1991), West Bengal (Talwar et al. 1992), Gujarat (Barman et al. 2000), Puducherry (Mishra & Krishnan 2003), Andhra Pradesh (Barman et al. 2004), Odisha (Barman et al. 2007), Tamil Nadu (Barman et al. 2011), Maharashtra (Barman et al. 2012), and Karnataka (Barman et al. 2013). Among other more recent contributions, there is a checklist of 667 native freshwater fish species by Rema Devi & Indra (2012); an updated checklist of 1,434 fishes from the Andaman and Nicobar Islands by Rajan et al. (2013); a list of 905 species from Kerala by Bijukumar & Raghavan (2015); and a list of 370 species from the Sundarbans by Mishra & Gopi (2017). Most recently, Rajendra (2018) and Bineesh et al. (2018) provided lists of 1,542 marine and 34 freshwater fishes from the Andaman and Nicobar Islands. Mishra et al. (2019) documented 659 species from India's mangrove habitats, while Mohapatra et al. (2020) listed 1,905 species from the Indian marine coasts. Rajan et al. (2021) updated the list of 856 fish species from the Lakshadweep Archipelago, and Sreeraj & Sen (2024) compiled a list of 258 gobioid fishes across India. Notably, some recent checklists suffer from an absence of references for each occurrence, and often a lack of details on the examined material. As a result, we attempted here to compile the list of species of all fishes occurring in the Indian subcontinent with proper support of the literature, producing our review of the complete ichthyofauna of India.

METHODOLOGY

We present here a compilation of all reports of the fishes from the Indian sub-continent with their taxonomic status and corrections in nomenclature to date, in addition documenting their distribution in various regions and habitats of India; this complete review has not been attempted before in the available literature. In terms of fresh water, India is bestowed with 12 major rivers with their various tributaries and distributaries, including numerous minor rivers (Fig. 1). There are also vast regions of wetlands, ponds, lakes and other aquatic habitats. All variations of marine habitats are present, including mangroves, coral reefs, brackish-water habitats, seagrass ecosystems, open seas, deep seas to the abyss. For the preparation of the checklist of Indian fishes, we started with the *State Fauna Series* of the Zoological Survey of India. A reverse search was used to compile the old literature and other reports. Online articles have been accessed through Google search, Google Scholar, ResearchGate, the Biodiversity Heritage Library, etc. Books and other old articles which have not been published online have been accessed from the Zoological Survey of India and the Central Library, Kolkata. Some distribution data has been listed in the checklist from preprints of various authors' original work. Taxonomic status and accepted nomenclature and classification for follows the Catalog of Fishes (Fricke et al. 2024). The habitat categorizations for the species were confirmed from the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS 2024) and FishBase (Froese & Pauly 2024). The type locality details are provided only for those species described from India. The list of the fishes in Table 1 follows alphabetical order among the various class, orders, and families. For the analysis of the ichthyofaunal distribution Primer Version 6 (Clarke & Warwick 2001) and PAST ver. 3.03 (Hammer et al. 2001) were used.

Fig. 1. The major river systems and offshore archipelagos of India (map not to scale).

RESULTS

During this study a total of 958 articles were used to compile fish data from India. The compilation of records and resulting analysis of the ichthyofauna of India yielded a total of 3,967 species of fishes belonging to 1,197 genera, 287 families, and 60 orders. Among the various states, Tamilnadu had the highest fish diversity with 1,919 species followed by the Andaman and Nicobar Islands with 1,544 species, and Kerala with 1,202 species (Fig. 2). Of the 3,967 species, 2,173 species occur exclusively in marine habitats, plus 401 found in both marine and brackish water (and not in fresh water). Only 20 species are limited only to brackish waters. In comparison, 1,026 species are restricted to freshwater habitats, plus 125 species found in both fresh and brackish-water habitats. In addition to these, 223 species of euryhaline fishes occupy all three habitats (Fig. 3). Overall then, in marine waters a total of 2,797 species can be found; in brackish waters a total of 768 species can be found; and a total of 1,374 species occur in fresh waters.

Fig. 2. Map showing the total numbers of fish species found in each of the states of India.

Fig. 3. Venn diagram of numbers of fishes in each habitat category for the fishes of India.

A list of the families and genera reported from India are given in Table 1 (presented at the end of the text section). The most speciose family of fishes in India is Cyprinidae with 337 species, followed by Gobiidae (250 species) and Sisoridae (148 species). A total of 59 families are monotypic and 204 families are represented by fewer than 10 species.

A detailed list of the total number of fish species occurring in various habitats in the states of India is given in Table 2. From the list, it is evident that exclusively marine fishes have the highest total from Tamilnadu (1,189 species), followed by Andaman and Nicobar Islands (1,105 species). Exclusively freshwater fishes have the highest total number of species from West Bengal (239 species) followed by Arunachal Pradesh (215 species) and Manipur (214 species) and the fewest from Lakshadweep Islands (7 species) and Andaman and Nicobar Islands (14 species).

Two interesting records are the presence of a single brackish-water species, *Etroplus suratensis* (Bloch, 1790), in landlocked Telengana state, which might have either travelled upward through the river Godavari or might have been transported from brackish areas downstream. Similarly, the presence of *Strongylura strongylura* (Van Hasselt, 1823) from the landlocked state of Tripura might also be transported via fishing activity in the rivers and streams of the region or potential upstream movement by the species.

During the past 250 years of ichthyofaunal research in India, many new species have been described from India. Over the years, most families and genera have expanded with newly described species. However, some species have been synonymized while new ones are described. Nonetheless, a net increase in valid species every year suggests that there are still many new discoveries and new records to be found in the diverse habitats and environments found in our marine and freshwater ecosystems. Among the numerous new species described over more than 250 years of research, 1,561 species remain valid species as of July 2024. Reviewing the trend of

TABLE 2

Numbers of fish species in various habitat categories in the states of India

(F= freshwater, B= brackish water, M= marine)

	total fishes	freshwater		brackish	marine		euryaline
		F	BF	B	MB	M	MBF
Andaman & Nicobar Islands	1544	14	37	1	245	1105	142
Lakshadweep Islands	929	7	12	2	141	727	40
Tamilnadu	1919	161	77	9	316	1189	167
West Bengal	940	239	74	4	204	290	129
Odisha	890	130	70	9	219	314	148
Andhra Pradesh	891	102	52	11	215	396	115
Kerala	1202	197	52	6	216	607	124
Karnataka	802	186	47	1	186	285	97
Goa	320	33	31	1	100	87	68
Maharashtra	879	165	54	1	202	348	109
Gujarat	617	70	41	0	164	259	83
Ladakh	21	21	0	0	0	0	0
Jammu and Kashmir	28	26	2	0	0	0	0
Himachal Pradesh	80	61	18	0	0	0	1
Punjab	61	38	23	0	0	0	0
Uttarakhand	126	91	33	0	0	0	2
Haryana	51	28	22	0	0	0	1
Delhi	84	51	31	0	0	0	2
Uttar Pradesh	82	50	30	0	0	0	2
Rajasthan	78	50	26	0	0	0	2
Madhya Pradesh	163	116	43	0	0	0	4
Telangana	163	110	44	1	0	0	8
Chhattisgarh	89	55	33	0	0	0	1
Bihar	82	52	29	0	0	0	1
Jharkhand	71	37	32	0	0	0	2
Sikkim	62	52	10	0	0	0	0
Assam	219	176	38	0	0	0	5
Meghalaya	165	129	35	0	0	0	1
Arunachal Pradesh	251	217	32	0	0	0	2
Nagaland	81	59	21	0	0	0	1
Manipur	247	214	27	0	0	0	6
Mizoram	146	127	15	0	0	0	4
Tripura	140	93	38	0	1	0	8

Fig. 4. Historical species-accumulation curve for newly described fish species from India.

taxonomic research in India, it is evident that there were many golden periods with sharp increases in species described (Fig. 4). The initial surge is by the pioneering work of Hamilton (1822). Subsequently, Valenciennes, Sykes, and Jerdon described numerous species between 1828–1849. Alcock added a set of species between 1889 and 1899 and then there was a gradual increase in the number of newly described species with a surge after 2010 by various authors, in part a result of recent developments in molecular taxonomy studies. A temporal analysis of the newly described species shows two peaks of species descriptions, during 1800–1849 and then 2000–2024 (Fig. 5). Specifically, from 2010 to 2024, a total of 401 fish species were described from India. Hence it is evident

Fig. 5. Historical period totals of newly described fish species from India.

Fig. 6. Cluster Analysis for the ichthyofaunal diversity for the coastal and island states of India.

Fig. 7. Cluster Analysis for the ichthyofaunal diversity of the landlocked states of India.

Fig. 8. Two-way Principal Component Analysis (PCA) for the ichthyofaunal diversity of the states of India.

that after two centuries, the current rate of new additions to the ichthyofauna of India has reached a peak, with numerous new discoveries and many new species in the process of being described.

Based on the presence and absence of species across various states in India, cluster analysis was carried out among the coastal and island states, as well as for landlocked states. For the analysis, similarity was calculated based on the presence and absence of species, and thus similarity indices were calculated based on Euclidean distance. Among the coastal and island states, the first clusters were formed at a distance of 450: Andaman and Nicobar Islands and Tamilnadu formed the first cluster, having almost the same species structure. Both states have higher species diversity and both have species from all habitats such as coral reef, seagrass, deepsea, brackish water, and mangrove ecosystems, as well as freshwater streams and ponds. The second cluster was formed by Kerala and Lakshadweep, likely caused by species similarity due to proximity. Among other states, Gujarat and Goa were distinct due to the absence of many species that occur in the same habitat in other locations (Fig. 6).

Among the landlocked states of India, the analysis showed that there is little variation among states, with a cluster formed by Manipur, Assam, and Arunachal Pradesh. Mizoram differed from the others. A major driver of this pattern was the presence of many endemic freshwater species (Fig. 7).

Two-way Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was carried out between the various states of India and different categories of aquatic habitats. It showed that the Lakshadweep Islands, as well as Andaman and Nicobar Islands, are distinct due to the marine ichthyofauna. States such as Arunachal Pradesh, Manipur, Assam, as well as Kerala, show similarity mainly because of freshwater ichthyofauna. Andhra Pradesh and Odisha were distinct because of the higher proportion of marine fishes which also occur in brackish waters (Fig. 8).

DISCUSSION

The global distribution of fish species is a complex and multifaceted topic, with significant variation across different countries and regions. The total number of fish species worldwide is estimated to be over 37,245, which includes both freshwater and marine species. Among these, freshwater fish constitute a substantial portion, with estimates suggesting that there are more than 18,990 named freshwater fish species, accounting for approximately

50% of global fish biodiversity (Fricke et al. 2025). This high level of diversity is attributed to various factors, including geographical isolation, habitat variability, and evolutionary processes (Phang et al. 2019). India is recognized as one of the top 10 mega-diverse countries in the world, particularly in terms of diversity of fishes. The total fish diversity in India is estimated in this study to include 3,967 species. This diversity is comparable to other countries renowned for their fish biodiversity, such as Australia, China, Brazil, Indonesia, and the United States.

According to FishBase data from June 2024, Australia has the highest fish diversity with 5,214 species (400 freshwater), followed by Indonesia (5041 species, 1292 freshwater), Brazil (4,967 species, 3668 freshwater), Japan (4322 species, 322 freshwater), China (3850 species, 1707 freshwater), the Philippines (3764 species, 362 freshwater), Taiwan (3166 species, 190 freshwater), the United States (3140 species, 993 freshwater), Papua New Guinea (2991 species, 367 freshwater), and India in 10th place with 2,904 species (1081 freshwater) (Froese & Pauly 2024).

Australia's freshwater fish diversity is exceptional, comprising about 1,500 species, many of which are endemic, particularly in biodiversity hotspots such as Queensland's Wet Tropics (Pearson et al. 2013). This diversity is shaped by Australia's geological and climatic history, resulting in distinctive evolutionary patterns (Feuvre et al. 2015). Australia's marine fish diversity is also notable, with around 3,500 species, particularly concentrated on the Great Barrier Reef, which is home to over 1,500 reef fish species and has relatively high levels of endemism (White et al. 2011). In comparison, both Australia and India exhibit rich fish diversity, with specific characteristics shaped by their respective geographical features and ecological conditions. Australia has a higher total number of fish species, particularly in marine environments, while India boasts significant freshwater fish diversity, especially in its extensive river systems.

Other than Australia, Brazil and the United States, the other countries in the top 10 are located in Southeast Asia. Brazil, ranking third, has a remarkable freshwater fish diversity, especially in the Amazon River basin, which is one of the largest river systems globally, supporting about 3,000 freshwater species, including many endemics (Fossile et al. 2023). The Amazon provides habitats for a broad range of species, including piranhas, arapaimas, and various catfishes (Virgilio et al. 2020). Brazil's marine fish diversity includes around 1,500 species, occupying diverse habitats along its extensive coastline, such as coral reefs, estuaries, and mangroves (Marceniuk et al. 2021). The nutrient-rich waters from the Amazon River also contributes to the rich biodiversity along Brazil's northern coast (Marceniuk et al. 2019). The United States, ranked 8th, has significant freshwater-fish diversity, particularly in the southeastern region and the Appalachian Mountains, where native species thrive in a variety of freshwater habitats (Hartman & Larson 2022). The United States also has around 300 marine fish species along its coastlines, especially in the Atlantic and Pacific Oceans, with the Gulf of Mexico being a key biodiversity hotspot hosting numerous species that are economically important for fisheries and recreational activities (Hartman & Larson 2022). Compared to India, freshwater-fish diversity is greater in Brazil while Indian fish diversity is greater than United States.

Aside from these three countries, the remaining 7 nations with high fish diversity are located in Southeast Asia. This region is known for its high fish biodiversity, driven by its unique geography, vast river systems, and varied marine habitats. Southeast Asia is home to a wide range of fish species, both freshwater and marine, making it one of the most biodiverse regions on Earth (Nguyen & Silva 2006). Indonesia, ranked second in global fish diversity, has an estimated 4,970 species, including both freshwater and marine fishes. This represents about 15% of the world's total fish diversity, underscoring Indonesia's crucial contribution to global aquatic diversity (Gustiano et al. 2021). Indonesia's freshwater-fish diversity is largely due to its geographic features, including thousands of islands and diverse inland water systems (Haryono et al. 2023). Endemic freshwater species are particularly concentrated in areas like Sumatra and Kalimantan (Usman 2024). Additionally, Indonesia's extensive coral reefs are recognized as global marine biodiversity hotspots, with a high number of reef fish species (Madduppa et al. 2012). Indonesia's location within the Coral Triangle further enhances its marine fish diversity, making it one of the richest marine areas in the world (Andriyono et al. 2022). Studies indicate that eastern Indonesia has a higher population of herbivorous fish, which are vital for maintaining coral reef health (Putra et al. 2020). Compared to India, the marine fish diversity of Indonesia is high, although the marine habitat between these two countries is comparable. India contains more freshwater fishes, which can be attributed the greater land area and more extensive freshwater systems.

Japan and China rank 4th and 5th, respectively, in global fish diversity. Japan's freshwater ecosystems, especially its lakes and rivers, are home to many endemic species. For instance, Lake Biwa, Japan's largest lake, hosts several distinctive fish species, such as the Japanese bagrid catfish, *Pseudobagrus nudiceps*, which exhibits high genetic diversity due to the lake's ancient geological origins (Watanabe & Nishida 2003, Tabata et al. 2016). Japan's unusual habitats have allowed the evolution of these specialized fish populations, although many now face threats from habitat destruction and pollution (Dai 2024). Japan's marine diversity is also notable, especially along its coasts influenced by the Kuroshio Current. The warm current fosters a wide variety of marine life, including tropical and subtropical species; the transport has been migrating northward likely due to climate change (Nakamura et al. 2013, Morioka et al. 2019). China also has great fish diversity, with about 3,000 freshwater species and 1,500 marine species (Gupta et al. 2016, Thakur et al. 2022). The Yangtze River, the longest river in Asia, is a vast habitat for numerous freshwater fish, including critically endangered species like the Yangtze giant softshell turtle (*Rafetus swinhoei*) and the Chinese sturgeon (*Acipenser sinensis*). However, many fish species in the Yangtze are threatened by dam construction, pollution, and overfishing (Gupta et al. 2016, Thakur et al. 2022). China's marine biodiversity is also rich, particularly in the South China Sea, which is home to a large fauna of reef fish species and many commercially important fish populations (Gupta et al. 2016). Compared to India, Japan has a greater diversity of marine fishes, largely due to its proximity to the Kuroshio Current, which significantly boosts its marine biodiversity. On the other hand, India has much more extensive freshwater systems, including vast rivers and reservoirs, contributing to its rich freshwater fish diversity. However, in terms of endemism, Japan is not far behind, with many endemic freshwater species of its own. China has a higher overall total of fish species (2023 data, although according to the present study, it is less than India), with a significant freshwater biodiversity, particularly in the Yangtze River. India, while having a smaller number of freshwater species, has greater marine diversity than China, due to its extensive coastline and island ecosystems. The difference in the number of the species can be attributed to India's especially diverse habitats, ranging from Himalayan rivers to tropical coral reefs and mangroves, while China's aquatic systems comprise mostly temperate and subtropical river systems plus the marine fauna of the South China Sea.

The Philippines, Taiwan, and Papua New Guinea are generally similar island-associated habitats and fauna. The Philippines is especially recognized as a global center of marine biodiversity, particularly for reef fishes. It is estimated to have over 2,000 species of reef fish, making it one of the richest marine ecosystems in the world (Go et al. 2015). The country is part of the Coral Triangle, which is known for its high levels of marine biodiversity and endemism. Freshwater fish diversity is also significant, with endemism to specific regions (Go et al. 2015), particularly in the Mindanao and Luzon regions. Endemic species include the Philippine tetras and a variety of gobies (Go et al. 2015). The marine fish diversity in the Philippines is extensive, with the country being dubbed the "global center of marine biodiversity" due to its high number of reef fish species per unit area (Go et al. 2015). Taiwan also has a diverse ichthyofauna, (Yagi et al. 2022). The island's unique geographical location and varied habitats contribute to its fish diversity. Taiwan's freshwater ecosystems include rivers, lakes, and wetlands, which support a range of endemic fishes, such as the Formosan landlocked salmon (*Oncorhynchus masou formosanus*) (Yagi et al. 2022), and the Formosan suckers (*Hypseleotris* spp.). The island's rivers and streams provide critical habitats for these species, but many are threatened by habitat loss due to urbanization and dam construction (Yagi et al. 2022). Papua New Guinea is also a part of the Coral Triangle and is known for its rich marine biodiversity, with over 1,500 species of reef fish documented (Drew et al. 2012). The country's diverse habitats, including coral reefs, mangroves, and seagrass beds, support this wide variety of marine species. Its freshwater fish diversity is also high, with many endemic species found in the region's rivers and lakes (Drew et al. 2012). The Philippines and Papua New Guinea have especially rich marine biodiversity due to being in the Coral Triangle. Taiwan and India also have high marine diversity, with India occupying the northern portion of the Indian Ocean, and Taiwan's fauna augmented by the Kuroshio Current. Taiwan and Papua New Guinea also have high freshwater fish diversity, while the Philippines, with highly fragmented coral-reef islands, has fewer freshwater species. India has greater freshwater habitat in terms of rivers and reservoirs compared to the Philippines, Taiwan, and PNG. All 4 countries are situated in especially biodiverse regions, with India spanning both tropical and temperate zones, while the Philippines, Taiwan, and PNG are limited to tropical and subtropical zones.

In terms of freshwater fish diversity, the Amazon River Basin in Brazil has the highest freshwater fish diversity, with over 3,000 species (Sun et al. 2017), followed by the Yangtze River (China) with almost 3000 species (Ren

et al. 2021), and the Congo Basin in Africa (1300 species), and the Mekong River Basin (1100 species) (Sithole et al. 2023, Yodsiri et al. 2017). India, with around 1,150 species, ranks lower, but still has significant diversity. These ecosystems contain a great variety of freshwater habitats. India's freshwater fauna occupies 14 major rivers, including the Ganges, Brahmaputra, Godavari, and Narmada, along with extensive lakes and reservoirs (Chandra et al. 2018). The Amazon River, the largest river by volume, includes a complex network of tributaries and wetland ecosystems. The Congo River, the second-longest river in Africa, features numerous tributaries and swamp forests (Sonet et al. 2019). The Mekong River flows through 6 countries, with diverse habitats including floodplains, swamps, and wetlands (Yodsiri et al. 2017). The Yangtze River is Asia's longest river and includes extensive floodplains and other habitats (Huang & Li 2016). India's freshwater habitats range from Himalayan rivers to tropical floodplains, lakes, reservoirs, and wetlands. The Amazon Basin contains rainforests, floodplains, and oxbow lakes, with annual flooding supporting seasonal fish migrations (Sun et al. 2017). The Congo Basin has swamps, rivers, rapids, and extensive floodplains, providing varied fish habitats (Harrison et al. 2016). The Mekong's seasonal flooding creates expansive wetlands, lakes, and floodplains, critical for breeding cycles (Yodsiri et al. 2017). The Yangtze River Basin includes floodplains, lakes, and wetlands that support a wide variety of fish habitats (Huang & Li 2016). Although India has considerable freshwater fish diversity, the Amazon Basin and Congo Basin surpass it in total fish species count and habitat richness.

Mangrove forests are vital coastal ecosystems that offer numerous ecological, economic, and social benefits. However, their global distribution is uneven, with a handful of countries hosting the majority of the world's mangroves. According to Giri et al. (2010), about 75% of global mangrove coverage is concentrated in just 15 countries. Indonesia, for example, has the largest area of mangroves, making up approximately 22% of the world's total, covering around 3.3 million hectares (Hamilton & Presotto 2024). Studies in Indonesia, from regions like the Segara Anakan Lagoon in Central Java and Lombok in West Nusa Tenggara, reported 40 genera and 48 species of brackish-water fishes (Setijanto & Rukayah 2016, Wahyudewantoro et al. 2024). Other significant mangrove areas, such as the Parnaíba River Delta in Brazil, which spans 100,000 hectares of mangroves, has just over 20 species of brackish-water fishes (Chielle et al. 2023, Guimarães-Costa et al. 2019). Similarly, the mangroves of tropical Queensland, Australia, which cover 0.4 million hectares, contained only 18 species of these fishes (Robertson & Duke 1990). However, Chinese mangroves present a different scenario, where there are more than 40 brackish water species from Zhanjiang mangroves, higher despite the country's mangrove area being only 29,200 hectares (Zhao et al. 2022, Lei et al. 2022). In the South China Sea, Larson et al. (2016) compiled a checklist of gobioid fishes from Singapore, listing 167 species. Most of these fishes are closely tied to brackish-water habitats, despite the fact that mangrove cover has been reduced due to habitat destruction and fragmentation. Similarly, nearly 300 fish species have been documented in Vietnam's Mekong Delta, with a notable abundance of brackish-water species (Dinh et al. 2024). In India, even though mangroves span 4,992 square kilometres, only 20 species of brackish-water fishes are enumerated in the present study. Mangroves and estuaries provide various microhabitats that serve as niches for these euryhaline species, which prefer salinity ranges not typical of freshwater or marine environments. Despite the productivity of these ecosystems, the diversity of brackish-water fish species is often undercounted, possibly due to their cryptic nature and selective habitats and lack of comprehensive studies, a trend also present for Indian mangroves (Cavalcante et al. 2021, Buitre et al. 2019, Faustino et al. 2020).

Coral reefs are some of the most diverse ecosystems on Earth, providing essential habitat for numerous marine species, especially coral reef fish. The Great Barrier Reef in Australia, the coral reefs of the Maldives, and those in Indonesia are known for their exceptional biodiversity and intricate ecosystems. The Great Barrier Reef, the largest coral reef system in the world, spans over 2,300 kilometres along the Queensland coast and hosts around 1,500 fish species, including well-known species like clownfish and parrotfish. Its habitats include coral reefs, seagrass beds, and mangroves, which are vital for the life cycles of many fish species (Bachtiar et al. 2023). However, the health of the reef is severely threatened by climate change, particularly coral bleaching, which has become more frequent and severe in recent decades (Sambrook et al. 2019). The Maldives also features stunning coral reefs that are crucial for biodiversity as well as for the local economy, primarily via tourism and fisheries. The reefs support over 1,000 fish species, including the iconic Maldives anemonefish. The reefs serve as nurseries for juvenile fish, offering protection from predators (Chong-Seng et al. 2012). However, rising sea temperatures and ocean acidification pose significant threats, leading to coral bleaching and habitat degradation (Hemingson & Bellwood 2017). Indonesia, located within the Coral Triangle, is recognized as the global epicenter of marine

biodiversity. Its coral reefs host over 2,000 fish species, making it one of the world's most species-rich marine ecosystems. Many of these species are endemic to the region (Luza et al. 2022). However, Indonesia's reefs are under severe pressure from overfishing, destructive fishing practices, and coastal development, causing substantial declines in both fish populations and coral health (Sievers 2024). In comparison, Indian coral reefs, particularly those in the Andaman and Nicobar Islands and Lakshadweep, support around 500 coral species and 1,500 fish species (Ditzel et al. 2022). Indian reefs play an essential role in supporting local fisheries and maintaining ecological balance. Fish diversity on Indian reefs is shaped by factors such as habitat complexity and coral health (Russ et al. 2020). Similar to other regions, Indian coral reefs face threats from climate change, overfishing, and habitat destruction, with coral bleaching being a major concern (Strona et al. 2021). While the Indian government has taken conservation measures, including the creation of marine protected areas, enforcing regulations and managing human activities remains challenging (Choi et al. 2020).

India's ichthyofauna faces numerous threats and challenges that significantly impact the health of aquatic ecosystems. These challenges stem from both anthropogenic activities and environmental changes, which collectively threaten the sustainability of fish populations and the overall biodiversity, especially of freshwater habitats. One of the primary threats to freshwater fish diversity in India is habitat destruction due to urbanization, industrialization, and agricultural expansion. The conversion of wetlands, rivers, and lakes into agricultural land or urban areas leads to the loss of critical fish habitats. For instance, the reclamation of wetlands for agriculture has been shown to reduce fish populations significantly, as these areas serve as essential breeding and nursery grounds for many species (Polidoro et al. 2010). Additionally, the degradation of mangrove ecosystems further exacerbates the loss of fish habitats, as mangroves provide vital shelter and food resources for juvenile fishes (Lennon & Sealey 2022).

The degradation of marine habitats, particularly coral reefs and mangroves, poses a significant threat to fish diversity. Coral reefs, which are critical habitats for many marine species, are increasingly threatened by climate change, pollution, and coastal development. Studies have shown that the loss of coral cover directly correlates with declines in fish diversity, particularly among specialized species that rely on coral habitats (Holbrook et al. 2015). Water pollution from agricultural runoff, industrial discharges, and untreated sewage pose a significant threat to fish diversity. Pollutants such as heavy metals, pesticides, and nutrients can lead to toxic conditions that are detrimental to fish health and reproductive success. Studies have indicated that polluted water bodies often exhibit reduced fish diversity and abundance, as many species are sensitive to changes in water quality (Zhao et al. 2022). In particular, the Sundarbans mangrove ecosystem has been affected by pollution, leading to declines in fish populations and changes in community structure (Wahyudewantoro 2018). The presence of heavy metals and microplastics in marine environments can also have detrimental effects on fish populations, leading to declines in biodiversity and changes in community structure (Oza et al. 2024). Overfishing is a critical issue that threatens fish diversity in India. The increasing demand for fish as a food source has led to unsustainable fishing practices, including the use of destructive gear and methods, lead to the depletion of fish stocks and disrupt the ecological balance of aquatic ecosystems. The decline in fish populations not only affects biodiversity but also threatens the livelihoods of communities that rely on fishing for their sustenance (Serafy et al. 2015). Overfishing is one of the most pressing threats to marine fish diversity in India, resulting in the depletion of fish stocks. The high fishing pressure has been linked to significant declines in fish populations, particularly among species that are already vulnerable due to their life-history traits (Yan et al. 2021). Overfishing not only reduces fish biomass but also disrupts ecological linkages within marine ecosystems, leading to broader ecological consequences (Aburto-Oropeza et al. 2011). Additionally, the introduction of invasive species can further complicate the dynamics of fish communities, often outcompeting native species for resources (Brooker et al. 2020). In India, the spread of invasive species in coastal and estuarine environments has been linked to declines in native fish populations, highlighting the need for effective management strategies to mitigate these impacts (Bonin et al. 2011). The construction of dams and water diversion projects has significant implications for fish diversity. Dams disrupt natural riverine ecosystems, blocking migratory routes for fish and altering flow regimes that are crucial for maintaining healthy fish populations. The Mekong River, for instance, has experienced declines in fish diversity due to damming, which has led to increased salinity and reduced connectivity between habitats (Durand et al. 2022). Similar concerns exist in India, where dam construction on major rivers has been linked to declines in fish populations and changes in community structure (Sambrook et al. 2019).

Climate change poses an overarching threat to fish diversity through its impact on water temperature, salinity, and hydrological patterns. Changes in rainfall and temperature can alter the habitats that fish rely on for spawning and growth. For example, increased temperatures can lead to thermal stress for many fish species, while altered precipitation patterns can affect river flows and wetland inundation, disrupting the life cycles of migratory fishes (Sarker et al. 2019). The Sundarbans, which is particularly vulnerable to rising sea levels and increased salinity, exemplifies how climate change can threaten fish diversity in sensitive ecosystems (Benejam et al. 2014). Coral bleaching is a critical phenomenon driven by rising sea temperatures, which leads to the expulsion of symbiotic zooxanthellae from coral tissues. This process not only affects the health of corals but also has cascading effects on the entire marine ecosystem. In India, coral reefs, particularly in the Gulf of Mannar and the Andaman and Nicobar Islands, have experienced significant bleaching events, especially during periods of elevated sea surface temperatures (Sadhukhan et al. 2022, Donner et al. 2017). Recent studies indicate that the warming of coral reef waters has increased globally, with the Gulf of Mannar documenting a thermal threshold of 30.73°C, which is critical for triggering bleaching (Sadhukhan et al. 2022). The cumulative risk of future bleaching events is particularly high in regions with rich marine biodiversity, such as India, where coral reefs host numerous endemic species (Mellin 2024). The impacts of these bleaching events are profound, leading to reduced coral cover, altered species composition, and diminished ecosystem services provided by healthy coral reefs (Bauman et al. 2022, Eakin et al. 2019). The frequency and intensity of cyclones in the Indian Ocean have increased due to climate change, posing additional threats to marine ecosystems. Cyclones can cause physical damage to coral reefs, leading to fragmentation and loss of habitat complexity, which are essential for supporting diverse marine life (Behera & Sharma 2019). The aftermath of cyclones often results in sedimentation and nutrient runoff, further stressing coral reefs and contributing to algal blooms that can outcompete corals for space and resources (Soni & Ansari 2017). In recent years, cyclones such as Cyclone Gaja and Cyclone Amphan have demonstrated the vulnerability of coastal ecosystems, including coral reefs, to extreme weather events. The destruction caused by these cyclones can lead to long-term ecological changes, making recovery difficult for already-stressed coral populations (Udaykumar et al. 2022). In addition to coral bleaching and cyclones, other catastrophic events driven by climate change, such as marine heatwaves, have been observed in Indian waters. These heatwaves can exacerbate the effects of bleaching, leading to widespread mortality of coral species and altering the dynamics of marine ecosystems (Eakin et al. 2019). The 2014–2017 global-scale coral-bleaching event, which affected many reefs worldwide, also had severe impacts on Indian coral reefs, highlighting the interconnectedness of global climate patterns and local biodiversity (Eakin et al. 2019). The cumulative effects of these stressors lead to a decline in fish populations that rely on coral reefs for habitat and food. The loss of biodiversity not only affects marine life but also has significant implications for local communities that depend on fisheries for their livelihoods (Soni & Ansari 2017).

India's freshwater and marine ecosystems support a rich variety of fish species, essential for maintaining ecological balance, supporting economic livelihoods, and preserving cultural heritage. However, these ecosystems are under serious threat from overfishing, habitat destruction, pollution, and climate change. Protecting fish diversity requires effective conservation measures, backed by thorough research on fish taxonomy to inform these efforts. Establishing protected areas and marine reserves is a key strategy for safeguarding fish populations and their habitats. In India, the Gulf of Mannar Marine National Park and the Sundarbans mangrove ecosystem are prime examples of protected habitats for various fish species. These areas minimize harmful human activities, promoting ecosystem recovery and growth. Research has shown that no-take zones in marine protected areas can lead to substantial increases in fish biomass and biodiversity (Sun et al. 2017). Involving local communities in fishery management is critical for conservation success. Community-based approaches empower fishers to actively participate in managing resources, fostering sustainable practices that benefit both the environment and local communities. Combining traditional ecological knowledge with scientific data has proven to strengthen conservation strategies and improve fishery management outcomes (Ren et al. 2021). In the Ganges River basin, for instance, involving local communities in conservation initiatives has been effective in maintaining fish diversity. Habitat restoration is another key element of fish conservation. Efforts to restore damaged habitats like wetlands and river banks can significantly boost fish diversity and population numbers. Restoration projects focusing on replanting mangroves and rehabilitating river ecosystems have been shown to improve water quality and create essential fish habitats. For example, initiatives aimed at restoring the health of the Yangtze River have been shown to be crucial for sustaining the diverse fish species that rely on these waters (Huang & Li 2016).

Lastly, enforcing fishing regulations is vital to prevent overfishing and protect vulnerable species. This includes setting catch limits, seasonal closures, and gear restrictions to ensure sustainable fishing practices. Regulating the ornamental fish import trade is also necessary to prevent the introduction of invasive species that can threaten native fish populations (Wang et al. 2016). Accurate fish taxonomy is crucial for understanding biodiversity and the ecological roles of different species, aiding in the identification and classification of species and providing vital information for conservation planning. In India, where many fish species remain under-documented, targeted taxonomic research is essential for uncovering hidden diversity and understanding the evolutionary relationships between species (Cheng et al. 2015). Advances in molecular techniques, such as DNA barcoding, have transformed fish taxonomy by enabling quick and precise species identification. These methods can complement traditional morphological techniques, especially for highly diverse groups where physical identification is difficult. For example, DNA barcoding has successfully identified cryptic species and evaluated genetic diversity in economically significant fishes, leading to improved management and conservation efforts (Sithole et al. 2023). Nevertheless, fish taxonomy in India faces challenges, including a shortage of trained taxonomists and limited research funding. These “taxonomic impediments” hinder conservation efforts, as many species remain unidentified or are misclassified, complicating management strategies. To overcome this, there is a need for increased investment in taxonomic research, training programs for new experts, and the creation of collaborative networks among researchers, conservationists, and policymakers (Sonet et al. 2019). Comprehensive taxonomic research is key to developing informed conservation policies and strategies. Proper species identification and classification allow for the evaluation of extinction risks, prioritization of conservation efforts, and the creation of effective management plans. For instance, understanding the taxonomic status of endangered fish species can guide conservation actions and resource allocation, ensuring that attention is focused on the most vulnerable populations (Decru et al. 2015). In summary, conserving fish diversity in India requires a multifaceted approach, including the establishment of protected areas, community-based management, habitat restoration, and regulation of fishing practices. Additionally, focused research on fish taxonomy is critical for enhancing our understanding of biodiversity, shaping conservation policies, and overcoming taxonomic challenges. By investing in both conservation strategies and taxonomic research, India can work toward sustainable management of its diverse fish resources and the protection of its aquatic ecosystems.

CONCLUSIONS

This review of fish diversity in India reveals a rich and dynamic ichthyofauna, influenced by the country’s varied geography and climatic conditions. India is home to 3,967 species of fish, both marine and freshwater, making it one of the world’s biodiversity hotspots. Key freshwater systems like the Ganges, Brahmaputra, and Cauvery Rivers, as well as important coastal ecosystems such as the Arabian Sea and Bay of Bengal, contribute significantly to this diversity. Despite this wealth of biodiversity, several challenges threaten the sustainability of fish populations in India. Habitat destruction, pollution, overfishing, and the introduction of invasive species have led to the decline of native fish species. Climate change, with its impact on water temperatures and water availability, also poses long-term risks to the fish population. Over 300 Indian species are classified as threatened according to the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) Red List. Efforts are being made to address these challenges, including the establishment of marine protected areas, restoration of critical habitats, and community-based fisheries management. Government policies, such as the National Fisheries Policy and various conservation programs, aim to promote sustainable fishing practices, biodiversity conservation, and habitat restoration. In conclusion, while India boasts immense fish diversity, concerted efforts in conservation, sustainable management, and research are crucial to protect this vital natural resource from ongoing environmental and human-induced pressures. Balancing ecological preservation with the livelihood needs of local communities remains a key challenge moving forward.

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Table 1

The list of the families and genera of fishes reported from India

Order	Family	Genera	Species
Myxini			
Myxiniformes	Myxinidae Rafinesque, 1815	1	1
Elasmobranchii			
Carcharhiniformes	Atelomycteridae White, 1936	1	1
	Carcharhinidae Jordan & Evermann, 1896	9	27
	Galeocerdonidae Poey, 1875	1	1
	Hemigaleidae Hasse, 1878	4	4
	Pentanchidae Smith, 1912	3	4
	Proscylliidae Fowler, 1941	2	2
	Pseudotriakidae Gill 1893	1	1
	Scyliorhinidae Gill, 1862	1	2
	Sphyrnidae Bonaparte, 1840	2	4
	Triakidae Gray, 1851	4	8
Echinorhiniformes	Echinorhinidae Gill, 1862	1	1
Heterodontiformes	Heterodontidae Gray, 1851	1	1
Hexanchiformes	Hexanchidae Gray, 1851	2	2
Lamniformes	Alopiidae Bonaparte, 1835	1	3
	Odontaspidae Müller & Henle, 1839	1	2
	Lamnidae Bonaparte, 1835	3	4
	Carchariidae Müller & Henle, 1838	1	2
	Pseudocarchariidae Taylor, Compagno & Struhsaker, 1983	1	1
Myliobatiformes	Aetobatidae Agassiz, 1858	1	3
	Dasyatidae Jordan & Gilbert, 1879	14	33
	Gymnuridae Fowler, 1934	1	5
	Hexatrygonidae Heemstra & Smith, 1980	1	1
	Mobulidae Gill, 1893	1	6
	Myliobatidae Bonaparte, 1835	1	4
	Plesiobatidae Nishida, 1990	1	1
	Rhinopteridae Jordan & Evermann, 1896	1	3
Orectolobiformes	Ginglymostomatidae Gill, 1862	1	1

	Hemiscylliidae Gill, 1862	1	6
	Parascylliidae Gill, 1862	1	1
	Rhincodontidae Müller & Henle, 1841	1	1
	Stegostomatidae Gill, 1862	1	1
Rajiformes			
	Gurgesiellidae de Buen, 1959	2	2
	Rajidae Blainville, 1816	4	4
Rhinopristiformes			
	Glaucostegidae Last, Séret & Naylor, 2016	1	5
	Pristidae Bonaparte, 1835	2	5
	Rhinobatidae Bonaparte, 1835	2	4
	Rhinidae Müller & Henle, 1841	2	5
Squaliformes			
	Centrophoridae Bleeker, 1859	2	6
	Etmopteridae Fowler, 1934	2	2
	Somniosidae Jordan, 1888	4	4
	Squalidae de Blainville, 1816	1	6
Squatiformes			
	Squatinae Blainville, 1816	1	2
Torpediniformes			
	Narcinidae Gill, 1862	2	9
	Narkidae Fowler, 1934	2	2
	Torpedinidae Henle, 1834	1	6
Holocephali			
Chimaeriformes			
	Chimaeridae Rafinesque, 1815	1	1
	Rhinochimaeridae Garman, 1901	2	3
Actinopteri			
Acanthuriformes			
	Acanthuridae Bonaparte, 1835	5	42
	Antigoniidae Jordan & Evermann, 1898	1	2
	Cepolidae Rafinesque, 1815	3	5
	Chaetodontidae Rafinesque, 1815	8	52
	Drepaneidae Gill, 1872	1	2
	Emmelichthyidae Poey, 1867	1	1
	Ephippidae Bleeker, 1859	3	6
	Gerreidae Bleeker, 1859	2	12
	Haemulidae Gill, 1885	3	29
	Leiognathidae Gill, 1893	9	29
	Lethrinidae Bonaparte, 1831	5	27
	Lobotidae Gill, 1861	3	3
	Lutjanidae Gill, 1861	15	70
	Malacanthidae Poey, 1861	2	4
	Monodactylidae Jordan & Evermann, 1898	1	3

	Nemipteridae Regan, 1913	3	31
	Pomacanthidae Jordan & Evermann, 1898	6	21
	Priacanthidae Günther, 1859	4	9
	Scatophagidae Gill, 1883	1	1
	Sciaenidae Cuvier, 1829	17	43
	Siganidae Richardson, 1837	1	17
	Sillaginidae Richardson, 1846	3	11
	Sparidae Rafinesque, 1818	7	15
	Zanclidae Bleeker, 1876	1	1
Acropomatiformes			
	Acropomatidae Gill, 1893	1	3
	Bathyclupeidae Gill, 1896	1	1
	Champsodontidae Jordan & Snyder, 1902	1	2
	Creediidae Waite, 1899	1	1
	Epigonidae Poey, 1861	1	1
	Hemerocoetidae Kaup, 1873	1	1
	Pempheridae Bleeker, 1859	2	13
	Pentacerotidae Bleeker, 1859	1	1
	Symphysanodontidae Katayama, 1984	1	2
	Synagropidae Smith, 1961	1	2
Albuliformes			
	Albulidae Bleeker, 1849	1	4
Alepocephaliformes			
	Alepocephalidae Bonaparte, 1846	4	5
	Platytroctidae Koefoed, 1927	1	2
Anabantiformes			
	Aenigmachannidae Britz, Anoop, Dahanukar & Raghavan, 2019	1	1
	Anabantidae Bonaparte, 1831	1	2
	Badidae Barlow, Liem & Wickler, 1968	2	22
	Channidae Fowler, 1934	1	30
	Nandidae Bleeker, 1852	1	4
	Osphronemidae van der Hoeven, 1832	7	11
	Pristolepididae Regan, 1913	1	6
Anguilliformes			
	Anguillidae Rafinesque, 1810	1	5
	Colocongridae Smith, 1976	3	3
	Congridae Kaup, 1856	16	38
	Moringuidae Gill, 1885	1	6
	Muraenidae Rafinesque, 1815	10	51
	Muraenesocidae Kaup, 1859	3	5
	Nemichthyidae Kaup, 1859	2	2
	Nettastomatidae Kaup, 1859	3	3
	Ophichthidae Günther, 1870	18	42
	Synaphobranchidae Johnson, 1862	2	2
Argentiniformes			

	Argentinidae Bonaparte, 1846	1	1
Ateleopodiformes			
	Ateleopodidae Bonaparte, 1850	2	2
Atheriniformes			
	Atherinidae Risso, 1827	3	8
	Atherionidae Schultz, 1948	1	1
	Isonidae Rosen, 1964	1	1
Aulopiformes			
	Alepisauridae Swainson, 1839	1	1
	Chlorophthalmidae Garman, 1899	1	2
	Ipnopidae Gill, 1884	2	4
	Evermannellidae Fowler, 1901	1	1
	Paralepididae Bonaparte, 1835	1	2
	Synodontidae Gill, 1861	4	25
Batrachoidiformes			
	Batrachoididae Jordan, 1896	4	7
Beloniformes			
	Adrianichthyidae Weber, 1913	1	6
	Belonidae Bonaparte, 1835	5	12
	Exocoetidae Risso, 1827	6	25
	Hemiramphidae Gill, 1859	5	19
	Zenarchopteridae Fowler, 1934	2	7
Beryciformes			
	Berycidae Lowe, 1839	2	4
Blenniiformes			
	Blenniidae Rafinesque, 1810	27	73
	Tripterygiidae Whitley, 1931	3	11
Carangiformes			
	Bothidae Smitt, 1892	11	27
	Carangidae Rafinesque, 1815	27	67
	Citharidae de Buen, 1935	1	1
	Coryphaenidae Rafinesque, 1815	1	2
	Cynoglossidae Jordan, 1888	3	25
	Echeneidae Rafinesque, 1810	3	6
	Istiophoridae Rafinesque, 1815	5	6
	Lactariidae Boulenger, 1904	1	1
	Latidae Jordan, 1888	2	2
	Menidae Fitzinger, 1873	1	1
	Paralichthyidae Regan, 1910	2	12
	Poecilopsettidae Norman, 1934	2	3
	Polynemidae Rafinesque, 1815	5	16
	Psettodidae Regan, 1910	1	1
	Rachycentridae Gill, 1896	1	1
	Samaridae Jordan & Goss, 1889	2	5
	Soleidae Bonaparte, 1833	12	29
	Sphyraenidae Rafinesque, 1815	1	13
	Toxotidae Bleeker, 1859	1	2
	Xiphiidae Rafinesque, 1815	1	1

Centrarchiformes			
	Cirrhitidae Macleay, 1841	4	9
	Kuhliidae Jordan & Evermann, 1896	1	3
	Kyphosidae Jordan, 1887	1	3
	Terapontidae Richardson, 1842	2	4
Characiformes			
	Characidae Latreille, 1825	1	1
	Serrasalminidae Bleeker, 1859	2	2
Cichliformes			
	Ambassidae Klunzinger, 1870	3	21
	Cichlidae Bonaparte, 1835	6	8
	Opistognathidae Bonaparte, 1835	1	7
	Pholidichthyidae Jordan, 1896	1	1
	Plesiopidae Günther, 1861	3	5
	Pomacentridae Bonaparte, 1831	21	103
	Pseudochromidae Müller & Troschel, 1849	4	8
Clupeiformes			
	Chirocentridae Bleeker, 1849	1	2
	Dorosomatidae Gill, 1861	11	29
	Dussumieriidae Gill, 1861	1	4
	Ehiravidae Deraniyagala, 1929	3	3
	Engraulidae Gill, 1861	5	43
	Pristigasteridae Bleeker, 1872	4	13
	Spratelloididae Jordan, 1925	1	2
Cyprinodontiformes			
	Aphaniidae Hoedeman, 1949	1	2
	Aplocheilidae Bleeker, 1859	1	7
	Poeciliidae Bonaparte, 1831	3	6
Cypriniformes			
	Balitoridae Swainson, 1839	6	19
	Botiidae Berg, 1940	2	8
	Cobitidae Swainson, 1838	5	24
	Cyprinidae Rafinesque, 1815	42	337
	Danionidae Bleeker, 1863	17	101
	Nemacheilidae Regan, 1911	13	138
	Psilorhynchidae Hora, 1926	1	21
	Tincidae Garsault, 1764	1	1
	Xenocyprididae Günther, 1868	2	3
Elopiformes			
	Elopidae Valenciennes, 1847	1	2
	Megalopidae Jordan & Gilbert, 1883	1	1
Gadiformes			
	Bregmacerotidae Gill, 1872	1	1
	Bathygadidae Jordan & Evermann, 1898	2	2
	Macrouridae Bonaparte, 1831	7	19
	Moridae Moreau, 1881	2	6
Gobiiformes			
	Eleotridae Bonaparte, 1835	11	21

	Gobiidae Cuvier, 1816	80	250
	Kraemeriidae Whitley, 1935	1	1
	Microdesmidae Regan, 1912	4	13
	Schindleriidae Giltay, 1934	1	2
Gonorynchiformes			
	Chanidae Günther, 1868	1	1
Holocentriformes			
	Holocentridae Bonaparte, 1833	4	27
Kurtiformes			
	Apogonidae Günther, 1859	25	91
	Kurtidae Bleeker, 1859	1	1
	Trichonotidae Günther, 1861	1	2
Lampriformes			
	Regalecidae Gill, 1884	1	1
	Trachipteridae Swainson, 1839	2	2
Lepisosteidae			
	Lepisosteidae Agassiz, 1832	1	1
Lophiiformes			
	Antennariidae Jarocki, 1822	3	12
	Ceratiidae Gill, 1861	2	2
	Chaunacidae Gill, 1863	1	4
	Diceratiidae Regan & Trewavas, 1932	2	3
	Himantolophidae Gill, 1861	1	1
	Lophiidae Rafinesque, 1810	2	6
	Ogcocephalidae Gill, 1893	7	14
	Oneirodidae Gill, 1878	1	1
Mugiliformes			
	Mugilidae Jarocki, 1822	12	24
Myctophiformes			
	Myctophidae Gill, 1893	10	27
	Neoscopelidae Jordan, 1901	2	2
Notacanthiformes			
	Halosauridae Günther, 1868	2	4
	Notacanthidae Rafinesque, 1810	1	1
Ophidiiformes			
	Bythitidae Gill, 1861	3	4
	Carapidae Poey, 1867	4	7
	Dinematichthyidae Whitley, 1928	3	3
	Ophidiidae Rafinesque, 1810	13	22
Osteoglossiformes			
	Notopteridae Bleeker, 1851	2	2
Perciformes			
	Ammodytidae Bonaparte, 1835	1	3
	Anthiadidae Poey, 1861	8	23
	Bembropidae Regan, 1913	2	4
	Centrogenyidae Fowler, 1907	1	1
	Epinephelidae Bloch, 1793	9	78
	Grammistidae Bleeker, 1857	4	6

	Labridae Cuvier, 1816	36	134
	Pinguipedidae Günther, 1860	1	16
	Plectrojeniidae Fowler, 1938	1	1
	Liopropomatidae Poey, 1867	3	4
	Platycephalidae Swainson, 1839	13	22
	Scorpaenidae Risso, 1827	18	46
	Serranidae Swainson, 1839	2	6
	Synanceiidae Swainson, 1839	20	36
	Triglidae Rafinesque, 1815	7	16
	Uranoscopidae Bonaparte, 1831	2	6
Polymixiiformes			
	Polymixiidae Bleeker, 1859	1	4
Salmoniformes			
	Salmonidae Cuvier, 1816	2	2
Scombriformes			
	Ariommatidae Haedrich, 1967	1	2
	Bramidae Bonaparte, 1831	3	4
	Centrolophidae Bonaparte, 1846	1	3
	Chiasmodontidae Jordan & Gilbert, 1883	3	5
	Gempylidae Gill, 1862	9	11
	Nomeidae Günther, 1860	2	4
	Pomatomidae Gill, 1863	1	1
	Scombridae Rafinesque, 1815	11	23
	Stromateidae Rafinesque, 1810	1	4
	Trichiuridae Rafinesque, 1810	6	12
Siluriformes			
	Ailiidae Bleeker, 1858	6	14
	Akysidae Gill, 1861	1	2
	Amblycipitidae Day, 1873	1	13
	Ariidae Bleeker, 1858	10	25
	Bagridae Bleeker, 1858	6	56
	Chacidae Bleeker, 1858	1	1
	Clariidae Bonaparte, 1845	3	10
	Erethistidae Bleeker, 1862	1	1
	Heteropneustidae Hora, 1936	1	3
	Horabagridae Jayaram, 2006	3	5
	Kryptoglanidae Britz, Kakkassery & Raghavan, 2014	1	1
	Loricariidae Rafinesque, 1815	1	4
	Pangasiidae Bleeker, 1858	2	5
	Plotosidae Bleeker, 1858	1	4
	Ritidae Bleeker, 1862	1	6
	Schilbeidae Bleeker, 1858	1	1
	Siluridae Rafinesque, 1815	4	14
	Sisoridae Bleeker, 1858	20	148
Syngnathiformes			
	Aulostomidae Rafinesque, 1815	1	1

	Callionymidae Bonaparte, 1831	4	22
	Centriscidae Bonaparte, 1831	4	4
	Dactylopteridae Gill, 1861	1	6
	Fistulariidae Stark, 1828	1	2
	Mullidae Rafinesque, 1815	3	32
	Pegasidae Bonaparte, 1831	2	3
	Solenostomidae Nardo, 1843	1	2
	Syngnathidae Bonaparte, 1831	15	39
Stomiiformes			
	Gonostomatidae Cocco, 1838	3	4
	Phosichthyidae Weitzman, 1974	3	4
	Sternoptychidae Duméril, 1805	3	7
	Stomiidae Bleeker, 1859	10	16
Synbranchiformes			
	Chaudhuriidae Annandale, 1918	2	2
	Mastacembelidae Swainson, 1839	2	12
	Synbranchidae Bonaparte, 1835	4	14
Tetraodontiformes			
	Balistidae Rafinesque, 1810	11	22
	Diodontidae Bonaparte, 1835	5	8
	Molidae Bonaparte, 1835	3	4
	Monacanthidae Nardo, 1843	17	35
	Ostraciidae Rafinesque, 1810	3	9
	Tetraodontidae Bonaparte, 1831	13	43
	Triacanthidae Bleeker, 1859	4	6
	Triacanthodidae Gill, 1862	6	6
Trachichthyiformes			
	Diretmidae Gill, 1893	1	1
	Monocentridae Gill, 1859	1	1
	Trachichthyidae Bleeker, 1856	2	4
Zeiformes			
	Parazenidae McAllister, 1968	1	1
	Zeidae Rafinesque, 1815	1	2
	Zeniontidae Myers, 1960	1	1

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APPENDIX

ICHTHYOFAUNA OF INDIA (1758-2024): REVIEW, ANALYSIS AND ANNOTATED CHECKLIST

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Table 1: Checklist of the fishes of India. Type locality is provided for only those species having type locality in India. (Habitat: M: Marine, B: Brackishwater, F: Freshwater) (ANI: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, LK: Lakshadweep Islands, WB: West Bengal, OD: Odisha, AP: Andhra Pradesh, TN: Tamilnadu, KL: Kerala, KA: Karnataka: GA: Goa, MH: Maharashtra, GJ: Gujarat, LD: Ladakh, J&K: Jammu & Kashmir, HP: Himachal Pradesh, PU: Punjab, UK: Uttarakhand, HY: Haryana, DL: Delhi, UP: Uttar Pradesh, RJ: Rajasthan, MP: Madhya Pradesh, TL: Telengana, CG: Chhattisgarh, BR: Bihar, JH: Jharkhand, SK: Sikkim, AS: Assam, ML: Meghalaya, AR: Arunachal Pradesh, NL: Nagaland, MN: Manipur, MZ: Mizoram, TR: Tripura)

	Classification	Habitat	Distribution	Reference(s)	Type Locality
	Class: Myxini				
	Order: Myxiniformes				
	Family: Myxinidae Rafinesque, 1815				
1	<i>Eptatretus wadgensis</i> Augustina, Sreeram, Sukumaran, Sreekumar, Jose, Joshi & Gopalakrishnan, 2022	M	LK	(Augustina et al. 2022)	Wadge Bank, Lakshadweep Sea, India, 7°35'14"N, 76°45'45"E
	Class: Elasmobranchii				
	Order: Carcharhiniformes				
	Family: Atelomycteridae White, 1936				
2	<i>Atelomycteris marmoratus</i> (Anonymous [Bennett], 1830)	M	AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012)	
	Family: Carcharhinidae Jordan & Evermann, 1896				
3	<i>Carcharhinus albimarginatus</i> (Rüppell, 1837)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
4	<i>Carcharhinus altimus</i> (Springer, 1950)	M	ANI, TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Tyabji et al. 2018)	
5	<i>Carcharhinus amblyrhynchoides</i> (Whitley, 1934)	M	TN, KL, KA, MH	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, 2013a)	
6	<i>Carcharhinus amblyrhynchos</i> (Bleeker, 1856)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
7	<i>Carcharhinus amboinensis</i> (Müller & Henle, 1839)	M	ANI, TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Tyabji et al. 2018)	
8	<i>Carcharhinus brevipinna</i> (Müller & Henle,	M	ANI, TN, KL, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	

	1839)				
9	<i>Carcharhinus dussumieri</i> (Müller & Henle, 1839)	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2003, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Puducherry, India
10	<i>Carcharhinus falciformis</i> (Müller & Henle, 1839)	M	LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
11	<i>Carcharhinus hemiodon</i> (Müller & Henle, 1839)	MB	ANI, WB, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a, 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Puducherry, India
12	<i>Carcharhinus leucas</i> (Müller & Henle, 1839)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a, Tyabji et al. 2018)	
13	<i>Carcharhinus limbatus</i> (Müller & Henle, 1839)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
14	<i>Carcharhinus longimanus</i> (Poey, 1861)	M	ANI, AP, TN, KL, KA, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
15	<i>Carcharhinus macloti</i> (Müller & Henle, 1839)	M	ANI, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
16	<i>Carcharhinus melanopterus</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1824)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
17	<i>Carcharhinus obscurus</i> (Lesueur, 1818)	MB	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
18	<i>Carcharhinus plumbeus</i> (Nardo, 1827)	MB	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
19	<i>Carcharhinus sealei</i> (Pietschmann, 1913)	M	ANI, TN, KL, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000)	
20	<i>Carcharhinus sorrah</i> (Müller & Henle, 1839)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
21	<i>Glyphis gangeticus</i> (Müller & Henle, 1839)	MBF	WB, OD, MH	(Pati et al. 2018, Mishra et al. 2017, Yennawar et al. 2015, Barman et al. 2012)	Ganges River, 60 hours above the sea at Hoogly, West Bengal
22	<i>Lamiopsis temminckii</i> (Müller & Henle, 1839)	MB	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Puducherry, India
23	<i>Loxodon macrorhinus</i> Müller & Henle, 1839	M	ANI, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
24	<i>Negaprion acutidens</i> (Rüppell, 1837)	MB	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
25	<i>Prionace glauca</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	MB	ANI, AP, TN, KL,	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a,	

			KA, GJ	Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
26	<i>Rhizoprionodon acutus</i> (Rüppell, 1837)	MBF	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Yennawar et al. 2015, Patie et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
27	<i>Rhizoprionodon oligolinx</i> Springer, 1964	M	ANI, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Patie et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
28	<i>Scoliodon laticaudus</i> Müller & Henle, 1838	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Kar et al. 2017, Khan 2002, Patie et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	India
29	<i>Triaenodon obesus</i> (Rüppell, 1837)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Galeocerdonidae Poey, 1875					
30	<i>Galeocerdo cuvier</i> (Péron & Lesueur, 1822)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Yennawar et al. 2015, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Hemigaleidae Hasse, 1878					
31	<i>Chaenogaleus macrostoma</i> (Bleeker, 1852)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
32	<i>Hemipristis elongata</i> (Klunzinger, 1871)	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Sanyal et al. 2012, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Tyabji et al. 2018)	
33	<i>Hemigaleus microstoma</i> Bleeker, 1852	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
34	<i>Paragaleus longicaudatus</i> (Bessednov, 1966)	M	ANI	(Kumar et al. 2018)	
Family: Pentanchidae Smith, 1912					
35	<i>Apristurus investigatoris</i> (Misra, 1962)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Andaman Sea, 11°46'30"N, 93°16'25"E
36	<i>Apristurus microps</i> (Gilchrist, 1922)	M	ANI	(Kumar et al. 2018)	
37	<i>Bythaelurus hispidus</i> (Alcock, 1891)	M	ANI, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Andaman Sea, 11°31'40"N, 92°46'40"E
38	<i>Halaaelurus quagga</i> (Alcock, 1899)	M	LK, KL, KA	(Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2013a)	Laccadive Sea, off Malabar coast, 8°23'N, 76°28'E
Family: Proscylliidae Fowler, 1941					
39	<i>Eridacnis radcliffei</i> Smith, 1913	M	ANI, WB, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Yennawar et al. 2015, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
40	<i>Proscyllium magnificum</i> Last & Vongpanich, 2004	M	ANI	(Kumar et al. 2018)	

	Family: Pseudotriakidae Gill, 1893				
41	<i>Planonasmus indicus</i> Ebert, Akhilesh & Weigmann, 2018	M	KL	(Ebert et al. 2018)	Cochin Fisheries Harbor, Kochi, Kerala
	Family: Scyliorhinidae Gill, 1862				
42	<i>Cephaloscyllium silasi</i> (Talwar, 1974)	M	ANI, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Kumar et al. 2016)	Arabian Sea off Quilon, Kerala, India, 9°N, 76°E
43	<i>Cephaloscyllium sufflans</i> (Regan, 1921)	M	Indian EEZ	(Jayaprakash et al. 2006)	
	Family: Sphyrnidae Bonaparte, 1840				
44	<i>Eusphyra blochii</i> (Cuvier, 1816)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
45	<i>Sphyrna lewini</i> (Griffith & Smith, 1834)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
46	<i>Sphyrna mokarran</i> (Rüppell, 1837)	MB	ANI, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Rajan et al. 2013)	
47	<i>Sphyrna zygaena</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	MB	ANI, LK, OD, TN, KL, KA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, 2013a)	
	Family: Triakidae Gray, 1851				
48	<i>Hemitriakis indroyonoi</i> White, Compagno & Dharmadi, 2009	M	ANI	(Kumar et al. 2018)	
49	<i>Hypogaleus hyugaensis</i> (Miyosi, 1939)	M	TN	(Padate et al. 2017)	
50	<i>Iago mangalorensis</i> (Cubelio, Remya & Kurup, 2011)	M	KA	(Cubelio et al. 2011)	Mangalore, Karnataka, 12°28'02"N, 74°09'05"E
51	<i>Iago omanensis</i> (Norman, 1939)	M	TN, KA, GJ	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2013a)	
52	<i>Mustelus amanensis</i> White, Arunrugstichai & Naylor, 2021	M	ANI	(White et al. 2021)	
53	<i>Mustelus canis</i> (Mitchill, 1815)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
54	<i>Mustelus mosis</i> Hemprich & Ehrenberg, 1899	M	ANI, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012, Tyabji et al. 2018)	
55	<i>Mustelus manazo</i> Bleeker, 1854	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
	Order: Echinorhiniformes				
	Family: Echinorhinidae Gill, 1862				
56	<i>Echinorhinus brucus</i> (Bonnaterre, 1788)	M	ANI, WB, TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Ray & Mohapatra 2020, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ranjan Kumar et al. 2018)	
	Order: Heterodontiformes				
	Family: Heterodontidae Gray, 1851				

57	<i>Heterodontus zebra</i> (Gray, 1831)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Order: Hexanchiformes					
Family: Hexanchidae Gray, 1851					
58	<i>Hexanchus griseus</i> (Bonnaterre, 1788)	M	ANI, TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ranjan Kumar et al. 2018)	
59	<i>Heptranchias perlo</i> (Bonnaterre, 1788)	M	ANI, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Ranjan Kumar et al. 2018)	
Order: Lamniformes Garman, 1885					
Family: Alopiidae Bonaparte, 1835					
60	<i>Alopias pelagicus</i> Nakamura, 1935	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL, KA, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2013a)	
61	<i>Alopias superciliosus</i> Lowe, 1841	M	ANI, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
62	<i>Alopias vulpinus</i> (Bonnaterre, 1788)	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL, KA, GA, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2013a, Talwar 1974)	
Family: Odontaspidae Müller & Henle, 1839					
63	<i>Odontaspis ferox</i> (Risso, 1810)	M	No specific location	(Akhilesh et al. 2014)	
64	<i>Odontaspis noronhai</i> (Maul, 1955)	M	No specific location	(Akhilesh et al. 2014)	
Family: Lamnidae Bonaparte, 1835					
65	<i>Carcharodon carcharias</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	MB	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
66	<i>Isurus oxyrinchus</i> Rafinesque, 1810	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012)	
67	<i>Isurus paucus</i> Guitart Manday, 1966	M	Indian south western EEZ	(Akhilesh et al. 2014, ICAR-CMFRI 2022)	
68	<i>Lamna nasus</i> (Bonnaterre, 1788)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Carchariidae Müller & Henle, 1838					
69	<i>Carcharias taurus</i> Rafinesque, 1810	M	ANI, KA, GJ	(Barman et al. 2000, 2013a, Tyabji et al. 2018)	
70	<i>Carcharias tricuspidatus</i> Day, 1878	M	TN, KL, MH	(Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012)	
Family: Pseudocarchariidae Taylor, Compagno & Struhsaker, 1983					
71	<i>Pseudocarcharias kamoharai</i> (Matsubara, 1936)	M	TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Order: Myliobatiformes					
Family: Aetobatidae Agassiz, 1858					
72	<i>Aetobatus flagellum</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	M	ANI, WB, OD, TN, GA	(Patil et al. 2018, Kar et al. 2017, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Hedge et al. 2013, Bineesh et al. 2020)	Coast of Coromandel (Present Tamilnadu & Andhrapradesh)
73	<i>Aetobatus narinari</i> (Euphrase, 1790)	MB	WB, OD, AP, TN, KA, MH, GJ	(Patil et al. 2018, Yennawar et al. 2015, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
74	<i>Aetobatus ocellatus</i> (Kuhl,	MB	ANI, LK,	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mishra et al.	

	1823)		WB, OD	2017, Patil et al. 2018)	
Family: Dasyatidae Jordan & Gilbert, 1879					
75	<i>Bathytoshia centroura</i> (Mitchill, 1815)	MB	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
76	<i>Bathytoshia lata</i> (Garman, 1880)	M	ANI, TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Rajan et al. 2013)	
77	<i>Brevitrygon imbricata</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	MBF	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	Tranquebar [Tharangambadi], Tamilnadu
78	<i>Brevitrygon manjajiae</i> Last, Weigmann & Naylor, 2023	M	MH, GJ	(Last et al. 2023)	
79	<i>Brevitrygon walga</i> (Müller & Henle, 1841)	M	WB, OD, AP, TN, GA	(Pati et al. 2018, Mishra et al. 2017, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Hedge et al. 2013)	Ganges Delta, India
80	<i>Dasyatis pastinaca</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	MB	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
81	<i>Hemitrygon bennettii</i> (Müller & Henle, 1841)	M	KL	(Biju et al. 2019)	
82	<i>Himantura fava</i> (Annandale, 1909)	M	WB, OD, AP, TN	(Pati et al. 2018, Mishra et al. 2017, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Bay of Bengal, off Orissa coast
83	<i>Himantura leoparda</i> Manjaji-Matsumoto & Last, 2008	M	ANI, WB	(Manjaji-Matsumoto et al. 2008, Bineesh et al. 2020)	Lower Bengal
84	<i>Himantura marginata</i> (Blyth, 1860)	MB	WB, AP, TN, GA	(Barman et al. 2004, Khan 2002, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Hedge et al. 2013)	Calcutta fish market, West Bengal
85	<i>Himantura uarnak</i> (Gmelin, 1789)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
86	<i>Himantura undulata</i> (Bleeker, 1852)	M	ANI, TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Bineesh et al. 2020)	
87	<i>Maculabatis arabica</i> Manjaji-Matsumoto & Last, 2016	M	KL, GJ	(Manjaji-Matsumoto & Last 2016)	Paratype from Kerala, Gujarat
88	<i>Maculabatis bineeshi</i> Manjaji-Matsumoto & Last, 2016	M	WB	(Manjaji-Matsumoto & Last 2016)	
89	<i>Maculabatis gerrardi</i> (Gray, 1851)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, TN, KL, GA	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Mishra et al. 2017, Biswas et al. 2012, Pati et al. 2018, Hedge et al. 2013)	India
90	<i>Maculabatis pastinacoides</i> (Bleeker, 1852)	M	OD	(Pati et al. 2018)	
91	<i>Megatrygon microps</i> (Annandale, 1908)	M	WB, OD, TN	(Pati et al. 2018, Danda et al. 2017, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
92	<i>Neotrygon caeruleopunctata</i> Last, White & Serét, 2016	M	ANI	(Bineesh et al. 2020)	
93	<i>Neotrygon indica</i> Pavan-Kumar et al., 2018	M	LK, AP, TN, KL	(Pavan-Kumar et al. 2018)	Gulf of Mannar, Tamil Nadu
94	<i>Neotrygon kuhlii</i> (Müller & Henle, 1841)	M	ANI, OD, AP, TN, KL, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Hedge et al. 2013)	
95	<i>Pastinachus ater</i> (Macleay, 1883)	M	ANI	(Bineesh et al. 2020)	

96	<i>Pastinachus sephen</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	MBF	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
97	<i>Pateobatis bleekeri</i> (Blyth, 1860)	MB	WB, OD, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a, Ansari et al. 1995)	Calcutta fish market, West Bengal
98	<i>Pateobatis fai</i> (Jordan & Seale, 1906)	M	ANI	(Bineesh et al. 2020)	
99	<i>Pateobatis jenkinsii</i> (Annandale, 1909)	M	ANI, OD, TN	(Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Bineesh et al. 2020)	Off Ganjam coast, Orissa
100	<i>Pteroplatytrygon violacea</i> (Bonaparte, 1832)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
101	<i>Taeniura lymma</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
102	<i>Taeniurops meyeri</i> (Müller & Henle, 1841)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
103	<i>Telatrygon crozieri</i> (Blyth, 1860)	M	Northern Indian coast	(Last et al. 2016)	
104	<i>Telatrygon zugei</i> (Müller & Henle, 1841)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Khan 2002, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	
105	<i>Urogymnus asperrimus</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	MB	ANI, LK, OD, TN, KL, KA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a, Bineesh et al. 2020)	Mumbai, Maharashtra
106	<i>Urogymnus granulatus</i> (Macleay, 1883)	MB	ANI, TN, KL, MH	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, Kumar et al. 2021a)	
107	<i>Urogymnus polylepis</i> (Bleeker, 1852)	BF	WB	(Sen et al. 2020)	
Family: Gymnuridae Fowler, 1934					
108	<i>Gymnura japonica</i> (Temminck & Schlegel, 1850)	M	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
109	<i>Gymnura micrura</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	M	AP, TN	(Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
110	<i>Gymnura poecilura</i> (Shaw, 1804)	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Khan 2002, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh
111	<i>Gymnura tentaculata</i> (Valenciennes, 1841)	M	WB, OD, AP	(Patil et al. 2018, Danada et al. 2017, Barman et al. 2004)	
112	<i>Gymnura zonurus</i> (Bleeker, 1852)	M	ANI, OD	(Patil et al. 2018, Kumar et al. 2021a)	
Family: Hexatrygonidae Heemstra & Smith, 1980					
113	<i>Hexatrygon bickelli</i> Heemstra & Smith, 1980	M	ANI	(Babu et al. 2011, Bineesh et al. 2020)	10° 44.3' N, long. 74°14.7' E, South west coast of India, Lakshadweep
Family: Mobulidae Gill, 1893					
114	<i>Mobula alfredi</i> (Krefft, 1868)	M	No specific	(Akhilesh et al. 2014)	

			location		
115	<i>Mobula birostris</i> (Walbaum, 1792)	M	ANI, LK, OD, TN, KL	(Patil et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019)	
116	<i>Mobula kuhlii</i> (Müller & Henle, 1841)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, TN, KL, KA, MH	(Ray & Mohapatra 2021, Patil et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, 2013a, Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Bineesh et al. 2020)	India
117	<i>Mobula mobular</i> (Bonnaterre, 1788)	M	AP, TN, MH, GJ	(Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
118	<i>Mobula tarapacana</i> (Philippi, 1892)	M	ANI, TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Kumar et al. 2018)	
119	<i>Mobula thurstoni</i> (Lloyd, 1908)	M	LK, TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	India
Family: Myliobatidae Bonaparte, 1835					
120	<i>Aetomylaeus maculatus</i> (Gray, 1834)	MB	OD, TN, KA, MH, GJ	(Patil et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	
121	<i>Aetomylaeus milvus</i> (Valenciennes, 1841)	M	TN, MH, GJ	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012)	
122	<i>Aetomylaeus nichofii</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	M	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Kar et al. 2017, Patil et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
123	<i>Aetomylaeus vespertilio</i> (Bleeker, 1852)	M	ANI, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Bineesh et al. 2020)	
Family: Plesiobatidae Nishida, 1990					
124	<i>Plesiobatis daviesi</i> (Wallace, 1967)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Rhinopterae Jordan & Evermann, 1896					
125	<i>Rhinoptera javanica</i> Müller & Henle, 1841	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, TN, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Patil et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a, Ray & Mohapatra 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Coast of Malabar
126	<i>Rhinoptera jayakari</i> Boulenger, 1895	M	ANI, TN, KL	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Biju et al. 2019, Pradeep et al. 2018)	
127	<i>Rhinoptera sewelli</i> Misra, 1947	M	KA	(Akhilesh et al. 2014)	West Hill, off Calicut coast, Kerala, Arabian Sea
Order: Orectolobiformes Compagno, 1973					
Family: Ginglymostomatidae Gill, 1862					
128	<i>Nebrius ferrugineus</i> (Lesson, 1831)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012, Tyabji et al. 2018)	
Family: Hemiscylliidae Gill, 1862					
129	<i>Chiloscyllium arabicum</i> Gubanov, 1980	M	TN, KL, KA	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a)	
130	<i>Chiloscyllium griseum</i> Müller & Henle, 1838	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012, Talwar 1974)	Puducherry
131	<i>Chiloscyllium hasseltii</i> Bleeker, 1852	M	ANI	(Kumar et al. 2018)	

132	<i>Chiloscyllium indicum</i> (Gmelin, 1789)	MBF	ANI, WB, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Danda et al. 2017, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012, Talwar 1974)	
133	<i>Chiloscyllium plagiosum</i> (Anonymous [Bennett], 1830)	M	WB, AP, TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Sanyal et al. 2012, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
134	<i>Chiloscyllium punctatum</i> Müller & Henle, 1838	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Sanyal et al. 2012, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004)	
Family: Parascylliidae Gill, 1862					
135	<i>Cirrhoscyllium exolitum</i> Smith & Radcliffe, 1913	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Rhinodontidae Müller & Henle, 1841					
136	<i>Rhinodon typus</i> Smith, 1828	M	LK, WB, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Kar et al. 2017, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012)	
Family: Stegostomatidae Gill, 1862					
137	<i>Stegostoma tigrinum</i> (Forster, 1781)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Order: Rajiformes					
Family: Gurgesiellidae de Buen, 1959					
138	<i>Cruriraja andamanica</i> (Lloyd, 1909)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Andaman Sea, 10°21'N, 92°46'15"E
139	<i>Fenestraja mamillidens</i> (Alcock, 1889)	M	GJ	(Barman et al. 2012)	
Family: Rajidae Blainville, 1816					
140	<i>Dipturus johannisdavisi</i> (Alcock, 1899)	M	LK, KL	(Alcock 1899)	Laccadive Sea, off Travancore coast, 11°14'30"N, 74°57'15"E
141	<i>Orbiraja powelli</i> (Alcock, 1898)	M	ANI, TN	(Bineesh et al. 2020)	
142	<i>Raja miraletus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
143	<i>Rostroraja alba</i> (Lacepède, 1803)	M	KL	(Nair 2006)	
Order: Rhinopristiformes					
Family: Glaucostegidae Last, Séret & Naylor, 2016					
144	<i>Glaucostegus granulatus</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	ANI, Wb, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Khan 2002, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Puducherry
145	<i>Glaucostegus halavi</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	M	No specific location	(Akhilesh et al. 2014)	
146	<i>Glaucostegus obtusus</i> (Müller & Henle, 1841)	M	WB, AP, TN, KL, GA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Mishra et al. 2017, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, Hedge et	Puducherry

				al. 2013)	
147	<i>Glaucoctegus thouin</i> (Anonymous [Lacepède], 1798)	M	AP, TN, KL, MH, GJ	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, Biju et al. 2019)	
148	<i>Glaucoctegus typus</i> (Anonymous [Bennett], 1830)	MBF	ANI, WB, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Mishra et al. 2017, Nazareth et al. 2022)	
Family: Pristidae Bonaparte, 1835					
149	<i>Anoxypristis cuspidata</i> (Latham, 1794)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Malabar
150	<i>Pristis clavata</i> Garman, 1906	MB	WB	(Mishra et al. 2017)	
151	<i>Pristis pectinata</i> Latham, 1794	MBF	WB, OD, TN	(Pati et al. 2018, Sanyal et al. 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
152	<i>Pristis pristis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, MH, GJ	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Yennawar et al. 2015, Mishra et al. 2017, Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012)	
153	<i>Pristis zijsron</i> Bleeker, 1851	MBF	ANI, OD, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Rhinobatidae Bonaparte, 1835					
154	<i>Acroteriobatus variegatus</i> (Nair & Lal Mohan, 1973)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Gulf of Mannar, off Mandapam, Tamil Nadu
155	<i>Rhinobatos annandalei</i> Norman, 1926	MB	WB, TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Yennawar et al. 2015, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	East channel, mouth of Hughli [Hooghly] River, Bay of Bengal
156	<i>Rhinobatos lionotus</i> Norman, 1926	M	WB, TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Mishra et al. 2017, Yennawar et al. 2015)	East Channel, mouth of Hooghly River, Bay of Bengal
157	<i>Rhinobatos punctifer</i> Compagno & Randall, 1987	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Rhinidae Müller & Henle, 1841					
158	<i>Rhina ancylostomus</i> Bloch & Schneider, 1801	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mishra et al. 2017, Yennawar et al. 2015, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Coromandel coast (Tamilnadu or Andhra Pradesh)
159	<i>Rhynchobatus australiae</i> Whitley, 1939	M	ANI	(Bineesh et al. 2020)	
160	<i>Rhynchobatus djiddensis</i> (Forskål, 1775)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mishra et al. 2017, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
161	<i>Rhynchobatus laevis</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	M	WB	(Yennawar et al. 2015)	
162	<i>Rhynchobatus palpebratus</i> Compagno & Last, 2008	M	No specific location	(Akhilesh et al. 2014)	

	Order: Squaliformes Compagno, 1973				
	Family: Centrophoridae Bleeker, 1859				
163	<i>Centrophorus atromarginatus</i> Garman, 1913	M	ANI	(Kumar et al. 2018)	
164	<i>Centrophorus granulosus</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	M	ANI, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
165	<i>Centrophorus moluccensis</i> Bleeker, 1860	M	TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
166	<i>Centrophorus squamosus</i> (Bonnaterre, 1788)	M	Western Indian coast EEZ	(Akhilesh et al. 2010)	
167	<i>Centrophorus uyato</i> (Rafinesque, 1810)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
168	<i>Deania profundorum</i> (Smith & Radcliffe, 1912)	M	Western Indian coast EEZ	(Akhilesh et al. 2010)	
	Family: Etmopteridae Fowler, 1934				
169	<i>Centroscyllium ornatum</i> (Alcock, 1889)	M	WB, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Sanyal et al. 2012)	Swatch off No-ground, Bay of Bengal, 21°06'30"N, 89°10'E
170	<i>Etmopterus pusillus</i> (Lowe, 1839)	M	Western Indian coast EEZ	(Akhilesh et al. 2010)	
	Family: Somniosidae Jordan, 1888				
171	<i>Centroselachus crepidater</i> (Barbosa du Bocage & de Brito Capello, 1864)	M	KL	(Biju et al. 2019)	
172	<i>Scymnodon ichiharai</i> Yano & Tanaka, 1984	M	ANI	(Kumar et al. 2018)	
173	<i>Somniosus microcephalus</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
174	<i>Zameus squamulosus</i> (Günther, 1877)	M	KL	(Akhilesh et al. 2013)	
	Family: Squalidae de Blainville, 1816				
175	<i>Squalus acanthias</i> Linnaeus, 1758	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
176	<i>Squalus blainville</i> (Risso, 1827)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
177	<i>Squalus hemipinnis</i> White, Last & Yearsley, 2007	M	ANI	(Kumar et al. 2018)	
178	<i>Squalus lalannei</i> Baranes, 2003	M	No specific location	(Akhilesh et al. 2014)	
179	<i>Squalus megalops</i> (MacLeay, 1881)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
180	<i>Squalus mitsukurii</i> Jordan & Snyder, 1903	M	KL, KA	(Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2013a)	
	Order: Squatiniformes				
	Family: Squatinidae Blainville, 1816				
181	<i>Squatina africana</i> Regan,	M	LK	(Ambily et al. 2018)	

	1908				
182	<i>Squatina leae</i> Weigmann, Vaz, Akhilesh, Leeney & Naylor, 2023	M	LK	(Weigmann et al. 2023)	Off Lakshadweep, southwestern India, 11°5'47"N, 72°2'21"E
Order: Torpediniformes					
Family: Narcinidae Gill, 1862					
183	<i>Benthobatis moresbyi</i> Alcock, 1898	M	ANI, LK	(Alcock 1898)	Laccadive Sea, off Travancore coast, 7°17'30"N, 76°54'30"E
184	<i>Narcine atzi</i> Carvalho & Randall, 2003	M	AP	(Sujatha et al. 2016)	
185	<i>Narcine brevilabiata</i> Bessednov, 1966	M	TN	(Sureandiran et al. 2022)	
186	<i>Narcine brunnea</i> Annandale, 1909	M	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004)	Bay of Bengal
187	<i>Narcine lingula</i> Richardson, 1846	M	TN, MH	(de Carvalho et al. 1999)	
188	<i>Narcine maculata</i> (Shaw, 1804)	M	WB, TN	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh
189	<i>Narcine oculifera</i> Carvalho, Compagno & Mee 2002	M	TN	(Akhilesh et al. 2014, Sureandiran et al. 2023b)	
190	<i>Narcine prodorsalis</i> Bessednov, 1966	M	OD, AP	(Roy et al. 2019a)	
191	<i>Narcine timlei</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	M	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Tranquebar [Tharangambadi], Tamilnadu
Family: Narkidae Fowler, 1934					
192	<i>Heteronarce mollis</i> (Lloyd, 1907)	M	KL	(Talwar 1981)	
193	<i>Narke dipterygia</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	M	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Bhatt et al. 2022)	Tranquebar [Tharangambadi], Tamilnadu
Family: Torpedinidae Henle, 1834					
194	<i>Torpedo fuscomaculata</i> Peters, 1855	MB	LK, OD	(Rajan et al. 2021, Roy et al. 2019a)	
195	<i>Torpedo marmorata</i> Risso, 1810	M	OD, TN	(Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
196	<i>Torpedo panthera</i> Olfers, 1831	M	OD, AP, TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
197	<i>Torpedo polleni</i> (Bleeker, 1865)	M	AP	(Ravali et al. 2019)	
198	<i>Torpedo sinuspersici</i> Olfers, 1831	MB	OD, TN, KL, MH	(Biju et al. 2019, Biswas et al. 2012, Barman et al. 2012, Roy et al. 2019a)	
199	<i>Torpedo zugmayeri</i> Engelhardt, 1912	M	No specific location	Akhilesh et al. 2014	
Class: Holocephali					
Order: Chimaeriformes					
Family: Chimaeridae Rafinesque, 1815					
200	<i>Hydrolagus</i>	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	

	<i>africanus</i> (Gilchrist, 1922)				
Family: Rhinochimaeridae Garman 1901					
201	<i>Neoharriotta pinnata</i> (Schnakenbeck, 1931)	M	ANI, TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ranjan Kumar et al. 2018)	
202	<i>Rhinochimaera atlantica</i> Holt & Byrne, 1909	M	TN	(Chembian 2007)	
203	<i>Rhinochimaera pacifica</i> (Mitsukuri, 1895)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Class: Actinopteri					
Order: Acanthuriformes					
Family: Acanthuridae Bonaparte, 1835					
204	<i>Acanthurus auranticavus</i> Randall, 1956	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
205	<i>Acanthurus bariene</i> Lesson, 1831	M	ANI, TN	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
206	<i>Acanthurus blochii</i> Valenciennes, 1835	M	LK, AP, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
207	<i>Acanthurus dussumieri</i> Valenciennes, 1835	M	ANI, LK, AP, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Silambarasan et al. 2022)	
208	<i>Acanthurus gahhm</i> (Gmelin, 1789)	M	OD, TN	(Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
209	<i>Acanthurus grammoptilus</i> Richardson, 1843	M	AP	(Silambarasan et al. 2022)	
210	<i>Acanthurus japonicus</i> (Schmidt, 1931)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
211	<i>Acanthurus leucosternon</i> Bennett, 1833	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
212	<i>Acanthurus lineatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
213	<i>Acanthurus mata</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a)	Coromandel coast (Tamilnadu or Andhra Pradesh)
214	<i>Acanthurus nigricans</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
215	<i>Acanthurus nigricauda</i> Duncker & Mohr, 1929	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
216	<i>Acanthurus nigrofuscus</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	ANI, LK, OD, AP, TN, KL, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
217	<i>Acanthurus nigroris</i> Valenciennes, 1835	M	Western Indian Coast?	(Kapoor 2002)	
218	<i>Acanthurus pyroferus</i> Kittlitz, 1834	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
219	<i>Acanthurus tennentii</i> Günther, 1861	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
220	<i>Acanthurus thompsoni</i> (Fowler, 1923)	MB	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	

221	<i>Acanthurus triostegus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
222	<i>Acanthurus tristis</i> Randall, 1993	M	ANI, WB, OD	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018)	
223	<i>Acanthurus xanthopterus</i> Valenciennes, 1835	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
224	<i>Ctenochaetus cyanocheilus</i> Randall & Clements, 2001	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
225	<i>Ctenochaetus striatus</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1825)	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
226	<i>Ctenochaetus strigosus</i> (Bennett, 1828)	M	LK, AP, TN, GA	(Rajan et al. 2021, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
227	<i>Ctenochaetus truncatus</i> Randall & Clements, 2001	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
228	<i>Naso annulatus</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1825)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Padate et al. 2017)	
229	<i>Naso brachycentron</i> (Valenciennes, 1835)	M	ANI, LK	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Rajan et al. 2021)	
230	<i>Naso brevirostris</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
231	<i>Naso elegans</i> (Rüppell, 1829)	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
232	<i>Naso hexacanthus</i> (Bleeker, 1855)	MB	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
233	<i>Naso lituratus</i> (Forster, 1801)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
234	<i>Naso lopezi</i> Herre, 1927	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
235	<i>Naso reticulatus</i> Randall, 2001	M	WB	(Mohapatra et al. 2013b)	
236	<i>Naso thynnoides</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	TN	(Padate et al. 2017)	
237	<i>Naso tonganus</i> (Valenciennes, 1835)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
238	<i>Naso tuberosus</i> Lacepède, 1801	MB	ANI, LK, AP, TN	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Rajan et al. 2021, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
239	<i>Naso unicornis</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
240	<i>Naso vlamingii</i> (Valenciennes, 1835)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
241	<i>Paracanthurus hepatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
242	<i>Zebrasoma desjardini</i> (Bennett, 1836)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
243	<i>Zebrasoma scopas</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
244	<i>Zebrasoma velifer</i> (Bloch, 1795)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	No locality, India. (Tranquebar given as locality in Bloch &

					Schneider 1801)
245	<i>Zebrasoma xanthurum</i> (Blyth, 1852)	M	TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
	Family: Antigonidae Jordan & Evermann, 1898				
246	<i>Antigonia rubescens</i> (Günther, 1860)	M	AP, KL, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2004, Barman et al. 2000)	
247	<i>Antigonia indica</i> Parin & Borodulina, 1986	M	No specific location	(Bogutskaya 2007)	Off South western Indian coastline (08°45'N, 75°39'E)
Family: Cepolidae Rafinesque, 1815					
248	<i>Acanthocepola abbreviata</i> (Valenciennes, 1835)	M	AP, TN	(Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
249	<i>Acanthocepola indica</i> (Day, 1888)	M	ANI, AP, TN	(Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Jayakumar et al. 2022)	Chennai, Tamilnadu
250	<i>Acanthocepola limbata</i> (Valenciennes, 1835)	M	WB, TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Sen et al. 2023a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
251	<i>Cepola macrophthalma</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	M	KL	(Nair & Geetha 2019)	
252	<i>Owstonia whiteheadi</i> (Talwar, 1973)	M	KL	(Talwar 1973)	Off Quilon (Kollam), Kerala, India, about 9°N, 76°E
Family: Chaetodontidae Rafinesque, 1815					
253	<i>Chaetodon andamanensis</i> Kuitert & Debelius, 1999	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	Great Nicobar Island, Nicobar Islands, eastern Indian Ocean
254	<i>Chaetodon auriga</i> Forsskål, 1775	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
255	<i>Chaetodon bennetti</i> Cuvier, 1831	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
256	<i>Chaetodon citrinellus</i> Cuvier, 1831	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
257	<i>Chaetodon collare</i> Bloch, 1787	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL, KA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, 2013a)	
258	<i>Chaetodon decussatus</i> Cuvier, 1829	M	ANI, LK, OD, AP, TN, KL, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, Mohanty et al. 2020)	India
259	<i>Chaetodon ephippium</i> Cuvier, 1831	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
260	<i>Chaetodon falcula</i> Bloch, 1795	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Tranquebar [Tharangambadi], Tamilnadu
261	<i>Chaetodon fasciatus</i> Forsskål, 1775	M	TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
262	<i>Chaetodon gardineri</i> Norman, 1939	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	

263	<i>Chaetodon guttatissimus</i> Bennett, 1833	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
264	<i>Chaetodon interruptus</i> Ahl, 1923	M	ANI, LK	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Rajan et al. 2021)	
265	<i>Chaetodon kleinii</i> Bloch, 1790	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
266	<i>Chaetodon leucopleura</i> Playfair, 1867	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
267	<i>Chaetodon lineolatus</i> Cuvier, 1831	M	ANI, LK, TN, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
268	<i>Chaetodon lunula</i> (Lacepède, 1802)	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
269	<i>Chaetodon madagaskariensis</i> Ahl, 1923	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
270	<i>Chaetodon melannotus</i> Bloch & Schneider, 1801	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Tranquebar [Tharangambadi], Tamilnadu
271	<i>Chaetodon mertensii</i> Cuvier, 1831	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
272	<i>Chaetodon meyeri</i> Bloch & Schneider, 1801	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
273	<i>Chaetodon octofasciatus</i> Bloch, 1787	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
274	<i>Chaetodon ornatissimus</i> Cuvier, 1831	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
275	<i>Chaetodon oxycephalus</i> Bleeker, 1853	M	ANI, TN	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
276	<i>Chaetodon plebeius</i> Cuvier, 1831	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
277	<i>Chaetodon punctatofasciatus</i> Cuvier, 1831	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
278	<i>Chaetodon rafflesii</i> (Bennett, 1830)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
279	<i>Chaetodon semeion</i> Bleeker, 1855	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
280	<i>Chaetodon semilarvatus</i> Cuvier, 1831	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
281	<i>Chaetodon speculum</i> Cuvier, 1831	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
282	<i>Chaetodon triangulum</i> Cuvier, 1831	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
283	<i>Chaetodon trifascialis</i> Quoy & Gaimard, 1825	M	ANI, LK, TN, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
284	<i>Chaetodon trifasciatus</i> Park, 1797	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
285	<i>Chaetodon vagabundus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	M	ANI, LK, OD, AP, TN, KL, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012)	
286	<i>Chaetodon unimaculatus</i> Bloch, 1787	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
287	<i>Chaetodon xanthocephalus</i> Bennett, 1833	M	ANI, LK, TN, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	

288	<i>Chaetodon xanthurus</i> Bleeker, 1857	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
289	<i>Chelmon rostratus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	MB	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
290	<i>Coradion altivelis</i> McCulloch, 1916	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
291	<i>Forcipiger flavissimus</i> Jordan & McGregor, 1898	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
292	<i>Forcipiger longirostris</i> (Broussonet, 1782)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
293	<i>Hemitaurichthys polylepis</i> (Bleeker, 1857)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
294	<i>Hemitaurichthys zoster</i> (Bennett, 1831)	M	ANI, LK	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Rajan et al. 2021)	
295	<i>Heniochus chrysostomus</i> Cuvier, 1831	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
296	<i>Heniochus diphreutes</i> Jordan, 1903	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
297	<i>Heniochus macrolepidotus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2012a, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a, Hedge et al. 2013)	
298	<i>Heniochus monoceros</i> Cuvier, 1831	M	AP, TN	(Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
299	<i>Heniochus pleurotaenia</i> Ahl, 1923	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
300	<i>Heniochus singularius</i> Smith & Radcliffe, 1911	M	ANI, LK, TN, AP	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Kumar et al. 2024)	
301	<i>Heniochus varius</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
302	<i>Parachaetodon ocellatus</i> (Cuvier, 1831)	M	KL	(Biju et al. 2019)	
303	<i>Roa excelsa</i> (Jordan, 1921)	M	AP	(Silambarasan et al. 2022)	
304	<i>Roa jayakari</i> (Norman, 1939)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Drepaneidae Gill, 1872					
305	<i>Drepane longimana</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, GA	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Hedge et al. 2013)	Tranquebar [Tharangambadi], Tamilnadu
306	<i>Drepane punctata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
Family: Emmelichthyidae Poey, 1867					
307	<i>Erythrocles acarina</i> Kotthaus, 1974	M	KL	(Heemstra & Randall 1977)	
Family: Ephippidae Bleeker, 1859					
308	<i>Ephippus orbis</i> (Bloch, 1787)	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Tranquebar [Tharangambadi], Tamilnadu

309	<i>Platax batavianus</i> Cuvier, 1831	M	ANI	(Rajan & Vikas 2016)	
310	<i>Platax orbicularis</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
311	<i>Platax pinnatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
312	<i>Platax teira</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, 2013a, Hedge et al. 2013)	
313	<i>Tripteronodon orbis</i> Playfair, 1867	M	AP, TN	(Kapoor et al. 2002)	
Family: Gerreidae Bleeker, 1859					
314	<i>Gerres erythrourus</i> (Bloch, 1791)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Hedge et al. 2013)	
315	<i>Gerres filamentosus</i> Cuvier, 1829	MBF	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Rajan et al. 2021, Shaji et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
316	<i>Gerres infasciatus</i> Iwatsuki & Kimura, 1998	M	WB	(Mishra et al. 2018)	
317	<i>Gerres limbatus</i> Cuvier, 1830	MB	LK, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Nandi et al. 2008)	Malabar
318	<i>Gerres longirostris</i> (Lacepède, 1801)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, GA, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Hedge et al. 2013)	
319	<i>Gerres macracanthus</i> Bleeker, 1854	MB	AP, TN, KL, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
320	<i>Gerres methueni</i> Regan, 1920	MBF	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
321	<i>Gerres oblongus</i> Cuvier, 1830	M	ANI, LK, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a)	
322	<i>Gerres oyena</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
323	<i>Gerres phaiya</i> Iwatsuki & Heemstra, 2001	MB	WB, OD, KL, KA, MH	(Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, 2013a)	Mangalore, Karnataka, India
324	<i>Gerres setifer</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA,	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	Ganges River estuaries, West Bengal

			MH, GJ		
325	<i>Pentaprion longimanus</i> (Cantor, 1849)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Kar et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Haemulidae Gill, 1885					
326	<i>Diagramma pictum</i> (Thunberg, 1792)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	
327	<i>Plectorhinchus albovittatus</i> (Rüppell, 1838)	MB	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
328	<i>Plectorhinchus ceylonensis</i> (Smith, 1956)	M	ANI	(Rajan & Vikas 2016)	
329	<i>Plectorhinchus chaetodonoides</i> Lacepède, 1801	MB	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Sandra et al. 2022)	
330	<i>Plectorhinchus cinctus</i> (Temminck & Schlegel, 1843)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
331	<i>Plectorhinchus diagrammus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
332	<i>Plectorhinchus flavomaculatus</i> (Cuvier, 1830)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
333	<i>Plectorhinchus gaterinus</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
334	<i>Plectorhinchus gibbosus</i> (Lacepède, 1802)	MBF	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Hedge et al. 2013)	
335	<i>Plectorhinchus griseus</i> (Cuvier, 1830)	MB	AP, KA, GJ	(Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a)	Malabar
336	<i>Plectorhinchus lineatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	MB	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
337	<i>Plectorhinchus pictus</i> (Tortonese, 1936)	M	LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a, Barman et al. 2000)	
338	<i>Plectorhinchus polytaenia</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	M	LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
339	<i>Plectorhinchus schotaf</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	MB	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Hedge et al. 2013)	
340	<i>Plectorhinchus vittatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	
341	<i>Plectorhinchus sordidus</i> (Klunzinger, 1870)	M	ANI, AP	(Rajan et al. 2013, Silambarasan et al. 2022)	
342	<i>Pomadasys andamanensis</i> McKay & Satapoomin, 1994	M	ANI	(Das & Sivaperuman 2023)	

343	<i>Pomadasy argenteus</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
344	<i>Pomadasy argyreus</i> (Valenciennes, 1833)	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Coromandel coast (Tamilnadu or Andhra Pradesh)
345	<i>Pomadasy commersonii</i> (Lacepède, 1801)	MB	OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
346	<i>Pomadasy furcatus</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Hedge et al. 2013)	
347	<i>Pomadasy grunniens</i> (Forster, 1801)	MB	ANI, TN, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
348	<i>Pomadasy jubelini</i> (Cuvier, 1830)	MBF	MH	(Dorairaj 1970)	
349	<i>Pomadasy kaakan</i> (Cuvier, 1830)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Puducherry & Mahé
350	<i>Pomadasy maculatus</i> (Bloch, 1793)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
351	<i>Pomadasy multimaculatus</i> (Playfair, 1867)	MB	KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	
352	<i>Pomadasy olivaceus</i> (Day, 1875)	MB	AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
353	<i>Pomadasy stridens</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	No specific location	(Kapoor et al. 2002)	
354	<i>Pomadasy trifasciatus</i> Fowler, 1937	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Leiognathidae Gill, 1893					
355	<i>Aurigequula fasciata</i> (Lacepède, 1803)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
356	<i>Aurigequula longispinis</i> (Valenciennes, 1835)	M	ANI, OD, AP	(Barman et al. 2004, Rajan et al. 2021, Patil et al. 2018)	
357	<i>Aurigequula striata</i> (James & Badrudeen, 1991)	M	TN, KL	(James & Badrudeen 1991, Abraham et al. 2011)	Gulf of Mannar at Pamban, Mandapam & Kilakarai, Tamilnadu
358	<i>Deveximentum insidiator</i> (Bloch, 1787)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL,	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018,	Surat District, Gujarat

			KA, GA, MH, GJ	Mogalear et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
359	<i>Deveximentum indicium</i> (Monkolprasit, 1973)	MB	GJ	(Azaz et al. 2021)	
360	<i>Deveximentum interruptum</i> (Valenciennes, 1835)	MB	Puducherry, Tamilnadu	(Cuvier & Valenciennes 1835)	Puducherry
361	<i>Deveximentum ruconius</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Khan 2002, Rajan et al. 2013, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalear et al. 2018, Talwar 1974, Abraham et al. 2011)	Ganges River estuaries, West Bengal
362	<i>Equulites absconditus</i> Chakrabarty & Sparks, 2010	M	TN, KL	(Mogalear et al. 2018, Abraham et al. 2011)	
363	<i>Equulites elongatus</i> (Günther, 1874)	M	OD, TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Patil et al. 2018, Mogalear et al. 2018)	
364	<i>Equulites leuciscus</i> (Günther, 1860)	M	ANI, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalear et al. 2018)	
365	<i>Equulites lineolatus</i> (Valenciennes, 1835)	M	ANI, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalear et al. 2018)	
366	<i>Equulites oblongus</i> (Valenciennes, 1835)	M	TN	(Suzuki & Kimura 2017)	
367	<i>Equulites popei</i> (Whitley, 1932)	M	Western Coast of India	(Kapoor et al. 2002)	
368	<i>Eubleekeria jonesi</i> (James, 1971)	M	OD, TN, KL	(Pati et al. 2018, Mogalear et al. 2018, Abraham et al. 2011)	Palk Bay, vicinity of Mandapam, Tamil Nadu
369	<i>Eubleekeria splendens</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalear et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	Visakhapattanam, Andhra Pradesh
370	<i>Eubleekeria rapsoni</i> (Munro, 1964)	M	ANI, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalear et al. 2018, Abraham et al. 2011)	
371	<i>Gazza achlamys</i> Jordan & Starks, 1917	MB	ANI, OD, TN, KL, KA	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalear et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a)	
372	<i>Gazza dentex</i> (Valenciennes, 1835)	M	OD	(Seth et al. 2019)	
373	<i>Gazza minuta</i> (Bloch, 1795)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalear et al. 2018, Hedge et al. 2013)	Malabar
374	<i>Karalla daura</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA,	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalear et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	Visakhapattanam, Andhra Pradesh

			MH, GJ		
375	<i>Karalla dussumieri</i> (Valenciennes, 1835)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalear et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	Coromandel coast (Tamilnadu or Andhra Pradesh)
376	<i>Leiognathus berbis</i> (Valenciennes, 1835)	MB	ANI, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalear et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
377	<i>Leiognathus equula</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	MBF	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021: Khan 2002, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalear et al. 2018, Abraham et al. 2011)	
378	<i>Nuclequula blochii</i> (Valenciennes, 1835)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalear et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a, Talwar 1974)	Kerala
379	<i>Nuclequula gerreoides</i> (Bleeker, 1851)	M	WB, KA	(Mishra et al. 2017, Barman et al. 2013a)	
380	<i>Nuclequula mannusella</i> Chakrabarty & Sparks, 2007	M	TN, KL	(Mishra et al. 2017, Abraham et al. 2011)	
381	<i>Nuclequula nuchalis</i> (Temminck & Schlegel, 1845)	M	TN, KL	(Mogalear et al. 2018, Abraham et al. 2011)	
382	<i>Photopectoralis aureus</i> (Abe & Haneda, 1972)	M	KL	(Abraham et al. 2011)	
383	<i>Photopectoralis bindus</i> (Valenciennes, 1835)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Khan 2002, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalear et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh
Family: Lethrinidae Bonaparte, 1831					
384	<i>Gnathodentex aureolineatus</i> (Lacepède, 1802)	M	ANI, LK, AP, KA	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Barman et al. 2004, 2013a)	
385	<i>Gymnocranius elongatus</i> Senta, 1973	M	ANI, AP, TN, KA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
386	<i>Gymnocranius grandoculis</i> (Valenciennes, 1830)	M	ANI, AP, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a)	
387	<i>Gymnocranius griseus</i> (Temminck & Schlegel, 1843)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
388	<i>Lethrinus amboinensis</i> Bleeker, 1854	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
389	<i>Lethrinus borbonicus</i> Valenciennes, 1830	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
390	<i>Lethrinus conchyliatus</i> (Smith, 1959)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	

391	<i>Lethrinus erythracanthus</i> Valenciennes, 1830	M	ANI, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
392	<i>Lethrinus erythropterus</i> Valenciennes, 1830	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
393	<i>Lethrinus harak</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	MB	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
394	<i>Lethrinus laticaudis</i> Alleyne & Macleay, 1877	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
395	<i>Lethrinus lentjan</i> (Lacepède, 1802)	MB	ANI, LK, KL, KA	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2013a)	
396	<i>Lethrinus mahsena</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
397	<i>Lethrinus microdon</i> Valenciennes, 1830	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
398	<i>Lethrinus miniatus</i> (Forster, 1801)	MB	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
399	<i>Lethrinus nebulosus</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	MB	ANI, LK, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	
400	<i>Lethrinus obsoletus</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
401	<i>Lethrinus olivaceus</i> Valenciennes, 1830	M	ANI, OD, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Mohanty et al. 2023b)	
402	<i>Lethrinus ornatus</i> Valenciennes, 1830	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
403	<i>Lethrinus reticulatus</i> Valenciennes, 1830	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
404	<i>Lethrinus rubrioperculatus</i> Sato, 1978	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
405	<i>Lethrinus semicinctus</i> Valenciennes, 1830	M	Southern India	(Kapoor et al. 2002)	
406	<i>Lethrinus variegatus</i> Valenciennes, 1830	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
407	<i>Lethrinus xanthochilus</i> Klunzinger, 1870	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
408	<i>Monotaxis grandoculis</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
409	<i>Monotaxis heterodon</i> (Bleeker, 1854)	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Karuppiyah et al. 2024)	
410	<i>Wattisia mossambica</i> (Smith, 1957)	M	ANI, AP	(Rajan et al. 2013, Barman et al. 2004)	
Family: Lobotidae Gill, 1861					
411	<i>Datnioides polota</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	WB, OD, TN	(Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Ganges River estuaries, West Bengal
412	<i>Hapalogenys bengalensis</i> Mohapatra, Ray & Kumar, 2013	M	WB	(Mohapatra et al. 2013a)	Digha Mohana, West Bengal

413	<i>Lobotes surinamensis</i> (Bloch, 1790)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Lutjanidae Gill, 1861					
414	<i>Aphareus furca</i> (Lacepède, 1801)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
415	<i>Aphareus rutilans</i> Cuvier, 1830	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
416	<i>Aprion virescens</i> Valenciennes, 1830	M	ANI, LK, WB, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Misra 1959, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
417	<i>Apsilus fuscus</i> Valenciennes, 1830	M	LK	(Kapoor et al. 2002)	
418	<i>Caesio caeruleaurea</i> Lacepède, 1801	M	ANI, LK, WB, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Chakraborty et al. 2020a, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
419	<i>Caesio cuning</i> (Bloch, 1791)	M	ANI, AP, TN, GA	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biswas et al. 2012, Barman et al. 2004, Hedge et al. 2013)	
420	<i>Caesio lunaris</i> Cuvier, 1830	M	ANI, LK, AP, KL, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012)	
421	<i>Caesio striata</i> Rüppell, 1830	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
422	<i>Caesio teres</i> Seale, 1906	M	ANI, AP	(Rajan et al. 2013, Barman et al. 2004)	
423	<i>Caesio varilineata</i> Carpenter, 1987	M	ANI, TN, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012)	
424	<i>Caesio xanthonota</i> Bleeker, 1853	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Ray & Mohapatra 2017, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Mohanty et al. 2021c)	
425	<i>Dipterygonotus balteatus</i> (Valenciennes, 1830)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
426	<i>Etelis carbunculus</i> Cuvier, 1828	M	ANI, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a)	
427	<i>Etelis coruscans</i> Valenciennes, 1862	M	ANI, AP, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a)	
428	<i>Gymnocaesio gymnoptera</i> (Bleeker, 1856)	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL, KA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, 2013a)	
429	<i>Lipocheilus carnolabrum</i> (Chan, 1970)	M	ANI, AP, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a)	
430	<i>Lutjanus argentimaculatus</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	MBF	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	
431	<i>Lutjanus bengalensis</i> (Bloch, 1790)	M	ANI, LK, WB, AP,	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Barman et al. 2000,	Bay of Bengal, eastern Indian

			TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Ocean
432	<i>Lutjanus biguttatus</i> (Valenciennes, 1830)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
433	<i>Lutjanus bohar</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	MBF	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
434	<i>Lutjanus bouton</i> (Lacepède, 1802)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
435	<i>Lutjanus carponotatus</i> (Richardson, 1842)	M	ANI, WB, AP	(Rajan et al. 2013, Manna & Goswami 1985, Barman et al. 2004)	
436	<i>Lutjanus coeruleolineatus</i> (Ruppell, 1838)	M	AP, TN	(Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
437	<i>Lutjanus decussatus</i> (Cuvier, 1828)	M	ANI, WB, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Ray et al. 2017, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
438	<i>Lutjanus dodecakanthoides</i> (Bleeker, 1854)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
439	<i>Lutjanus ehrenbergii</i> (Peters, 1869)	MBF	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
440	<i>Lutjanus erythropterus</i> Bloch, 1790	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	
441	<i>Lutjanus fulviflamma</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Manna & Goswami 1985, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	
442	<i>Lutjanus fulvus</i> (Forster, 1801)	MBF	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2013a)	
443	<i>Lutjanus gibbus</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
444	<i>Lutjanus guilcheri</i> Fourmanoir, 1959	M	ANI, WB, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Talwar et al. 1992, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
445	<i>Lutjanus indicus</i> Allen, White & Erdmann, 2013	MBF	LK, WB, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
446	<i>Lutjanus johnii</i> (Bloch, 1792)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Khan 2002, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a, Ansari et al. 1995)	
447	<i>Lutjanus kasmira</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Talwar et al. 1992, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
448	<i>Lutjanus lemniscatus</i> (Valenciennes, 1828)	M	ANI, AP, TN, KA	(Rajan et al., 2013, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a)	

449	<i>Lutjanus lunulatus</i> (Park, 1797)	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Ray et al. 2017, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995, Mohanty et al. 2020)	
450	<i>Lutjanus lutjanus</i> Bloch, 1790	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	
451	<i>Lutjanus madras</i> (Valenciennes, 1831)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	
452	<i>Lutjanus malabaricus</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a, Ansari et al. 1995)	Coromandal Coast (Tamilnadu or Andhra Pradesh)
453	<i>Lutjanus monostigma</i> (Cuvier, 1828)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Ray et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
454	<i>Lutjanus notatus</i> (Cuvier, 1828)	M	AP	(Velamala et al. 2017)	
455	<i>Lutjanus quinquelineatus</i> (Bloch, 1790)	M	ANI, LK, WB, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Ray et al. 2017, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
456	<i>Lutjanus rivulatus</i> (Cuvier, 1828)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Das et al. 2007, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
457	<i>Lutjanus rufolineatus</i> (Valenciennes, 1830)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
458	<i>Lutjanus russellii</i> (Bleeker, 1849)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
459	<i>Lutjanus sanguineus</i> (Cuvier, 1828)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, TN, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al., 2013, Rajan et al., 2021, Das et al. 2007, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a, Barman et al. 2012, Barman et al. 2000)	
460	<i>Lutjanus sebae</i> (Cuvier, 1816)	MB	ANI, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
461	<i>Lutjanus vitta</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1824)	MB	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
462	<i>Lutjanus xanthopinnis</i> Iwatsuki, Tanaka & Allen, 2015	M	ANI	(Praveenraj et al. 2018)	
463	<i>Macolor macularis</i> Fowler, 1931	M	KL	(Biju et al. 2019)	

464	<i>Macolor niger</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
465	<i>Pterocaesio chrysozona</i> (Cuvier, 1830)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
466	<i>Pterocaesio digramma</i> (Bleeker, 1864)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
467	<i>Pterocaesio marri</i> Schultz, 1953	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
468	<i>Pterocaesio pisang</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	M	ANI, LK, AP, KL, KA	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2004, 2013a)	
469	<i>Paracaesio sordida</i> Abe & Shinohara, 1962	M	ANI, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
470	<i>Pterocaesio tessellata</i> Carpenter, 1987	M	ANI, WB, AP	(Rajan et al. 2013, Ray & Mohapatra 2017, Barman et al. 2004)	
471	<i>Pterocaesio tile</i> (Cuvier, 1830)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
472	<i>Pterocaesio trilineata</i> Carpenter, 1987	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, Sandra et al. 2022)	
473	<i>Paracaesio xanthurus</i> (Bleeker, 1869)	M	ANI, LK, AP, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a)	
474	<i>Pinjalo lewisi</i> Randall, Allen & Anderson, 1987	M	ANI, TN, KL, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
475	<i>Pinjalo pinjalo</i> (Bleeker, 1850)	M	ANI, WB, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Ray et al. 2017, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
476	<i>Pristipomoides argyrogrammicus</i> (Valenciennes, 1832)	M	OD	(Pati et al. 2018)	
477	<i>Pristipomoides auricilla</i> (Jordan, Evermann & Tanaka, 1927)	M	TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
478	<i>Pristipomoides filamentosus</i> (Valenciennes, 1830)	M	ANI, WB, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Ray et al. 2017, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
479	<i>Pristipomoides multidentis</i> (Day, 1871)	M	ANI, WB, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Ray et al. 2017, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Andaman Islands, India
480	<i>Pristipomoides sieboldii</i> (Bleeker, 1855)	M	ANI, AP, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a)	
481	<i>Pristipomoides typus</i> Bleeker, 1852	M	ANI, WB, TN, KA	(Rajan et al. 2013, Ray et al. 2017, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a)	
482	<i>Pristipomoides zonatus</i> (Valenciennes, 1830)	M	ANI, AP, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
483	<i>Symphorus nematophorus</i> (Bleeker, 1860)	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
Family: Malacanthidae Poey, 1861					
484	<i>Hoplolatilus andamanensis</i> Allen &	M	ANI	(Allen & Erdmann 2019)	"The Wall" dive site, Havelock

	Erdmann, 2019				Island, Andaman Islands
485	<i>Hoplostethus frontocinctus</i> (Günther, 1887)	M	TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
486	<i>Malacanthus brevirostris</i> Guichenot, 1848	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
487	<i>Malacanthus latovittatus</i> (Lacepède, 1801)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Monodactylidae Jordan & Evermann, 1898					
488	<i>Monodactylus argenteus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	MBF	ANI, LK, WB, OD, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a, Hedge et al. 2013)	India
489	<i>Monodactylus falciformis</i> Lacepède, 1801	MBF	TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a,)	
490	<i>Monodactylus kottelati</i> Pethiyagoda, 1991	MBF	OD	(Mohapatra et al. 2014)	
Family: Nemipteridae Regan, 1913					
491	<i>Nemipterus andamanensis</i> Bineesh, Russell & Chandra, 2018	M	ANI	(Bineesh et al. 2018)	Junglighat fish market, Port Blair, Cinque Island, south Andaman Islands
492	<i>Nemipterus bipunctatus</i> (Valenciennes, 1830)	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Hedge et al. 2013)	
493	<i>Nemipterus furcosus</i> (Valenciennes, 1830)	MB	ANI, OD, TN, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
494	<i>Nemipterus hexodon</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1824)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
495	<i>Nemipterus japonicus</i> (Bloch, 1791)	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
496	<i>Nemipterus mesoprion</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
497	<i>Nemipterus nematophorus</i> (Bleeker, 1854)	M	WB, OD, AP, TN	(Mohapatra et al. 2013, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Roul et al. 2022)	
498	<i>Nemipterus nemurus</i> (Bleeker, 1857)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
499	<i>Nemipterus peronii</i> (Valenciennes, 1830)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Roul et al. 2022)	
500	<i>Nemipterus randalli</i> Russell, 1986	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mohapatra et al. 2013, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Roul et al. 2022)	
501	<i>Nemipterus zysron</i> (Bleeker, 1856)	M	ANI, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	

502	<i>Parascolopsis aspinosa</i> (Rao & Rao, 1981)	M	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Mohapatra et al. 2013, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Mohanty et al. 2020)	Off Waltair, Andhra Pradesh, Eastern coast of India
503	<i>Parascolopsis baranesi</i> Russell & Golani, 1993	M	TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
504	<i>Parascolopsis boesemani</i> (Rao & Rao, 1981)	M	AP, TN	(Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Waltair, Andhra Pradesh, eastern coast of India, 17°42'N, 83°20'E
505	<i>Parascolopsis capitinis</i> Russell, 1996	M	KL	(Nair et al. 2016)	
506	<i>Parascolopsis eriomma</i> (Jordan & Richardson, 1909)	M	ANI, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Biswas et al. 2012)	
507	<i>Parascolopsis inermis</i> (Temminck & Schlegel, 1843)	M	ANI, AP, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
508	<i>Parascolopsis townsendi</i> Boulenger, 1901	M	KA, GA, GJ	(Barman et al. 2000, 2013a, Hedge et al. 2013)	
509	<i>Scolopsis aurata</i> (Park, 1797)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
510	<i>Scolopsis bilineata</i> (Bloch, 1793)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
511	<i>Scolopsis bimaculata</i> Rüppell, 1828	M	AP, TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
512	<i>Scolopsis ciliata</i> (Lacepède, 1802)	MB	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
513	<i>Scolopsis frenata</i> (Cuvier, 1830)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
514	<i>Scolopsis ghanam</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	ANI, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Barman et al. 2012)	
515	<i>Scolopsis lineata</i> Quoy & Gaimard, 1824	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
516	<i>Scolopsis margaritifera</i> (Cuvier, 1830)	M	ANI, TN, GA	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
517	<i>Scolopsis monogramma</i> (Cuvier, 1830)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
518	<i>Scolopsis taeniata</i> (Cuvier, 1830)	M	TN, GJ	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000)	
519	<i>Scolopsis taenioptera</i> (Cuvier, 1830)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
520	<i>Scolopsis vosmeri</i> (Bloch, 1792)	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mohapatra et al. 2013, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
521	<i>Scolopsis xenochrous</i> Günther, 1872	M	LK, TN, KL	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karuppasamy et al. 2020)	
Family: Pomacanthidae Jordan & Evermann, 1898					
522	<i>Apolemichthys trimaculatus</i> (Cuvier, 1831)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
523	<i>Apolemichthys xanthurus</i> (Bennett, 1833)	M	ANI, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a)	

524	<i>Centropyge bicolor</i> (Bloch, 1787)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
525	<i>Centropyge bispinosa</i> (Günther, 1860)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
526	<i>Centropyge eibli</i> Klausewitz, 1963	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Nicobar Islands, India
527	<i>Centropyge flavivectoralis</i> Randall & Klausewitz, 1977	M	ANI, TN	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
528	<i>Centropyge flavissima</i> (Cuvier, 1831)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
529	<i>Centropyge multispinis</i> (Playfair, 1867)	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
530	<i>Centropyge nox</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
531	<i>Centropyge tibicen</i> (Cuvier, 1831)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
532	<i>Centropyge vrolikii</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
533	<i>Chaetodontoplus melanosoma</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
534	<i>Chaetodontoplus mesoleucus</i> (Bloch, 1787)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
535	<i>Genicanthus lamarck</i> (Lacepède, 1802)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
536	<i>Pomacanthus annularis</i> (Bloch, 1787)	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Ray et al. 2012, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2013a, Talwar 1974)	
537	<i>Pomacanthus imperator</i> (Bloch, 1787)	M	ANI, LK, WB, AP, TN, KL, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Ray et al. 2012, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, Barman et al. 2012)	
538	<i>Pomacanthus navarchus</i> (Cuvier, 1831)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
539	<i>Pomacanthus semicirculatus</i> (Cuvier, 1831)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Ray et al. 2012, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, Mohanty et al. 2020)	
540	<i>Pomacanthus sexstriatus</i> (Cuvier, 1831)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
541	<i>Pomacanthus xanthometopon</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
542	<i>Pygoplites diacanthus</i> (Boddaert, 1772)	M	ANI, LK, TN, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
Family: Priacanthidae Günther, 1859					
543	<i>Cookeolus japonicus</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	MH	(Barman et al. 2012)	
544	<i>Heteropriacanthus cruentatus</i> (Lacepède, 1801)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	
545	<i>Priacanthus blochii</i> Bleeker, 1853	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	

546	<i>Priacanthus hamrur</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Kar et al. 2017, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	
547	<i>Priacanthus macracanthus</i> Cuvier, 1829	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
548	<i>Priacanthus prolixus</i> Starnes, 1988	M	WB, KL, KA	(Motomura et al. 2001, Mohanty et al. 2019)	
549	<i>Priacanthus tayenus</i> Richardson, 1846	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
550	<i>Pristigenys nipponia</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
551	<i>Pristigenys refulgens</i> (Valenciennes, 1862)	M	AP	(Silambarasan et al. 2022)	
Family: Scatophagidae Gill, 1883					
552	<i>Scatophagus argus</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Shaji et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2013a, Karmakar et al. 2012, Talwar 1974)	India
Family: Sciaenidae Cuvier, 1829					
553	<i>Atrobucca alcocki</i> Talwar, 1980	M	MH	(Barman et al. 2012)	Arabian Sea off Mumbai, India, depth about 60 meters
554	<i>Atrobucca antonbruun</i> Sasaki, 1995	M	East Coast Of India	(Sasaki 1995)	
555	<i>Atrobucca nibe</i> (Jordan & Thompson, 1911)	M	OD, AP, TN	(Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
556	<i>Atrobucca trewavasae</i> Talwar & Sathiarajan, 1975	M	TN	(Talwar & Sathiarajan 1975)	Bay of Bengal off Madras
557	<i>Argyrosomus amoyensis</i> (Bleeker, 1863)	M	OD, TN, MH, GJ	(Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012)	
558	<i>Argyrosomus hololepidotus</i> (Lacepède, 1801)	M	MH, GJ	(Barman et al. 2000, 2012)	
559	<i>Bahaba chaptis</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MB	WB	(Mishra et al. 2017)	Chinsura (Hooghly estuary), West Bengal
560	<i>Chrysochir aurea</i> (Richardson, 1846)	MB	WB, OD, AP, TN, MH	(Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
561	<i>Daysciaena albida</i> (Cuvier, 1830)	MB	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH	(Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	Puducherry
562	<i>Dendrophysa russelii</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Hedge et al. 2013)	Visakhapatnam

563	<i>Johnius amblycephalus</i> (Bleeker, 1855)	MBF	ANI, OD, TN, KL, GA	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Hedge et al. 2013)	
564	<i>Johnius belangerii</i> (Cuvier, 1830)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	Malabar
565	<i>Johnius borneensis</i> (Bleeker, 1851)	MBF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
566	<i>Johnius carouna</i> (Cuvier, 1830)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Malabar
567	<i>Johnius carutta</i> Bloch, 1793	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Hedge et al. 2013)	Hooghly Estuary near Diamond Harbor
568	<i>Johnius coitor</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MBF	WB, OD, TN, GA, UP, AS, MN, MZ, TR	(Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman 2002, Hedge et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2021a, Kar & Sen 2007)	Ganges River as far as Kanpur & Jumna River at Angra & at Visakhapatnam
569	<i>Johnius distinctus</i> (Tanaka, 1916)	M	AP	(Shameem & Rao 1998)	
570	<i>Johnius dorsalis</i> (Peters, 1855)	MB	OD, MH	(Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
571	<i>Johnius dussumieri</i> (Cuvier, 1830)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	Malabar
572	<i>Johnius elongatus</i> Lal Mohan, 1976	M	AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	Veraval, Gujarat
573	<i>Johnius gangeticus</i> Talwar, 1991	BF	WB, OD, UP	(Mishra et al. 2017, Puvala et al. 2023)	Ganga River at Allahabad, Uttar Pradesh
574	<i>Johnius macropterus</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a, Talwar 1974)	
575	<i>Johnius macrorhynchus</i> (Lal Mohan, 1976)	M	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Mumbai, Maharashtra
576	<i>Johnius mannarensis</i> Lal Mohan, 1971	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Off Pamban, Gulf of Mannar, Tamilnadu
577	<i>Johnius sina</i> (Cuvier, 1830)	M	AP, TN, GJ	(Barman et al. 2000, 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Puducherry & Malabar

578	<i>Kathala axillaris</i> (Cuvier, 1830)	M	OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	Malabar
579	<i>Macrospinosa cuja</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MB	WB, OD	(Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018)	Ganges River estuaries, West Bengal
580	<i>Nibea chui</i> Trewavas, 1971	M	OD, TN, MH	(Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
581	<i>Nibea coibor</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MB	WB, OD, TN, KA	(Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a)	Ganges River estuaries, West Bengal
582	<i>Nibea maculata</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	M	LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Tharangambadi, Tamil Nadu
583	<i>Nibea soldado</i> (Lacepède, 1802)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	
584	<i>Otolithes cuvieri</i> Trewavas, 1974	M	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	Malabar
585	<i>Otolithes ruber</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	
586	<i>Otolithoides biauritus</i> (Cantor, 1849)	M	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
587	<i>Otolithoides pama</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MB	WB, OD, TN, GA, MH	(Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, Talwar 1974)	
588	<i>Panna heterolepis</i> Trewavas, 1977	M	WB, TN	(Danda et al. 2017, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Kolkata, West Bengal
589	<i>Panna microdon</i> (Bleeker, 1849)	MB	WB, OD, AP, TN, KA	(Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
590	<i>Paranibea semiluctuosa</i> (Cuvier, 1830)	M	OD, AP, TN, KA, MH, GJ	(Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Malabar
591	<i>Pennahia aneus</i> (Bloch, 1793)	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	Malabar
592	<i>Pennahia macrocephalus</i> (Tang, 1937)	M	WB, AP, GJ	(Yennawar et al. 2015, Barman et al. 2000, 2004)	
593	<i>Protonibea diacanthus</i> (Lacepède, 1802)	MB	LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA,	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	

			MH, GJ		
594	<i>Pterolithus maculatus</i> (Cuvier, 1830)	MB	WB, OD, AP, TN, GA	(Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
595	<i>Umbrina canariensis</i> Valenciennes, 1843	M	GJ	(Barman et al. 2000)	
Family: Siganiidae Richardson, 1837					
596	<i>Siganus argenteus</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1825)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
597	<i>Siganus canaliculatus</i> (Park, 1797)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a, Talwar 1974)	
598	<i>Siganus corallinus</i> (Valenciennes, 1835)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
599	<i>Siganus fuscescens</i> (Houttuyn, 1782)	MB	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
600	<i>Siganus guttatus</i> (Bloch, 1787)	MB	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Sandra et al. 2022)	
601	<i>Siganus javus</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a, Talwar 1974)	
602	<i>Siganus insomnis</i> Woodland & Anderson, 2014	M	LK, AP, TN, KL	(Woodland & Anderson, 2014, Silambarasan et al. 2022)	
603	<i>Siganus labyrinthodes</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
604	<i>Siganus lineatus</i> (Valenciennes, 1835)	MB	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
605	<i>Siganus magnificus</i> (Burgess, 1977)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
606	<i>Siganus puelloides</i> Woodland & Randall, 1979	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
607	<i>Siganus punctatus</i> (Schneider & Forster, 1801)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
608	<i>Siganus spinus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
609	<i>Siganus stellatus</i> (Forskål, 1775)	M	ANI, LK, TN, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
610	<i>Siganus vermiculatus</i> (Valenciennes, 1835)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, 2013a)	
611	<i>Siganus virgatus</i> (Valenciennes, 1835)	MB	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
612	<i>Siganus vulpinus</i> (Schlegel & Müller, 1845)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
Family: Sillaginidae Richardson, 1846					

613	<i>Sillaginopodys chondropus</i> (Bleeker, 1849)	MB	ANI, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012,2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
614	<i>Sillaginopsis domina</i> (Cuvier, 1816)	MB	WB, OD, AP, TN	(Khan 2002, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Pondicherry
615	<i>Sillago aeolus</i> Jordan & Evermann, 1902	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
616	<i>Sillago indica</i> McKay Dutt & Sujatha, 1985	M	AP, MH	(Barman et al. 2004, Barman et al. 2012)	Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh
617	<i>Sillago ingenua</i> McKay, 1985	M	AP	(Barman et al. 2004)	
618	<i>Sillago intermedia</i> Wongratana, 1977	M	OD, AP, TN, KA, MH	(Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2012,2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
619	<i>Sillago lutea</i> McKay, 1985	M	OD, AP, TN, KL, KA	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
620	<i>Sillago maculata</i> Quoy & Gaimard, 1824	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
621	<i>Sillago sihama</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Khan 2002, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012,2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	
622	<i>Sillago soringa</i> Dutt & Sujatha, 1982	M	AP, TN	(Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Off Visakhapatnam
623	<i>Sillago vincenti</i> McKay, 1980	MB	OD, AP, TN, KL, KA	(Shaji et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Kavanad near Neendakara, Kerala
Family: Sparidae Rafinesque, 1818					
624	<i>Acanthopagrus arabicus</i> Iwatsuki, 2013	M	Western coast of India	(Iwatsuki 2013)	
625	<i>Acanthopagrus berda</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012,2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
626	<i>Acanthopagrus bifasciatus</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	MB	AP, KA, MH, GJ	(Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012,2013a)	
627	<i>Acanthopagrus datnia</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MBF	WB	(Mishra et al. 2017)	Ganges River mouths, West Bengal
628	<i>Acanthopagrus latus</i> (Houttuyn, 1782)	MBF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KA, MH, GJ	(Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012,2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
629	<i>Argyrops bleekeri</i> Oshima, 1927	M	WB, OD	(Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018)	
630	<i>Argyrops spinifer</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012,2013a)	
631	<i>Cheimerius nufar</i> (Valenciennes, 1830)	M	KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2012,2013a)	

632	<i>Crenidens crenidens</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	OD, TN, KA, MH, GJ	(Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	
633	<i>Crenidens indicus</i> Day, 1873	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Northern Indian Ocean
634	<i>Crenidens macracanthus</i> Günther, 1874	M	TN	(Iwatsuki & Maclaine 2013)	Chennai, Tamilnadu
635	<i>Diplodus noct</i> (Valenciennes, 1830)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
636	<i>Diplodus sargus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	M	GJ	(Barman et al. 2000)	
637	<i>Rhabdosargus sarba</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	MB	LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
638	<i>Sparidentex hasta</i> (Valenciennes, 1830)	M	TN, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a, Hedge et al. 2013)	Malabar
Family: Zanclidae Bleeker, 1876					
639	<i>Zanclus cornutus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Order: Acropomatiformes					
Family: Acropomatidae Gill, 1893					
640	<i>Acropoma argentistigma</i> Okamoto & Ida, 2002	M	WB	(Yennawar et al. 2012)	
641	<i>Acropoma japonicum</i> Günther, 1859	M	TN, KL, KA, MH	(Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2012, 2013a, Padate et al. 2017)	
642	<i>Acropoma lacrima</i> Okamoto & Golami, 2017	M	MH	(Okamoto & Golani 2017)	Maharashtra, Arabian Sea, India, 18°59.1'N, 72°48.7'E
Family: Bathyclupeidae Gill, 1896					
643	<i>Bathyclupea hoskynii</i> Alcock, 1891	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Andaman Sea, 11°31'40"N, 92°46'40"E
Family: Champsodontidae Jordan & Snyder, 1902					
644	<i>Champsodon capensis</i> Regan, 1908	M	ANI, LK, WB, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Ray et al. 2022b)	
645	<i>Champsodon nudivittis</i> (Ogilby, 1895)	M	Arabian Sea of India	(Ganga et al. 2014)	
Family: Creediidae Waite, 1899					
646	<i>Chalixodytes tauensis</i> Schultz, 1943	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
Family: Epigonidae Poey, 1861					
647	<i>Epigonus indicus</i> Idrees Babu & Akhilesh, 2020	M	LK	(Idrees Babu & Akhilesh 2020)	Kavaratti Island, Lakshadweep
Family: Hemerocoetidae Kaup, 1873					
648	<i>Pteropsaron indicum</i> Victor & Kumar, 2019	M	LK, KL	(Victor & Kumar 2019)	Off Kerala coast, Lakshadweep Sea, India, 8.16°N, 73.4°E
Family: Pempheridae Bleeker, 1859					
649	<i>Parapriacanthus ransonneti</i> Steindachner, 1870	M	ANI, LK	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Rajan et al. 2021)	
650	<i>Pempheris adusta</i> Bleeker, 1877	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Silambarasan et al. 2022)	

651	<i>Pempheris bineeshi</i> Randall & Victor, 2015	M	TN	(Randall & Victor 2015)	Tuticorin, Tamilnadu
652	<i>Pempheris flavicycla</i> Randall, Satapoomin & Alpermann, 2014	M	ANI, LK, AP	(Randall & Bineesh 2014, Silambarasan et al. 2022)	
653	<i>Pempheris malabarica</i> Cuvier, 1831	M	OD, TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ray et al. 2022c)	Mahé & Malabar
654	<i>Pempheris mangula</i> Cuvier, 1829	M	OD, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Barik et al. 2020)	Coromandel coast, Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh
655	<i>Pempheris molucca</i> Cuvier, 1829	MB	ANI, TN, KL, GA	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Hedge et al. 2013)	
656	<i>Pempheris nesogallica</i> Cuvier, 1831	M	KL	(Koeda et al. 2014)	
657	<i>Pempheris oualensis</i> Cuvier, 1831	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
658	<i>Pempheris sarayu</i> Randall & Bineesh, 2014	M	KL	(Biju et al. 2019)	Kerala, Kovalam, 300 meters north of lighthouse
659	<i>Pempheris schwenkii</i> Bleeker, 1855	M	OD, TN	(Randall & Bineesh 2014, Barik et al. 2020)	
660	<i>Pempheris tominagai</i> Koeda, Yoshino & Tachihara 2014	M	TN	(Randall & Bineesh 2014)	
661	<i>Pempheris vanicolensis</i> Cuvier, 1831	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Pentacerotidae Bleeker, 1859					
662	<i>Histiopterus typus</i> Temminck & Schlegel, 1844	M	KL	(Biju et al. 2019)	
Family: Symphysanodontidae Katayama, 1984					
663	<i>Symphysanodon typus</i> Bleeker, 1877	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
664	<i>Symphysanodon xanthopterygion</i> Anderson & Bineesh, 2011	M	KL	(Anderson & Bineesh 2011)	Off Quilon, Kerala coast
Family: Synagropidae Smith, 1961					
665	<i>Parascombrops pellucidus</i> Alcock, 1889	M	OD, TN, KL	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018)	16 miles east of Mahanadi Delta, depth 68 fathoms
666	<i>Synagrops japonicus</i> (Döderlein, 1883)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Order: Albuliformes					
Family: Albulidae Bleeker, 1849					
667	<i>Albula argentea</i> (Forster, 1801)	MB	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
668	<i>Albula glossodonta</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	B	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
669	<i>Albula oligolepis</i> Hidaka, Iwatsuki & Randall, 2008	MB	TN	(Hidaka et al. 2008)	
670	<i>Albula vulpes</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	MB	ANI, LK, TN, KL, KA	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a)	
Order: Alepocephaliformes					
Family: Alepocephalidae Bonaparte, 1846					

671	<i>Alepocephalus longiceps</i> Lloyd, 1909	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Bay of Bengal, depth 693 fathoms
672	<i>Aulastomatomorpha phospherops</i> Alcock, 1890	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	Off Elicapeni Bank, Laccadive Sea, 11°12'47"N, 74°25'30"E
673	<i>Bathytroctes macrolepis</i> Günther, 1887	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
674	<i>Bathytroctes squamosus</i> Alcock, 1890	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	About 75 miles west of Goa coast, Laccadive Sea
675	<i>Narcetes erimelas</i> Alcock, 1890	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	about 75 miles west of Goa coast, Laccadive Sea, 15°02'N, 72°34'E
Family: Platyroctidae Koefoed, 1927					
676	<i>Platyroctes apus</i> Günther, 1878	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
677	<i>Platyroctes mirus</i> (Lloyd, 1909)	M	LK	(Lloyd 1909)	Laccadive Sea, Bay of Bengal, 12°18'46"N, 74°05'29"E
Order: Anabantiformes					
Family: Aenigmachannidae Britz, Dahanukar, Anoop, Philip, Clark, Raghavan & Rüber, 2020					
678	<i>Aenigmachanna gollum</i> Britz Anoop Dahanukar & Raghavan, 2019	F	KL	(Britz et al. 2020)	Oorakam, Malappuram, Kerala
Family: Anabantidae Bonaparte, 1831					
679	<i>Anabas cobojius</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, MH, CG, NL	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Mishra et al. 2017, Chanda & Jana 2021, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Gangetic provinces
680	<i>Anabas testudineus</i> (Bloch, 1792)	BF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ, UK, UP, MP, TL, CG, BR, JH, AS, ML, AR, NL, MN, TR	(Rajan et al. 2013, Shaji et al. 2019, Karmakar & Das 2005, Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Yadav 2008, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Mishra et al. 2021a, Kumar et al. 2011)	Tharangambadi, Tamil Nadu
Family: Badidae Barlow, Liem & Wickler, 1968					
681	<i>Badis andrewraoi</i> Valdesalici & van der Voort, 2015	F	WB	(Valdesalici & Van der voort 2015)	West Bengal, Darjeeling district
682	<i>Badis assamensis</i> Ahl, 1937	F	WB, AR	(Dey et al. 2015, Bagra et al. 2009)	3 kilometers north of Digholtarang, about 100 kilometers southeastern of

					Dubrugarh (Brahmaputra River drainage), Assam
683	<i>Badis autumnum</i> Valdesalici & van der Voort, 2015	F	WB	(Valdesalici & Van der voort 2015)	West Bengal, Cooch Behar district
684	<i>Badis badis</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, TN, MH, GJ, HP, UK, DL, UP, MP, CG, SK, AS, ML, AR, NL, MN, MZ, TR	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1995, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Bagra et al. 2009, Husain 1997, Barman 2002, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Karmakar 2006, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Sharma 2007, , Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Sharma & Dhanze 2018, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Mishra et al. 2021a, Kar & Sen 2007)	about 65 kilometers north-northeast of Calcutta, West Bengal
685	<i>Badis blosyrus</i> Kullander & Britz, 2002	F	AS	(Kullander & Britz 2002)	Janali River, Raimana, 26°39'00"N, 89°58'00"E, Brahmaputra River drainage, Kokrajhar district, Assam
686	<i>Badis britzi</i> Dahanukar, Kumkar, Katwate & Raghavan, 2015	F	KA	(Dahanukar et al. 2015)	Karnataka, Nagodi tributary of the west-flowing Sharavati River, near the town of Nittur
687	<i>Badis dibruensis</i> Geetakumari & Vishwanath, 2010	F	AS	(Geetakumari & Vishwanath 2010)	7°32'09.98"N, 94°58'02.31"E, Dibru, Dibru River, Brahmaputra River drainage, Assam
688	<i>Badis ferrarisi</i> Kullander & Britz, 2002	F	MN	(Devi & Indra 2012)	
689	<i>Badis kaladanensis</i> Lalramliana, Lalronunga & Singh, 2021	F	MZ	(Lalramliana et al. 2021)	Palak river in the vicinity of Phurra Village, Mizoram
690	<i>Badis kanabos</i> Kullander & Britz, 2002	F	AS	(Kullander & Britz 2002)	Janali River, Raimana, 26°39'00"N, 89°58'00"E, Brahmaputra River drainage, Kokrajhar District, Assam
691	<i>Badis kyanos</i> Valdesalici & van der Voort, 2015	F	WB	(Valdesalici & Van der voort 2015)	West Bengal, Jalpaiguri

692	<i>Badis laspiophilus</i> Valdesalici & van der Voort, 2015	F	WB	(Valdesalici & Van der voort 2015a)	West Bengal, Jalpaiguri
693	<i>Badis limaakumi</i> Praveenraj, 2023	F	NL	(Praveenraj 2023)	Milak River, Mokokchung District, Nagaland, India, 26°26.6270'N, 94°29.0880'E
694	<i>Badis singenensis</i> Geetakumari & Kadu, 2011	F	WB, AR	(Mogelekar et al. 2017)	Brahmaputra drainage, Arunachal Pradesh
695	<i>Badis soraya</i> Valdesalici & van der Voort, 2015	F	WB	(Valdesalici & Van der voort 2015)	West Bengal, Jalpaiguri
696	<i>Badis triocellus</i> Khyriam & Sen, 2013	F	AR	(Khyriam & Sen 2013)	Subansiri river below damsite, lower Subansiri district, Arunachal Pradesh
697	<i>Badis tuivaiei</i> Vishwanath & Shanta, 2004	F	MN	(Vishwanath & Shanta 2004a)	Tuivai River, Churachandpur District, Manipur
698	<i>Dario dario</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	AS, MZ, TR	(Hamilton 1822, Kar & Sen 2007)	Janali River, Raimana, 26°39'00"N, 89°58'00"E, Brahmaputra River drainage, Kokrajhar District, Assam
699	<i>Dario huli</i> Britz & Ali, 2015	F	KA	(Britz & Ali 2015)	Karnataka, unnamed stream between Balehalli & Agumbe, tributary of the Tunga River
700	<i>Dario kaja</i> Britz & Kullander, 2013	F	ML	(Britz & Kullander 2013)	Meghalaya, Jaintia Hills
701	<i>Dario neela</i> Britz, Anoop & Dahanukar, 2018	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Kabini river, Kerala
702	<i>Dario urops</i> Britz, Ali & Philip, 2012	F	KL, KA	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Karnataka, off the Barapole tributary of Valapattanam river
Family: Channidae Fowler, 1934					
703	<i>Channa amphibeus</i> (McClelland, 1845)	F	WB	(Sanyal et al. 2012)	northern Bengal, India
704	<i>Channa andrao</i> Britz, 2013	F	WB	(Britz 2013)	West Bengal, Jalpaiguri district
705	<i>Channa aristonei</i> Praveenraj, Thackeray, Singh, Uma, Moulitharan & Mukhim, 2020	F	ML	(Praveenraj et al. 2020)	Streams at Puriang, East Khasi Hills,

					Meghalaya
706	<i>Channa aurantimaculata</i> Musi kasinthorn, 2000	F	WB	(Mogalekar et al. 2017)	Dibrugarh, Assam
707	<i>Channa aurantipectoralis</i> Lalhlimpuia, Lalronunga & Lalramliana, 2016	F	MZ	(Lalhlimpuia et al. 2016)	Keisalam River, a tributary of Karnaphuli River, in the vicinity of Phuldungsei, Mamit District, Mizoram
708	<i>Channa barca</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, AS, ML, NL, TR	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1995, Barman 2002, Sen 1985)	Brahmaputra river nr. Goalpara, Assam
709	<i>Channa bipuli</i> Praveenraj, Uma, Moulitharan & Bleher, 2018	F	AS	(Praveenraj et al. 2018a)	Small stream at the outskirts of Garbhanga forest, Assam
710	<i>Channa bleheri</i> Vierke, 1991	F	WB, AS	(Dey et al. 2015)	Upper Diburu near Guijam, Assam
711	<i>Channa brahmacharyi</i> Chakraborty, Yardi & Mukherjee, 2020	F	ML	(Chakraborty et al. 2020b)	Simsang river, East Garo Hills district, Meghalaya, India, 25°34'08"N, 90°30'04"E
712	<i>Channa brunnea</i> Praveenraj, Uma, Moulitharan & Kannan, 2019	F	WB	(Dey et al. 2019)	Jalpaiguri district, West Bengal
713	<i>Channa diplogramma</i> (Day, 1865)	F	KL	(Shaji et al., 2019)	Cochin, Malabar coast
714	<i>Channa gachua</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	ANI, WB, OD, TN, KL, KA, HP, UK, DL, UP, RJ, TL, CG, BR, JH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Shaji et al. 2019, Dubey et al. 2015, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Jagtap 2013, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Mishra et al. 2021a, Hembrom & Bodra 2021, Kumar et al. 2011)	West Bengal
715	<i>Channa harcourtbutleri</i> (Annandale, 1918)	F	ANI, AP	(Praveenraj et al. 2018b, Laskar et al. 2023)	
716	<i>Channa kelaartii</i> (Günther, 1861)	F	Southern Peninsular India	(Sudasinghe et al. 2020)	
717	<i>Channa lipor</i> Praveenraj, Uma, Moulitharan & Singh, 2019	F	ML	(Praveenraj et al. 2019)	Umraling River, Umraling village, Ri-Bhoi district, Meghalaya

718	<i>Channa marulius</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ, HP, PU, DL, UP, RJ, MP, TL, CG, BR, JH, AS, ML, AR, MN, TR	(Shaji et al. 2019, Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Barman 2002, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Jagtap 2013, Mishra et al. 2021a, Brraich & Saini 2019, Hembrom & Bodra 2021, Murugan & Prabakaran 2012)	River Ganges
719	<i>Channa melanostigma</i> Geetakumari & Vishwanath, 2011	F	AR	(Geetakumari & Vishwanath 2011)	Lohit River, Brahmaputra River drainage, Tezu, 27°54'41"N, 96°10'23"E, Lohit District, Arunachal Pradesh
720	<i>Channa micropeltes</i> (Cuvier, 1831)	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2000)	
721	<i>Channa orientalis</i> Bloch & Schneider, 1801	F	WB, OD, AP, TN, GA, MH, GJ, PU, MP, CG, SK, AS, ML, AR, MN, MZ, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman 1993, 2002, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Bagra et al. 2009, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Karmakar 2006, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Yadav 2008, Brraich & Saini 2019, Kar & Sen 2007)	
722	<i>Channa ornatipinnis</i> Britz, 2008	F	MZ	(Muthukumar et al. 2017)	Collected from Mizoram, Champhai district, Tuivawl village, Tuivawl River
723	<i>Channa pardalis</i> Knight, 2016	F	ML	(Knight 2016)	Streams in Nongstoin, West Khasi Hills, Meghalaya
724	<i>Channa pomanensis</i> Gurumayum & Tamang, 2016	F	AR	(Gurumayum & Tamang 2016)	Poma River at Poma (Brahmaputra basin) about 10 km west to capital town, Itanagar, Papum Pare district, Arunachal Pradesh
725	<i>Channa pseudomarulius</i> (Günther, 1861)	F	KL	(Shaji et al., 2019)	East Indian continent

726	<i>Channa punctata</i> (Bloch, 1793)	BF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ, HP, PU, UK, HY, DL, UP, RJ, MP, TL, CG, BR, JH, SK, AS, ML, AR, NL, MN, TR	(Rajan et al. 2013, Shaji et al. 2019, Karmakar & Das 2005, Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar 2006, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Yadav 2008, Jagtap 2013, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a, Brraich & Saini 2019, Hembrom & Bodra 2021, Murugan & Prabaharan 2012)	Coromandal coast
727	<i>Channa quinquefasciata</i> Praveenraj, Uma, Knight, Moulitharan, Balasubramanian, Bineesh & Bleher, 2018	F	WB	(Dey et al. 2015)	Torsa River, Howlong bridge, near Bhutan foothills, North Bengal
728	<i>Channa rara</i> Britz, Dahanukar, Anoop & Ali, 2019	F	MH	(Britz et al. 2019)	Ratnagiri District, Maharashtra
729	<i>Channa stewartii</i> (Playfair, 1867)	F	ANI, WB, MH, GJ, MP, AS, ML, AR, MN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Bagra et al. 2009, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000)	Cachar, Assam
730	<i>Channa striata</i> (Bloch, 1793)	BF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ, PU, UK, HY, DL, UP, RJ, MP, TL, CG, BR, JH, AS, ML, AR, MN, TR	(Rajan et al. 2013, Shaji et al. 2019, Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a, Brraich & Saini 2019, Hembrom & Bodra 2021, Murugan & Prabaharan 2012)	Tharangambadi
731	<i>Channa stiktos</i> Lalramliana, Knight, Lalhlimpaia & Singh, 2018	F	MZ	(Lalramliana et al. 2018)	Tiau River in the vicinity of Zokhawthar Village, Kaladan River drainage, Mizoram
732	<i>Channa torsaensis</i> Dey, Nur, Chowdhury, Sarkar, Kosygin & Barat, 2019	F	WB	(Dey et al. 2019a)	orsa River, Dakshin Barajhar forest, Alipurduar district, West Bengal
Family: N&idae Bleeker, 1852					

733	<i>Nandus andrewi</i> Ng & Jaafar, 2008.	F	WB	(Ng & Jaafar 2008)	Ichamati River drainage, vicinity of Duttaphulia, 23°14'N, 88°43'E, Nadia District, West Bengal
734	<i>Nandus banshlaii</i> Kapuri, Sinha, De, Roy & Bhakat, 2021	F	WB	(Chanda & Jana 2021)	Birbhum district, West Bengal
735	<i>Nandus meni</i> Hossain & Sarker, 2013	F	WB	(Chanda & Jana 2021)	
736	<i>Nandus nandus</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	WB, OD, TN, KL, MH, GJ, PU, UK, DL, UP, MP, TL, CG, BR, AS, ML, AR, TR	(Shaji et al. 2019, Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Husain 1997, Sen 1985, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Mishra et al. 2021a, Braich & Saini 2019, Murugan & Prabakaran 2012)	Ponds of the Gangetic provinces
Family: Osphronemidae van der Hoeven, 1832					
737	<i>Ctenops nobilis</i> McClelland, 1845	BF	WB, OD, MP, CG, SK, AS	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Chanda & Jana 2021, Sen 1985, Karmakar 2006, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Sharma 2007)	Rivers at Sikkim passes, northern Bengal
738	<i>Macropodus opercularis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	F	TN	(Knight & Balasubramanian 2015)	
739	<i>Osphronemus goramy</i> Lacepède, 1801	F	AP, TN, KA, MH, UK, RJ, TL, TR	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar et al. 2012, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021)	
740	<i>Pseudosphromenus cupanus</i> (Cuvier, 1831)	BF	TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, NL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Karmakar & Das 2005, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar et al. 2012, Yadav 2008)	Arian-Coupang River, Puducherry,
741	<i>Pseudosphromenus dayi</i> (Köhler, 1908)	BF	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Kerala
742	<i>Trichogaster chuna</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, MH, UP, BR, SK, AS, ML, AR, MN, TR	(Dubey et al. 2017, Sen 1995, Bagra et al. 2009, Barman 2002, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Karmakar 2006, Karmakar et al. 2012, Mishra et al. 2021a, Kumari & Yadav 2020)	Brahmaputra River at Gualpara [Goalpara], Assam
743	<i>Trichogaster fasciata</i> Bloch & Schneider, 1801	F	LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, GJ, HP, UK, HY, DL, UP, RJ, MP, TL, CG, BR, AS, ML, AR, NL, MN, TR	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Barman 2002, Dubey et al. 2017, Sen 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Bagra et al. 2009, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Jagtap 2013, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a, Murugan & Prabakaran 2012)	Tharangambadi
744	<i>Trichogaster labiosa</i> Day, 187	F	WB, AR,	(Paul & Das 2016, Bagra et al. 2009,	

	7		MN	Karmakar & Das 2005a)	
745	<i>Trichogaster lalius</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	AS	(Kar & Sen 2007)	common in the ponds, marshes, & ditches of the Gangetic provinces
746	<i>Trichopodus trichopterus</i> (Pallas, 1770)	F	TN	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	
747	<i>Trichopsis vittata</i> (Cuvier, 1831)	F	WB, TN	(Knight & Balasubramanian 2015, Dutta et al. 2024)	
Family: Pristolepididae Regan, 1913					
748	<i>Pristolepis fasciata</i> (Bleeker, 1851)	F	MP	(Sharma 2007)	
749	<i>Pristolepis malabarica</i> (Günther, 1864)	F	KL	(Günther 1864a)	Hill-ranges of Travancore, Malabar coast
750	<i>Pristolepis marginata</i> Jerdon, 1849	F	OD, TN, KL, KA, MH	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Pati et al. 2018, , Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar et al. 2012)	north Malabar, near Canote
751	<i>Pristolepis pentacantha</i> Plamoottil, 2014	F	KL	(Plamoottil 2014b)	Bavali, Kabani River, Wayanad, Kerala
752	<i>Pristolepis procerus</i> Plamoottil, 2017	F	KL	(Plamoottil 2017)	Chaliyar, Kozhikode District, Kerala
753	<i>Pristolepis rubripinnis</i> Britz, Kumar & Baby, 2012	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Pamba River near Edathua, Kerala
Order: Anguilliformes					
Family: Anguillidae Rafinesque, 1810					
754	<i>Anguilla australis</i> Richardson, 1841	MBF	ANI, OD	(Rajan et al. 2013, Pati et al. 2018)	
755	<i>Anguilla bengalensis</i> (Gray, 1831)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ, MP, TL, JH, AR, MN, TR	(Rajan et al. 2013, Shaji et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Barman et al. 2000, Yadav 2008, Hembrom & Bodra 2021)	River Ganges
756	<i>Anguilla bicolor</i> McClelland, 1844	MBF	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ, TL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Shaji et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016)	
757	<i>Anguilla marmorata</i> Quoy & Gaimard, 1824	MBF	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
758	<i>Anguilla nebulosa</i> McClelland, 1844	MBF	WB, TN	(Mishra et al. 2017, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Bengal
Family: Colocongridae Smith, 1976					
759	<i>Coloconger raniceps</i> Alcock, 1889	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Andaman sea off Ross Island
760	<i>Congrhynchus</i>	M	ANI, KL	(Smith et al. 2018, Kodeeswaran et al.	

	<i>talabonoides</i> Fowler, 1934			2023f)	
761	<i>Paraconger notialis</i> Kanazawa, 1961	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Congridae Kaup, 1856					
762	<i>Ariosoma albimaculatum</i> Kodeeswaran, Dash, Kumar & Lal, 2022	M	TN	(Kodeeswaran et al. 2022c)	Off Kanyakumari [Colachel fishing harbour], Arabian Sea, southwest coast of India
763	<i>Ariosoma anago</i> (Temminck & Schlegel, 1846)	M	LK, OD, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
764	<i>Ariosoma anagoides</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
765	<i>Ariosoma bengalense</i> Ray, Acharya, Khatua, Roy, Mohapatra & Mishra, 2022	M	WB	(Ray et al. 2022c)	Petua Ghat, West Bengal, India, depth 168 meters
766	<i>Ariosoma bowersi</i> (Jenkins, 1903)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
767	<i>Ariosoma dolichopterum</i> Karmovskaya, 2015	M	TN	(Kodeeswaran et al. 2021)	
768	<i>Ariosoma gnanadossi</i> Talwar & Mukherjee, 1977	M	TN	(Talwar & Mukherjee 1977)	off Madras, east coast of India, Bay of Bengal
769	<i>Ariosoma gracile</i> Kodeeswaran, Kathirvelpandian, Mohapatra, Kumar & Sarkar, 2024	M	KL	(Kodeeswaran et al. 2024)	Kalamukku Fishing Harbour, Kochi, Kerala, Arabian Sea
770	<i>Ariosoma indicum</i> Kodeeswaran, Kathirvelpandian, Acharya, Mohanty, Mohapatra, Kumar & Lal, 2022	M	WB, KL	(Kodeeswaran et al. 2022, 2024)	Trawl bycatch. Kalamukku fish landing centre, off Kochi
771	<i>Ariosoma kannani</i> Kodeeswaran, Kathirvelpandian, Ray, Kumar, Mohapatra & Sarkar, 2024	M	WB, TN	(Kodeeswaran et al. 2024)	Rameshwaram Fish Landing Centre, Tamil Nadu, Gulf of Mannar, east coast of India, Bay of Bengal (9°16'N, 79°18'E)
772	<i>Ariosoma majus</i> (Asano, 1958)	M	WB	(Roy et al. 2021)	
773	<i>Ariosoma mauritianum</i> (Pappenheim, 1914)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
774	<i>Ariosoma maurostigma</i> Kodeeswaran, Mohapatra, Dhinakaran, Kumar & Lal, 2022	M	KL	(Kodeeswaran et al. 2022b)	Off Kerala coast

775	<i>Ariosoma melanospilos</i> Kodeeswaran, Jayakumar, Akash, Kumar & Lal, 2021	M	TN	(Kodeeswaran et al. 2021)	Off Kanyakumari [Colachel fish landing centre], southwest coast of India, Indian Ocean, 8°10'21.92"N, 77°15'2.98"E
776	<i>Bathycongrus macrocerus</i> (Alcock, 1894)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Andaman Sea, 7 miles south-east by south of Ross Island
777	<i>Bathymyrus echinorhynchus</i> Alcock, 1889	M	OD	(Pati et al. 2018)	16 miles east of Devi River mouth in Mahanadi Delta
778	<i>Bathymyrus simus</i> Smith, 1965	M	WB, TN, KA	(Kodeeswaran et al. 2022d, Jayakumar et al. 2020)	
779	<i>Bathyyuroconger vicinus</i> (Vaillant, 1888)	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
780	<i>Conger cinereus</i> Rüppell, 1830	MB	ANI, LK, OD, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al., 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
781	<i>Conger melanopterus</i> Kodeeswaran, Smith, Dhas, Kumar & Lal, 2023	M	TN	(Kodeeswaran et al. 2023e)	Colachel fishing harbour (deep-sea trawl), Indian Ocean, southwest coast of India, 8°10'21.92"N, 77°15'2.98"E
782	<i>Conger myriaster</i> (Brevoort, 1856)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
783	<i>Diploconger polystigmatus</i> Kottaus, 1968	M	WB	(Mohanty et al. 2019a, Sen et al. 2021)	
784	<i>Gavialiceps taeniola</i> Alcock, 1889	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Andaman sea
785	<i>Gnathophis musteliceps</i> (Alcock, 1894)	M	ANI	(Alcock 1984)	Bay of Bengal
786	<i>Gorgasia maculata</i> Klausewitz & Eibl-Eibesfeldt, 1959	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Tillanchong, entrance to Castle Bay, Nicobar Islands
787	<i>Heteroconger hassi</i> (Klausewitz & Eibl-Eibesfeldt, 1959)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
788	<i>Heteroconger obscurus</i> (Klausewitz & Eibl-Eibesfeldt, 1959)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Great Nicobar Island, Nicobar Islands
789	<i>Heteroconger tomberua</i> Castle & Randall, 1999	M	TN	(Biswas et al. 2012a)	
790	<i>Parabathymyrus macrophthalmus</i> Kamohara, 1938	M	WB	(Ray et al. 2020)	
791	<i>Paraconger macrops</i> (Günther, 1870)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
792	<i>Promyllantor purpureus</i> Alcock, 1890	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	Off Elicapeni Bank, Laccadive

					Sea
793	<i>Rhynchoconger bicoloratus</i> Kodeeswaran et al., 2023	M	KL	(Kodeeswaran et al. 2023)	Kalamukku Fishing Harbour (deep see trawl), off kerala coast
794	<i>Rhynchoconger nitens</i> (Jordan & Bollman, 1890)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
795	<i>Rhynchoconger randalli</i> Acharya, Mohanty, Ray, Mishra & Mohapatra, 2022	M	OD	(Acharya et al. 2022)	Paradeep fishing harbour, Odisha, Bay of Bengal
796	<i>Rhynchoconger smithi</i> Mohapatra, Ho, Acharya, Ray & Mishra, 2022	M	WB	(Mohapatra et al. 2022)	Petuaghat fishing harbour, West Bengal
797	<i>Uroconger lepturus</i> (Richardson, 1845)	M	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 200, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
798	<i>Xenomystax trucidans</i> Alcock, 1894	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Laccadive Sea, 7°05'45"N, 75°04'E
Family: Moringuidae Gill, 1885					
799	<i>Moringua abbreviata</i> (Bleeker, 1863)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
800	<i>Moringua bicolor</i> Kaup, 1856	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
801	<i>Moringua guthriana</i> (McClelland, 1844)	MBF	WB, OD	(Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018)	Bengal
802	<i>Moringua javanica</i> (Kaup, 1856)	MB	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
803	<i>Moringua macrochir</i> Bleeker, 1853	MBF	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
804	<i>Moringua raitaborua</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MBF	WB, OD, TN, MN	(Mishra et al. 2017, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar & Das 2005a)	Ganges River basin
Family: Muraenidae Rafinesque, 1815					
805	<i>Anarchias allardicei</i> Jordan & Starks, 1906	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
806	<i>Anarchias cantonensis</i> (Schultz, 1943)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
807	<i>Echidna delicatula</i> (Kaup, 1856)	M	LK, KL	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019)	
808	<i>Echidna leucotaenia</i> Schultz, 1943	MBF	LK, KL	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019)	
809	<i>Echidna nebulosa</i> (Ahl, 1789)	M	ANI, LK, WB, AP, TN, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Rajan et al. 2021, Danda et al. 2017, Yennawar et al. 2015, Barman et al. 200, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
810	<i>Echidna polyzona</i> (Richardson, 1845)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
811	<i>Echidna rhodochilus</i> Bleeker, 1863	MBF	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
812	<i>Echidna xanthospilos</i> (Bleeker, 1859)	M	ANI	(Goutham-Bharathi et al. 2017)	
813	<i>Enchelycore octaviana</i> (Myers & Wade, 1941)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	

814	<i>Enchelycore propinqua</i> Mohapatra, Smith, Mohanty, Mishra & Tudu, 2017	M	AP	(Mohapatra et al. 2017a)	Visakhapatnam fishing harbour (actual trawl site is not known), Andhra Pradesh
815	<i>Enchelynassa canina</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1824)	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
816	<i>Gymnomuraena zebra</i> (Shaw, 1797)	M	ANI, LK, WB, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Yennawar et al. 2015, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
817	<i>Gymnothorax afer</i> Bloch, 1795	M	TN	(Kapoor et al. 2002)	
818	<i>Gymnothorax andamanensis</i> Mohapatra, Kiruba-Sankar, Praveenraj & Mohanty, 2019	M	ANI	(Mohapatra et al. 2019c)	Port Mout, Port Blair, South Andaman
819	<i>Gymnothorax aurocephalus</i> Nashad, Mohapatra, Varghese, Ramalingam, Bineesh & Mohanty, 2020	M	ANI	(Nashad et al. 2020)	Dweep Island, Andaman & Nicobar Islands
820	<i>Gymnothorax buroensis</i> (Bleeker, 1857)	MB	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
821	<i>Gymnothorax enigmaticus</i> McCosker & Randall, 1982	M	KL	(Biju et al. 2019)	
822	<i>Gymnothorax favagineus</i> Bloch & Schneider, 1801	MB	ANI, LK, WB, TN, KL, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2011, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	Tharangambadi
823	<i>Gymnothorax fimbriatus</i> (Bennett, 1832)	MB	ANI, LK, AP	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Barman et al. 2004)	
824	<i>Gymnothorax flavimarginatus</i> (Rüppell, 1830)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
825	<i>Gymnothorax hepaticus</i> (Rüppell, 1830)	M	Coasts of India	(Kapoor et al. 2002)	
826	<i>Gymnothorax indicus</i> Mohapatra, Ray, Smith & Mishra, 2016	M	WB	(Yennawar et al. 2011)	Shankarpur, West Bengal
827	<i>Gymnothorax javanicus</i> (Bleeker, 1859)	M	ANI, LK, WB, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Yennawar et al. 2011, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
828	<i>Gymnothorax meleagris</i> (Shaw, 1795)	MBF	LK, WB, OD, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Yennawar et al. 2015, Biswas et al. 2012, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	
829	<i>Gymnothorax mishrai</i> Ray, Mohapatra & Smith, 2015	M	WB	(Ray et al. 2015)	Shankarpur, West Bengal
830	<i>Gymnothorax monochrous</i> (Bleeker, 1856)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
831	<i>Gymnothorax monostigma</i> (Regan, 1909)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
832	<i>Gymnothorax odishi</i> Mohapatra, Mohanty, Smith, Mishra & Roy, 2018	M	OD	(Mohapatra et al. 2018)	Gopalpur beach, Odisha, northeastern coast of India

833	<i>Gymnothorax pictus</i> (Ahl, 1789)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, TN, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mukherjee 1995, Yennawar et al. 2015, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	
834	<i>Gymnothorax prolatus</i> Sasaki & Amaoka, 1991	M	WB, AP	(Mohapatra et al. 2015, Mohapatra et al. 2021a)	
835	<i>Gymnothorax pseudothyrsoides</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	M	LK, TN, KA, GA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, 2013a, Hedge et al. 2013)	
836	<i>Gymnothorax pseudotile</i> Mohapatra, Smith, Ray, Mishra & Mohanty, 2017	M	WB, OD	(Mohapatra et al. 2017, Mohanty et al. 2020)	Shankarpur fishing harbour, West Bengal
837	<i>Gymnothorax punctatofasciatus</i> Bleeker, 1863	M	TN, MH	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
838	<i>Gymnothorax punctatus</i> Bloch & Schneider, 1801	M	WB, OD, AP, TN	(Pati et al. 2018, Kar et al. 2017, Barman 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Tharangambadi
839	<i>Gymnothorax reticularis</i> Bloch, 1795	M	LK, WB, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2013, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Coromandel coast
840	<i>Gymnothorax richardsonii</i> (Bleeker, 1852)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
841	<i>Gymnothorax rueppelliae</i> (McClelland, 1844)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, McClelland, 1844, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
842	<i>Gymnothorax smithi</i> Sumod, Mohapatra, Sanjeevan, Kishor & Bineesh, 2019	M	KL	(Sumod et al. 2019)	Off Kochi
843	<i>Gymnothorax tamilnaduensis</i> Kodeeswaran, Kantharajan, Mohapatra, Kumar & Sarkar, 2023	M	TN	(Kodeeswaran et al. 2023a)	Mudasalodai fish landing centre, off Cuddalore coast, Bay of Bengal, Tamil Nadu
844	<i>Gymnothorax thyrsoides</i> (Richardson, 1845)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
845	<i>Gymnothorax tile</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP	(Rajan et al. 2013, Khan 2002, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004)	Ganges River system
846	<i>Gymnothorax undulatus</i> (Lacepède, 1803)	MB	ANI, LK, TN, KL, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000)	
847	<i>Gymnothorax visakhaensis</i> Mohapatra, Smith, Mohanty, Mishra & Tudu, 2017	M	AP	(Mohapatra et al. 2017b)	Visakhapatnam fish harbour (17°42.452'N, 83°18.823'E), Andhra Pradesh, along the south east coast of India
848	<i>Gymnothorax zonipectis</i> Seale, 1906	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2018)	
849	<i>Rhinomuraena quaesita</i> Garman, 1888	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
850	<i>Scuticaria tigrina</i> (Lesson, 1828)	M	ANI, LK, WB	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mujherjee 1995)	

851	<i>Strophidon dorsalis</i> (Seale, 1917)	M	WB, AP	(Ray & Mohapatra 2015, Mohapatra et al. 2021a)	
852	<i>Strophidon sathete</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	Ganges River system
853	<i>Uropterygius concolor</i> Rüppell, 1838	MB	ANI, WB, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Kar et al. 2017, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
854	<i>Uropterygius marmoratus</i> (Lacepède, 1803)	MB	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
855	<i>Uropterygius micropterus</i> (Bleeker, 1852)	MB	TN	(Padate et al. 2017)	
Family: Muraenesocidae Kaup, 1859					
856	<i>Congresox talabon</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	MB	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, MH	(Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Visakhapatnam
857	<i>Congresox talabonoides</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
858	<i>Muraenesox bagio</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MB	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Hedge et al. 2013)	Ganges River estuaries
859	<i>Muraenesox cinereus</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	MBF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
860	<i>Sauromuraenesox vorax</i> Alcock, 1889	M	WB	(Alcock 1889)	Off West Bengal, Bay of Bengal
Family: Nemichthyidae Kaup, 1859					
861	<i>Avocettina infans</i> (Günther, 1878)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
862	<i>Nemichthys scolopaceus</i> Richardson, 1848	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
Family: Nettastomatidae Kaup, 1859					
863	<i>Nettastoma solitarium</i> Castle & Smith, 1981	M	ANI	(Sumod et al. 2016)	
864	<i>Nettenchelys taylori</i> Alcock, 1898	M	LK	(Alcock 1898)	Laccadive Sea, off Travancore coast, India, 7°17'30"N, 76°54'30"E,
865	<i>Saurenchelys petersi</i> Day, 1878	M	OD	(Pati et al. 2018)	Sea of Orissa
Family: Ophichthidae Günther, 1870					
866	<i>Allips concolor</i> McCosker, 1972	B	OD	(Mohapatra et al. 2019d)	
867	<i>Bascanichthys deraniyagalai</i> Menon, 1961	MB	OD, TN	(Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Mouth of Arasalar River, Karaikkal, Tanjore, Coromandel Coast

868	<i>Bascanichthys longipinnis</i> (Kner & Steindachner, 1867)	MBF	OD	(Pati et al. 2018)	
869	<i>Caecula pterygera</i> Vahl, 1794	MB	TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
870	<i>Callechelys catostoma</i> (Schneider, 1801)	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
871	<i>Cirrhimuraena indica</i> Mohapatra, Mohanty, Ray, Mishra & Seth, 2021	MB	WB	(Mohapatra et al. 2021, Sen et al. 2021)	Paradip fishing harbour, Odisha
872	<i>Cirrhimuraena odishaensis</i> Mohanty, Behera, Patro & Mohapatra, 2023	MB	OD	(Mohanty et al. 2023a)	Palur canal, Odisha, India, 19.47068889°, 85.14005833°
873	<i>Cirrhimuraena playfairii</i> (Günther, 1870)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
874	<i>Lamnostoma orientale</i> (McClelland, 1844)	MBF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Coromandel coast
875	<i>Leiuranus semicinctus</i> (Lay & Bennett, 1839)	MB	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
876	<i>Muraenichthys gymnopterus</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	M	WB, MH	(Mohapatra et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2012)	
877	<i>Muraenichthys hibinoi</i> Mohapatra, Behera, Ray, Acharya, Mohanty & Mishra, 2023	M	WB	(Mohapatra et al. 2023)	Shankarpur fishing harbor, West Bengal, India, depth about 30 meters
878	<i>Muraenichthys schultzei</i> Bleeker, 1857	M	ANI, TN, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000)	
879	<i>Scolecenchelys macroptera</i> (Bleeker, 1857)	M	ANI, LK, OD, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Pati et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
880	<i>Myrichthys colubrinus</i> (Boddaert, 1781)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
881	<i>Myrichthys maculosus</i> (Cuvier, 1816)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
882	<i>Myrophis lepturus</i> Kotthaus, 1968	M	OD	(Pati et al. 2018)	
883	<i>Neenchelys buitendijki</i> Weber & de Beaufort, 1916	M	WB, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
884	<i>Neenchelys cheni</i> (Chen & Weng, 1967)	M	OD, AP	(Ray & Mohapatra 2016, Mohapatra et al. 2021a)	
885	<i>Ophichthus apicalis</i> (Anonymous [Bennett], 1830)	MB	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, MH	(Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
886	<i>Ophichthus altipennis</i> (Kaup, 1856)	M	WB, OD	(Pati et al. 2018, Kar et al. 2017)	
887	<i>Ophichthus cephalozona</i> Bleeker, 1864	M	OD, TN, MH	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, Mohanty et al. 2021a)	
888	<i>Ophichthus chennaiensis</i> Das, Mohapatra, Rajendar & Bhaskar, 2020	M	TN	(Das et al. 2020)	Kasimedu fishing harbour, Chennai, Tamil Nadu
889	<i>Ophichthus chilkaensis</i> Chaudhuri, 1916	M	WB	(Mishra et al. 2011)	Rambha Bay, Chilika [Chilika] Lake, Orissa

890	<i>Ophichthus hijala</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MBF	WB, OD	(Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018)	West Bengal
891	<i>Ophichthus johnmccoskeri</i> Mohapatra, Ray, Mohanty & Mishra, 2018	M	WB, OD	(Mohapatra et al. 2018a)	Shankarpur fishing harbor, West Bengal
892	<i>Ophichthus kailashchandrai</i> Mohapatra, Ray, Mohanty & Mishra, 2020	M	WB	(Mohapatra et al. 2020)	Shankarpur fishing harbour, northern Bay of Bengal
893	<i>Ophichthus lithinus</i> (Jordan & Richardson, 1908)	M	WB	(Ray et al. 2015a)	
894	<i>Ophichthus macrochir</i> (Bleeker, 1852)	M	southern India	(Allen & Erdmann 2012)	
895	<i>Ophichthus machidai</i> McCosker, Ide & Endo, 2012	M	WB	(Mohapatra et al. 2019a)	
896	<i>Ophichthus mccoskeri</i> Sumod, Hibino, Manjabrayakath & Sanjeevan, 2019	M	ANI	(Sumod et al. 2019a)	Off South Great Nicobar, andaman Islands
897	<i>Ophichthus naevius</i> Kodeeswaran, Kathirvelpandian, Mohapatra, Kumar & Sarkar, 2023	M	TN	(Kodeeswaran et al. 2023c)	Mudasalodai fish landing center [trawl landing], off Cuddalore coast, Bay of Bengal, 11°29'N, 79°46"E, depth around 25 - 30 meters
898	<i>Ophichthus nigroventralis</i> Kodeeswaran, Mohapatra & Kumar, 2023	M	KL	(Kodeeswaran et al. 2023d)	Kalamukku Fishing Harbour [deep-see trawl], off Kerala coast, Arabian Sea, 9°59'02"N, 76°14'08"E
899	<i>Pisodonophis boro</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MBF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, GA, MH, TL, AS, MN, TR	(Shaji et al. 2019, Dubey et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman 2002, 2004, 2012, Prashad & Srinivasulu 2021, Talwar 1974)	West Bengal, Ganges River estuary
900	<i>Pisodonophis cancrivorus</i> (Richardson, 1848)	MBF	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, GA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
901	<i>Pisodonophis kalinga</i> Mohanty, Behera, Acharya, Patnaik, Ray, Seth, Patro, Mishra & Mohapatra, 2023	B	OD	(Mohanty et al. 2023)	Palur canal, Odisha, India, 19°28'14.48"N, 85°08'24.21"E
902	<i>Pisodonophis sangjuensis</i> Ji & Kim, 2011	M	WB	(Mohapatra et al. 2020a)	
903	<i>Skythrenchelys zabra</i> Castle & McCosker, 1999	M	WB	(Mohapatra et al. 2019b)	Thevara, Ernakulam, southern India, 10°00'N,

					76°16'E, shallow turbid water.
904	<i>Xestochilus nebulosus</i> (Smith, 1962)	M	LK, AP	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
905	<i>Xyrias anjaalai</i> Augustina, Sreeram, Sukumaran, Jose & Sreekumar, 2020	M	KL	(Augustina et al. 2020)	Kollam, Kerala
906	<i>Yirrkala misolensis</i> (Günther, 1872)	M	ANI	(Chiu et al. 2022)	
Family: Synaphobranchidae Johnson, 1862					
907	<i>Dysomma bucephalus</i> Alcock, 1889	M	ANI, LK	(Karmovskaya 2023)	Bay of Bengal near the Nicobar Islands
908	<i>Synaphobranchus brevidorsalis</i> Günther, 1887	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
Order: Argentiniformes					
Family: Argentinidae Bonaparte, 1846					
909	<i>Glossanodon macrocephalus</i> Bineesh, Nashad, Kumar & Endo, 2019	M	KL	(Bineesh et al. 2019)	Off Kerala, India, 10°45'27.0"N, 75°14'24.6"E
Order: Ateleopodiformes					
Family: Ateleopodidae Bonaparte, 1850					
910	<i>Ijimaia loppei</i> Roule, 192	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
911	<i>Parateleopus indicus</i> (Alcock, 1891)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Andaman Sea, 11°31'40"N, 92°46'40"E
Order: Atheriniformes					
Family: Atherinidae Risso, 1827					
912	<i>Atherinomorus forskalii</i> (Rüppell, 1838)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
913	<i>Atherinomorus lacunosus</i> (Forster, 1801)	MBF	ANI, LK, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
914	<i>Atherinomorus pinguis</i> (Lacepède, 1803)	M	KA	(Kimura et al. 2007)	
915	<i>Atherinomorus endrachtensis</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1825)	MB	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
916	<i>Doboatherina duodecimalis</i> (Valenciennes 1835)	MB	ANI, LK, OD, TN, KL, KA	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a)	
917	<i>Doboatherina valenciennei</i> (Bleeker, 1854)	M	MH	(Ivantsoff & Kottelat 1988)	
918	<i>Hypoatherina barnesi</i> Schultz, 1953	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
919	<i>Hypoatherina temminckii</i> (Bleeker, 1854)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Atherionidae Schultz, 1948					
920	<i>Atherion africanum</i> Smith, 1965	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
Family: Isonidae Rosen, 1964					

921	<i>Iso natalensis</i> Regan, 1919	M	GJ	(Barman et al. 2000)	
Order: Aulopiformes					
Family: Alepisauridae Swainson, 1839					
922	<i>Alepisaurus ferox</i> Lowe, 1833	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
Family: Chlorophthalmidae Garman, 1899					
923	<i>Chlorophthalmus agassizi</i> Bonaparte, 1840	MB	AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
924	<i>Chlorophthalmus corniger</i> Alcock, 1894	M	TN, KL, KA	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a)	Bay of Bengal, 13°51'12"N, 80°28'12"E
Family: Ipnopidae Gill, 1884					
925	<i>Bathypterois atricolor</i> Alcock, 1896	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	Laccadive Sea, western Indian Ocean
926	<i>Bathypterois guentheri</i> Alcock, 1889	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	Andaman Sea, 7.5 miles east of North Cinque Island
927	<i>Bathypterois insularum</i> Alcock, 1892	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	Laccadive Sea, 14°35'15"N, 72°02'37"E
928	<i>Ipnops agassizii</i> Garman, 1899	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
Family: Evermannellidae Fowler, 1901					
929	<i>Coccorella atrata</i> (Alcock, 1894)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Bay of Bengal, 14°13'08"N, 80°24'02"E
Family: Paralepididae Bonaparte, 1835					
930	<i>Lestidiops blanci</i> (Kartha, 1971)	M	KL	(Kartha 1971)	About or km off Quilon, Cochin Cape Comorin Section, Arabian Sea, 8°45'N, 75°50'E
931	<i>Lestidiops indopacificus</i> (Ege, 1953)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
Family: Synodontidae Gill, 1861					
932	<i>Harpadon nehereus</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MB	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Kar et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	Estuaries of West Bengal
933	<i>Harpadon nudus</i> Ganga & Thomas, 2016	M	GJ	(Ganga et al. 2016)	Arabian Sea, 19°53'N, 69°23'E, depth 371 meters
934	<i>Harpadon squamosus</i> Alcock, 1891	M	AP	(Alcock 1891)	Bay of Bengal, India, 15°56'50"N, 81°30'30"E, Investigator station 120, depth 240-276 fathoms.
935	<i>Saurida argentea</i> Macleay,	M	WB	(Danda et al. 2017)	

	1881				
936	<i>Saurida gracilis</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1824)	M	ANI, LK, OD, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
937	<i>Saurida isarankurai</i> Shindo & Yamada, 1972	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
938	<i>Saurida lessepsianus</i> Russell, Golani & Tikochinski, 2015	M	MH	(Silpa et al. 2021)	
939	<i>Saurida longimanus</i> Norman, 1939	M	TN, GJ	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000)	
940	<i>Saurida micropectoralis</i> Shindo & Yamada, 1972	M	ANI, OD, TN, KL, KA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, 2013a)	
941	<i>Saurida nebulosa</i> Valenciennes, 1850	MB	ANI, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019)	
942	<i>Saurida pseudotumbil</i> Dutt & Sagar, 1981	M	OD, AP, TN	(Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Visakhapatnam
943	<i>Saurida tumbil</i> (Bloch, 1795)	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	Malabar or Tranquebar
944	<i>Saurida undosquamis</i> (Richardson, 1848)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
945	<i>Saurida wanieso</i> Shindo & Yamada, 1972	M	WB, KA	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Barman et al. 2013a)	
946	<i>Synodus binotatus</i> Schultz, 1953	M	KL	(Biju et al. 2019)	
947	<i>Synodus dermatogenys</i> Fowler, 1912	M	LK	(Anto et al. 2024)	
948	<i>Synodus hoshinonis</i> Tanaka, 1917	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
949	<i>Synodus indicus</i> (Day, 1873)	M	ANI, LK, OD, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Chennai
950	<i>Synodus jaculum</i> Russell & Cressey, 1979	M	TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
951	<i>Synodus macrops</i> Tanaka, 1917	M	MH, GJ	(Barman et al. 2000, 2012)	
952	<i>Synodus oculus</i> Cressey, 1981	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
953	<i>Synodus sagineus</i> Waite, 1905	M	TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
954	<i>Synodus variegatus</i> (Lacepède, 1803)	M	ANI, LK, WB, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Sanyal et al. 2012, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
955	<i>Trachinocephalus myops</i> (Forster, 1801)	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2017, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a, Hedge et al. 2013)	
956	<i>Trachinocephalus trachinus</i> (Temminck & Schlegel, 1846)	M	AP	(Kapoor et al. 2002)	

	Order: Batrachoidiformes				
	Family: Batrachoididae Jordan, 1896				
957	<i>Allenbatrachus grunniens</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	M	WB, OD, TN, KA, MH	(Yennawar et al. 2015, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, 2013a, Barman et al. 2012)	
958	<i>Allenbatrachus reticulatus</i> (Steindachner, 1870)	MBF	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
959	<i>Batrachomoeus trispinosus</i> (Günther, 1861)	MB	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
960	<i>Colletteichthys dussumieri</i> (Valenciennes, 1837)	M	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Sanyal et al. 2012, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	Mumbai, Maharashtra
961	<i>Colletteichthys flavipinnis</i> Greenfield, Bineesh & Akhilesh, 2012	M	TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019)	Kerala
962	<i>Colletteichthys occidentalis</i> Greenfield, 2012	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
963	<i>Perulibatrachus aquilonarius</i> Greenfield, 2005	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Ennur Fisheries Station, Madras
	Order: Beloniformes				
	Family: Adrianichthyidae Weber, 1913				
964	<i>Oryzias andrewi</i> Roberts, Chakraborty, Yardi & Mukherjee, 2021	F	AS	(Roberts et al. 2021)	Sutinmari River, Sankosh River drainage, Alipurduar District near Barobisha Town, Brahmaputra River basin, Assam
965	<i>Oryzias carnaticus</i> (Jerdon, 1849)	BF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KA	(Sen & Sreeraj 2022, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Angel 2019)	Vaniyambadi, Tamil Nadu
966	<i>Oryzias dancena</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, GA, GJ, MP, TL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Dutta et al. 2013, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Pati et al. 2018, Barman 1993, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Sharma 2007, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Talwar 1974)	Botanical Garden of Calcutta, Ganges River estuary
967	<i>Oryzias javanicus</i> (Bleeker, 1854)	BF	ANI, TN	(Angel 2019, Sreeraj & Sen 2022)	
968	<i>Oryzias melastigma</i> (McClelland, 1839)	BF	ANI, WB, TN, KL	(McClelland 1839)	From the streams of West Bengal
969	<i>Oryzias setnai</i> (Kulkarni, 1940)	BF	KL, KA, MH	(Shaji et al. 2019, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Creeks near Mumbai
	Family: Belonidae Bonaparte, 1835				
970	<i>Ablennes hians</i> (Valenciennes, 1846)	MB	ANI, LK, OD, AP, TN, KL, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Roul et al. 2019a)	
971	<i>Platybelone argalus</i> (Lesueur, 1821)	MB	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
972	<i>Platybelone platyura</i> (Bennett, 1832)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	

973	<i>Strongylura incisa</i> (Valenciennes, 1846)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
974	<i>Strongylura leiurus</i> (Bleeker, 1850)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
975	<i>Strongylura scapularis</i> (Jordan & Gilbert, 1882)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
976	<i>Strongylura strongylura</i> (van Hasselt, 1823)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ, TR	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Khan 2002, Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Visakhapatnam
977	<i>Tylosurus acus</i> (Lacepède, 1803)	M	AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
978	<i>Tylosurus choram</i> (Rüppell, 1837)	M	OD, TN, MH, GJ	(Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012)	
979	<i>Tylosurus crocodilus</i> (Péron & Lesueur, 1821)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mishra et al. 2017, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
980	<i>Tylosurus melanotus</i> (Bleeker, 1850)	MBF	LK, TN, KA	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a)	
981	<i>Xenentodon cancila</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KA, GA, MH, GJ, HP, PU, UK, HY, DL, UP, RJ, MP, TL, CG, BR, JH, AS, ML, AR, NL, MZ, TR	(Shaji et al. 2019, Karmakar & Das 2005, Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2000, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Prasad & Srinivasulu 2021, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Yadav 2008, Jagtap 2013, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a, Brraich & Saini 2019, Tudu et al. 2022, Murugan & Prabakaran 2012, Kar & Sen 2007)	Ponds & smaller rivers of Gangetic provinces
Family: Exocoetidae Risso, 1827					
982	<i>Cheilopogon abei</i> Parin, 1996	M	LK, MH	(Sundaram 2010)	
983	<i>Cheilopogon atrisignis</i> (Jenkins, 1903)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
984	<i>Cheilopogon cyanopterus</i> (Valenciennes, 1847)	M	LK, WB, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Ray et al. 2020a, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
985	<i>Cheilopogon formosus</i> (Kotthaus, 1969)	M	GA	(Jayakumar et al. 2019)	Off Goa, India, 14°45'N, 73°54'E
986	<i>Cheilopogon furcatus</i> (Mitchill, 1815)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
987	<i>Cheilopogon intermedius</i> Parin, 1961	M	WB, OD	(Ray et al. 2020a, Mohanty et al. 2021b)	
988	<i>Cheilopogon nigricans</i> (Bennett, 1840)	M	AP, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a)	
989	<i>Cheilopogon</i>	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	

	<i>pinnatibarbatus</i> (Bennett, 1831)				
990	<i>Cheilopogon spilopterus</i> (Valenciennes, 1847)	M	ANI, LK, TN, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2021, 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012)	
991	<i>Cheilopogon suttoni</i> (Whitley & Colefax, 1938)	M	WB, KA	(Ray et al. 2020a, Barman et al. 2013a)	
992	<i>Cypselurus angusticeps</i> Nichols & Breder, 1935	M	LK, GJ	(Jayakumar et al. 2019)	
993	<i>Cypselurus comatus</i> (Mitchill, 1815)	M	TN, GA	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
994	<i>Cypselurus naresii</i> (Günther, 1889)	M	LK, WB, KA	(Rajan et al. 2021, Ray et al. 2020a, Barman et al. 2013a)	
995	<i>Cypselurus oligolepis</i> (Bleeker, 1865)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
996	<i>Cypselurus opisthopus</i> (Bleeker, 1865)	M	KL	(Jayakumar et al. 2019)	
997	<i>Cypselurus poecilopterus</i> (Valenciennes, 1847)	M	WB, OD, TN, KA, MH	(Mohapatra et al. 2012, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, 2013a)	
998	<i>Exocoetus monocirrhus</i> Richardson, 1846	M	AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
999	<i>Exocoetus volitans</i> Linnaeus, 1758	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1000	<i>Hirundichthys coromandelensis</i> (Hornell, 1923)	M	AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Coromandel Coast, southeastern India
1001	<i>Hirundichthys indicus</i> Shakhovskoy & Parin, 2013	M	ANI	(Shakhovskoy & Parin, 2013)	
1002	<i>Hirundichthys oxycephalus</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	M	LK, AP, TN, KL, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1003	<i>Hirundichthys speculiger</i> (Valenciennes, 1847)	M	WB	(Ray et al. 2020a)	
1004	<i>Parexocoetus brachypterus</i> (Richardson, 1846)	M	ANI, LK, WB, TN, KA	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Talwar et al. 1992, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a)	
1005	<i>Parexocoetus mento</i> (Valenciennes, 1847)	M	WB, OD, AP, TN, KA, MH, GJ	(Ray et al. 2020a, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Puducherry
1006	<i>Prognichthys brevipinnis</i> (Valenciennes, 1847)	M	LK, AP, TN, KA, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2021, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Hemiramphidae Gill, 1859					
1007	<i>Euleptorhamphus viridis</i> (van Hasselt, 1823)	M	AP, TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Visakhapatnam
1008	<i>Hemiramphus archipelagicus</i> Collette & Parin, 1978	M	KA, MH	(Barman et al. 2012, 2013a)	

1009	<i>Hemiramphus far</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1010	<i>Hemiramphus lutkei</i> Valenciennes, 1847	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1011	<i>Hemiramphus marginatus</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	ANI, LK, WB, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Kar et al. 2017, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1012	<i>Hemiramphus robustus</i> Günther, 1866	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1013	<i>Hyporhamphus affinis</i> (Günther, 1866)	M	Coasts of India	(Kapoor et al. 2002)	
1014	<i>Hyporhamphus balinensis</i> (Bleeker, 1858)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
1015	<i>Hyporhamphus dussumieri</i> (Valenciennes, 1847)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
1016	<i>Hyporhamphus limbatus</i> (Valenciennes, 1847)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ, TL	(Khan 2002, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Rajan et al. 2013, Shaji et al. 2019, Prasad & Srinivasulu 2021, Karmakar et al. 2012, Hedge et al. 2013)	Malabar coast
1017	<i>Hyporhamphus unicuspis</i> Collette & Parin, 1978	M	OD	(Pati et al. 2018)	
1018	<i>Hyporhamphus unifasciatus</i> (Ranzani, 1841)	MB	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
1019	<i>Hyporhamphus quoyi</i> (Valenciennes, 1847)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, TN, KA, GA	(Rajan et al. 2013, Kar et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a, Talwar 1974)	
1020	<i>Hyporhamphus sindensis</i> (Regan, 1905)	M	Northwestern Indian Ocean	(Kapoor et al. 2002)	
1021	<i>Hyporhamphus xanthopterus</i> (Valenciennes, 1847)	MBF	ANI, OD, TN, KL, KA, MH, TL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Shaji et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, 2013a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016)	Fresh waters of Alleppey [now Alappuzha], southeastern India
1022	<i>Oxyporhamphus micropterus</i> (Valenciennes, 1847)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
1023	<i>Rhynchorhamphus georgii</i> (Valenciennes, 1847)	MBF	LK, WB, OD, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Kar et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, 2013a, Talwar 1974)	Mumbai & Coromandel
1024	<i>Rhynchorhamphus malabaricus</i> Collette, 1976	M	OD, AP, TN, KL, MH	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1025	<i>Rhynchorhamphus naga</i> Collette 1976	M	KL	(Behera et al. 2022)	
Family: Zenarchopteridae Fowler, 1934					
1026	<i>Dermogenys brachynotus</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	BF	WB, OD	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Pati et al. 2018)	Hooghly River, Calcutta

1027	<i>Zenarchopterus buffonis</i> (Valenciennes, 1847)	MB	ANI, WB, OD	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018)	
1028	<i>Zenarchopterus dispar</i> (Valenciennes, 1847)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, KA	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a)	
1029	<i>Zenarchopterus ectuntio</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	WB, OD	(Khan 2002, Pati et al. 2018)	Smaller rivers & ponds of Gangetic provinces
1030	<i>Zenarchopterus gilli</i> Smith, 1945	MBF	ANI, OD	(Rajan et al. 2013, Pati et al. 2018)	
1031	<i>Zenarchopterus pappenheimi</i> Mohr, 1926	MB	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1032	<i>Zenarchopterus striga</i> (Blyth, 1858)	BF	WB, KL	(Mishra et al. 2017, Zeena & Beevi 2012)	Calcutta fish market
Order: Beryciformes					
Family: Berycidae Lowe 1839					
1033	<i>Beryx decadactylus</i> Cuvier, 1829	M	TN, KA	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a)	
1034	<i>Beryx splendens</i> Lowe, 1834	M	KA	(Barman et al. 2013a)	
1035	<i>Centroberyx gerrardi</i> (Günther, 1887)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1036	<i>Centroberyx rubricaudus</i> Liu & Shen, 1985	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Order: Blenniiformes					
Family: Blenniidae Rafinesque, 1810					
1037	<i>Alloblennius frondiculus</i> Smith-Vaniz & Allen, 2012	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	South Cinque Islands, Andaman, India
1038	<i>Alticus kirkii</i> (Günther, 1868)	M	ANI, KL, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2012)	
1039	<i>Alticus saliens</i> (Forster, 1788)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1040	<i>Andamia heteroptera</i> (Bleeker, 1857)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1041	<i>Andamia reyi</i> (Sauvage, 1880)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1042	<i>Antennablennius bifilum</i> (Günther, 1861)	M	North West Coast of India	(Randall 1995)	
1043	<i>Aspidontus taeniatus</i> Quoy & Gaimard, 1834	M	ANI, LK, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019)	
1044	<i>Atrosalarias fuscus</i> (Rüppell, 1838)	M	ANI, TN, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
1045	<i>Blenniella bilitonensis</i> (Bleeker, 1858)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1046	<i>Blenniella cyanostigma</i> (Bleeker, 1849)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1047	<i>Blenniella interrupta</i> (Bleeker, 1857)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1048	<i>Blenniella leopardus</i> (Fowler, 1904)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1049	<i>Blenniella periphthalmus</i> (Valencienne, 1836)	M	ANI, LK, KL, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2012)	
1050	<i>Cirripectes auritus</i> Carlson, 1981	M	LK	(Anto et al. 2024)	

1051	<i>Cirripectes castaneus</i> (Valenciennes, 1836)	MB	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
1052	<i>Cirripectes filamentosus</i> (Alleyne & MacLeay, 1877)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1053	<i>Cirripectes perustus</i> Smith, 1959	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1054	<i>Cirripectes polyzona</i> (Bleeker, 1868)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, Anto et al. 2024)	
1055	<i>Cirripectes quagga</i> (Fowler & Ball, 1924)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
1056	<i>Cirripectes stigmaticus</i> Strasburg & Schultz, 1953	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
1057	<i>Cirripectes variolosus</i> (Valenciennes, 1836)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
1058	<i>Ecsenius bicolor</i> (Day, 1888)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Anto et al. 2024)	
1059	<i>Ecsenius frontalis</i> (Valenciennes, 1836)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1060	<i>Ecsenius lineatus</i> Klauswitz, 1962	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1061	<i>Ecsenius midas</i> Starck, 1969	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1062	<i>Ecsenius paroculus</i> Springer, 1988	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1063	<i>Ecsenius pulcher</i> (Murray, 1887)	M	GJ	(Springer 1988)	
1064	<i>Ecsenius trilineatus</i> Springer, 1972	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1065	<i>Ecsenius stictus</i> Springer, 1988	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
1066	<i>Ecsenius yaeyamaensis</i> (Aoyagi, 1954)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
1067	<i>Enchelyurus kraussii</i> (Klunzinger, 1871)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
1068	<i>Entomacrodus epalzeocheilos</i> (Bleeker, 1859)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1069	<i>Entomacrodus striatus</i> (Valenciennes, 1836)	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
1070	<i>Entomacrodus vermiculatus</i> (Valenciennes, 1836)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Biswas et al. 2012, Kumar et al. 2024)	
1071	<i>Exallias brevis</i> (Kner, 1868)	M	ANI, LK, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Barman et al. 2000)	
1072	<i>Glyptoparus delicatulus</i> Smith, 1959	M	LK	(Anto et al. 2024)	
1073	<i>Haptogenys bipunctata</i> (Day, 1876)	M	TN, KL	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Calicut, Malabar coast
1074	<i>Istiblennius dussumieri</i> (Valenciennes, 1836)	MB	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Malabar

1075	<i>Istiblennius edentulus</i> (Forster & Schneider, 1801)	MB	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biswas et al. 2012)	
1076	<i>Istiblennius lineatus</i> (Valenciennes, 1836)	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
1077	<i>Istiblennius spilotos</i> Springer & Williams, 1994	M	GJ	(Springer & Williams 1994)	Gulf of Kutch, Okha Point
1078	<i>Istiblennius steindachneri</i> (Pfeffer, 1893)	M	AP	(Barman et al. 2004)	
1079	<i>Meiacanthus grammistes</i> (Valenciennes, 1836)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1080	<i>Meiacanthus smithi</i> Klausewitz, 1962	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, Sandra et al. 2022)	
1081	<i>Meiacanthus vicinus</i> Smith-Vaniz, 1987	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
1082	<i>Omobranchus elongatus</i> (Peters, 1855)	MB	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1083	<i>Omobranchus fasciolatus</i> (Valenciennes, 1836)	M	Northwestern India	(Randall 1995)	
1084	<i>Omobranchus ferox</i> (Herre, 1927)	MBF	TN	(Allen & Erdmann 2012, Iyyappan et al. 2023)	
1085	<i>Omobranchus obliquus</i> (Garman, 1903)	MB	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1086	<i>Omobranchus punctatus</i> (Valenciennes, 1836)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, TN, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Sen et al. 2023, Barman et al. 2012, Iyyappan et al. 2023)	Mumbai
1087	<i>Omobranchus smithi</i> (Rao, 1974)	MB	WB, AP	(Chakraborty et al. 2020)	Godavari estuary
1088	<i>Omobranchus zebra</i> (Bleeker, 1868)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Chakraborty et al. 2020, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1089	<i>Parablennius cyclops</i> (Rüppell, 1830)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1090	<i>Parablennius thysanius</i> (Jordan & Seale, 1907)	M	Southern coast of India	(Randall 1995)	
1091	<i>Parenchelyurus hepburni</i> (Snyder, 1908)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1092	<i>Plagiotremus phenax</i> Smith-Vaniz, 1976	M	ANI, LK	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Sandra et al. 2022)	
1093	<i>Plagiotremus rhinorhynchos</i> (Bleeker, 1852)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
1094	<i>Plagiotremus tapeinosoma</i> (Bleeker, 1857)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
1095	<i>Praealticus bilineatus</i> (Peters, 1868)	M	GA	(Talwar 1974)	
1096	<i>Praealticus triangulus</i> (Chapman, 1951)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Andaman Islands
1097	<i>Petroscirtes breviceps</i> (Valenciennes, 1836)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mukherjee 1995, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Mohanty et al. 2019b)	Bay of Bengal, northeastern Indian Ocean
1098	<i>Petroscirtes mitratus</i> Rüppell, 1830	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1099	<i>Petroscirtes variabilis</i> Cantor, 1849	M	ANI, WB, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mukherjee 1995, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	

1100	<i>Petrosciartes xestus</i> Jordan & Seale, 1906	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
1101	<i>Praealticus dayi</i> (Whitley, 1929)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Andaman Islands
1102	<i>Praealticus triangulus</i> (Chapman, 1951)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Andaman Islands
1103	<i>Rhabdoblennius snowi</i> (Fowler, 1928)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1104	<i>Salarias alboguttatus</i> Kner, 1867	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1105	<i>Salarias fasciatus</i> (Bloch, 1786)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1106	<i>Salarias guttatus</i> Valenciennes, 1836	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1107	<i>Scartella emarginata</i> (Günther, 1861)	M	GA, MH	(Barman et al. 2012, Talwar 1974)	
1108	<i>Xiphiasa setifer</i> Swainson, 1839	M	ANI, LK, OD, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Visakhapatnam
Family: Tripterygiidae Whitley, 1931					
1109	<i>Enneapterygius abeli</i> (Klausewitz, 1960)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2020)	
1110	<i>Enneapterygius elegans</i> (Peters, 1876)	M	TN	(Fricke 1994)	
1111	<i>Enneapterygius fasciatus</i> (Weber, 1909)	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1112	<i>Enneapterygius pusillus</i> Rüppell, 1835	M	TN	(Lal Mohan 1971)	
1113	<i>Helcogramma ellioti</i> (Herre, 1944)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Cape Comorin, Tamil Nadu
1114	<i>Helcogramma gymnauchen</i> (Weber, 1909)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
1115	<i>Helcogramma striata</i> Hansen, 1986	M	ANI, LK	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Rajan et al. 2021)	
1116	<i>Helcogramma shinglensis</i> Lal Mohan, 1971	M	TN	(Lal Mohan 1971)	Shingle Island, Gulf of Mannar
1117	<i>Helcogramma obtusirostris</i> (Klunzinger, 1871)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2020)	
1118	<i>Helcogramma trigloides</i> (Bleeker, 1858)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
1119	<i>Ucla xenogrammus</i> Holleman, 1993	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
Order: Carangiformes					
Family: Bothidae Smitt, 1892					
1120	<i>Arnoglossus arabicus</i> Norman, 1939	M	KL	(Biju et al. 2019)	
1121	<i>Arnoglossus macrolophus</i> Alcock, 1889	M	OD	(Pati et al. 2018)	Bay of Bengal, 5 miles south of Brahmapur
1122	<i>Arnoglossus tapeinosoma</i> (Bleeker, 1865)	M	ANI, OD, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1123	<i>Arnoglossus waitei</i> Norman, 1926	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	

1124	<i>Asterorhombus intermedius</i> (Bleeker, 1865)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1125	<i>Bothus mancus</i> (Broussonet, 1782)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1126	<i>Bothus myriaster</i> (Temminck & Schlegel, 1846)	M	ANI, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1127	<i>Bothus pantherinus</i> (Rüppell, 1830)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1128	<i>Chascanopsetta lugubris</i> Alcock, 1894	M	TN, KL, KA, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2013a)	Bay of Bengal, 13°51'12"N, 80°28'12"E
1129	<i>Chascanopsetta prognatha</i> Norman, 1939	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1130	<i>Crossorhombus azureus</i> (Alcock, 1889)	M	OD, TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Eight to 20 miles southwest of Puri, Bay of Bengal
1131	<i>Crossorhombus valderostratus</i> (Alcock, 1890)	M	LK, OD, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1132	<i>Engyprosopon grandisquama</i> (Temminck & Schlegel, 1846)	M	ANI, WB, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Sanyal et al. 2012, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1133	<i>Engyprosopon latifrons</i> (Regan, 1908)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
1134	<i>Engyprosopon macrolepis</i> (Regan, 1908)	M	ANI	(Rajan & Vikas 2016)	
1135	<i>Engyprosopon mozambiquense</i> Hensley, 2003	M	ANI	(Hensley 2003)	
1136	<i>Engyprosopon natalensis</i> Regan, 1920	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1137	<i>Grammatobothus polyophthalmus</i> (Bleeker, 1865)	M	ANI, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1138	<i>Kamoharaia megastoma</i> (Kamohara, 1936)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1139	<i>Laeops guentheri</i> Alcock, 1890	M	OD, TN	(Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	off Ganjam & Visakhapatnam coasts
1140	<i>Laeops macrophthalmus</i> (Alcock, 1889)	M	OD, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018)	
1141	<i>Laeops natalensis</i> Norman, 1931	M	TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1142	<i>Laeops nigrescens</i> Lloyd, 1907	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1143	<i>Laeops nigromaculatus</i> von Bonde, 1922	M	TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1144	<i>Laeops parviceps</i> Günther, 1880	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1145	<i>Parabothus polylepis</i> (Alcock, 1889)	M	KL	(Biju et al. 2019)	

1146	<i>Psettina brevirectis</i> (Alcock, 1890)	M	OD	(Pati et al. 2018)	9.5 miles southeast by south of Bawanapadu Bacon, off Ganjam coast, Bay of Bengal
Family: Carangidae Rafinesque, 1815					
1147	<i>Alectis ciliaris</i> (Bloch, 1787)	M	ANI, LK, WB, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Surat
1148	<i>Alepes djedaba</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
1149	<i>Alepes kleinii</i> (Bloch, 1793)	M	ANI, WB, OD, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Ray et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, 2013a, Ansari et al. 1995)	Malabar coast
1150	<i>Alepes melanoptera</i> (Swainson, 1839)	MB	ANI, WB, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Ray et al. 2022, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	Visakhapatnam
1151	<i>Alepes vari</i> (Cuvier, 1833)	MB	WB, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Talwar et al. 1992, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Puducherry
1152	<i>Atropus atropos</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	Tranquebar [Tharangambadi]
1153	<i>Atropus armatus</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Ray et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1154	<i>Atropus hedlandensis</i> (Whitley, 1934)	M	ANI, WB, OD, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Ray et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1155	<i>Atule mate</i> (Cuvier, 1833)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	Puducherry
1156	<i>Atropus mentalis</i> (Cuvier, 1833)	M	ANI, LK, WB, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al., 2013, Rajan et al., 2021, Biju et al., 2019, Ray et al. 2022, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1157	<i>Carangichthys dinema</i> (Bleeker, 1851)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1158	<i>Carangichthys humerosus</i> (McCulloch, 1915)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1159	<i>Carangichthys oblongus</i> (Cuvier, 1833)	M	ANI, LK, WB, TN, KL, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Ray et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012)	
1160	<i>Carangoides plagiotaenia</i>	M	ANI, LK,	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al.	

	Bleeker, 1857		TN	2018)	
1161	<i>Carangoides praeustus</i> (Anonymous [Bennett], 1830)	M	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Ray et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1162	<i>Caranx heberi</i> (Bennett, 1830)	MB	LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Ray et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1163	<i>Caranx hippos</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	M	ANI, WB, OD, TN, KL, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
1164	<i>Caranx ignobilis</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Khan 2002, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1165	<i>Caranx lugubris</i> Poey, 1860	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1166	<i>Caranx melampygus</i> Cuvier, 1833	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Ray et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
1167	<i>Caranx papuensis</i> Alleyne & MacLeay, 1877	MB	AP, TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1168	<i>Caranx sexfasciatus</i> Quoy & Gaimard, 1825	MBF	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
1169	<i>Caranx tille</i> Cuvier, 1833	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Puducherry
1170	<i>Decapterus akaadsi</i> Abe, 1958	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1171	<i>Decapterus kurroides</i> Bleeker, 1855	M	ANI, TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Rajan et al. 2013)	
1172	<i>Decapterus macarellus</i> (Cuvier, 1833)	M	TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1173	<i>Decapterus macrosoma</i> Bleeker, 1851	M	ANI, LK, WB, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Ray et al. 2022, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1174	<i>Decapterus maruadsi</i> (Temminck & Schlegel, 1843)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1175	<i>Decapterus russelli</i> (Rüppell, 1830)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1176	<i>Decapterus tabl</i> Berry, 1968	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1177	<i>Elagatis bipinnulata</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1825)	M	ANI, LK, WB, AP, TN, KL, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012)	
1178	<i>Flavocaranx bajad</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	M	TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1179	<i>Ferdauia ferdau</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, AP,	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Ray et al. 2022, Barman et al. 2000, 2004,	

			TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	
1180	<i>Ferdauia orthogrammus</i> (Jordan & Gilbert, 1882)	M	LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1181	<i>Gnathanodon speciosus</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Ray et al. 2022, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012)	
1182	<i>Kaiwarinus equula</i> (Temminck & Schlegel, 1844)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1183	<i>Megalaspis cordyla</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	
1184	<i>Naucrates ductor</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	M	LK, WB, AP, TN, KL, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1185	<i>Parastromateus niger</i> (Bloch, 1795)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	Tranquebar [Tharangambadi]
1186	<i>Platyaranx chrysophrys</i> (Cuvier, 1833)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
1187	<i>Platyaranx malabaricus</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Khan 2002, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	
1188	<i>Platyaranx talamparoides</i> (Bleeker, 1852)	M	ANI, WB, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Ray et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	
1189	<i>Scomberoides commersonnianus</i> Lacepède, 1801	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a, Hedge et al. 2013)	
1190	<i>Scomberoides lysan</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
1191	<i>Scomberoides tala</i> (Cuvier, 1832)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Khan 2002, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	

1192	<i>Scomberoides tol</i> (Cuvier, 1832)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Ray et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a, Talwar 1974)	Malabar coast
1193	<i>Scomberoides pelagicus</i> Abdussamad, Rethesh & Gopalakrishnan, 2022	M	TN, KL	(Abdussamad et al. 2022)	Indian Seas, southern coast of India
1194	<i>Selar boops</i> (Cuvier, 1833)	M	ANI, OD, AP, TN, KL, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1195	<i>Selar crumenophthalmus</i> (Bloch, 1793)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1196	<i>Selaroides leptolepis</i> (Cuvier, 1833)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1197	<i>Seriola dumerili</i> (Risso, 1810)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1198	<i>Seriola lalandi</i> Valenciennes, 1833	MB	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
1199	<i>Seriola rivoliana</i> Valenciennes, 1833	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biswas et al. 2012)	
1200	<i>Seriolina nigrofasciata</i> (Rüppell, 1829)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Ray et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
1201	<i>Scyris indica</i> Rüppell, 1830	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Khan 2002, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
1202	<i>Trachinotus africanus</i> Smith, 1967	MB	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1203	<i>Trachinotus baillonii</i> (Lacepède, 1801)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Misra 1959, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1204	<i>Trachinotus blochii</i> (Lacepède, 1801)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1205	<i>Trachinotus botla</i> (Shaw, 1803)	MB	WB, OD, TN, KL, KA, MH	(Biju et al. 2019, Misra 1959, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, 2013a)	
1206	<i>Trachinotus mookalee</i> Cuvier, 1832	M	OD, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a, Hedge et al. 2013)	Malabar coast
1207	<i>Trachurus indicus</i> Nekrasov, 1966	M	MH	(Barman et al. 2012)	
1208	<i>Trachurus novaezelandiae</i> Richardson,	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	

	1843				
1209	<i>Turrum coeruleopinnatum</i> (Rüppell, 1830)	M	ANI, WB, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Ray et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	
1210	<i>Turrum fulvoguttatum</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	ANI, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	
1211	<i>Turrum gymnostethus</i> (Cuvier, 1833)	M	ANI, TN, KL, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012)	
1212	<i>Uraspis helvola</i> (Forster, 1801)	M	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Ray et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1213	<i>Uraspis uraspis</i> (Günther, 1860)	M	ANI, WB, AP, TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ramees et al. 2024)	
Family: Citharidae de Buen, 1935					
1214	<i>Laiopteryx novaezeelandiae</i> (Günther, 1862)	M	WB, OD, TN	(Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Coryphaenidae Rafinesque, 1815					
1215	<i>Coryphaena equiselis</i> Linnaeus, 1758	M	TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	
1216	<i>Coryphaena hippurus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Khan 2002, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Cynoglossidae Jordan, 1888					
1217	<i>Cynoglossus arel</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	Tharangambadi
1218	<i>Cynoglossus brachycephalus</i> Bleeker, 1870	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1219	<i>Cynoglossus carpenteri</i> Alcock, 1889	M	OD, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	68 miles east of mouth of Devi River, Mahanaddi delta, Bay of Bengal
1220	<i>Cynoglossus cynoglossus</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, TN, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	Ganges River tidal mouths
1221	<i>Cynoglossus dispar</i> Day, 1877	M	TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a, Hedge et al. 2013)	
1222	<i>Cynoglossus dubius</i> Day, 1873	M	OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	
1223	<i>Cynoglossus itinus</i> (Snyder, 1909)	M	OD, TN	(Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1224	<i>Cynoglossus kopsii</i> (Bleeker, 1851)	M	ANI, LK, OD, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	

1225	<i>Cynoglossus lida</i> (Bleeker, 1851)	M	ANI, WB, OD, TN, KL, KA, GA	(Rajan et al. 2013, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a, Talwar 1974)	
1226	<i>Cynoglossus lingua</i> Hamilton, 1822	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	Ganges River estuary
1227	<i>Cynoglossus macrolepidotus</i> (Bleeker, 1851)	M	WB, OD, TN	(Kar et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1228	<i>Cynoglossus macrostomus</i> Norman, 1928	MB	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	Hooghly River estuary near Calcutta
1229	<i>Cynoglossus monopus</i> (Bleeker, 1849)	M	OD, TN, MH	(Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
1230	<i>Cynoglossus puncticeps</i> (Richardson, 1846)	MBF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
1231	<i>Cynoglossus quadrilineatus</i> (Bleeker, 1851)	MB	OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
1232	<i>Cynoglossus semifasciatus</i> Day, 1877	M	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, MH	(Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Chennai
1233	<i>Cynoglossus zanzibarensis</i> Norman, 1939	M	KL	(Biju et al. 2019)	
1234	<i>Paraplagusia bilineata</i> (Bloch, 1787)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
1235	<i>Paraplagusia bleekeri</i> Kottelat, 2013	MB	WB, OD, TN, GA	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
1236	<i>Symphurus gilesii</i> (Alcock, 1889)	M	WB	(Sanyal et al. 2012)	Bay of Bengal, 20°17'N, 88°51'E
1237	<i>Symphurus macrophthalmus</i> Norman, 1939	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1238	<i>Symphurus ocellatus</i> von Bonde, 1922	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1239	<i>Symphurus septemstriatus</i> (Alcock, 1891)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Andaman Sea, 11°31'40"N, 92°46'06"E
1240	<i>Symphurus trifasciatus</i> (Alcock, 1894)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Bay of Bengal
1241	<i>Symphurus woodmasoni</i> (Alcock, 1889)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	7.5 miles east of North Cinque Island, Andaman Islands
Family: Echeneidae Rafinesque, 1810					

1242	<i>Echeneis naucrates</i> Linnaeus, 1758	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1243	<i>Phtheirichthys lineatus</i> (Menzies, 1791)	M	LK, KL	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019)	
1244	<i>Remora albescens</i> (Temminck & Schlegel, 1850)	M	ANI, LK, OD, KL, MH	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, Shirke et al. 2021)	
1245	<i>Remora brachyptera</i> (Lowe, 1839)	M	ANI, TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Shirke et al. 2021)	
1246	<i>Remora osteochir</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Shirke et al. 2021)	
1247	<i>Remora remora</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	M	ANI, WB, OD, TN, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000)	
Family: Istiophoridae Rafinesque, 1815					
1248	<i>Istiompax indica</i> (Cuvier, 1832)	M	LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1249	<i>Istiophorus platypterus</i> (Shaw, 1792)	M	ANI, LK, WB, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al., 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1250	<i>Kajikia audax</i> (Philippi, 1887)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1251	<i>Makaira mazara</i> (Jordan & Snyder, 1901)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1252	<i>Makaira nigricans</i> Lacepède, 1802	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1253	<i>Tetrapturus angustirostris</i> Tanaka, 1915	M	TN, KL, KA, MH	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, 2013a)	
Family: Lactariidae Boulenger, 1904					
1254	<i>Lactarius lactarius</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	
Family: Latidae Jordan, 1888					
1255	<i>Lates calcarifer</i> (Bloch, 1790)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Shaji et al. 2019, Kar et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Nandi et al. 2008)	Pattukottai, Tamil Nadu
1256	<i>Psammoperca waigiensis</i> (Cuvier, 1828)	MB	ANI, AP, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Menidae Fitzinger, 1873					
1257	<i>Mene maculata</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Tranquebar [Tharangambadi]
Family: Paralichthyidae Regan, 1910					
1258	<i>Cephalopsetta</i>	M	AP, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2004)	Visakhapatnam,

	<i>ventrocellata</i> Dutt & Rao, 1965				Andhra Pradesh
1259	<i>Pseudorhombus argus</i> Weber, 1913	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1260	<i>Pseudorhombus arsius</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	Botanical Garden of Calcutta, Ganges River estuary
1261	<i>Pseudorhombus diplospilus</i> Norman, 1926	M	TN	(Kodeeswaran et al. 2020)	
1262	<i>Pseudorhombus dupliciocellatus</i> Regan, 1905	M	ANI, OD, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1263	<i>Pseudorhombus elevatus</i> Ogilby, 1912	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1264	<i>Pseudorhombus javanicus</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	M	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
1265	<i>Pseudorhombus malayanus</i> Bleeker, 1865	M	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1266	<i>Pseudorhombus megalops</i> Fowler, 1934	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1267	<i>Pseudorhombus micrognathus</i> Norman, 1927	M	OD, TN	(Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Puri Beach, Orissa
1268	<i>Pseudorhombus natalensis</i> Gilchrist, 1904	M	TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1269	<i>Pseudorhombus triocellatus</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	M	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	Tharangambadi
Family: Poecilopsettidae Norman 1934					
1270	<i>Marleyella bicolorata</i> (von Bonde, 1922)	M	West Coast of India	(Heemstra 1986)	
1271	<i>Poecilopsetta colorata</i> Günther, 1880	M	ANI, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1272	<i>Poecilopsetta praelonga</i> Alcock, 1894	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
Family: Polynemidae Rafinesque, 1815					
1273	<i>Eleutheronema tetradactylum</i> (Shaw, 1804)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Shaji et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Nandi et al. 2008)	Gariahat, Calcutta
1274	<i>Filimanus heptadactyla</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	MB	ANI, OD, AP, TN, KL, GA, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
1275	<i>Filimanus perplexa</i> Feltes, 1991	M	ANI	(Mishra & Barman 2009)	
1276	<i>Filimanus similis</i> Feltes, 1991	M	LK, WB, OD, TN, KA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2021, Sanyal et al. 2012, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, 2013a)	

1277	<i>Filimanus xanthonema</i> (Valenciennes, 1831)	M	OD, TN, KA, MH	(Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, 2013a)	Puducherry
1278	<i>Leptomelanosoma indicum</i> (Shaw, 1804)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	Visakhapatnam
1279	<i>Polydactylus microstomus</i> (Bleeker, 1851)	MB	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1280	<i>Polydactylus mullani</i> (Hora, 1926)	M	TN, KL, MH	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	Mumbai, Maharashtra
1281	<i>Polydactylus multiradiatus</i> (Günther, 1860)	MB	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1282	<i>Polydactylus plebeius</i> (Broussonet, 1782)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1283	<i>Polydactylus sexfilis</i> (Valenciennes, 1831)	MBF	ANI, LK, OD, AP, TN, KL, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1284	<i>Polydactylus sextarius</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	MB	WB, OD, AP, TN, KA, MH, GJ	(Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Tranquebar [Tharangambadi]
1285	<i>Polynemus melanochir</i> Valenciennes, 1831	BF	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1286	<i>Polynemus dubius</i> Bleeker, 1853	MBF	WB, TN	(Yennawar et al. 2015, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1287	<i>Polynemus paradiseus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	MBF	OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Gariahat, Calcutta
1288	<i>Polynemus multifilis</i> Temminck & Schlegel, 1843	BF	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Psettodidae Regan, 1910					
1289	<i>Psettodes erumei</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	Tharangambadi
Family: Rachycentridae Gill, 1896					
1290	<i>Rachycentron canadum</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
Family: Samaridae Jordan & Goss, 1889					
1291	<i>Samaris cristatus</i> Gray, 1831	MB	ANI, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1292	<i>Samaris macrolepis</i> Norman, 1927	M	OD	(Pati et al. 2018)	
1293	<i>Samariscus huysmani</i> Weber, 1913	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1294	<i>Samariscus</i>	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	

	<i>longimanus</i> Norman, 1927				
1295	<i>Samariscus triocellatus</i> Woods, 1960	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Soleidae Bonaparte, 1833					
1296	<i>Aesopia cornuta</i> Kaup, 1858	M	ANI, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1297	<i>Aseraggodes cyaneus</i> (Alcock, 1890)	M	OD, TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Off Ganjam coast
1298	<i>Aseraggodes kobensis</i> (Steindachner, 1896)	M	ANI, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Ummath et al. 2024)	
1299	<i>Aseraggodes martine</i> Randall & Bogorodsky, 2013	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	Lakshadweep (Laccadive Islands), Andrott Island, lagoon, sand bottom
1300	<i>Aseraggodes umbratilis</i> (Alcock, 1894)	M	KL	(Biju et al. 2019)	Bay of Bengal, 21°52'N, 68°06'E
1301	<i>Brachirus annularis</i> Fowler, 1934	M	TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1302	<i>Brachirus macrolepis</i> (Bleeker, 1858)	M	WB, OD	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Pati et al. 2018)	
1303	<i>Brachirus orientalis</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Shaji et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Hedge et al. 2013)	Tharangambadi
1304	<i>Brachirus pan</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MBF	WB, OD, TN	(Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1305	<i>Brachirus panoides</i> (Bleeker, 1851)	BF	OD	(Pati et al. 2018)	
1306	<i>Dagetichthys albomaculatus</i> (Kaup, 1858)	MB	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, 2013a, Hedge et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2017, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Coromandel coast
1307	<i>Dagetichthys commersonnii</i> (Lacepède, 1802)	MB	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mishra et al. 2017, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1308	<i>Dagetichthys marginatus</i> (Boulenger, 1900)	MB	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1309	<i>Heteromycteris oculus</i> (Alcock, 1889)	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	About 32 miles southwest of Puri, Orissa coast, Bay of Bengal
1310	<i>Liachirus melanospilos</i> (Bleeker, 1854)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
1311	<i>Pardachirus marmoratus</i> (Lacepède, 1802)	M	ANI, OD, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1312	<i>Pardachirus pavoninus</i> (Lacepède, 1802)	M	ANI, OD, TN, AP	(Rajan et al. 2013, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Kumar et al. 2024)	
1313	<i>Pegusa nasuta</i> (Pallas, 1814)	MB	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1314	<i>Pseudaesopia cochinchensis</i> Rama-Rao, 1967	M	KL	(Rama-Rao 1967)	Off Vypeen Island, Cochin

1315	<i>Pseudaesopia synapturoides</i> (Jenkins, 1910)	M	OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
1316	<i>Solea elongata</i> Day, 1877	M	WB, OD, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a, Ansari et al. 1995)	Chennai
1317	<i>Solea heinii</i> Steindachner, 1903	M	Coasts of India	(Kapoor et al. 2002)	
1318	<i>Solea ovata</i> Richardson, 1846	M	OD, AP, TN, KL, GA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
1319	<i>Soleichthys heterorhinos</i> (Bleeker, 1856)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
1320	<i>Zebrias altipinnis</i> (Alcock, 1890)	M	WB, OD, AP, TN, MH	(Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	off Visakhapatnam coast
1321	<i>Zebrias annandalei</i> Talwar & Chakrapany, 1967	M	OD	(Pati et al. 2018)	Puri Beach, Orissa
1322	<i>Zebrias keralensis</i> Joglekar, 1976	M	TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Kerala Coast
1323	<i>Zebrias quagga</i> (Kaup, 1858)	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Mumbai
1324	<i>Zebrias zebra</i> (Bloch, 1787)	MB	OD, AP, TN	(Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Sphyraenidae Rafinesque, 1815					
1325	<i>Sphyraena arabiansis</i> Abdussamad & Retheesh, 2015	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	Lakshadweep Islands
1326	<i>Sphyraena acutipinnis</i> Day, 1876	MB	ANI, OD, TN, KA, GA	(Rajan et al. 2013, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a, Ansari et al. 1995)	
1327	<i>Sphyraena arabiansis</i> Abdussamad & Retheesh, 2015	M	LK	(Abdussamad et al. 2015)	Lakshadweep Islands
1328	<i>Sphyraena barracuda</i> (Edwards, 1771)	MB	ANI, LK, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1329	<i>Sphyraena flavicauda</i> Rüppell, 1838	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1330	<i>Sphyraena forsteri</i> Cuvier, 1829	M	ANI, LK, WB, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1331	<i>Sphyraena jello</i> Cuvier, 1829	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Visakhapatnam
1332	<i>Sphyraena novaehollandiae</i> Günther, 1860	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	

1333	<i>Sphyraena obtusata</i> Cuvier, 1829	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Puducherry
1334	<i>Sphyraena pinguis</i> Günther, 1874	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL, GA	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Talwar 1974, Kapoor et al. 2002)	
1335	<i>Sphyraena putnamae</i> Jordan & Seale, 1905	M	OD, TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1336	<i>Sphyraena qenie</i> Klunzinger, 1870	MB	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
1337	<i>Sphyraena stellata</i> Morishita & Motomura, 2020	M	Coasts of India	(Talwar & Kacker 1984)	
Family: Toxotidae Bleeker, 1859					
1338	<i>Toxotes chatareus</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	ANI, WB, OD, KL, KA	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a)	Ganges River estuaries
1339	<i>Toxotes jaculatrix</i> (Pallas, 1767)	BF	ANI, WB, KA	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2017, Barman et al. 2013a)	
Family: Xiphiidae Rafinesque, 1815					
1340	<i>Xiphias gladius</i> Linnaeus, 1758	M	LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Order: Centrarchiformes					
Family: Cirrhitidae Macleay, 1841					
1341	<i>Cirrhitichthys aprinus</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	MB	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1342	<i>Cirrhitichthys aureus</i> (Temminck & Schlegel, 1843)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1343	<i>Cirrhitichthys bleekeri</i> Day, 1874	M	TN, KL	(Day 1874, Ramachandran et al. 2020b)	Madras
1344	<i>Cirrhitichthys falco</i> Randall, 1963	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, Anto et al. 2024)	
1345	<i>Cirrhitichthys oxycephalus</i> (Bleeker, 1855)	M	ANI, LK	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Sandra et al. 2022)	
1346	<i>Cirrhitus pinnulatus</i> (Forster, 1801)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1347	<i>Oxycirrhites typus</i> Bleeker, 1857	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
1348	<i>Paracirrhites arcatus</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
1349	<i>Paracirrhites forsteri</i> (Schneider, 1801)	M	ANI, LK, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Barman et al. 2012)	
Family: Kuhliidae Jordan & Evermann, 1896					
1350	<i>Kuhlia marginata</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	BF	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1351	<i>Kuhlia mugil</i> (Forster, 1801)	MB	ANI, LK, AP, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a)	
1352	<i>Kuhlia rupestris</i> (Lacepède, 1802)	MBF	ANI, AP, KL, KA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, 2013a)	
Family: Kyphosidae Jordan, 1887					
1353	<i>Kyphosus bigibbus</i> Lacepède, 1801	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	

	1801				
1354	<i>Kyphosus cinerascens</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	ANI, LK, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1355	<i>Kyphosus vaigiensis</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1825)	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Terapontidae Richardson, 1842					
1356	<i>Pelates quadrilineatus</i> (Bloch, 1790)	MB	ANI, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1357	<i>Terapon jarbua</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	MBF	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Shaji et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a, Nandi et al. 2008)	
1358	<i>Terapon puta</i> Cuvier, 1829	MBF	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	Visakhapatnam
1359	<i>Terapon theraps</i> Cuvier, 1829	MBF	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a, Talwar 1974)	
Order: Characiformes					
Family: Characidae Latreille, 1825					
1360	<i>Gymnocorymbus ternetzi</i> (Boulenger, 1895)	F	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
Family: Serrasalminidae Bleeker, 1859					
1361	<i>Pygocentrus nattereri</i> Kner, 1858	F	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1362	<i>Piaractus brachypomus</i> (Cuvier, 1818)	F	KL	(Waterlake & Of 2015)	
Order: Cichliformes					
Family: Ambassidae Klunzinger, 1870					
1363	<i>Ambassis ambassis</i> (Lacepède, 1802)	MBF	ANI, LK, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Shaji et al. 2019, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Talwar 1974)	
1364	<i>Ambassis buruensis</i> Bleeker, 1856	BF	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1365	<i>Ambassis buton</i> Popta, 1918	BF	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1366	<i>Ambassis dussumieri</i> Cuvier, 1828	MBF	ANI, OD, KL, KA	(Rajan et al. 2013, Shaji et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a)	Malabar, India
1367	<i>Ambassis gymnocephalus</i> (Lacepède, 1802)	MBF	ANI, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
1368	<i>Ambassis interrupta</i> Bleeker, 1853	MBF	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1369	<i>Ambassis kopsii</i> Bleeker, 1858	MBF	ANI, WB,	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati	

			OD	et al. 2018)	
1370	<i>Ambassis macracanthus</i> Bleeker, 1849	BF	Eastern Indian Coastal Waters	(Kapoor 2002)	
1371	<i>Ambassis miops</i> Günther, 1872	MBF	TN, KL, GA	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Nandi et al. 2008)	
1372	<i>Ambassis nalua</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Fresh waters of lower Bengal
1373	<i>Ambassis urotaenia</i> Bleeker, 1852	MBF	ANI, LK, OD, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1374	<i>Chanda nama</i> Hamilton, 1822	BF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ, PU, UK, HY, DL, UP, RJ, MP, TL, CG, BR, JH, AS, ML, AR, NL, MN, MZ, TR	(Shaji et al. 2019, Karmakar & Das 2005, Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Yadav 2008, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a, Kaur et al. 2017, Tudu et al. 2022, Murugan & Prabakaran 2012, Kar & Sen 2007)	Ponds of Bengal
1375	<i>Parambassis baculis</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, MH, HP, DL, RJ, MP, SK, AS, ML, AR, MN, TR	(Mishra et al. 2017, Sen 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Bagra et al. 2009, Husain 1997, Barman 2002, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Karmakar 2006, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sharma & Dhanze 2018)	Assam
1376	<i>Parambassis bistigmata</i> Geetakumari, 2012	F	AR	(Geetakumari 2012)	Ranga River, Kimin Station, Brahmaputra drainage, 27°21'01"N, 93°57'11"E, Arunachal Pradesh
1377	<i>Parambassis dayi</i> (Bleeker, 1874)	BF	ANI, OD, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Shaji et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Malabar (Kochi), Kerala
1378	<i>Parambassis lala</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, TN, MH	(Chini et al. 2019, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Chowdhury et al. 2023)	Gangetic provinces
1379	<i>Parambassis ranga</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ, UK, HY, DL, UP, RJ, MP, TL, CG, BR, JH, SK, AS, ML, AR, MN, MZ, TR	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Sen 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar 2006, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a, Tudu et al. 2022,	Gangetic provinces

				Murugan & Prabakaran 2012, Kar & Sen 2007)	
1380	<i>Parambassis serrata</i> Mayanglambam & Vishwanath, 2015	F	MZ	(Mayanglambam & Vishwanath 2015)	Kolo River, Kaladan drainage, Lawngtlai District, Mizoram
1381	<i>Parambassis tenasserimensis</i> Roberts, 1995	F	MZ	(Kar & Sen 2007)	
1382	<i>Parambassis thomassi</i> (Day, 1870)	MBF	KL, KA, GA, MH	(Shaji et al. 2019, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Barman et al. 2012, Yadav 2008)	Calicut & Mangalore
1383	<i>Parambassis waikhomi</i> Geetakumari & Basudha, 2012	F	MN	(Geetakumari & Basudha 2012)	Chindwin basin, Loktak Lake, Manipur
Family: Cichlidae Bonaparte, 1835					
1384	<i>Amphilophus trimaculatus</i> (Günther, 1867)	F	WB, TN	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Chakraborty et al. 2020)	
1385	<i>Astronotus ocellatus</i> (Agassiz, 1831)	F	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
1386	<i>Etroplus canarensis</i> Day, 1877	F	KA	(Rema Devi et al. 2013)	South Canara, southwestern India
1387	<i>Etroplus suratensis</i> (Bloch, 1790)	B	LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, TL	(Rajan et al. 2021, Shaji et al. 2019, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar et al. 2012, Yadav 2008)	Tamilnadu (Probably Tanquebar)
1388	<i>Oreochromis mossambicus</i> (Peters, 1852)	BF	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, NL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Shaji et al. 2019, Karmakar & Das 2005, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	
1389	<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	BF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	
1390	<i>Pseudetroplus maculatus</i> (Bloch, 1795)	BF	OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, TL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Pati et al. 2018, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar et al. 2012, Yadav 2008)	Coromandal, Tamilnadu
1391	<i>Pterophyllum scalare</i> (Schultze, 1823)	F	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
Family: Opistognathidae Bonaparte, 1835					
1392	<i>Opistognathus albicaudatus</i> Smith-Vaniz, 2011	M	ANI	(Smith-Vaniz 2011)	Fusilier Strait, 11°52.6'N, 93°03.13'E, Andaman Islands
1393	<i>Opistognathus ensiferus</i> Smith-Vaniz, 2016	M	TN	(Smith-Vaniz 2016)	Gulf of Mannar, Manauli Reef, Musal Tivu Island (Hare Island)

1394	<i>Opistognathus evermanni</i> (Jordan & Snyder, 1902)	M	TN	(Mariasingarayan et al. 2021)	
1395	<i>Opistognathus macrolepis</i> Peters, 1866	M	WB, TN	(Biswas et al. 2013, Ray & Mohapatra 2015)	
1396	<i>Opistognathus nigromarginatus</i> Rüppell, 1830	M	ANI, AP, TN, KL	(Smith-Vaniz 2011, Biju et al. 2019, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1397	<i>Opistognathus pardus</i> Smith-Vaniz, Bineesh & Akhilesh, 2012	M	KL	(Biju et al. 2019)	Kerala
1398	<i>Opistognathus rosenbergii</i> Bleeker, 1856	M	ANI, WB, AP, TN	(Smith-Vaniz 2011, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ray & Mohapatra 2015)	
Family: Pholidichthyidae Jordan, 1896					
1399	<i>Pholidichthys leucotaenia</i> Bleeker, 1856	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
Family: Plesiopidae Günther, 1861					
1400	<i>Acanthoplesiops indicus</i> (Day, 1888)	M	Tamilnadu	(Day 1888)	Madras
1401	<i>Calloplesiops altivelis</i> (Steindachner, 1903)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
1402	<i>Plesiops coeruleolineatus</i> Rüppell, 1835	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
1403	<i>Plesiops corallicola</i> Bleeker, 1853	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1404	<i>Plesiops oxycephalus</i> Bleeker, 1855	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
Family: Pomacentridae Bonaparte, 1831					
1405	<i>Abudefduf bengalensis</i> (Bloch, 1787)	M	ANI, LK, OD, AP, TN, KL, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	Bay of Bengal
1406	<i>Abudefduf natalensis</i> Hensley & Randall, 1983	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1407	<i>Abudefduf notatus</i> (Day, 1870)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Andaman Islands
1408	<i>Abudefduf septemfasciatus</i> (Cuvier, 1830)	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1409	<i>Abudefduf sexfasciatus</i> (Lacepède, 1801)	M	LK, TN, KL, GA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, Talwar 1974)	
1410	<i>Abudefduf sordidus</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	MB	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Biswas et al. 2012, Barman et al. 2004)	
1411	<i>Abudefduf vaigiensis</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1825)	M	ANI, LK, WB, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1412	<i>Amblyglyphidodon aureus</i> (Cuvier, 1830)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1413	<i>Amblyglyphidodon indicus</i> Allen & Randall, 2002	M	ANI, LK	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Sandra et al. 2022)	

1414	<i>Amblyglyphidodon silolona</i> Allen, Erdmann & Drew, 2012	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	North Button Island, 12°18.560'N, 93°04.070'E, Andaman Islands
1415	<i>Amblyglyphidodon leucogaster</i> (Bleeker, 1847)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
1416	<i>Amblyglyphidodon ternatensis</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1417	<i>Amblypomacentrus annulatus</i> (Peters, 1855)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
1418	<i>Amblypomacentrus breviceps</i> (Schlegel & Müller, 1839)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1419	<i>Amphiprion akallopisos</i> Bleeker, 1853	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1420	<i>Amphiprion biaculeatus</i> (Bloch, 1790)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1421	<i>Amphiprion bicinctus</i> Rüppell, 1830	M	LK	(Kapoor et al. 2002)	
1422	<i>Amphiprion chrysogaster</i> Cuvier, 1830	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
1423	<i>Amphiprion clarkii</i> (Bennett, 1830)	M	ANI, LK, OD, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Mohanty et al. 2020)	
1424	<i>Amphiprion ephippium</i> (Bloch, 1790)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Tharangambadi
1425	<i>Amphiprion frenatus</i> Brevoort, 1856	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1426	<i>Amphiprion nigripes</i> Regan, 1908	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
1427	<i>Amphiprion ocellaris</i> Cuvier, 1830	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1428	<i>Amphiprion perideraion</i> Bleeker, 1855	MB	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1429	<i>Amphiprion percula</i> (Lacepède, 1802)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1430	<i>Amphiprion polymnus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1431	<i>Amphiprion sebae</i> Bleeker, 1853	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1432	<i>Azurina lepidolepis</i> (Bleeker, 1876)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
1433	<i>Cheiloprion labiatus</i> (Day, 1877)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Bay of Bengal
1434	<i>Chromis atripectoralis</i> Welander & Schultz, 1951	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1435	<i>Chromis chrysurus</i> (Bliss, 1883)	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1436	<i>Chromis flavicauda</i> (Günther, 1880)	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
1437	<i>Chromis opercularis</i> (Günther, 1867)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1438	<i>Chromis ternatensis</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	M	ANI, LK,	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Rajan et al.	

	1856)		TN	2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1439	<i>Chromis viridis</i> (Cuvier, 1830)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1440	<i>Chromis weberi</i> Fowler & Bean, 1928	M	ANI, LK	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Rajan et al. 2021)	
1441	<i>Chromis xanthochira</i> (Bleeker, 1851)	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
1442	<i>Chrysiptera biocellata</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1825)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1443	<i>Chrysiptera brownriggii</i> (Bennett, 1828)	M	ANI, LK	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Rajan et al. 2021)	
1444	<i>Chrysiptera caeruleolineata</i> (Allen, 1973)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1445	<i>Chrysiptera cyanea</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1825)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1446	<i>Chrysiptera glauca</i> (Cuvier, 1830)	M	ANI, LK, TN, GA	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
1447	<i>Chrysiptera leucopoma</i> (Cuvier, 1830)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1448	<i>Chrysiptera rollandi</i> (Whitley, 1961)	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
1449	<i>Chrysiptera talboti</i> (Allen, 1975)	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
1450	<i>Chrysiptera unimaculata</i> (Cuvier, 1830)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1451	<i>Dascyllus aruanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1452	<i>Dascyllus carneus</i> Fischer, 1885	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1453	<i>Dascyllus marginatus</i> (Rüppell, 1829)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1454	<i>Dascyllus melanurus</i> Bleeker, 1854	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1455	<i>Dascyllus reticulatus</i> (Richardson, 1846)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
1456	<i>Dascyllus trimaculatus</i> (Rüppell, 1829)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1457	<i>Dischistodus perspicillatus</i> (Cuvier, 1830)	MB	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1458	<i>Dischistodus prosopotaenia</i> (Bleeker, 1852)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1459	<i>Hemiglyphidodon plagiometopon</i> (Bleeker, 1852)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1460	<i>Lepidozygus tapeinosoma</i> (Bleeker, 1856)	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1461	<i>Neoglyphidodon bonang</i> (Bleeker, 1852)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1462	<i>Neoglyphidodon melas</i> (Cuvier, 1830)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1463	<i>Neoglyphidodon nigroris</i> (Cuvier, 1830)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1464	<i>Neoglyphidodon oxyodon</i> (Bleeker, 1858)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	

1465	<i>Neopomacentrus azyron</i> (Bleeker, 1877)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1466	<i>Neopomacentrus cyanomos</i> (Bleeker, 1856)	M	LK, TN, MH	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
1467	<i>Neopomacentrus filamentosus</i> (MacLeay, 1882)	M	TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1468	<i>Neopomacentrus sororius</i> Randall & Allen, 2005	M	KL	(Randall & Allen 2005)	
1469	<i>Neopomacentrus taeniurus</i> (Bleeker, 1856)	M	ANI, LK, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019)	
1470	<i>Neopomacentrus violascens</i> (Bleeker, 1848)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1471	<i>Parma oligolepis</i> Whitley, 1929	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
1472	<i>Plectroglyphidodon dickii</i> (Liénard, 1839)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1473	<i>Plectroglyphidodon johnstonianus</i> Fowler & Ball, 1924	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
1474	<i>Plectroglyphidodon leucozona</i> (Bleeker, 1859)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
1475	<i>Plectroglyphidodon luteobrunneus</i> (Smith, 1960)	M	LK	(Anto et al. 2024)	
1476	<i>Plectroglyphidodon phoenixensis</i> (Schultz, 1943)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
1477	<i>Pomacentrus alleni</i> Burgess, 1981	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
1478	<i>Pomacentrus amboinensis</i> Bleeker, 1868	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1479	<i>Pomacentrus azuremaculatus</i> Allen, 1991	M	ANI	(Allen & Erdmann 2012)	
1480	<i>Pomacentrus bankanensis</i> Bleeker, 1854	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1481	<i>Pomacentrus brachialis</i> Cuvier, 1830	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
1482	<i>Pomacentrus caeruleus</i> Quoy & Gaimard, 1825	M	TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1483	<i>Pomacentrus chrysurus</i> Cuvier, 1830	M	ANI, LK	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Rajan et al. 2021)	
1484	<i>Pomacentrus indicus</i> Allen, 1991	M	ANI, LK	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Anto et al. 2024)	
1485	<i>Pomacentrus lepidogenys</i> Fowler & Bean, 1928	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
1486	<i>Pomacentrus littoralis</i> Cuvier, 1830	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
1487	<i>Pomacentrus moluccensis</i> Bleeker, 1853	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1488	<i>Pomacentrus nagasakiensis</i> Tanaka, 1917	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
1489	<i>Pomacentrus pavo</i> (Bloch, 1787)	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1490	<i>Pomacentrus philippinus</i> Evermann &	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	

	Seale, 1907				
1491	<i>Pomacentrus similis</i> Allen, 1991	M	ANI, TN, AP	(Rajan et al. 2013, Padate et al. 2017, Kumar et al. 2024)	
1492	<i>Pomacentrus sulfureus</i> Klunzinger, 1871	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
1493	<i>Pomacentrus trilineatus</i> Cuvier, 1830	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1494	<i>Pomacentrus tripunctatus</i> Cuvier, 1830	MB	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1495	<i>Pomacentrus umbratilus</i> Allen, Erdmann & Pertiwi, 2023	M	ANI	(Allen et al. 2021)	
1496	<i>Pomacentrus vaiuli</i> Jordan & Seale, 1906	MB	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1497	<i>Pomacentrus xanthocercus</i> Allen, Erdmann & Pertiwi, 2023	M	LK	(Anto et al. 2024)	
1498	<i>Pristotis cyanostigma</i> Rüppell, 1838	M	TN	(Padate et al. 2017)	
1499	<i>Pristotis obtusirostris</i> (Günther, 1862)	M	LK, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1500	<i>Pycnochromis dimidiatus</i> (Klunzinger, 1871)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1501	<i>Pycnochromis margaritifera</i> (Fowler, 1946)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1502	<i>Pycnochromis nigrurus</i> (Smith, 1960)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
1503	<i>Stegastes albifasciatus</i> (Schlegel & Müller, 1839)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
1504	<i>Stegastes lividus</i> (Forster, 1801)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1505	<i>Stegastes lacrymatus</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1825)	M	ANI, LK, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019)	
1506	<i>Stegastes nigricans</i> (Lacepède, 1802)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1507	<i>Stegastes punctatus</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1825)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
Family: Pseudochromidae Müller & Troschel, 1849					
1508	<i>Congrogadus subducens</i> (Richardson, 1843)	MB	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1509	<i>Halidesmus thomasoni</i> (Nielsen, 1961)	M	WB	(Yennawar et al. 2015)	
1510	<i>Ogilbyina novaehollandiae</i> (Steindachner, 1879)	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
1511	<i>Pseudochromis caudalis</i> Boulenger, 1898	M	MH	(Barman et al. 2012)	
1512	<i>Pseudochromis cyanotaenia</i> Bleeker, 1857	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1513	<i>Pseudochromis dutoiti</i> Smith, 1955	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
1514	<i>Pseudochromis fuscus</i> Müller & Troschel, 1849	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	

1515	<i>Pseudochromis tapeinosoma</i> Bleeker, 1853	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
Order: Clupeiformes					
Family: Chirocentridae Bleeker, 1849					
1516	<i>Chirocentrus dorab</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Biju et al. 2019, Khan 2002, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012, Ansari et al. 1995)	
1517	<i>Chirocentrus nudus</i> Swainson, 1839	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Visakhapatnam
Family: Dorosomatidae Gill, 1861					
1518	<i>Amblygaster clupeioides</i> Bleeker, 1849	M	ANI, LK, OD, AP, TN, KL, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Jagtap 2013)	
1519	<i>Amblygaster indiana</i> Mary, Balasubramanian, Selvaraju & Shiny, 2017	M	TN	(Mary et al. 2017)	Eraviputhenthura i landing centre, fish market, west coast, India, 11°15'49.26"N, 77°08'11.67"E
1520	<i>Amblygaster leiogaster</i> (Valenciennes, 1847)	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Kar et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1521	<i>Amblygaster sirm</i> (Walbaum, 1792)	MB	ANI, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1522	<i>Anodontostoma chacunda</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Ganges River estuary
1523	<i>Anodontostoma selangkat</i> (Bleeker, 1852)	MB	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1524	<i>Anodontostoma thailandiae</i> Wongratana, 1983	MB	ANI, WB	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2017)	
1525	<i>Escualosa thoracata</i> (Valenciennes, 1847)	MBF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Khan 2002, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	Puducherry
1526	<i>Ethmalosa fimbriata</i> (Bowdich, 1825)	MBF	OD	(Patil et al. 2018)	
1527	<i>Gonialosa manmina</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	WB, OD, MH, GJ, UP, MP, CG, AS	(Mishra et al. 2017, Chanda & Jana 2021, Sen 1985, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Mishra et al. 2021a)	Freshwater branches of Ganges River

1528	<i>Gudusia chapra</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	WB, OD, AP, TN, GJ, PU, UK, HY, DL, UP, RJ, MP, CG, BR, AS, ML, MZ, TR	(Mishra et al. 2017, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman 1993, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Husain 1997, Barman 2002, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a, Kaur et al. 2017, Murugan & Prabakaran 2012, Kar & Sen 2007)	Upper parts of Ganges River, Gandak River in Saran, Bihar
1529	<i>Gudusia variegata</i> (Day, 1870)	F	WB, AS	(Biswas et al. 2018, Sen 1985)	
1530	<i>Herklotsichthys punctatus</i> (Rüppell, 1837)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
1531	<i>Herklotsichthys quadrimaculatus</i> (Rüppell, 1837)	MBF	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
1532	<i>Hilsa kelee</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2017, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Talwar 1974)	Visakhapatnam
1533	<i>Nematalosa galathea</i> Nelson & Rothman, 1973	MBF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KA	(Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1534	<i>Nematalosa nasus</i> (Bloch, 1795)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KA, GA, MH, GJ, TR	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	Malabar
1535	<i>Sardinella albella</i> (Valenciennes, 1847)	MB	ANI, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Puducherry
1536	<i>Sardinella brachysoma</i> Bleeker, 1852	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1537	<i>Sardinella dayi</i> Regan, 1917	M	TN, KA	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Karwar, Karnataka
1538	<i>Sardinella fimbriata</i> (Valenciennes, 1847)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	Malabar coast
1539	<i>Sardinella gibbosa</i> (Bleeker, 1849)	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1540	<i>Sardinella jussieu</i> (Lacepède, 1803)	M	OD, KL, KA	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a)	
1541	<i>Sardinella longiceps</i> Valenciennes, 1847	M	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	Puducherry
1542	<i>Sardinella melanura</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	ANI, LK, OD, TN,	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018,	

			KL, KA, MH, GJ	Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	
1543	<i>Sardinella sindensis</i> (Day, 1878)	M	OD, TN, KL, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012)	
1544	<i>Tenualosa ilisha</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MBF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ, DL, MP, TL, AS, MN, TR	(Shaji et al. 2019, Khan 2002, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Barman et al. 2013a, Husain 1997, Sen 1985, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Talwar 1974)	Ganges estuaries
1545	<i>Tenualosa reevesii</i> (Richardson, 1846)	MBF	OD	(Pati et al. 2018)	
1546	<i>Tenualosa toli</i> (Valenciennes, 1847)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Khan 2002, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 1993, 2000, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Mumbai
Family: Dussumieriidae Gill, 1861					
1547	<i>Dussumieria acuta</i> Valenciennes, 1847	MBF	ANI, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	Coromandel, southeastern India
1548	<i>Dussumieria albulina</i> (Fowler, 1934)	M	KL	(Hata et al. 2021)	
1549	<i>Dussumieria elopsoides</i> Bleeker, 1849	M	ANI, LK, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1550	<i>Dussumieria modakandai</i> Singh, Teena Jayakumar, Kumar, Murali, Mishra, Singh & Lal, 2021	M	TN	(Singh et al. 2021)	Pattinapakkam fish market, Chennai coast, Bay of Bengal, Tamil Nadu
Family: Ehiravidae Deraniyagala, 1929					
1551	<i>Corica soborna</i> Hamilton, 1822	MBF	WB, OD, KL, TL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Khan 2002, Pati et al. 2018, Prasad & Srinivasulu 2021)	Mahananda river, Bihar
1552	<i>Dayella malabarica</i> (Day, 1873)	MBF	TN, KL, MH	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	Malabar, India
1553	<i>Ehirava fluviatilis</i> Deraniyagala, 1929	MBF	OD, TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Engraulidae Gill, 1861					
1554	<i>Coilia borneensis</i> Bleeker, 1852	MBF	OD, TN	(Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1555	<i>Coilia dussumieri</i> Valenciennes, 1848	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	Mumbai
1556	<i>Coilia mystus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	MBF	KL	(Talwar 1976)	
1557	<i>Coilia neglecta</i> Whitehead, 1967	MB	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	

1558	<i>Coilia ramcarati</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Ganges River estuary
1559	<i>Coilia reynaldi</i> Valenciennes, 1848	MBF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1560	<i>Encrasicholina heteroloba</i> (Rüppell, 1837)	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012, Talwar 1974)	
1561	<i>Encrasicholina intermedia</i> Hata & Motomura, 2016	M	KL	(Hata & Motomura 2016)	
1562	<i>Encrasicholina punctifer</i> Fowler, 1938	M	TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a, Karmakar et al. 2012)	
1563	<i>Setipinna breviceps</i> (Cantor, 1849)	M	Along the coastline	(Kapoor et al. 2002)	
1564	<i>Setipinna brevifilis</i> (Valenciennes, 1848)	F	WB, DL, ML	(Mishra et al. 2017, Yennawar et al. 2015, Sen 1995, Husain 1997)	Bengal
1565	<i>Setipinna melanochir</i> (Bleeker, 1849)	MBF	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1566	<i>Setipinna phasa</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, GA, UP, MP, AR	(Rajan et al. 2013, Yennawar et al. 2015, Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman et al. 2004, Bagra et al. 2009, Sharma 2007, Talwar 1974, Mishra et al. 2021a)	Brackish rivers of Bengal
1567	<i>Setipinna taty</i> (Valenciennes, 1848)	MB	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Puducherry
1568	<i>Setipinna tenuifilis</i> (Valenciennes, 1848)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1569	<i>Stolephorus andhraensis</i> Babu Rao, 1966	M	OD, AP, TN	(Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Waltair, Kakinara, Andhra Pradesh
1570	<i>Stolephorus baganensis</i> Hardenberg, 1933	MB	WB, OD, TN, KL, GA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Khan 2002, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012, Barman et al. 2000, Talwar 1974)	
1571	<i>Stolephorus bengalensis</i> (Dutt & Babu Rao, 1959)	MB	TN	(Dutt & Babu Rao 1959)	Kilakarai, Gulf of Mannar, India
1572	<i>Stolephorus commersonnii</i> Lacepède, 1803	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Shaji et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012)	
1573	<i>Stolephorus dubiosus</i> Wongratana, 1983	MB	OD, TN	(Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1574	<i>Stolephorus hindustanensis</i> Hata & Motomura, 2022	M	MH	(Hata & Motomura 2022)	Sassoon Docks, Mumbai, Maharashtra State

1575	<i>Stolephorus indicus</i> (van Hasselt, 1823)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Pamban Island, Tamil Nadu
1576	<i>Stolephorus mercurius</i> Hata, Lavoué & Motomura, 2021	M	OD	(Gouda et al. 2023)	
1577	<i>Stolephorus rex</i> Jordan & Seale, 1926	M	KL	(Jordan & Seale 1926)	Cannanore [Kannur], Malabar coast, Kerala State
1578	<i>Stolephorus tamilensis</i> Gangan, Pavan-Kumar, Jahageerdar & Jaiswar, 2020	M	TN	(Gangan et al. 2020)	Thoothukudi fish landing centre, Tamil Nadu
1579	<i>Stolephorus tri</i> (Bleeker, 1852)	MB	OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012, Talwar 1974)	
1580	<i>Stolephorus waitei</i> Jordan & Seale, 1926	MBF	ANI, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012)	
1581	<i>Thryssa baelama</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	MB	ANI, OD, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1582	<i>Thryssa cultella</i> (Hata & Motomura, 2019)	M	TN	(Hata & Motomura 2019)	Bay of Bengal, Chennai, Tamil Nadu
1583	<i>Thryssa dayi</i> Wongratana, 1983	M	TN, KA, MH	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Mumbai
1584	<i>Thryssa dussumieri</i> (Valenciennes, 1848)	MB	LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Shaji et al. 2019, Rajan et al. 2021, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012, Talwar 1974)	Gulf of Khambhat, Gujarat
1585	<i>Thryssa encrasicholoides</i> (Bleeker, 1852)	MB	South eastern coast of India	(Kapoor et al. 2002)	
1586	<i>Thryssa gautamiensis</i> Babu Rao, 1971	MB	WB, OD, TN	(Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Near Bhairavapalem village, Gautami branch of Godavari Estuary, Andhra Pradesh
1587	<i>Thryssa kammalensis</i> (Bleeker, 1849)	MB	WB, OD, AP, TN	(Mishra & Kannan 1999, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1588	<i>Thryssa kammalensoides</i> Wongratana, 1983	B	OD, TN	(Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Godavari estuary, eastern coast of India
1589	<i>Thryssa malabarica</i> (Bloch, 1795)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012, Nandi et al. 2008)	Parengipettai, Tamil Nadu

1590	<i>Thryssa mystax</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012, Hedge et al. 2013)	Malabar
1591	<i>Thryssa polybranchialis</i> Wongratana, 1983	M	OD, TN, KA, MH	(Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Mumbai
1592	<i>Thryssa purava</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MB	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012, Talwar 1974)	Backwaters of West Bengal
1593	<i>Thryssa setirostris</i> (Broussonet, 1782)	MB	ANI, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012, Hedge et al. 2013)	
1594	<i>Thryssa serena</i> (Hata & Motomura, 2019)	M	North Western coast of India	(Hata & Motomura 2019)	
1595	<i>Thryssa stenosoma</i> Wongratana, 1983	MB	WB	(Mishra et al. 2017)	Godavari estuary, eastern coast of India.
1596	<i>Thryssa vitirostris</i> (Gilchrist & Thompson, 1908)	MB	OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012, Talwar 1974)	
Family: Pristigasteridae Bleeker, 1872					
1597	<i>Ilisha elongata</i> (Anonymous [Bennett], 1830)	MB	WB, OD, TN, KL, KA, MH	(Biju et al. 2019, Khan 2002, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a, Karmakar et al. 2012)	
1598	<i>Ilisha filigera</i> (Valenciennes, 1847)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Mumbai
1599	<i>Ilisha kampeni</i> (Weber & de Beaufort, 1913)	MBF	WB, OD, AP, TN	(Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
1600	<i>Ilisha megaloptera</i> (Swainson, 1839)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Coromandel Coast
1601	<i>Ilisha melastoma</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	MBF	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ, AS	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Shaji et al. 2019, Khan 2002, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Sen 1985, Karmakar et al. 2012, Talwar 1974)	Coromandal, Tamil Nadu
1602	<i>Ilisha obfuscata</i> Wongratana, 1983	M	TN, MH	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Mumbai
1603	<i>Ilisha sirishae</i> Seshagiri Rao, 1975	MB	WB, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Hedge et al. 2013)	Vishakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh
1604	<i>Ilisha striatula</i> Wongratana, 1983	MB	AP, TN, KL, KA, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	

1605	<i>Opisthopterus tardoore</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Khan 2002, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012, Ansari et al. 1995)	Puducherry
1606	<i>Opisthopterus valenciennesi</i> Bleeker, 1872	MB	WB	(Mishra et al. 2017)	
1607	<i>Pellona dayi</i> Wongratana, 1983	MB	ANI, AP, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Porto Novo, southern India
1608	<i>Pellona ditchela</i> Valenciennes, 1847	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Khan 2002, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012, Ansari et al. 1995)	Visakhapatnam
1609	<i>Raconda russeliana</i> Gray, 1831	MB	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Khan 2002, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Saugar Roads [= ? Sangor Rocks], India.
Family: Spratelloididae Jordan, 1925					
1610	<i>Spratelloides delicatulus</i> (Bennett, 1832)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012)	
1611	<i>Spratelloides gracilis</i> (Temminck & Schlegel, 1846)	M	LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012)	
Order: Cyprinodontiformes					
Family: Aphaniidae Hoedeman, 1949					
1612	<i>Aphaniops dispar</i> (Rüppell, 1829)	BF	GJ	(Devi & Indra 2012)	
1613	<i>Aphaniops stoliczkanus</i> (Day, 1872)	MBF	KA, GJ, RJ	(Day 1872, Bhat 2000, Kapoor et al. 2002)	Stream at the village Joorun & along edge of the Rann River, Lodai, Gujarat, India, 22°30'N, 69°20'E
Family: Aplocheilidae Bleeker, 1859					
1614	<i>Aplocheilus andamanicus</i> (Köhler, 1906)	F	ANI	(Kottelat 2013)	Andaman Islands
1615	<i>Aplocheilus blockii</i> Arnold, 1911	BF	TN, KL, KA, GA, GJ	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Yadav 2008)	Cochin, Kerala
1616	<i>Aplocheilus dayi</i> Steindachner, 1892	BF	No specific location	(Devi & Indra 2012)	
1617	<i>Aplocheilus kirchmayeri</i> Berkenkamp & Etzel, 1986	F	KA, GA	(Berkenkamp & Etzel 1986)	Goa, between Margao (Madgaon) & Colva-Strand, southwestern India, 15°18'N, 73°57'E

1618	<i>Aplocheilus lineatus</i> (Valenciennes, 1846)	BF	OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ, RJ, TL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Yadav 2008)	Mumbai
1619	<i>Aplocheilus parvus</i> (Sundara Raj, 1916)	BF	TN	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	Chennai
1620	<i>Aplocheilus panchax</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KA, GA, MH, GJ, UK, MP, TL, JH, AS, ML, MN, TR	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman 1993, 2002, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Yadav 2008, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Tudu et al. 2022)	Ditches & ponds of Bengal
Family: Poeciliidae Bonaparte, 1831					
1621	<i>Gambusia affinis</i> (Baird & Girard, 1853)	BF	LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ, UK, DL, RJ, TL, JH	(Rajan et al. 2021, Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Yadav 2008, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Tudu et al. 2022)	
1622	<i>Gambusia holbrooki</i> Girard, 1859	F	J&K	(Bhat et al. 2020)	
1623	<i>Poecilia reticulata</i> Peters, 1859	BF	LK, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, TL, SK	(Rajan et al. 2021, Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar 2006, Karmakar et al. 2012, Yadav 2008)	
1624	<i>Poecilia sphenops</i> Valenciennes, 1846	BF	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
1625	<i>Xiphophorus hellerii</i> Heckel, 1848	BF	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	
1626	<i>Xiphophorus maculatus</i> (Günther, 1866)	F	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	
Order: Cypriniformes					
Family: Balitoridae Swainson, 1839					
1627	<i>Balitora arunachalensis</i> (Nath, Dam, Bhutia, Dey & Das, 2007)	F	AR	(Nath et al. 2007)	River Noadhing drainage near Namsai, about 30 kilometers from Tezu, Arunachal Pradesh
1628	<i>Balitora brucei</i> Gray, 1830	F	WB, UK, AS, ML, AR, NL, MZ	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1995, Bagra et al. 2009, Sen 1985, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Kar & Sen 2007)	Cherrapunji, Meghalaya
1629	<i>Balitora burmanica</i> Hora, 1932	F	MN	(Devi & Indra 2012)	
1630	<i>Balitora chipkali</i> Kumar, Katwate, Raghavan & Dahanukar, 2016	F	KA	(Kumar et al. 2016)	

1631	<i>Balitora jalpalli</i> Raghavan et al., 2013	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Silent Valley National Park, Kerala
1632	<i>Balitora laticauda</i> Bhoite, Jadhav & Dahanukar, 2012	F	MH	(Bhoite et al. 2012)	Stream of Krishna River drainage at Venegaon Village near Krishno River bridge (17.499°N, 74.118°E), Satara District, Maharashtra
1633	<i>Balitora mysorensis</i> Hora, 1941	F	KL, KA, MH	(Shaji et al. 2019, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Sivasamudram, Karnataka
1634	<i>Bhavana annandalei</i> Hora, 1920	F	KL	(CoF, 2023)	Western side of the eastern Ghats, Travancore [Kerala]
1635	<i>Bhavana australis</i> (Jerdon, 1849)	F	TN, KL, KA	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013)	Walliar forest, Nilgiris
1636	<i>Ghatsa menoni</i> (Shaji & Easa, 1995)	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Muthikulam forest, Palghat, Kerala
1637	<i>Ghatsa montana</i> (Herre, 1945)	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Anamalai Hills, South India
1638	<i>Ghatsa pillaii</i> (Indra & Rema Devi, 1981)	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Silent Valley National Park, Kerala
1639	<i>Ghatsa santhampariensis</i> (Arunachalam, Johnson & Rema Devi, 2002)	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Santhampari Hills, Idukki district, Kerala
1640	<i>Ghatsa silasi</i> (Kurup & Radhakrishnan, 2011)	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Periyar Tiger Reserve, Kerala
1641	<i>Hemimyzon indicus</i> Lalramliana, Solo, Lalronunga & Lalnuntluanga, 2018	F	MZ	(Lalramliana et al. 2018a)	Kaladan River in the vicinity of Lungbun village, Siaha District, Mizoram
1642	<i>Homalopteroides manipurensis</i> (Arunkumar, 1999)	F	MN	(Arunkumar 1999)	Lokchao River near Moreh, 110 kilometers from Imphal City of Manipur
1643	<i>Homalopteroides rupicola</i> (Prashad & Mukerji, 1929)	F	North eastern India	(Prashad & Mukerji 1929)	
1644	<i>Travancoria elongata</i> Pethiyagoda & Kottelat, 1994	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Chalakydy River, Kerala
1645	<i>Travancoria jonesi</i> Hora, 1941	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Peerumedu, Kerala

Family: Botiidae Berg, 1940					
1646	<i>Botia almorhae</i> Gray, 1831	F	WB, UK, UP	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021)	Almorah [Almorha], Uttar Pradesh, northern India.
1647	<i>Botia birdi</i> Chaudhuri, 1909	F	WB, J&K, HP, PU, HY	(Mishra et al. 2003, Bhat et al. 2020, Sharma & Dhanze 2018, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Brraich & Saini 2019)	Rupar, where the Sirhind Canal diverges from the Sutlej, Punjab
1648	<i>Botia dario</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, HP, UK, UP, BR, AS, ML, AR, MN, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1995, Bagra et al. 2009, Barman 2002, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Sharma & Dhanze 2018, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Mishra et al. 2021a, Kumar et al. 2011)	Dumdum, Bengal
1649	<i>Botia histrionica</i> Blyth, 1860	F	WB, ML	(Dey & Barat 2015, Sen 1995, Karmakar & Das 2005a)	
1650	<i>Botia lohachata</i> Chaudhuri, 1912	F	WB, PU, UK, DL, RJ, BR, ML	(Jana et al. 2020, Sen 1995, Husain 1997, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Brraich & Saini 2019, Kumari & Yadav 2020)	Saran, Bihar
1651	<i>Botia rostrata</i> Günther, 1868	F	WB, UK, MP, AS, ML, AR, NL, MZ, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1995, Bagra et al. 2009, Barman 2002, Sen 1985, Sharma 2007, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Karmakar & Das 2005, Kar & Sen 2007)	Bengal
1652	<i>Botia striata</i> Narayan Rao, 1920	F	KA, MH	(Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Thumga River, Shimoga, Mysore State, Karnataka
1653	<i>Syncrossus berdmorei</i> Blyth, 1860	F	ML	(Menon 1999)	
Family: Cobitidae Swainson, 1838					
1654	<i>Acantopsis dialuzona</i> van Hasselt, 1823	F	AS	(Sen 1995)	
1655	<i>Acantopsis multistigmatus</i> Vishwanath & Laisram, 2005	F	MN	(Vishwanath & Laisram 2005)	Manipur
1656	<i>Acantopsis spectabilis</i> (Blyth, 1860)	F	MN	(Vishwanath & Laisram 2005a)	
1657	<i>Canthophrys gongota</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, SK, AS, ML, AR, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Bagra et al. 2009, Barman 2002, Karmakar 2006)	Patgong, Northern Bengal
1658	<i>Lepidocephalichthys annandalei</i> Chaudhuri, 1912	F	WB, UK, AS, ML, AR, MZ, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Bagra et al. 2009, Barman 2002, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Kar & Sen 2007)	Mahananda River at Siliguri & Tista River near Jalpaiguri, West Bengal
1659	<i>Lepidocephalichthys arunachalensis</i> (Datta & Barman, 1984)	F	WB, AR	(Dey et al. 2015, Bagra et al. 2009)	Namdapha Wildlife Sanctuary, Tirap District, Arunachal Pradesh
1660	<i>Lepidocephalichthys berdmorei</i> (Blyth, 1860)	F	WB, TL, AS, ML, MN, TR	(Dey et al. 2015, Sen 1985, 1995, Barman 2002, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016)	

1661	<i>Lepidocephalichthys coromandelensis</i> (Menon, 1992)	F	AP	(Menon 1992)	Araku valley, Andhra Pradesh
1662	<i>Lepidocephalichthys furcatus</i> (de Beaufort, 1933)	F	ML, MN	(Sen 1995, Karmakar & Das 2005a)	
1663	<i>Lepidocephalichthys goalparensis</i> Pillai & Yazdani, 1976	F	WB, UK, AS	(Mogalekar et al. 2017, Sen 1985, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021)	About 6 kilometers west of Dudhnai, Inspection Bungalow, Goalpara District, Assam
1664	<i>Lepidocephalichthys guntea</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KA, GA, MH, GJ, HP, UK, DL, RJ, MP, TL, CG, BR, JH, AS, ML, AR, NL, MN, TR	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Yadav 2008, Sharma & Dhanze 2018, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Hembrom & Bodra 2021, Kumari & Yadav 2020)	Bengal
1665	<i>Lepidocephalichthys irrorata</i> Hora, 1921	F	WB, AS, ML, MN	(Mogalekar et al. 2017, Sen 1995, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985)	Lakes & streams of the Manipur Valley
1666	<i>Lepidocephalichthys longipinnis</i> (Menon, 1992)	F	MN	(Menon 1992)	Kharangpat Lake, 20 kilometers south of Imphal, Manipur
1667	<i>Lepidocephalichthys micropogon</i> (Blyth, 1860)	F	WB	(Mogalekar et al. 2017)	
1668	<i>Lepidocephalichthys thermalis</i> (Valenciennes, 1846)	F	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ, MP, BR	(Shaji et al. 2019, Paul & Chanda 2017, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Yadav 2008, Kumari & Yadav 2020)	
1669	<i>Neoeucirrhichthys maydelli</i> Bănărescu & Nalbant, 1968	F	AS	(Bănărescu & Nalbant 1968)	Janali River at Raimona, Goalpara District, Brahmaputra drainage, Assam
1670	<i>Pangio ammophila</i> Britz, Ali & Raghavan, 2012	F	KA	(Britz, Ali & Raghavan 2012)	Kumaradhara River, 12°00'N, 75°53'24"E, Subramanya, Karnataka
1671	<i>Pangio apoda</i> Britz & Maclaine, 2007	F	WB	(Britz & Maclaine 2007)	Tista River at Tista Barrage, Brahmaputra drainage, West

					Bengal
1672	<i>Pangio bashai</i> (Easa & Shaji, 1997)	F	KL	(Sarkar et al. 2013)	Silent Valley, Kerala
1673	<i>Pangio bhujia</i> Anoop, Britz, Arjun, Dahanukar & Raghavan, 2019	F	KL	(Anoop et al. 2019)	Cherinjil, Kozhikode district, Kerala
1674	<i>Pangio goaensis</i> (Tilak, 1972)	F	KL, GA	(Shaji et al. 2019, Chanda & Jana 1995, Nandi et al. 2008)	Colem River, Goa
1675	<i>Pangio oblonga</i> (Valenciennes, 1846)	F	No specific location	(Devi & Indra 2012)	
1676	<i>Pangio pangia</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, GA, SK, AS, ML, MN, MZ	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Karmakar 2006, Yadav 2008, Kar & Sen 2007)	Brahmaputra River, Gualpara, Assam
1677	<i>Pangio pathala</i> Sundar, Arjun, Sidharthan, Dahanukar & Raghavan 2022	F	KL	(Sundar et al. 2022)	Well at Thiruvandoor, near the town of Chengannur, Kerala
Family: Cyprinidae Rafinesque, 1815					
1678	<i>Bhava vittata</i> (Day, 1865)	BF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ, RJ, MP, TL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2017, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Yadav 2008)	Cochin, Kerala
1679	<i>Bangana almora</i> (Chaudhuri, 1912)	F	WB, OD, TN, ML, NL	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	Almorha District, western Himalayas, Uttar Pradesh,
1680	<i>Bangana dero</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	MH, HP, PU, UK, DL, RJ, MP, SK, AS, AR, MN	(Bagra et al. 2009, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Karmakar 2006, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Jagtap 2013, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Brraich & Saini 2019)	Brahmaputra River, Gualpara, Assam
1681	<i>Bangana diplostomus</i> (Heckel, 1838)	F	J&K, TL	(Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Bhat et al. 2020)	Kashmir
1682	<i>Bangana nukta</i> (Sykes, 1839)	F	AP, KA, MH, TL, TR	(Barman 1993, 2002, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Inderanee River, 18 miles north of Poona, Deccan, Maharashtra, India.
1683	<i>Barbodes bovanicus</i> (Day, 1877)	F	TN, KA, GJ	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Sen & Banerjee 2000)	Bowany River, base of Neilgherry hills, Madras
1684	<i>Barbonymus gonionotus</i> (Bleeker, 1849)	F	WB, UP	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Mishra et al. 2021a)	
1685	<i>Carassius auratus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	BF	LK, TN, MH, SK	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Karmakar 2006, Karmakar et al. 2012)	

1686	<i>Carassius carassius</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	BF	TN, KA, J&K, UK, RJ	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Bhat et al. 2020, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021)	
1687	<i>Chagunius chagunio</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, UK, HY, DL, RJ, MP, BR, JH, SK, AS, ML, AR, NL, MZ, TR	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Bagra et al. 2009, Husain 1997, Barman 2002, Sen 1985, Karmakar 2006, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Tudu et al. 2022, Gunasekar & Isaac 2017, Kar & Sen 2007)	Yamuna & northers rivers of Bihar & Bengal
1688	<i>Chagunius nicholsi</i> (Myers, 1924)	F	WB	(Sanyal et al. 2012)	
1689	<i>Cirrhinus cirrhosus</i> (Bloch, 1795)	BF	LK, OD, AP, TN, KA, GA, MH, MP, TL, JH, TR	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Pati et al. 2018, Barman 1993, Rema devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Yadav 2008, Tudu et al. 2022, Kar & Sen 2007)	Malabar coast
1690	<i>Cirrhinus mrigala</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ, HP, PU, UK, HY, DL, UP, RJ, MP, TL, CG, BR, JH, SK, AS, ML, AR, NL, MN, MZ, TR	(Shaji et al. 2019, Karmakar & Das 2005, Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar 2006, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Jagtap 2013, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a, Kaur et al. 2017, Hembrom & Bodra 2021, Murugan & Prabaharan 2012, Kar & Sen 2007)	Ponds & freshwater rivers of Gangetic provinces
1691	<i>Cirrhinus reba</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, AP, TN, KA, MH, GJ, HP, PU, UK, HY, DL, UP, RJ, MP, TL, CG, BR, JH, AS, ML, AR, NL, MN, TR	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Sanyal et al. 2012, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Jagtap 2013, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a, Braich & Saini 2019, Tudu et al. 2022, Murugan & Prabaharan 2012)	Rivers & ponds of Bihar & Bengal
1692	<i>Cyprinus carpio</i> Linnaeus, 1758	BF	ANI, LK, WB, KL, ML	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Shaji et al. 2019, Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1995)	
1693	<i>Dawkinsia apsara</i> Katwate, Marcus Knight, Anoop, Raghavan & Dahanukar, 2020	F	KA	(Katwate et al. 2020)	Sita River, Karnataka
1694	<i>Dawkinsia arulius</i> (Jerdon, 1849)	F	TN, KL, MP	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Sharma 2007)	Cauvery river at Srirangapatnam, Tamilnadu

1695	<i>Dawkinsia assimilis</i> (Jerdon, 1849)	F	KL, KA	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Canara, Karnataka
1696	<i>Dawkinsia austellus</i> Katwate, Marcus Knight, Anoop, Raghavan & Dahanukar, 2020	MB	KA	(Katwate et al. 2020)	Sita River, Karnataka
1697	<i>Dawkinsia chalakkudiensis</i> (Menon, Rema Devi & Thobias, 1999)	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Chalakkudy river, Kerala
1698	<i>Dawkinsia crassa</i> Katwate, Marcus Knight, Anoop, Raghavan & Dahanukar, 2020	F	KA	(Katwate et al. 2020)	Nethravati River, Dharmasthala, Karnataka
1699	<i>Dawkinsia denisonii</i> (Day, 1865)	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Mundakayam, Kerala
1700	<i>Dawkinsia exclamatio</i> (Pethiyagoda & Kottelat, 2005)	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Kallada River, Kerala
1701	<i>Dawkinsia filamentosa</i> (Valenciennes, 1844)	BF	OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, MP, TL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Yadav 2008)	Alleppey, Kerala
1702	<i>Dawkinsia rohani</i> (Rema Devi, Indra & Knight, 2010)	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Koadayar Wildlife Sanctuary, Kanyakumari, Tami Nadu
1703	<i>Dawkinsia rubrotincta</i> (Jerdon, 1849)	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Kabini River, Kerala
1704	<i>Dawkinsia tambraparniei</i> (Silas, 1954)	F	TM	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	Stream 7 miles from Kalladaikurichi, Tambraparni watershed, Tinnevely District, Madras State
1705	<i>Dawkinsia utara</i> Katwate, Apte & Raghavan, 2020	F	MH	(Katwate et al. 2020b)	Kajali River, Shiposhi, Ratnagiri District, Maharashtra, India, 16°55'07.27"N, 73°37'59.39"E
1706	<i>Diptychus maculatus</i> Steindachner, 1866	F	LD, J&K	(Bhat et al. 2020, Tilak 1990)	
1707	<i>Eechathalakenda ophicephalus</i> (Raj, 1941)	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Kaller River, Kerala
1708	<i>Garra abhoyai</i> Hora, 1921	F	AS, MN	(Hora 1921)	Manipur, Assam & the neighbourhood of Ukhral, Naga Hills

1709	<i>Garra alticaputus</i> Arunachalam, Nandagopal & Mayden, 2013	F	AR	(Arunachalam et al. 2013a)	Dikrong River at Boorum Village, tributary of Ranga River, Lower Subanshri District, Anunachal Pradesh
1710	<i>Garra annandalei</i> Hora, 1921	F	WB, OD, GJ, CG, JH, SK, ML, AR, NL	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Bagra et al. 2009, Karmakar 2006, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Tudu et al. 2022, Bhakta et al. 2022)	Mahananda river, Below Darjeeling, Himalaya
1711	<i>Garra arunachalami</i> Johnson & Soranam, 2001	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Santhamparai hills, Idukki, Kerala
1712	<i>Garra arupi</i> Nebeshwar, Vishwanath & Das, 2009	F	WB, AR	(Mogalekar et al. 2017)	Deopani River at Roing, Lower Divang Valley, Arunachal Pradesh
1713	<i>Garra arunachalensis</i> Nebeshwar & Vishwanath, 2013	F	AR	(Nebeshwar & Vishwanath 2013)	Lower Divang valley district, Deapani River at Roing, Brahmaputa basin, 29°09'35"N, 95°54'08"E, Arunachal Pradesh
1714	<i>Garra bicornuta</i> Narayan Rao, 1920	F	KA, MH	(Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Tunga River at Shimoga, Karnataka
1715	<i>Garra bilobrostris</i> Roni & Vishwanath, 2017	F	AS	(Roni & Vishwanath 2017)	Kanamakra River, Brahmaputra River basin, Chirang district, Assam
1716	<i>Garra binduensis</i> Das, Kosygin & Panigrahi, 2016	F	WB	(Das et al. 2016)	Jaldhaka River at Bindu near Jaldhaka Hydrel complex, Brahmaputra River basin, North Bengal Darjeeling district
1717	<i>Garra birostris</i> Nebeshwar & Vishwanath, 2013	F	AR	(Nebeshwar & Vishwanath 2013)	Papum Pare district, Dikrong River at Doimukh, Brahmaputra basin, 27°08'19"N,

					93°44'51"E, Arunachal Pradesh
1718	<i>Garra chakpiensis</i> Nebeshwar & Vishwanath, 2015	F	MN	(Nebeshwar & Vishwanath 2015)	Chindwin River basin, Chakpi River at Tankpol, Manipur
1719	<i>Garra chathensis</i> Ezung, Shangningam & Pankaj, 2020	F	NL	(Ezung et al. 2020)	Chathe River, Brahmaputra basin, Nagaland
1720	<i>Garra chaudhurii</i> Hora, 1921	F	WB	(Hora 1921)	Darjiling [Darjeeling] District, Himalayas, West Bengal
1721	<i>Garra chindwinensis</i> Premananda, Kosygin & Saidullah, 2017	F	MN	(Premananda et al. 2017)	Laniye River near Laii, Chindwin basin, Senapati District, Manipur
1722	<i>Garra chingaiensis</i> Abonmai, Linthoingambi, Ngangbam, Thoidingjam & Singh, 2023	F	MN	(Abonmai et al. 2023)	Chalou River, Chingai Village, Chindwin basin, Ukhrlul district, Manipur
1723	<i>Garra chivaensis</i> Moyon & Arunkumar, 2020	F	MN	(Moyon & Arunkumar 2020)	Chiva River, Khongjon village, Chandel District, Manipur
1724	<i>Garra clavirostris</i> Roni, Sarbojit & Vishwanath, 2017	F	AS	(Roni et al. 2017)	Dilaima River at Boro Chenam Village below the confluence of Dilaima & Dihandi, Brahmaputra drainage, Dima Hasao District, Assam
1725	<i>Garra compressus</i> Kosygin & Vishwanath, 1998	F	MN	(Kosygin & Vishwanath 1998)	Wanze stream at Khamsom, 25°12'N, 94°32'E, Manipur
1726	<i>Garra cornigera</i> Shangningam & Vishwanath, 2015	F	MN	(Shangningam & Vishwanath 2015)	Sanalok River, Chindwin basin, Ukhrlul district, Manipur
1727	<i>Garra dampensis</i> Lalronunga, Lalnuntluanga & Lalramliana, 2013	F	MZ	(Lalronunga et al. 2013)	Seling River, tributary to Khawthlang Tuipui (Karnaphuti River) in the vicinity of

					Damparengpui, Mizoram
1728	<i>Garra deccanensis</i> Jadhav, Karuthapandi, Shangningam, Jaiswal & Shankar, 2022	F	AP	(Jadhav et al. 2022)	Godavari River at Bobbarlanka village, near Rajahmundry, East Godavari district, Andhra Pradesh, India, 16°56'8"N, 81°45'16"E
1729	<i>Garra elongata</i> Vishwanath & Kosygin, 2000	F	MN	(Vishwanath & Kosygin 2000a)	Hill stream near Tolloi, 25°12'N, 94°20'E, Chindwin basin, Manipur
1730	<i>Garra emarginata</i> Kurup & Radhakrishnan, 2011	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Pooyamkutty, Periyar River, Kerala
1731	<i>Garra gotyla</i> (Gray, 1830)	F	WB, OD, AP, TN, KA, GA, MH, HP, PU, UK, DL, RJ, MP, TL, CG, SK, AS, ML, AR, NL, MN, MZ, TR	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar 2006, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Yadav 2008, Sharma & Dhanze 2018, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Brraich & Saini 2019, Kar & Sen 2007)	Sikkim, Tista River at Rangpo
1732	<i>Garra gravelyi</i> (Annandale, 1919)	F	MN, MZ	(Karmakar & Das 2005a, Kar & Sen 2007)	
1733	<i>Garra hughi</i> Silas, 1955	F	TN, KL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	High Ranges of Travancore, Kerala
1734	<i>Garra jaldhakaensis</i> Kosygin, Shangningam, Singh & Das, 2021	F	WB	(Kosygin et al. 2021)	Jaldhaka River near Jhalong, Brahmaputra River basin, Kalimpong district, West Bengal
1735	<i>Garra jerdoni</i> Day, 1867	F	TN	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	Seegoor River & Bowany River, Tamilnadu
1736	<i>Garra joshuai</i> (Silas, 1954)	F	TN	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	Tambraparni River at Singampatty, Tinnevely District, Tamil Nadu
1737	<i>Garra kalakadensis</i> Rema Devi, 1993	F	TN	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	Kalakad Wildlife Sanctuary,

					Tirunelveli District, Tamil Nadu
1738	<i>Garra kalpangi</i> Nebeshwar, Bagra & Das, 2012	F	AR	(Bagra et al. 2009)	27°25'54"N, 93°46'42"E, Lower Subansiri District, Arunachal Pradesh
1739	<i>Garra kempi</i> Hora, 1921	F	ML, AR, MN, MZ	(Sen 1995, Bagra et al. 2009, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Kar & Sen 2007)	Siyom River, below Damda, among the Abor Hills, Assam
1740	<i>Garra khawbung</i> Arunachalam, Nandagopal & Mayden, 2014	F	MZ	(Arunachalam et al. 2014c)	Tuipui River, Khawbung Village, Champhai District, Mizoram
1741	<i>Garra kimini</i> Arunachalam, Nandagopal & Mayden 2013	F	AR	(Arunachalam et al. 2013a)	Tributary of Ranga River, 7 km from Hola camp, Lower Subansiri District, Arunachal Pradesh
1742	<i>Garra koladynensis</i> Nebeshwar & Vishwanath, 2017	F	MZ	(Nebeshwar & Vishwanath 2017)	Koladyne River at Kawlchaw, Lawntlai district, Mizoram
1743	<i>Garra laishrami</i> Surachita, Chowdhury & Palita, 2023	F	OD	(Surachita et al. 2023)	Kolab River at Ghatguda near Sunabeda Town, Gadavari River drainage, Eastern Ghats, Koraput District, Odisha
1744	<i>Garra lamta</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, AP, GJ, HP, UK, MP, TL, JH, SK, AS, ML, AR, MZ	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman 1993, Bagra et al. 2009, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar 2006, Sharma 2007, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Sharma & Dhanze 2018, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Hembrom & Bodra 2021, Kar & Sen 2007)	Behar Province & Rapti River, Gorakhpur District, Uttar Pradesh
1745	<i>Garra langlungensis</i> Ezung, Shangningam & Pankaj, 2021	F	NL	(Ezung et al. 2021)	Langlung River near Zutovi Village, Dimapur District, Brahmaputra basin, Nagaland
1746	<i>Garra lissorhynchus</i> (McClelland, 1842)	F	WB, AS, ML, AR, MN, MZ	(Ng 2006, Sen 1985, 1995, Bagra et al. 2009, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Kar & Sen 2007)	Khasi Hills, Meghalaya
1747	<i>Garra litanensis</i> Vishwanath,	F	MN	(Vishwanath 1993)	Litan stream at

	1993				Litan, Manipur
1748	<i>Garra lungongza</i> Ngangbam & Lithoingambi, 2023	F	NL	(Ngangbam & Linthoingambi 2023)	Dei-thung Shumang River, Sangsangyu village, Tuensang district, Nagaland
1749	<i>Garra magnacavus</i> Shangningam, Kosygin & Sinha, 2019	F	AR	(Shangningam et al. 2019)	Ranga River, Brahmaputra River basin, Lower Subansiri District, Arunachal Pradesh
1750	<i>Garra magnidiscus</i> Tamang 2013	F	AR	(Tamang 2013)	Tributary of the Siang River, about 3 km from Bomdo Village on main road to Tuting, Upper Siang district, Arunachal Pradesh
1751	<i>Garra manipurensis</i> Vishwanath & Sarojnalini, 1988	F	MN	(Karmakar & Das 2005a)	Manipur River at Sherou, Manipur
1752	<i>Garra matensis</i> Nebeshwar & Vishwanath, 2017	BF	MZ	(Nebeshwar & Vishwanath 2017)	Mat River at Thualthu, Lunglei district, Mizoram
1753	<i>Garra maclellandi</i> (Jerdon, 1849)	F	AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, TL, ML, AR	(Shaji et al. 2019, Sen 1995, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Bhavani river at the Nilgiris, Tamilnadu
1754	<i>Garra menoni</i> Rema Devi & Indra, 1984	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Kunthi River, Silent valley, Kerala
1755	<i>Garra minima</i> Arunachalam, Nandagopal & Mayden, 2013	F	AR	(Arunachalam et al. 2013a)	Tributary of Ranga River, Lower Subansiri District, Arunachal Pradesh
1756	<i>Garra mlapparaensis</i> Kurup & Radhakrishnan, 2011	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Mlappara, Periyar River, Kerala
1757	<i>Garra moyonkhulleni</i> Moyon & Arunkumar, 2018	F	MN	(Moyon & Arunkumar 2018)	Moyon Khullen, 10 km from north-eastern side of Lokchao bridge, Chandel District, Manipur
1758	<i>Garra mullya</i> (Sykes, 1839)	F	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ, RJ,	(Shaji et al. 2019, Sanyal et al. 2012, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016,	The Bhima river at Daund, Maharashtra

			MP, TL, CG, JH	Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Yadav 2008, Tudu et al. 2022)	
1759	<i>Garra ngatangka</i> Arunkumar & Moyon, 2019	F	MN	(Arunkumar & Moyon 2019)	Tumit River, Chindwin basin, Purum Chumbang village, Chandel Distric, Manipur
1760	<i>Garra naganensis</i> Hora, 1921	F	AS, ML, AR, NL, MN, MZ	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Sen 1985, 1995, Bagra et al. 2009, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Kar & Sen 2007)	near Kairong, Naga hills, Nagaland
1761	<i>Garra nambulica</i> Vishwanath & Joyshree, 2005	F	MN	(Vishwanath & Joyshree 2005)	Ireng lok (stream of Nambul River), Singda village, Manipur
1762	<i>Garra namyaensis</i> Shangningam & Vishwanath, 2012	F	MN	(Shangningam & Vishwanath 2012)	Namya River, close to Indo-Myanmar border, 24°52'N, 94°39'E, Ukhrul District, Manipur
1763	<i>Garra nasuta</i> (McClelland, 1838)	F	WB, SK, AS, ML, AR, MN	(Mogalekar et al. 2017, Sen 1985, 1995, Bagra et al. 2009, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Karmakar 2006)	Khasi Hills, Meghalaya
1764	<i>Garra nethravathiensis</i> Arunachalam & Nandagopal 2014	F	KA	(Arunachalam & Nandagopal 2014)	Kannikaya Village, where two rivers (Addahole & Kuaradhara), tributaries to Nethravathi River basin, Karnataka
1765	<i>Garra nigricauda</i> Arunachalam, Nandagopal & Mayden, 2013	F	AR	(Arunachalam et al. 2013a)	Suang River, near Pagsighat, Arunachal Pradesh
1766	<i>Garra notata</i> (Blyth, 1860)	F	MH, MZ	(Karmakar et al. 2012, Kar & Sen 2007)	
1767	<i>Garra palaniensis</i> (Rema Devi & Menon, 1994)	F	TN	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	Palani Hills, Western Ghats, southern India
1768	<i>Garra palaruvica</i> Arunachalam, Raja, Nandagopal & Mayden, 2013	F	KL	(Arunachalam et al. 2013b)	Palaruvi, near Thenmala, Kallada River basin, Kollam district, Kerala
1769	<i>Garra paratrilobata</i> Roni, Chinglemba, Rameshori & Vishwanath, 2019	F	MN	(Roni et al. 2019)	Leimatak River, a tributary of Irang River (Barak drainage), at Awangkhum Village, Noney District, Manipur

1770	<i>Garra paralissorhynchus</i> Vishwanath & Shanta, 2005	F	MN	(Vishwanath & Shanta 2005)	Khuga River, Churachandpur District, Manipur
1771	<i>Garra periyarensis</i> Gopi, 2001	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Thannikkudy, Periyar Tiger Reserve, Kerala
1772	<i>Garra platycephala</i> Narayan Rao, 1920	F	KA	(Narayan Rao 1920)	Cauvery River at Seringapatam, Karnataka
1773	<i>Garra quadratiostris</i> Nebeshwar & Vishwanath, 2013	F	SK	(Nebeshwar & Vishwanath 2013)	Sikkim, Tista River at Rangpo, Ganga basin
1774	<i>Garra rakhinica</i> Kullander & Fang, 2004	F	MZ	(Arunachalam et al. 2014c)	Tyao River, Tyao Village, Champhai District, Mizoram
1775	<i>Garra ranganensis</i> Tamang, Sinha, Abujam & Kumar, 2019	F	AR	(Tamang et al. 2019)	Ranga River (Brahmaputra basin), about 5 km upstream from Yazali, Lower Subansiri District, Arunachal Pradesh
1776	<i>Garra rupicola</i> (McClelland, 1839)	F	AS, ML, AR, MN	(Sen 1985, 1995, Bagra et al. 2009, Karmakar & Das 2005a)	Mishmee Hills, Arunachal Pradesh
1777	<i>Garra simbalbaraensis</i> Rath, Shangningam & Kosygin, 2019	F	HP	(Rath et al. 2019)	Simbalbara River, Yamuna River basin, Sirmaur District, Himachal Pradesh
1778	<i>Garra stenorhynchus</i> (Jerdon, 1849)	F	AP, TN, KL, GA, MH, TL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar et al. 2012, Yadav 2008)	Bhavani river at the Nilgiris
1779	<i>Garra substrictorostri</i> Roni & Vishwanath, 2018	F	MN	(Roni & Vishwanath 2018)	Leimatak River, Barak River drainage, Churachandpur District, Manipur
1780	<i>Garra surendranathanii</i> Shaji, Arun & Easa, 1996	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Chalakydy River, Kerala
1781	<i>Garra tamangi</i> Gurumayum & Kosygin, 2016	F	AR	(Gurumayum & Kosygin 2016)	Dikrong River at Hoj near NHPC Hydrel complex, a tributary of the Brahmaputra River basin, Papum Pare district, Arunachal Pradesh

1782	<i>Garra tezuensis</i> Thoidingjam, Ngangbam, Linthoingambi & Singh, 2023	F	AR	(Thoidingjam et al. 2023)	Lohit River at Tezu, Brahmaputra basin, Lohit District, Arunachal Pradesh
1783	<i>Garra trilobata</i> Shangningam & Vishwanath, 2015	F	MN	(Shangningam & Vishwanath 2015)	Sanalok River, Chindwin basin, Ukhrul district, Manipur
1784	<i>Garra triangularis</i> Shangningam, Rath & Kosygin, 2021	F	Dadra & Nagar Haveli	(Shangningam et al. 2021, Shibanada et al. 2022)	Sakartod River at Khanvel, Dadra & Nagar Haveli district, Dadra & Nagar Haveli Union territory
1785	<i>Garra ukhrulensis</i> Nebeshwar & Vishwanath, 2015	F	MN	(Nebeshwar & Vishwanath 2015)	Ukhrul district, Clallou River at Khamson, Manipur
1786	<i>Gymnostomus ariza</i> (Hamilton, 1807)	F	AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, MP, TL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Tungabhadra River, Krishna basin, Karnataka, Southern India
1787	<i>Gymnostomus fulungee</i> (Sykes, 1839)	F	OD, AP, TN, KA, MH, MP, TL	(Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Deccan
1788	<i>Haludaria afasciata</i> (Jayaram, 1990)	F	TN	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	Vellakaravi & Vathakad village, Nagercoil, Tamil Nadu
1789	<i>Haludaria fasciata</i> (Jerdon, 1849)	F	TN, KL, KA, GA, MH	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar et al. 2012, Yadav 2008)	Malabar
1790	<i>Haludaria kannikattiensis</i> (Arunachalam & Johnson, 2003)	F	TN	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	Kalakad Mundanthurai Tiger Reserve, Tamil Nadu
1791	<i>Haludaria melanampyx</i> (Day, 1865)	F	OD, AP, TN, KL, TL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016)	Mundikyum, Kerala
1792	<i>Haludaria pradhani</i> (Tilak, 1973)	F	KA, GA	(Rema Devi et al. 2013)	2 kilometers northeast of Forest Rest House, Goa
1793	<i>Hypselobarbus basavarajai</i> Arunachalam, Chinnaraja & Mayden, 2016	F	KA	(Arunachalam et al. 2016)	Bhadra River at Bhadravathi, Karnataka
1794	<i>Hypselobarbus bicolor</i> Knight, Rai, d'Souza, Philip & Dahanukar, 2016	F	KA	(Knight et al. 2016)	Sita River, Chara, Karnataka
1795	<i>Hypselobarbus carnaticus</i> (Jerdon, 1849)	F	TN, KL, KA, MH, TL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa &	Bhavani & Cauvery river,

				Bakshi 2016, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Tamilnadu
1796	<i>Hypselobarbus curmuca</i> (Hamilton, 1807)	F	AP, TN, KL, MP, TL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Sharma 2007)	Tunga River, Karnataka
1797	<i>Hypselobarbus dobsoni</i> (Day, 1876)	F	OD, TN, KL, KA, TL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016)	Deccan
1798	<i>Hypselobarbus dubius</i> (Day, 1867)	F	TN, KA	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013)	Bowany River, Tamilnadu
1799	<i>Hypselobarbus gracilis</i> (Jerdon, 1849)	F	TN	(Arunachalam et al. 2016d)	Madras
1800	<i>Hypselobarbus jerdoni</i> (Day, 1870)	F	AP, TN, KL, GA, MH, GJ, MP, TL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Yadav 2008)	Mangalore, Karnataka
1801	<i>Hypselobarbus keralaensis</i> Arunachalam, Chinnaraja & Mayden, 2016	F	KL	(Arunachalam et al. 2016a)	Thodaiyar stream, Karamana River basin, Kerala
1802	<i>Hypselobarbus kolus</i> (Sykes, 1839)	F	OD, AP, KA, MH, MP, TL, CG	(Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Deccan
1803	<i>Hypselobarbus kurali</i> Menon & Rema Devi, 1995	F	TN, KL, KA	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013)	Dakshin Kannada, Karnataka
1804	<i>Hypselobarbus kushavali</i> Arunachalam, Chinnaraja, Sivakumar & Mayden, 2016	F	KA	(Arunachalam et al. 2016b)	Kali River at Dandeli, Karnataka
1805	<i>Hypselobarbus lithopidos</i> (Day, 1874)	F	TN, KL, KA	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013)	South Canara, Karnataka
1806	<i>Hypselobarbus maciveri</i> (Annandale, 1919)	F	MH	(Plamoottil & Vineeth 2022)	Krishna River near Mahuli, 3 miles from Satara, Maharashtra
1807	<i>Hypselobarbus menoni</i> Arunachalam, Chinnaraja, Chandran & Mayden, 2014	F	KL	(Arunachalam et al. 2014d)	Periyar River at Mieppara, 12 km east of Thannikuda Forest, Kerala
1808	<i>Hypselobarbus micropogon</i> (Valenciennes, 1842)	F	TN, KL, KA	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013)	Mysore, Karnataka
1809	<i>Hypselobarbus mussullah</i> (Sykes, 1839)	F	OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, MP, TL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Koland, Maharashtra
1810	<i>Hypselobarbus nilgiriensis</i> Arunachalam, Chinnaraja & Mayden, 2016	F	TN	(Arunachalam et al. 2016c)	Bhavani River at Nellithurai, Tamil Nadu

1811	<i>Hypselobarbus nitidus</i> Plamoottil & Vineeth, 2022	F	KL	(Plamoottil & Vineeth 2022)	Stream at Pallangod [Pallamkod], Kasaragod District, Kerala
1812	<i>Hypselobarbus periyarensis</i> (Raj, 1941)	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Periyar valley, Kerala
1813	<i>Hypselobarbus procerus</i> Plamoottil, 2022	F	KL	(Plamoottil 2021a)	Bhavani River at Attappady, Palakkad, Kerala
1814	<i>Hypselobarbus pulchellus</i> (Day, 1870)	F	OD, TN, KA	(Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013)	Nethravathi River at Nidugal, Karnataka
1815	<i>Hypselobarbus tamiraparaniei</i> Arunachalam, Chinnaraja, Chandran & Mayden, 2014	F	TN	(Arunachalam et al. 2014d)	Manimuthar River, a tributary of Tamiraparani drainage at Aladiyur, before confluence with Tamiraparani River, south Tamil Nadu
1816	<i>Hypselobarbus thomassi</i> (Day, 1874)	F	KL, KA, MH	(Shaji et al. 2019, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar et al. 2012)	South Canara, Karnataka
1817	<i>Hypselobarbus vaigaiensis</i> Arunachalam, Chinnaraja, Chandran & Mayden, 2014	F	KL	(Arunachalam et al. 2014d)	Periyar Tiger Reserve, Kerala
1818	<i>Hypsibarbus myitkyinae</i> (Prashad & Mukerji, 1929)	F	MN	(Vishwanath & Tombi Singh 1986)	Manipur
1819	<i>Kantaka brevadorsalis</i> (Day, 1873)	F	TN, KL, KA, MH	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Rivers below Nilgiri Hills, Western Ghats
1820	<i>Labeo altivelis</i> Peters, 1852	F	TN	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	
1821	<i>Labeo angra</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, RJ, MP, CG, BR, JH, NL, MN	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Sanyal et al. 2012, Chanda & Jana 2021, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Tudu et al. 2022, Gunasekar & Isaac 2017)	Brahmaputra river
1822	<i>Labeo bata</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, AP, TN, KA, MH, GJ, PU, UK, HY, DL, UP, RJ, MP, TL, CG, BR, JH, AS, ML, AR, MN, MZ, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a, Brraich & Saini 2019, Hembrom & Bodra 2021, Murugan & Prabaharan 2012, Kar & Sen 2007)	Rivers & ponds of Bengal

1823	<i>Labeo boga</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, AP, TN, KA, MH, HP, UK, DL, RJ, MP, TL, CG, AS, ML, AR, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Barman 1993, 2002, Sen 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Sen 1985, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Jagtap 2013, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021)	Goyalpara, Brahmaputra River
1824	<i>Labeo boggut</i> (Sykes, 1839)	F	OD, AP, TN, KA, MH, GJ, RJ, MP, TL, CG	(Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000)	Deccan
1825	<i>Labeo calbasu</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	WB, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ, HP, PU, UK, HY, DL, RJ, MP, TL, CG, BR, JH, AS, ML, AR, MN, TR	(Shaji et al. 2019, Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Jagtap 2013, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Kaur et al. 2017, Hembrom & Bodra 2021, Murugan & Prabakaran 2012)	Rivers & tanks of Bengal
1826	<i>Labeo catla</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ, HP, PU, UK, HY, DL, UP, RJ, MP, TL, CG, BR, JH, SK, AS, ML, MN, TR	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Shaji et al. 2019, Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Rema devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar 2006, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Jagtap 2013, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a, Kaur et al. 2017, Hembrom & Bodra 2021, Murugan & Prabakaran 2012)	Rivers & ponds of West Bengal
1827	<i>Labeo dussumieri</i> (Valenciennes, 1842)	F	WB, OD, AP, KL, KA, GA, MH, MP, TL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Chanda nad Jana 2021, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Yadav 2008)	Alleppey, Kerala
1828	<i>Labeo dyocheilus</i> (McClelland, 1839)	F	WB, GJ, HP, PU, UK, HY, RJ, MP, TL, SK, AR, MN	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Bagra et al. 2009, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar 2006, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Jagtap 2013, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Brraich & Saini 2019)	Brahmaputra River
1829	<i>Labeo fimbriatus</i> (Bloch, 1795)	F	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ, RJ, MP, TL, CG	(Shaji et al. 2019, Sanyal et al. 2012, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar	Malabar coast

				1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000)	
1830	<i>Labeo filiferus</i> Plamoottil & Zupančič, 2017	F	KL	(Plamoottil & Zupančič 2017)	Pamba River at Edakadathy, Kerala
1831	<i>Labeo gonius</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, AP, MH, GJ, HP, PU, UK, HY, DL, UP, RJ, MP, TL, CG, BR, AS, ML, AR, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Husain 1997, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Jagtap 2013, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a, Brraich & Saini 2019, Niraj & Singh 2013)	Brahmaputra River, Assam
1832	<i>Labeo kawrus</i> (Sykes, 1839)	F	MH, TL	(Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Beema River, Deccan
1833	<i>Labeo kontius</i> (Jerdon, 1849)	F	TN, KA, GJ, TL	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Sen & Banerjee 2000)	Cavery River & its tributaries, southern India
1834	<i>Labeo microphthalmus</i> Day, 1877	F	TL	(Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016)	Himalayas from Punjab, Murree, Kangra, & Cashmere
1835	<i>Labeo nandina</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, MP, AS, ML, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Barman 2002, Sharma 2007)	Bolahat, Gorakhpur District
1836	<i>Labeo nigrescens</i> Day, 1870	F	KL, KA, MH	(Shaji et al. 2019, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Mangalore, Karnataka
1837	<i>Labeo nigripinnis</i> Day, 1877	F	RJ	(Datta & Majumdar 1964)	
1838	<i>Labeo pangusia</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, AP, TN, KA, MH, HP, PU, DL, MP, TL, JH, AS, ML, AR, MN, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Jagtap 2013, Brraich & Saini 2019, Tudu et al. 2022)	Mainai, Kosi River
1839	<i>Labeo potail</i> (Sykes, 1839)	F	AP, TN, KA, MH, GJ, TL	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000)	Deccan
1840	<i>Labeo porcellus</i> (Heckel, 1844)	F	AP, KA, MH, GJ, MP, TL	(Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000)	Mumbai
1841	<i>Labeo rajasthanicus</i> Datta & Majumdar, 1970	F	RJ	(Datta & Majumdar 1964)	Tidi River, Udaipur, Rajasthan
1842	<i>Labeo ricnorhynchus</i> (McClelland, 1839)	F	WB	(McClelland 1839)	Northern Bengal

1843	<i>Labeo rohita</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ, HP, PU, UK, HY, DL, UP, RJ, MP, TL, CG, BR, JH, SK, AS, ML, AR, NL, MN, TR	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Shaji et al. 2019, Karmakar & Das 2005, Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar 2006, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Jagtap 2013, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a, Braich & Saini 2019, Hembrom & Bodra 2021, Murugan & Prabakaran 2012)	Freshwater rivers of Gangetic Provinces
1844	<i>Labeo shivamogaensis</i> Arunachalam, Anusha & Sivakumar, 2018	F	KA	(Arunachalam et al. 2018)	Bhadra Reservoir, Shimoga, Karnataka
1845	<i>Lepidopygopsis typus</i> Raj, 1941	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Periyar Lake, Kerala
1846	<i>Naziritor chelynoides</i> (McClelland, 1839)	F	PU, UK, MP, ML, NL	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Sen 1995, Sharma 2007, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Brraich & Saini 2019)	Simla
1847	<i>Neochela dadiburjori</i> (Menon, 1952)	F	OD, TN, KL, GA, MH, MP	(Shaji et al. 2019, Chanda nad Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Yadav 2008)	Cochin, Kerala
1848	<i>Neolissochilus acutirostris</i> Arunachalam, Sivakumar & Murugan, 2017	F	KA	(Arunachalam et al. 2017)	Abby falls, a stream in the Cauvery River drainage in Kodagu District, Karnataka
1849	<i>Neolissochilus capudelphinus</i> Arunachalam, Sivakumar & Murugan, 2017	F	TN	(Arunachalam et al. 2017)	Upstream of the diverted water from Periyar River, 12 km from the town of Cumbum, Tamil Nadu
1850	<i>Neolissochilus dukai</i> (Day, 1878)	F	WB	(Sanyal et al. 2012)	Teesta River, near Darjeeling
1851	<i>Neolissochilus hexagonolepis</i> (McClelland, 1839)	F	WB, TN, MH, SK, AS, ML, AR, NL, MN, MZ, TR	(Karmakar & Das 2005, 2005a, Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Bagra et al. 2009, Karmakar 2006, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Upper Assam
1852	<i>Neolissochilus hexastichus</i> (McClelland, 1839)	F	WB, SK, ML, AR, NL, MN, MZ	(Karmakar & Das 2005, 2005a, Acharjee & Barat 2014, Sen 1995, Bagra et al. 2009, Karmakar 2006)	Great rivers in the plains of India
1853	<i>Neolissochilus kaladanensis</i> Lalramliana, Lalronunga, Kumar & Singh,	F	MZ	(Lalramliana et al. 2019a)	Kaladan River in the vicinity of Kawlchaw

	2019				Village, Mizoram
1854	<i>Neolissochilus microphthalmus</i> Arunachalam, Sivakumar & Murugan, 2017	F	KL	(Arunachalam et al. 2017)	Ambayathode in the forest reserves in the Kannur District, Kerala
1855	<i>Neolissochilus minimus</i> Arunachalam, Sivakumar & Murugan, 2017	F	TN	(Arunachalam et al. 2017)	Diverted water of Periyar River in the forest reserves of Cumbam Valley, Western Ghats
1856	<i>Neolissochilus paucisquamatus</i> (Smith, 1945)	F	No specific location	(Devi & Indra 2012)	
1857	<i>Neolissochilus pnar</i> Dahanukar, Sundar, Rangad, Proudlove & Raghavan, 2023	F	ML	(Dahanukar et al. 2023)	Cave, 92 m below the surface in Krem Um Ladaw, Meghalaya
1858	<i>Neolissochilus spinulosus</i> (McClelland, 1845)	F	SK	(Karmakar 2006)	Rivers at foot of Sikkim Mountains
1859	<i>Neolissochilus stracheyi</i> (Day, 1871)	F	No specific location	(Devi & Indra 2012)	
1860	<i>Neolissochilus tamiraparaniensis</i> Arunachalam, Sivakumar & Murugan, 2017	F	TN	(Arunachalam et al. 2017)	<i>Neolissochilus tamiraparaniensis</i> Arunachalam, Sivakumar & Murugan 2017
1861	<i>Neolissochilus wynaadensis</i> (Day, 1873)	F	TN, KL, KA	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Shaji et al. 2019, Rema Devi et al. 2013)	Vithry, Wynaad, Kerala
1862	<i>Oreochthys andrewi</i> Knight, 2014	F	AS	(Knight 2014)	River Dibru at Guijan Gnat, Tinsukia District, Assam
1863	<i>Oreochthys coorgensis</i> (Jayaram, 1982)	F	KA	(Rema Devi et al. 2013)	Coorg District, Karnataka
1864	<i>Oreochthys cosuatis</i> (Hamilt, 1822)	F	WB, OD, AP, KA, MH, MP, CG	(Schafer 2009, Chanda nad Jana 2021, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Nathpur, Kosi River, Uttar Pradesh
1865	<i>Oreochthys crenuchoides</i> Schäfer, 2009	F	WB	(Schafer 2009)	River Jorai, a tributary of Brahmaputra River, near border with Assam
1866	<i>Oreochthys duospilus</i> Knight & Kumar, 2015	F	KA	(Knight & Kumar 2015)	Small stream by the side of the road, west of Nagara, Karnataka
1867	<i>Oreochthys incognito</i> Knight & Kumar, 2015	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Kunthipuzha, Mannarkkad,

					Kerala
1868	<i>Osteobrama alfredianus</i> (Valenciennes, 1844)	F	KA	(Cuvier & Valenciennes 1844)	Mysore
1869	<i>Osteobrama bakeri</i> (Day, 1873)	F	KL, MH, GJ	(Shaji et al. 2019, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000)	Kottayam, Kerala
1870	<i>Osteobrama belangeri</i> (Valenciennes, 1844)	F	WB, AP, KA, TL, MN	(Sahu 2020, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016)	Bengal
1871	<i>Osteobrama cotio</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, AP, TN, KA, MH, GJ, HP, PU, UK, HY, DL, UP, RJ, MP, CG, JH, AS, ML, AR, MN, MZ, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Sharma & Dhanze 2018, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a, Kaur et al. 2017, Tudu et al. 2022, Kar & Sen 2007)	Bengal
1872	<i>Osteobrama cunma</i> (Day, 1888)	F	OD, TL, MN	(Chanda & Jana 2021, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016)	
1873	<i>Osteobrama dayi</i> (Hora & Misra, 1940)	F	AP, KA, MH	(Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Godavari River, Andhra Pradesh
1874	<i>Osteobrama feae</i> Vinciguerra, 1890	F	North eastern India	(Vishwanath & Shanta Kumar 2007)	
1875	<i>Osteobrama neilli</i> (Day, 1873)	F	AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ, TL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Prasad & Srinivasulu 2021, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000)	Bhavani river at the Nilgiris
1876	<i>Osteobrama peninsularis</i> Silas, 1952	F	OD, TN, KA, MH, TL	(Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar et al. 2012)	upper Krishna River drainage, Maharashtra
1877	<i>Osteobrama tikarpadaensis</i> Shangningam, Rath, Tudu & Kosygin, 2020	F	OD, MH	(Shangningam et al. 2020, Rath et al. 2021)	Mahanadi River at Marada, 3 km from Tikarpada, Angul District, Odisha
1878	<i>Osteobrama vigorsii</i> (Sykes, 1839)	F	OD, AP, TN, KA, MH, GJ, MP, TL, CG	(Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000)	Bhima River at Pairgoan, Maharashtra
1879	<i>Osteochilus longidorsalis</i> (Pethiyagoda & Kottelat, 1994)	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Chalakydy River, near Vettilappara, Kerala
1880	<i>Osteochilus vittatus</i> (Valenciennes, 1842)	F	KL	(Schgal 1999)	
1881	<i>Osteochilichthys augraoides</i> (Jerdon, 1849)	F	KA	(Plamoottil & Vineeth 2020b)	Cauvery River & its tributaries, Karnataka

1882	<i>Osteochilichthys elegans</i> Plamoottil, 2022	F	KL	(Plamoottil 2022)	Stream at Mannarkkad, Palakkad District, Kerala
1883	<i>Osteochilichthys formosus</i> Plamoottil & Vineeth, 2022	F	KL	(Plamoottil & Vineeth 2022a)	Water stream at Chullikkara, Kazargod district, Kerala
1884	<i>Osteochilichthys longidorsalis</i> Pethiyagoda & Kottelat, 1994	F	KL	(Pethiyagoda & Kottelat 1994)	Chalakydy River, 26 kilometers upstream of Chalakydy town, near Vettilappara, Kerala
1885	<i>Osteochilichthys nashii</i> (Day, 1869)	F	OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, TL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Chanda nad Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Fraserpett river, Coorg Dist., Karnataka
1886	<i>Osteochilichthys thomassi</i> (Day, 1877)	F	WB, AP, KL, KA, MH	(Shaji et al. 2019, Chanda nad Jana 2021, Rema devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar et al. 2012, Barman 1993)	South Canara
1887	<i>Parapsilorhynchus alluriensis</i> Jadhav, Karuthapandi, Chandra, Jaiswal, Dinesh & Narahari, 2020	F	AP	(Jadhav et al. 2020)	Dharamattam stream, near Golugonda village, Alluri Forest, Visakhapatnam District, Andhra Pradesh State
1888	<i>Psilorhynchus arunachalensis</i> (Nebeshwar, Bagra & Das, 2007)	F	AR	(Nebeshwar et al. 2007)	West Kameng District, Dirang River at Dirang, Brahmaputra River system, Arunachal Pradesh
1889	<i>Parapsilorhynchus discophorus</i> Hora, 1921	F	MH, HY	(Karmakar et al. 2012, Bhatnagar et al. 2016)	Pophli, Vashishti valley, western Ghats, Ratnagiri District, Maharashtra
1890	<i>Parapsilorhynchus elongatus</i> Singh, 1994	F	MH	(Karmakar et al. 2012)	Ghod River, Khondwal village, Ambegaon taluka, Pune District, Maharashtra
1891	<i>Parapsilorhynchus odishaensis</i> Baliarsingh, Kosygin & Swain, 2017	F	OD	(Baliarsingh et al. 2017)	Mahendra Tanaya River, Tiniamba village,

					Rayagada District, Odisha
1892	<i>Parapsilorhynchus prateri</i> Hora & Misra, 1938	F	KA, MH	(Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Deolali, Maharashtra
1893	<i>Parapsilorhynchus swaini</i> Baliarsingh & Kosygin, 2017	F	OD	(Baliarsingh & Kosygin 2017)	Stream near Harisankar, Mahanadi River basin, Odisha
1894	<i>Parapsilorhynchus tentaculatus</i> (Annandale, 1919)	F	MH	(Karmakar et al. 2012)	Hill streamlets at Khandalla, Poona District, Maharashtra
1895	<i>Pethia arunachalensis</i> Shangningam, Kosygin & Chowdhury, 2020	F	AR	(Shangningam et al. 2020a)	Nao-dhing River near Miao, Brahmaputra River drainage, Changlang District, Arunachal Pradesh
1896	<i>Pethia atra</i> (Linthoingambi & Vishwanath, 2007)	F	MN	(Linthoingambi & Vishwanath 2007)	Chindwin River basin, Manipur
1897	<i>Pethia aurea</i> Knight, 2013	F	WB, KA	(Knight 2013, Rema Devi et al. 2013)	Ponds in South 24, Parganas District, West Bengal
1898	<i>Pethia canius</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB	(Knight 2013)	Pond in Cooch Behar District, West Bengal
1899	<i>Pethia chakpiensis</i> Shangningam & Kosygin, 2023	F	MN	(Shangningam & Kosygin 2023)	Akaphe stream at Konem Paddy field, Akaphe Village, Chakpi River, Chindwin-Irrawaddy basin, Chandel District, Manipur
1900	<i>Pethia conchoni</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ, J&K, HP, PU, UK, DL, UP, RJ, MP, TL, BR, JH, SK, AS, ML, AR, NL, MN, MZ, TR	(Shaji et al. 2019, Karmakar & Das 2005, Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar 2006, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Bhat et al. 2020, Sharma & Dhanze 2018, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Mishra et al. 2021a, Brraich & Saini 2019, Tudu et al. 2022, Kumari & Yadav 2020, Kar & Sen 2007)	Ponds of north east Bengal & Kosi river & Ami river
1901	<i>Pethia dikhuensis</i> Praveenraj, Limaakum, Knight, Moulitharan & Imchen, 2022	F	NL	(Praveenraj et al. 2022a)	Dikhu River, Mokokchung district, Nagaland

1902	<i>Pethia expletiforis</i> Mayanglambam & Vishwanath, 2013	F	MZ	(Mayanglambam & Vishwanath 2013)	Mizoram, Saiha District, Ka-ao River near new Serkawr village, Kalidan drainage
1903	<i>Pethia gelius</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, AP, TN, MH, UK, MP, TL, CG, AS, ML, MN, TR	(Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021)	River Torsa at Totapara in Jalpaiguri, West Bengal
1904	<i>Pethia guganio</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, AP, KA, DL, RJ, MP, CG, AS, AR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Chanda nad Jana 2021, Barman 1993, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Sen 1985, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Sharma 2007)	Brahmaputra & Yamuna rivers
1905	<i>Pethia khugae</i> (Linthoingambi & Vishwanath, 2007)	F	MN	(Linthoingambi & Vishwanath 2007)	Khuga River at Churachandpur, Chindwin River basin, Manipur
1906	<i>Pethia longicauda</i> Katwate, Paingankar, Raghavan & Dahanukar, 2014	F	MH	(Katwate et al. 2014a)	Maharashtra: Kolhapur District: Hiranyakeshi River near Gavse-Ajara, 16°04'06"N, 74°05'30"E
1907	<i>Pethia lutea</i> Katwate, Katwate, Raghavan, Paingankar & Dahanukar, 2014	F	MH	(Katwate et al. 2014)	Bhira (18.441°N, 73.267°E), Kundalika River, Raigad District, Maharashtra
1908	<i>Pethia manipurensis</i> (Menon, Rema Devi & Vishwanath, 2000)	F	MN	(Menon et al. 2000)	Lake Loktak, Moirang
1909	<i>Pethia meingangbii</i> (Arunkumar & Tombi Singh, 2003)	F	MN	(Arunkumar & Tombi Singh 2003)	Moreh Bazar, Moreh 110 kilometers from Imphal, Chindwin River basin, Manipur
1910	<i>Pethia muvattupuzhaensis</i> (Jameela Beevi & Ramachandran, 2005)	F	KL	(Jameela Beevi & Ramachandran 2005)	Muvattupuzha River, Ooramana, Ernakulam District, Kerala
1911	<i>Pethia narayani</i> (Hora, 1937)	F	KA, GA, MH	(Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar et al. 2012, Yadav 2008)	Coorg State, Karnataka
1912	<i>Pethia nigripinnis</i> (Knight, Rema Devi, Indra & Arunachalam, 2012)	F	TN, KL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	Wayanad, Kerala
1913	<i>Pethia nigrofasciata</i> (Günther, 1868)	F	TN, KA	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013)	
1914	<i>Pethia ornata</i> (Vishwanath &	F	MN	(Vishwanath & Laisram 2004)	Lokchao River,

	Laisram, 2004)				Moreh, Manipur
1915	<i>Pethia phutunio</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, KA, GJ, PU, CG, BR, AS, ML, MN	(Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Brraich & Saini 2019, Kumari & Yadav 2020)	Ponds at Pergunj, northeastern Bengal
1916	<i>Pethia poiensis</i> Shangningam & Vishwanath, 2018	F	MN	(Shangningam & Vishwanath 2018)	Challou River at Poi Village, Ukhrul District, Manipur
1917	<i>Pethia pookodensis</i> (Mercy & Jacob, 2007)	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Pookode Lake, Kerala
1918	<i>Pethia punctata</i> (Day, 1865)	F	OD, TN, KL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Chanda nad Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	Cochin, Kerala
1919	<i>Pethia rutila</i> Lalramliana, Knight & Laltlanhlua, 2014	F	MZ	(Lalramliana et al. 2014)	Aivapui River, in the vicinity of Phuldungsei Village, Mizoram
1920	<i>Pethia sahit</i> Katwate, Kumkar, Raghavan & Dahanukar, 2018	F	MH	(Katwate et al. 2018)	Hiranyakeshi River near Ghatkarwadi, Ajara Taluk, Kolhapur District, Maharashtra
1921	<i>Pethia sanjaymoluri</i> Katwate, Jadhav, Kumkar, Raghavan & Dahanukar, 2016	F	MH	(Katwate et al. 2016)	Pavana river near Rawet, Pune district, Maharashtra
1922	<i>Pethia setnai</i> (Chhapgar & Sane, 1992)	F	KA, GA	Rema Devi et al. 2013	Sanguem, Goa
1923	<i>Pethia shalynius</i> (Yazdani & Talukdar, 1975)	F	WB, AS, ML, AR, NL, MN	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Mogalekar et al. 2017, Sen 1985, 1995, Bagra et al. 2009, Karmakar & Das 2005a)	Barapani lake, near Shillong, Meghalaya
1924	<i>Pethia sharmai</i> (Menon & Rema Devi, 1993)	F	TN, KA	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013)	Mogappair, West Annanagar, Madras, Tamil Nadu
1925	<i>Pethia stoliczkana</i> (Day, 1871)	F	MN	(Linthoingambi & Vishwanath 2007)	
1926	<i>Pethia striata</i> Atkore, Knight, Rema Devi & Krishnaswamy, 2015	F	KA	(Atkore et al. 2015)	Karnataka, Chikmagalur District, Tunga River basin, Balipehalla, Mudba stream
1927	<i>Pethia ticto</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ, HP, PU, UK, HY, DL, UP, RJ, MP, TL, CG, BR, JH, SK, AS,	(Shaji et al. 2019, Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar 2006, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee	Southern parts of Bengal

			ML, AR, NL, MN, TR	2000, Yadav 2008, Sharma & Dhanze 2018, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a, Braich & Saini 2019, Tudu et al. 2022, Kumar et al. 2011)	
1928	<i>Pethia yuensis</i> (Arunkumar & Tombi Singh, 2003)	F	MN	(Arunkumar & Tombi Singh 2003)	Maklang River, 21 kilometers from Moreh, Chindwin River basin, Manipur
1929	<i>Poropuntius burtoni</i> (Mukerji, 1934)	F	MN	(Karmakar & Das 2005a)	Taret hill stream, Saibol, 20 kilometers east of Tengenoupal, Manipur
1930	<i>Plesiopuntius bimaculatus</i> (Bleeker, 1863)	F	TN, KL, KA, TL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Prasad & Srinivasulu 2021)	
1931	<i>Poropuntius shanensis</i> (Hora & Mukerji, 1934)	F	MN	(Karmakar & Das 2005a)	
1932	<i>Ptychobarbus conirostris</i> Steindachner, 1866	F	LD	(Tilak 1990)	Near Monastery at Hanle, Ladakh
1933	<i>Puntius ambassis</i> (Day, 1869)	F	OD, TN	(Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	Kurnool, Andhra Pradesh
1934	<i>Puntius amphibius</i> (Valenciennes, 1842)	F	OD, AP, KA, GA, MH, GJ, HY, RJ, MP, TL	(Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Yadav 2008, Bhatnagar et al. 2016)	Mumbai
1935	<i>Puntius arenatus</i> (Day, 1878)	F	TN, MH, GJ, MP	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000)	Chennai
1936	<i>Puntius burmanicus</i> (Day, 1878)	F	LK, AS, MN, MZ	(Rajan et al. 2021, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Kar & Sen 2007)	
1937	<i>Puntius cauveriensis</i> (Hora, 1937)	F	TN, KL, KA	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013)	Cauvery river, Coorg, Karnataka
1938	<i>Puntius chola</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ, HP, PU, UK, HY, DL, UP, RJ, MP, TL, CG, BR, JH, AS, ML, AR, NL, MN, MZ, TR	(Shaji et al. 2019, Karmakar & Das 2005, Mishra et al. 2017, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Sharma & Dhanze 2018, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a, Braich & Saini 2019, Tudu et al. 2022, Murugan & Prabakaran 2012, Kar & Sen 2007)	Northeastern parts of Bengal

1939	<i>Puntius crescentus</i> Yazdani & Singh, 1994	F	KA, GA	(Yadav 2008)	Kalinadi at Sunderi, about 7 kilometers east of Karwar, Karnataka
1940	<i>Puntius deccanensis</i> Yazdani & Babu Rao, 1976	F	MH	(Karmakar et al. 2012)	Nalla near Katraj tank, 13 kilometers south of Poona, Maharashtra
1941	<i>Puntius dolichopterus</i> Plamoottil, 2015	F	KL, MH	(Plamoottil 2015)	Kayamkulam, Kerala
1942	<i>Puntius dorsalis</i> (Jerdon, 1849)	F	OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, RJ, MP, TL, CG	(Shaji et al. 2019, Chanda nad Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Madras
1943	<i>Puntius euspilurus</i> Plamoottil, 2016	F	KL	(Plamoottil 2016a)	Kerala, Mananthavady River
1944	<i>Puntius fraseri</i> (Hora & Misra, 1938)	F	TN, MH, GJ	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000)	Darna River, Deolali, Mumbai
1945	<i>Puntius khohi</i> Dobriyal, Singh, Uniyal, Joshi, Phurailatpam & Bisht, 2004	F	UK	(Dobriyal et al. 2004)	Silgad-Khoh, Stream Dogadda, 15 kilometers before Kotdwara, Garwal Himalaya, Uttaranchal
1946	<i>Puntius kyphus</i> Plamoottil, 2019	F	KL	(Plamoottil 2019)	Stream at Thiruvalla, Kerala
1947	<i>Puntius madhusoodani</i> Krishnakumar, Benno Pereira & Radhakrishnan, 2012	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Manimala River, Pattanamthitta, Kerala.
1948	<i>Puntius mahecola</i> (Valenciennes, 1844)	F	TN, KL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	Mahe, Kerala
1949	<i>Puntius melanostigma</i> (Day, 1878)	F	TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ, MP, TL, BR	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Kumar et al. 2011)	Wayanad, Kerala
1950	<i>Puntius mudumalaiensis</i> Menon & Rema Devi, 1992	F	TN, KA	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013)	Kakkanhalla road, Mudumalai, Tamil Nadu
1951	<i>Puntius muzaffarpurensis</i> Srivastava, Verma & Sharma, 1977	F	BR	(Srivastava et al. 1977)	Baghmati River, Saidpur, Bihar
1952	<i>Puntius nangalensis</i> Jayaram, 1990	F	HP	(Jayaram 1990)	Nangal Lake, eastern Punjab,

					Himachal Pradesh
1953	<i>Puntius nelsoni</i> Plamoottil, 2014	F	KL	(Plamoottil 2014)	Kallumkal, Manimala River, Kerala
1954	<i>Puntius nigronotus</i> Plamoottil, 2014	F	KL	(Plamoottil 2014a)	Kerala, Mananthavady River
1955	<i>Puntius ocellus</i> Plamoottil & Vineeth, 2020	F	KL	(Plamoottil & Vineeth 2020a)	Stream at Kasargod, Kerala
1956	<i>Puntius parrah</i> Day, 1865	F	AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ, TL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000)	Cochin, Kerala
1957	<i>Puntius punjabensis</i> (Day, 1871)	F	DL, MP	(Husain 1997, Sharma 2007)	
1958	<i>Puntius puntio</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, MP, MZ	(Barman 2007, Sharma 2007, Kar & Sen 2007)	Southern Bengal
1959	<i>Puntius sanctus</i> Plamoottil, 2020	F	TN	(Plamoottil 2020)	Small stream at Velamkanni, Tamil Nadu
1960	<i>Puntius sophore</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ, HP, PU, UK, HY, DL, UP, RJ, MP, TL, CG, BR, JH, SK, AS, ML, AR, NL, MN, TR	(Shaji et al. 2019, Karmakar & Das 2005, Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar 2006, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Sharma & Dhanze 2018, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a, Kaur et al. 2017, Tudu et al. 2022, Kumar et al. 2011)	Ponds & rivers in the Gangetic provinces
1961	<i>Puntius sophoroides</i> (Günther, 1868)	F	WB	(Günther 1868)	Cachar & Hooghly [Hoogley] River
1962	<i>Puntius stigma</i> (Valenciennes, 1844)	F	WB, HP, JH	(Chanda & Jana 2021, Jagtap 2013, Hembrom & Bodra 2021)	Mysore
1963	<i>Puntius terio</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, AP, HP, UK, HY, DL, TL, AS, ML, AR	(Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman 1993, Husain 1997, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Jagtap 2013, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Jha et al. 2013)	Brahmaputra River, Goalpara, Assam
1964	<i>Puntius viridis</i> Plamoottil & Abraham, 2014	F	KL	(Plamoottil & Abraham 2013)	Kallumkal, Manimala River, Kerala
1965	<i>Puntius waageni</i> (Day, 1872)	F	MP	(Sharma 2007)	
1966	<i>Rohtee ogilbii</i> Sykes, 1839	F	AP, KA, MH, TL	(Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Beema River near Pairgaon, Maharashtra
1967	<i>Schizopygopsis stoliczkai</i> Steindachner, 1866	F	LD, AS, AR	(Bagra et al. 2009, Sen 1985, Tilak 1990)	Chushul, Ladakh
1968	<i>Semiplotus</i>	F	MN	(Vishwanath & Kosygin 2000)	

	<i>cirrhusus</i> Chaudhuri, 1919				
1969	<i>Semiplotus gangulyi</i> Dey, 1975	F	AS	(Dey 1975)	Pagladia River, tributary of the Brahmaputra River in Kamrup District, Assam
1970	<i>Semiplotus manipurensis</i> Vishwanath & Kosygin, 2000	F	MN	(Vishwanath & Kosygin 2000)	Chall ou River at Thetsi, near Jessami, Manipur
1971	<i>Semiplotus modestus</i> Day, 1870	F	MN, MZ	(Vishwanath & Kosygin 2000, Kar & Sen 2007)	
1972	<i>Semiplotus semiplotus</i> (McClelland, 1839)	BF	WB, OD, SK, AS, AR, TR	(Chanda & Jana 2021, Bagra et al. 2009, Barman 2002, Sen 1985, Karmakar 2006)	Brahmaputra River rapids, Upper Assam
1973	<i>Schizothorax curvifrons</i> Heckel, 1838	F	LD, J&K, UK	(Bhat et al. 2020, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021)	Kashmir
1974	<i>Schizothorax chivae</i> Arunkumar & Moyon, 2016	F	MN	(Arunkumar & Moyon 2016)	Chiva River at Khongjon village, Chandel District, Manipur
1975	<i>Schizothorax esocinus</i> Heckel, 1838	F	LD, J&K, UK, AR	(Bagra et al. 2009, Bhat et al. 2020, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Tilak 1990)	Kashmir
1976	<i>Schizothorax huegelii</i> Heckel, 1838	F	J&K	(Heckel 1838)	Kashmir
1977	<i>Schizothorax kumaonensis</i> Menon, 1971	F	UK, UP	(Uniyal & Uniyal 2021)	Nainital, Uttar Pradesh, Himalayas
1978	<i>Schizothorax labiatus</i> (McClelland, 1842)	F	LD, J&K	(Bhat et al. 2020, Tilak 1990)	
1979	<i>Schizothorax macropogon</i> Regan, 1905	F	LD	(Tilak 1990)	
1980	<i>Schizothorax molesworthi</i> (Chaudhuri, 1913)	F	WB, AS	(Sanyal et al. 2012)	Abor Hills, Assam
1981	<i>Schizothorax nasus</i> Heckel, 1838	F	J&K	(Heckel 1838)	Kashmir
1982	<i>Schizothorax niger</i> Heckel, 1838	F	J&K	(Bhat et al. 2020)	Kashmir
1983	<i>Schizothorax plagiostomus</i> Heckel, 1838	F	J&K, HP, UK	(Bhat et al. 2020, Jagtap 2013, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021)	Kashmir, Tschilum River.
1984	<i>Schizothorax progastus</i> (McClelland, 1839)	F	WB, UK, HY, SK, AS, AR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Bagra et al. 2009, Sen 1985, Karmakar 2006, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016)	Mountain streams at Simla, Upper Assam
1985	<i>Schizothorax richardsonii</i> (Gray, 1832)	F	WB, LD, J&K, UK, SK, AS, AR, NL, MN	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Sanyal et al. 2012, Bagra et al. 2009, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Karmakar 2006, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Tilak 1990)	Nepal
1986	<i>Schizothorax sikusirumensis</i> Jha, 2020	F	AR	(Jha 2020)	Sikusirum River, Siang River basin, East Sing District, Arunachal Pradesh
1987	<i>Systemus chryseus</i> Plamoottil, 2014	F	KL	(Plamoottil 2014)	Keezhvaipur, Manimala River, Kerala

1988	<i>Systomus clavatus</i> (McClelland, 1845)	F	WB, SK, AS, ML, AR, MN, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Bagra et al. 2009, Barman 2002, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Karmakar 2006)	Rivers at foot of Sikkim Mountains, northern frontier of Bengal
1989	<i>Systomus deliciosus</i> (McClelland, 1839)	F	AS	(Ramalingam & Parasivan 2020)	Upper Assam
1990	<i>Systomus gracilus</i> Plamoottil & Maji, 2020	F	WB	(Chanda & Jana 2021)	Ganges River near Naihati, West Bengal
1991	<i>Systomus immaculatus</i> McClelland, 1839	F	AS	(Pethiyagoda et al. 2012)	Assam
1992	<i>Systomus laticeps</i> Plamoottil, 2016	F	KL	(Plamoottil 2016)	Freshwater stream at Thiruvalla, Pathanamthitta district, Kerala
1993	<i>Systomus orphoides</i> (Valenciennes, 1842)	F	TN	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	
1994	<i>Systomus pleurotaenia</i> (Bleeker, 1863)	F	GJ	(Sen & Banerjee 2000)	
1995	<i>Systomus rufus</i> Plamoottil, 2014	F	KL	(Plamoottil 2014)	Venpala, Manimala River, Kerala
1996	<i>Systomus sarana</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ, HP, PU, UK, HY, DL, UP, RJ, MP, TL, CG, BR, JH, SK, AS, ML, AR, MN, TR	(Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Barman 2002, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar 2006, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Yadav 2008, Sharma & Dhanze 2018, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a, Braich & Saini 2019, Tudu et al. 2022, Murugan & Prabakaran 2012)	Ponds & rivers of Bengal
1997	<i>Systomus sewelli</i> (Prashad & Mukerji, 1929)	F	MN	(Arunkumar & Tombi Singh 1998a)	
1998	<i>Tariqilabeo burmanicus</i> (Hora, 1936)	F	AR, NL, MN	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Sen 1995, Bagra et al. 2009, Karmakar & Das 2005a)	Assam
1999	<i>Tariqilabeo diplochilus</i> (Heckel, 1838)	F	J&K, HP	(Bhat et al. 2020, Sharma & Dhanze 2018)	Kashmir
2000	<i>Tariqilabeo latius</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	WB, OD, AP, KA, MH, GJ, HP, PU, UK, DL, MP, TL, JH, SK, AS, ML, AR, NL, MN, TR	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar 2006, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Sharma & Dhanze 2018, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Braich & Saini	Teesta river, Darjeeling, Himalaya

				2019, Tudu et al. 2022)	
2001	<i>Tariqilabeo periyarensis</i> (Menon & Jacob, 1996)	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Periyar river, Thanikkudy, Kerala
2002	<i>Tariqilabeo wattanah</i> (Sykes, 1839)	F	MH	(Sykes 1839)	Right bank of the canal below the Empress Garden, Pune
2003	<i>Thynnichthys sandkhol</i> (Sykes, 1839)	F	AP, KA, MH, TL	(Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar et al. 2012)	River at Kullumb, Deccan
2004	<i>Tor barakae</i> Arunkumar & Basudha, 2003	F	MN	(Arunkumar & Basudha 2003)	Barak River at Barak Bridge, Manipur,
2005	<i>Tor khudree</i> (Sykes, 1839)	F	WB, OD, TN, KL, KA, MH, RJ, MP, TL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Chanda nad Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Mula-Mutha River, Pune, Maharashtra
2006	<i>Tor kulkarnii</i> Menon, 1992	F	MH	(Karmakar et al. 2012)	Darna River, Deolali, Maharashtra
2007	<i>Tor mahanadicus</i> David, 1953	F	OD	(Johnson et al. 2023)	Hirakud [Hirakhud] stretch, Mahanadi River, Orissa
2008	<i>Tor malabaricus</i> (Jerdon, 1849)	F	TN, KL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	Mountain streams of Malabar
2009	<i>Tor mosal</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	BR, SK, MZ, TR	(Karmakar 2006, Kar & Sen 2007)	Nathpur, Kosi River [= Koshi River], upper Ganges drainage, Bihar
2010	<i>Tor putitora</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, TN, GJ, J&K, HP, PU, UK, HY, MP, SK, AS, ML, AR, NL, MN, TR	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Bagra et al. 2009, Barman 2002, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Karmakar 2006, Sharma 2007, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Bhat et al. 2020, Jagtap 2013, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Braich & Saini 2019)	Eastern parts of Bengal
2011	<i>Tor remadeviae</i> Kurup & Radhakrishnan, 2011	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Pambar River, Chinnar Wildlife Sanctuary, Kerala
2012	<i>Tor tor</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, TN, MH, GJ, UK, DL, MP, CG,	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Bagra et al. 2009, Husain 1997, Barman 2002, Karmakar & Das	Sannashigotta, Mahananda River

			AS, ML, AR, MN, MZ, TR	2005a, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021)	
2013	<i>Waikhomia hira</i> Katwate, Kumkar, Raghavan & Dahanukar, 2020	F	KA	(Katwate et al. 2020a)	Kali River near Chandewadi, Kamra, Uttara Kannada District, Karnataka
2014	<i>Waikhomia sahyadriensis</i> (Silas, 1953)	F	MH	(Karmakar et al. 2012)	Yenna River, Mahabaleshwar, Satara District
Family: Danionidae Bleeker, 1863					
2015	<i>Amblypharyngodon atkinsonii</i> (Blyth, 1860)	F	Northern India	(Kapoor et al. 2002)	
2016	<i>Amblypharyngodon melettinus</i> (Valenciennes, 1844)	F	TN, KL, KA, MP	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Sharma 2007)	Bombay Presidency
2017	<i>Amblypharyngodon microlepis</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	F	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MP, TL, BR	(Shaji et al. 2019, Chini et al. 2019, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Sharma 2007, Gunasekar & Isaac 2017)	Hooghly River, Kolkata
2018	<i>Amblypharyngodon mola</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, AP, TN, KA, MH, GJ, HP, PU, UK, DL, UP, RJ, MP, TL, CG, BR, JH, SK, AS, ML, AR, NL, MN, TR	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Barman 2002, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar 2006, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Jagtap 2013, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Mishra et al. 2021a, Kaur et al. 2017, Tudu et al. 2022, Kumar et al. 2011)	Ponds & freshwater rivers of Gangetic provinces
2019	<i>Barilius barila</i> (Hamilton, 182 2)	F	WB, OD, AP, KA, MH, HP, UK, DL, RJ, MP, TL, CG, BR, JH, AS, ML, MN, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman 1993, 2002, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Barman 2002, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sharma & Dhanze 2018, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Tudu et al. 2022, Kumari & Yadav 2020)	Northern Bengal
2020	<i>Barilius evezardi</i> Day, 1872	F	AP, MH, GJ, MP	(Barman 1993, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000)	Maharashtra
2021	<i>Barilius modestus</i> Day, 1872	F	HP	(Sharma & Dhanze 2018)	
2022	<i>Barilius torsai</i> Kumari, Munivenkatappa, Sinha, Borah & Das, 2019	F	WB	(Kumari et al. 2019)	Torsa River, Jaldapara, Alipurduar District, West Bengal

2023	<i>Barilius vagra</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, KA, MH, HP, PU, UK, RJ, MP, CG, SK, AS, ML, AR, MN, MZ, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Karmakar 2006, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sharma & Dhanze 2018, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Brraich & Saini 2019, Kar & Sen 2007)	Ganges River at Patna, Bihar
2024	<i>Bengala elanga</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, TL, BR, AS, ML, AR, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Bagra et al. 2009, Barman 2002, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Gunasekar & Isaac 2017)	Ganges River
2025	<i>Betadevario ramachandrani</i> Pramod, Fang, Rema Devi, Liao, Indra, Jameela Beevi & Kullander, 2010	F	KA	(Pramod et al. 2010)	Agumbe, small stream tributary to Sita River, 2 kilometers upstream from Onake Abbi Fall, 13°30.79'N, 75°04.49'E, Shimoga District, Dakshina Kannada, Karnataka
2026	<i>Cabdio crassus</i> Lalramliana, Lalronunga & Singh, 2019	F	MZ	(Lalramliana et al. 2019)	Kaladan River, in the vicinity of Kawlchaw village, Mizoram
2027	<i>Cabdio jaya</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, UK, MP, BR, SK, AS, AR, MZ	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Bagra et al. 2009, Sen 1985, Karmakar 2006, Sharma 2007, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Kar & Sen 2007)	Mainai, Ganges River, northern Bihar
2028	<i>Cabdio morar</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, AP, KA, MH, HP, PU, UK, HY, DL, RJ, MP, TL, CG, BR, SK, AS, AR, NL, MN, MZ, TR	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Sanyal et al. 2012, Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Prasad & Srinivasulu 2021, Karmakar 2006, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Jagtap 2013, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Brraich & Saini 2019, Niraj & Singh 2013, Kar & Sen 2007)	Yamuna river & Tista river
2029	<i>Cabdio ukhrulensis</i> (Selim & Vishwanath, 2001)	F	MN	(Selim & Vishwanath 2001)	Chatrickong River, Ukhrul District, Manipur
2030	<i>Chela cachiuis</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KA, GA, MH, GJ, DL, MP, TL, JH, AS, ML, AR, NL, MN, TR	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Yadav 2008, Tudu et al. 2022)	Ganga river about commencement of delta

2031	<i>Chela macrolepis</i> Knight & Rema Devi, 2014	F	TN	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	Chembarampakkam Lake, Chennai
2032	<i>Danio assamila</i> Kullander, 2015	F	AS	(Kullander 2015)	Assam, Brahmaputra River drainage, tributary of Dibru River, 2 km north of Digholtrang, Amguri, India, about 27°37'48"N, 95°23'43"E
2033	<i>Danio dangila</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, GJ, MP, BR, AS, AR, MN, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Bagra et al. 2009, Barman 2002, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Sharma 2007, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Kumari & Yadav 2020)	Mountain streams of Mongger, Bihar
2034	<i>Danio jaintianensis</i> (Sen, 2007)	F	ML	(Sen 2007)	Rangriang Jowai, Jaintia Hills district, Meghalaya, 25°26'11.9"N, 92°11'08.7"E
2035	<i>Danio meghalayensis</i> Sen & Dey, 1985	F	ML	(Sen & Dey 1985)	Rheophilic torrent near Barapani, Khasi Hills, Meghalaya
2036	<i>Danio rerio</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ, HP, UK, RJ, MP, TL, CG, BR, SK, AS, ML, NL, TR	(Shaji et al. 2019, Karmakar & Das 2005, Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar 2006, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Sharma & Dhanze 2018, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021)	Kosi River, Uttar Pradesh
2037	<i>Danionella priapus</i> Britz, 2009	F	WB	(Britz 2009)	Outskirts of Barobisha town, 26°28'52.3"N, 89°49'29.8"E, Jorai River, a tributary of the Sankosh at Laskarpara, Bramaputra River drainage, Jalpaiguri District, West Bengal
2038	<i>Devario acuticephalus</i> (Hora, 1921)	F	NL, MN	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Karmakar & Das 2005a)	Streams & ponds of Yaribuk, Manipur Valley

2039	<i>Devario aequipinnatus</i> (McClelland, 1839)	F	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ, RJ, MP, TL, CG, SK, AS, ML, NL, MN, MZ, TR	(Shaji et al. 2019, Karmakar & Das 2005, Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar 2006, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Yadav 2008, Kar & Sen 2007)	Assam
2040	<i>Devario deruptotalea</i> Ramananda & Vishwanath, 2014	F	MN	(Ramananda & Vishwanath 2014)	Manipur state, Chandel District, Dutah Stream, a tributary of Yu River (Chindwin drainage)
2041	<i>Devario devario</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, AP, KA, MH, GJ, HP, PU, UK, HY, RJ, MP, TL, CG, JH, AS, ML, AR, NL, MN, MZ, TR	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Sharma & Dhanze 2018, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Brraich & Saini 2019, Tudu et al. 2022)	Rivers & ponds of Bengal
2042	<i>Devario fraseri</i> (Hora, 1935)	F	KA, MH, GJ	(Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000)	Nasik, Maharashtra
2043	<i>Devario horai</i> (Barman, 1983)	F	AS, AR	(Sen 1985)	Namdapha River, Tirap District, Arunachal Pradesh
2044	<i>Devario malabaricus</i> (Jerdon, 1849)	F	OD, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Shaji et al. 2019, Chini et al. 2019, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000)	Chalakydy River, Kerala
2045	<i>Devario manipurensis</i> (Barman, 1987)	F	MN	(Karmakar & Das 2005a)	Manipur
2046	<i>Devario naganensis</i> (Chaudhuri, 1912)	F	AS, NL, MN, MZ, TR	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Channda & Jana 2021, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Kar & Sen 2007)	Lungting river, Nagaland
2047	<i>Devario neilgherriensis</i> (Day, 1867)	F	TN, KL, MP	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Sharma 2007)	Pykara, Avelanche & Kaity streams, Nilgiri Hills, Tamil Nadu
2048	<i>Devario regina</i> (Fowler, 1934)	F	MN	(Karmakar 2000)	Chindwin drainage, Brahmaputra drainage
2049	<i>Devario yuensis</i> (Arunkumar & Tombi Singh, 1998)	F	MN	(Arunkumar & Tombi Singh 1998)	Yu River System, Moreh Bazar, near the

					border areas of Manipur
2050	<i>Esomus bengalensis</i> Bhakat & Sinha, 2020	F	WB	(Bhakat & Sinha 2020)	Tilpara barrage, Mayurakshi River, Suri, Birbhum district, West Bengal
2051	<i>Esomus danrica</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, HP, PU, UK, HY, DL, UP, RJ, MP, TL, CG, BR, JH, AS, ML, AR, NL, MN, MZ, TR	(Shaji et al. 2019, Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sharma & Dhanze 2018, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a, Kaur et al. 2017, Hembrom & Bodra 2021, Gunasekar & Isaac 2017, Kar & Sen 2007)	Ponds & ditches of Bengal
2052	<i>Esomus nimasowi</i> Abujam, Gogoi, Das, Das, Biswas & Bleher, 2021	F	AS	(Abujam et al. 2021)	Phongloso stream, tributary of Kopili River, Brahmaputra basin, Wasubil Village, Dima Hasao District, Assam
2053	<i>Esomus thermoicos</i> (Valenciennes, 1842)	F	AP, TN, KL, KA, MP, TL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Sharma 2007, Barman 1993)	
2054	<i>Horadandia atukorali</i> Deraniyagala, 1943	BF	TN	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	
2055	<i>Horadandia brittani</i> Rema Devi & Menon, 1992	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Pond on Pathiramanal Island, Kerala
2056	<i>Laubuka fasciata</i> (Silas, 1958)	F	OD, TN, KL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	Chittur, Kerala
2057	<i>Laubuka khujairokensis</i> (Arunkumar, 2000)	F	MN	(Arunkumar 2000)	Khujairok stream, a tributary of the Yu River, at Moreh, near the adjoining borderland areas of Manipur
2058	<i>Laubuka latens</i> Knight, 2015	F	KA	(Knight 2015)	Channel, 200 meters downstream of branching from the main river, Cauvery River at Gandehosahalli, Karnataka

2059	<i>Laubuka laubuca</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ, UK, MP, TL, CG, JH, AS, ML, AR, NL, MN, MZ, TR	(Shaji et al. 2019, Karmakar & Das 2005, Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Hembrom & Bodra 2021, Kar & Sen 2007)	Ponds in northern parts of Bengal
2060	<i>Laubuka parafasciata</i> Lalramliana, Vanlalhlimpaia & Singh, 2017	F	MZ	(Lalramliana et al. 2017)	Sala River, a tributary of Kaladan River, in the vicinity of Lungpuk, Siaha District, Mizoram
2061	<i>Laubuka trevori</i> Knight, 2015	F	KA	(Knight 2015)	Streams in Yemmemaadu, Coorg, Karnataka
2062	<i>Opsarius ardens</i> (Knight, Rai, d'Souza & Vijaykrishnan, 2015)	F	KA	(Knight et al. 2015)	Swarna River, Karnataka
2063	<i>Opsarius arunachalensis</i> (Nath, Dam & Kumar, 2010)	F	AR	(Nath et al. 2010)	Agari River mouth, D'Ering Memorial Wildlife Sanctuary, near Pasighat, East Siang District, Arunachal Pradesh
2064	<i>Opsarius bakeri</i> (Day, 1865)	F	AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, TL, AS, MN, MZ, TR	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar et al. 2012, Kar & Sen 2007)	Mundikyum, Cochin, Kerala
2065	<i>Opsarius barna</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, AP, KA, MH, HP, UK, RJ, MP, TL, CG, JH, SK, AS, ML, AR, MN, MZ, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar 2006, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sharma & Dhanze 2018, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Tudu et al. 2022, Kar & Sen 2007)	Brahmaputra River, Goalpara, Assam
2066	<i>Opsarius barnoides</i> (Vinciguerra, 1890)	F	AS, MN, MZ, TR	(Kar & Sen 2007)	
2067	<i>Opsarius bendelisis</i> (Hamilton, 1807)	F	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ, HP, PU, UK, HY, RJ, MP, TL,	(Shaji et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2011, Sen 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar	Mysore, Karnataka

			CG, JH, SK, AS, ML, AR, NL, MN, MZ, TR	2006, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Sharma & Dhanze 2018, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Brraich & Saini 2019, Hembrom & Bodra 2021, Kar & Sen 2007)	
2068	<i>Opsarius canarensis</i> Jerdon, 1849	F	KA	(Rema Devi et al. 2013)	Karnataka
2069	<i>Opsarius chatricensis</i> (Selim & Vishwanath, 2002)	F	MN	(Selim & Vishwanath 2002)	Chatrikong River, Ukhrul District, 150 kilometers from Imphal, Manipur
2070	<i>Opsarius cocsa</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB	(Hamilton 1822)	Sanashygotia, West Bengal
2071	<i>Opsarius cyanochlorus</i> (Plamoottil & Vineeth, 2020)	F	KL	(Plamoottil & Vineeth 2020)	Water stream (Eramkunnuchaal) at Chully, Kasargod, Kerala
2072	<i>Opsarius dimorphicus</i> (Tilak & Husain, 1990)	F	UK, UP, TR	(Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Kar & Sen 2007)	Song River, easatern Doon Valley, Rajaji National Park, District Dehra Doon, Uttar Pradesh
2073	<i>Opsarius dogarsinghi</i> (Hora, 1921)	F	AS, MN, TR	(Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Kar & Sen 2007)	Etok stream near Chanderkhong, southern watershed of the Naga Hills, Manipur, Assam
2074	<i>Opsarius gatensis</i> (Valenciennes, 1844)	F	TN, KL, KA, MH, MP, MN, TR	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Barman 2002, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Peninsular India
2075	<i>Opsarius howesi</i> (Barman, 1986)	F	WB	(Barman et al. 2011)	Stream near Sulkapara, Jalpaiguri District, West Bengal
2076	<i>Opsarius kamjongensis</i> (Arunkumar, Thoibi & Jajo 2023)	F	MN	(Arunkumar et al. 2023)	Taret-lok River at Lunbung, Kamjong District, Manipur
2077	<i>Opsarius kanaensis</i> Arunkumar & Moyon, 2017	F	MN	(Arunkumar & Moyon 2017)	Kana River at Sajik-Tampak, Chakpikarong of Chandel, Yu River basin about 43 km towards South from district headquarter,

					Chandel from Chandel Bazar, Chandel District, Manipur
2078	<i>Opsarius lairokensis</i> (Arunkumar & Tombi Singh, 2000)	F	MN	(Arunkumar & Tombi Singh 2000)	Lairok Maru, Moreh, Chandel district, Manipur
2079	<i>Opsarius maculatus</i> McClelland, 1839	F	WB	(McClelland 1839)	Ganges & Brahmaputra rivers, West Bengal
2080	<i>Opsarius malabaricus</i> Jerdon, 1849	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	North Malabar
2081	<i>Opsarius ngawa</i> (Vishwanath & Manojkumar, 2002)	F	MN	(Vishwanath & Manojkumar 2002)	Sherou River, tributary of Manipur River, 24°18'N, 93°54'E, 83 kilometers south of Imphal, Manipur
2082	<i>Opsarius ornatus</i> (Sauvage, 1883)	F	MN	(Karmakar & Das 2005a)	
2083	<i>Opsarius pectoralis</i> (Husain, 2012)	F	UK, UP	(Uniyal & Uniyal 2021)	Tons river, Haripur near Kalasi, District Dehradun
2084	<i>Opsarius profundus</i> (Mayanglambam & Vishwanath, 2012)	F	MZ	(Mayanglambam & Vishwanath 2012)	Koladyne River at Kolchaw, 22°23'N, 92°57'E, Lawntlai District, Mizoram
2085	<i>Opsarius radiolatus</i> (Günther, 1868)	F	TR	(Barman 2002)	Gumti River, Udaypur subdivision, South Tripura District
2086	<i>Opsarius sajikensis</i> Moyon & Arunkumar, 2019	F	MN	(Moyon & Arunkumar 2019)	Kana River at Sajik-Tampak near Molnaum village, Yu river basin, about 43 km towards South from district headquarter Chandel, Chandel Bazar, Chandel district, Manipur

2087	<i>Opsarius shacra</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, HP, PU, UK, MP, SK, AS, ML, AR, NL, MN, MZ, TR	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Bagra et al. 2009, Barman 2002, Karmakar 2006, Sharma 2007, Sharma & Dhanze 2018, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Brraich & Saini 2019, Kar & Sen 2007)	Kosi river, Uttarpradesh
2088	<i>Opsarius tileo</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, UP, MP, AS, ML, AR, NL, TR	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Bagra et al. 2009, Barman 2002, Sharma 2007)	Kosi river, Uttarpradesh
2089	<i>Raiamas bola</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, GJ, HP, UK, HY, UP, RJ, MP, JH, AS, ML, AR, MN, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Bagra et al. 2009, Barman 2002, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Sharma & Dhanze 2018, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a, Tudu et al. 2022)	Brahmaputra River, Goalpara, Assam
2090	<i>Raiamas guttatus</i> (Day, 1870)	F	AS, MN	(Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985)	
2091	<i>Rasbora ataenia</i> Plamoottil, 2016	F	KL	(Plamoottil 2016b)	Small freshwater stream at Alappuzha, Kerala
2092	<i>Rasbora caverii</i> (Jerdon, 1849)	F	AP, TN, KA, GA, TL	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Yadav 2008)	Kaveri River at Srirangapattana
2093	<i>Rasbora dandia</i> (Valenciennes, 1844)	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	
2094	<i>Rasbora daniconius</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KA, GA, MH, GJ, HP, PU, UK, HY, DL, RJ, MP, TL, CG, JH, AS, ML, AR, MN, TR	(Rajan et al. 2013, Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Yadav 2008, Sharma & Dhanze 2018, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Brraich & Saini 2019, Tudu et al. 2022)	Southern Bengal
2095	<i>Rasbora hobelmani</i> Kottelat, 1984	F	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2096	<i>Rasbora kobonensis</i> Chaudhuri, 1913	F	AS	(Sen 1985)	Brahmaputra River, Kobo, Abor Hills, Assam
2097	<i>Rasbora labiosa</i> Mukerji, 1935	F	KA, MH	(Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Nasik, Maharashtra
2098	<i>Rasbora microcephalus</i> (Jerdon, 1849)	F	TN	(Jerdon 1849)	Mamallapuram, Tamil Nadu
2099	<i>Rasbora ornata</i> Vishwanath & Laisram, 2005	F	MN	(Vishwanath & Laisram 2005)	Lokchao River, a tributary of the Yu River (Chindwin drainage),

					Moreh, Manipur
2100	<i>Rasbora rasbora</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, AP, KA, GA, MH, MP, TL, AS, ML, NL, MN, MZ	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Yadav 2008, Kar & Sen 2007)	Ponds of Bengal
2101	<i>Salmostoma acinaces</i> (Valenciennes, 1844)	F	OD, TN, KL, KA, MH, MP, TL, NL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Karmakar & Das 2005, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Kaveri drainage, Mysore
2102	<i>Salmostoma bacaila</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	WB, OD, AP, TN, MH, GJ, HP, PU, UK, HY, DL, UP, RJ, MP, TL, CG, JH, AS, ML, AR, NL, MN, MZ, TR	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Husain 1997, Barman 2002, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Sharma & Dhanze 2018, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a, Brraich & Saini 2019, Hembrom & Bodra 2021, Kar & Sen 2007)	Freshwater rivers of Gangetic province
2103	<i>Salmostoma balookee</i> (Sykes, 1839)	F	OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, UP, TL, AS, TR	(Shaji et al. 2019, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Sen 1985, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar et al. 2012, Mishra et al. 2021a)	Deccan
2104	<i>Salmostoma belachi</i> Jayaraj, Krishna Rao, Ravichandra Reddy, Shakuntala & Devaraj, 1999	F	KA	(Rema Devi et al. 2013)	Nelligudda reservoir, 35 kilometers from Bangalore
2105	<i>Salmostoma boopis</i> (Day, 1874)	F	OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ, MP, TL, MN	(Shaji et al. 2019, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Yadav 2008)	South Canara, Karnataka
2106	<i>Salmostoma horai</i> (Silas, 1951)	F	WB, AP, KA, MH, HY, TL	(Mogalekar et al. 2017, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar et al. 2012, Bhatnagar et al. 2016)	Cauvery River, Coorg, Mysore
2107	<i>Salmostoma novacula</i> (Valenciennes, 1838)	F	TN, KA, MH, TL	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Prasad & Srinivasulu 2021, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Chennai
2108	<i>Salmostoma orissaense</i> Bănărescu, 1968	F	OD	(Bănărescu 1968)	Lower Mahannadi, Orissa

2109	<i>Salmostoma phulo</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, AP, KA, MH, PU, UK, DL, RJ, MP, TL, CG, JH, AS, ML, AR, MN, MZ, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman 1993, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Kaur et al. 2017, Tudu et al. 2022, Kar & Sen 2007)	Brahmaputra River at Goalpara, Assam
2110	<i>Salmostoma punjabense</i> (Day, 1872)	F	PU	(Kapoor et al. 2002)	
2111	<i>Salmostoma sardinella</i> (Valenciennes, 1844)	F	WB, MH, MZ	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Karmakar et al. 2012, Kar & Sen 2007)	
2112	<i>Salmostoma sladoni</i> (Day, 1870)	F	No specific location	(Devi & Indra 2012)	
2113	<i>Salmostoma untrahi</i> (Day, 1869)	F	OD, AP, TN, KA, MH, TL	(Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Mahanadi
2114	<i>Securricula gora</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, HP, DL, RJ, MP, BR, AS, ML, AR, MN, MZ, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Bagra et al. 2009, Husain 1997, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Jagtap 2013, Murugan & Prabakaran 2012, Kar & Sen 2007)	Brahmaputra River at Goalpara, Assam
Family: Nemacheilidae Regan, 1911					
2115	<i>Aborichthys bajpaii</i> Singh & Kosygin, 2022	F	AR	(Singh & Kosygin 2022)	A stream of Siang River near Ramsing Village, Brahmaputra River basin, Upper Siang District, Arunachal Pradesh
2116	<i>Aborichthys barapensis</i> Nanda & Tamang, 2021	F	AR	(Nanda & Tamang 2021)	Barap stream near Lazu Village, Brahmaputra River basin, Arunachal Pradesh
2117	<i>Aborichthys cataracta</i> Arunachalam, Raja, Punniyam & Mayden, 2014	F	AR	(Arunachalam et al. 2014b)	Arunachal Pradesh, stream joining with Ranga River, Hong Village, Upper Subanshri District, 27°32'766"N, 93°51'57E
2118	<i>Aborichthys elongatus</i> Hora, 1921	F	WB, SK, AS, ML, AR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Bagra et al. 2009, Karmakar 2006)	Reang River, Darjeeling, West Bengal
2119	<i>Aborichthys garoensis</i> Hora,	F	WB, AS,	(Sen 1985, 1995, Bagra et al. 2009)	Tura, Garo Hills,

	1925		ML, AR		Meghalaya
2120	<i>Aborichthys iphipaniensis</i> Kosygin, Gurumayum, Singh & Chowdhury, 2019	F	AR	(Kosygin et al. 2019)	Iphipani River at Roing, Lower Dibang Valley, Arunachal Pradesh
2121	<i>Aborichthys kailashi</i> Shangningam, Kosygin, Sinha & Gurumayum, 2019	F	AR	(Shangningam et al. 2019a)	Pange River at Arolenching, Ziro, Brahmaputra basin, Lower Subansiri District, Arunachal Pradesh
2122	<i>Aborichthys kempfi</i> Chaudhuri, 1913	F	WB, AS, ML, AR	(Mogalekar et al. 2017, Sen 1985, 1995, Bagra et al. 2009)	Egar stream between Renging & Rotung, Dihang River near Yembung, & Sirpo River near Renging, Abor Hills
2123	<i>Aborichthys palinensis</i> Nanda & Tamang, 2021	F	AR	(Nanda & Tamang 2021a)	Tributary of the Palin River, upper Brahmaputra River basin, Kra Daadi District, Arunachal Pradesh
2124	<i>Aborichthys pangensis</i> Shangningam, Kosygin, Sinha & Gurumayum, 2019	F	AR	(Shangningam et al. 2019a)	Pange River at Arolenching, Ziro, Brahmaputra basin, Lower Subansiri District, Arunachal Pradesh
2125	<i>Aborichthys tikaderi</i> Barman, 1985	F	AR	(Bagra et al. 2009)	Arunachal Pradesh
2126	<i>Aborichthys uniobarensis</i> Nanda, Machahary, Tamang & Das, 2021	F	AR	(Nanda et al. 2021)	Senkhi stream, near Police Colony, Vivek Vihar, Itana-gar, upper Brahmaputra River basin, Papum pare District, Arunachal Pradesh

2127	<i>Aborichthys verticauda</i> Arunachalam, Raja, Punniyam & Mayden, 2014	F	AR	(Arunachalam et al. 2014b)	Arunachal Pradesh, tributary of Ranga River, 7 km away from Hola camp, Lower Subanshri District, 27°18'50.7"N, 93°57'51.2"E
2128	<i>Aborichthys waikhomi</i> Kosygin, 2012	F	AR	(Kosygin 2012)	Arunachal Pradesh, Bulbulia stream near Bulbulia a tributary of Noa-Dihing river
2129	<i>Acanthocobitis pavonacea</i> (McClelland, 1839)	F	AS	(McClelland 1839)	Assam
2130	<i>Indoreonectes evezardi</i> (Day, 1872)	F	OD, AP, KA, GA, MH, GJ, MP, TL	(Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Yadav 2008, Kazi et al. 2018)	Pune, India
2131	<i>Indoreonectes keralensis</i> (Rita & Nalbant, 1978)	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Pampadampara, Kerala
2132	<i>Indoreonectes neeleshi</i> Kumkar, Pise, Gorule, Verma & Kalous, 2021	F	MH	(Kumar et al. 2021)	Mula River, Godavari River system, Harishchandragad, Maharashtra
2133	<i>Indoreonectes rajeevi</i> Kumkar, Pise, Gorule, Verma & Kalous, 2021	F	MH	(Kumar et al. 2021)	Hiranyakeshi River, Krishna River system, Amboli, Maharashtra
2134	<i>Indoreonectes telanganaensis</i> Prasad, Srinivasulu, Srinivasulu, Anoop & Dahanukar, 2020	F	TL	(Prasad & Srinivasulu 2021)	Maisamma Loddi, Kawal Tiger Reserve, Mancheriyal District, Telangana State
2135	<i>Mustura chhintuipuiensis</i> (Lalramliana, Lalhlimpaia, Solo & Vanramliana, 2016)	F	MZ	(Lalramliana et al. 2016)	Ngengpui River, a tributary of Kaladan River, in the vicinity of Khawmawi, Lunglei district, Mizoram
2136	<i>Mustura chindwinensis</i> (Lokeshwor & Vishwanath, 2012)	F	MN	(Lokeshwor & Vishwanath 2012)	River at Moreh, 24°15'03"N, 94°17'59"E, Chindwin basin, Manipur

2137	<i>Mustura dikrongensis</i> (Lokeshwor & Vishwanath, 2012)	F	AR	(Lokeshwor & Vishwanath 2012a)	Arunachal Pradesh: from Dikarong river at Doimukh (Brahmaputra basin), 27°08'19"N, 93°44'51"E
2138	<i>Mustura daral</i> Rameshori, Chinglemba, Darshan & Vishwanath, 2022	F	AR	(Rameshori et al. 2022)	Siang River at Pasighat, Brahmaputra basin, East Siang District, Arunachal Pradesh
2139	<i>Mustura harkishorei</i> (Das & Darshan, 2017)	F	AR	(Das & Darshan 2017)	Dibang River, Brahmaputra basin, Lower Dibang Valley district, Arunachal Pradesh
2140	<i>Mustura prashadi</i> (Hora, 1921)	F	AS, AR, MN	(Bagra et al. 2009, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985)	Naga Hills
2141	<i>Mustura subhashi</i> Choudhury, Das, Bharali, Sarma, Tyagi, Lal & Sarma, 2021	F	AR	(Choudhury et al. 2021)	Unnamed tributary of Dikal River at Upper Dikalmukh, Brahmaputra basin, East Kameng District, Arunachal Pradesh
2142	<i>Mustura taretensis</i> Chinglemba, Rameshori & Vishwanath, 2021	F	MN	(Chinglemba et al. 2021)	Taret River, a tributary of the Yu River, Chindwin River drainage, Tengnoupal District, Manipur
2143	<i>Mustura tigrina</i> (Lokeshwor & Vishwanath, 2012)	F	AR	(Lokeshwor & Vishwanath 2012b)	Phungrei, Changa River (the Chindwin drainage), 25°12'26"N, 94°31'35"E, Ukhrul district, Manipur
2144	<i>Mustura tuivaiensis</i> (Lokeshwor, Vishwanath & Shanta, 2012)	F	AR	(Lokeshwor et al. 2012)	Tuiva River at Likhailok, 24°04'41"N, 93°33'67"E, Brahmaputra River basin, Churchandpur

					district, Manipur
2145	<i>Mustura walongensis</i> (Tamang & Sinha, 2016)	F	AR	(Tamang & Sinha 2016)	Arunachal Pradesh, small diverted water course of Lohit River (Brahmaputra River basin) at Walong
2146	<i>Mesonoemacheilus guentheri</i> (Day, 1867)	F	TN, KL, KA	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Shaji et al. 2019, Rema Devi et al. 2013)	Rapids on the slopes of the Neilgherry hills, India
2147	<i>Mesonoemacheilus herrei</i> Nalbant & Bănărescu, 1982	F	TN, KL, AS	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Sen 1985)	Periyar River, Malappara, Kerala
2148	<i>Mesonoemacheilus menoni</i> (Zacharias & Minimol, 1999)	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Periyar River, Malappara, Kerala
2149	<i>Mesonoemacheilus pambarensis</i> (Rema Devi & Indra, 1994)	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Pambar River at border of Chinnar Sanctuary, Kerala
2150	<i>Mesonoemacheilus periyarensis</i> (Kurup & Radhakrishnan, 2005)	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Pambar River at border of Chinnar Sanctuary, Kerala
2151	<i>Mesonoemacheilus petrubanarescui</i> (Menon, 1984)	F	KA	(Rema Devi et al. 2013)	Netravati River, Dharmasthala, Karnataka
2152	<i>Mesonoemacheilus pulchellus</i> (Day, 1873)	F	TN, KL, KA	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013)	Pambar River at border of Chinnar Sanctuary, Kerala
2153	<i>Mesonoemacheilus remadeviae</i> Shaji, 2002	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Pambar River at border of Chinnar Sanctuary, Kerala
2154	<i>Mesonoemacheilus tambaraparniensis</i> (Menon, 1987)	F	TN	(Menon 1987)	ambaraparni basin near Courtalam, Tamil Nadu
2155	<i>Mesonoemacheilus triangularis</i> (Day, 1865)	F	TN, KL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	Cochin, Kerala
2156	<i>Neonoemacheilus assamensis</i> (Menon, 1987)	F	WB	(Mogalekar et al. 2017)	Pagladia River, Assam
2157	<i>Neonoemacheilus labeosus</i> (Kottelat, 1982)	F	AS	(Talwar & Jhingran 1991)	

2158	<i>Neonoemacheilus morehensis</i> Arunkumar, 2000	F	MN	(Arunkumar 2000a)	Lokchao River at Moreh, Manipur
2159	<i>Neonoemacheilus peguensis</i> (Hora, 1929)	F	MN	(Vishwanath & Laisram 2001)	
2160	<i>Nemachilichthys ruppelli</i> (Sykes, 1839)	F	KA, MH, GJ, MP	(Rema Devi et al. 2013, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000)	Deccan, Mula-Mutha River
2161	<i>Nemacheilus anguilla</i> Annandale, 1919	F	AP, KL, KA, MH, GJ, MP, TL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000)	Yenna River at Medha, Satara District, Maharashtra
2162	<i>Nemacheilus corica</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, HP, UK, DL, AS, ML	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Husain 1997, Jagtap 2013, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021)	Mainayi, Kosi River
2163	<i>Nemacheilus kaimurensis</i> Husain & Tilak, 1998	F	UP	(Husain & Tilak 1998)	Kanhar stream, near village of Kota, Chopan, District Sonbhadra, Uttar Pradesh
2164	<i>Nemacheilus longistriatus</i> Kottelat, 1990	F	TN	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	
2165	<i>Nemacheilus monilis</i> Hora, 1921	F	TN, KL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	Mettupalayam, base of Nilgiris, Tamilnadu
2166	<i>Nemacheilus shehensis</i> Tilak, 1990	F	LD	(Tilak 1990)	Irrigation canal at Sheh, nearly 12 Kms. east of Leh (Ladakh)
2167	<i>Nemacheilus stigmofasciatus</i> Arunachalam & Muralidharan, 2009	F	KA	(Arunachalam & Muralidharan 2009)	Thuttinjet, Seethanathi River, Karnataka
2168	<i>Paracanthocobitis aurea</i> (Day, 1872)	F	OD	(Chanda & Jana 2021)	Jabbalpur
2169	<i>Paracanthocobitis botia</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	KA, GA, MH, GJ, HP, PU, UK, HY, UP, RJ, TL, CG, BR, JH, AS, ML, AR, NL, MN, MZ	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Sen 1995, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Yadav 2008, Sharma & Dhanze 2018, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a, Brraich & Saini 2019, Tudu et al. 2022, Kumari & Yadav 2020)	Northeastern Bengal, Brahmapatra River
2170	<i>Paracanthocobitis hijumensis</i> Rime, Tamang & Das, 2022	F	AR	(Rime et al. 2022)	Hijum River, an eastward-flowing tributary of the Siang River, at Pidi Rime village, West Siang District, Arunachal Pradesh
2171	<i>Paracanthocobitis linypha</i> Singer & Page, 2015	F	MN	(Rameshori et al. 2021)	

2172	<i>Paracanthocobitis urophthalma</i> (Günther, 1868)	F	OD	(Chanda & Jana 2021)	
2173	<i>Paracanthocobitis marmorata</i> Singer, Pfeiffer & Page, 2017	F	AS, AR	(Singer et al. 2017, Arunkumar & Moyon 2019a)	Barak drainage, Assam
2174	<i>Paracanthocobitis mooreh</i> (Sykes, 1839)	F	OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ, TL	(Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar et al. 2012, Shaji et al. 2019)	Mula-Mutha River, Pune
2175	<i>Paracanthocobitis rubidipinnis</i> (Blyth, 1860)	F	KA	(Chandrashekhariah et al. 2000)	
2176	<i>Paracanthocobitis zonalternans</i> (Blyth, 1860)	F	AS, AR, MN	(Bagra et al. 2009, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985)	
2177	<i>Paraschistura bampurensis</i> (Nikolskii, 1900)	F	RJ	(Talwar & Jhingran 1991)	
2178	<i>Paraschistura montana</i> (McClelland, 1838)	F	HP, UK, DL, TR	(Husain 1997, Barman 2002, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021)	Mountain streams of Simla, Himachal Pradesh
2179	<i>Paraschistura punjabensis</i> (Hora, 1923)	F	J&K, HP	(Bhat et al. 2020, Sharma & Dhanze 2018)	
2180	<i>Physoschistura elongata</i> Sen & Nalbant, 1982	F	GA, AS, ML	(Sen 1985, 1995, Yadav 2008)	Barapani, near Shillong, Meghalaya
2181	<i>Physoschistura ranikhetensis</i> Singh & Das, 2019	F	UK	(Singh & Das 2019)	Stream at Dhobighat near Ranikhet, Ganga River basin, Almora district, Uttarakhand
2182	<i>Schistura aizawlensis</i> Lalramliana, 2012	F	MZ	(Lalramliana 2012)	Mizoram, Muthi River, a tributary of Tuirial River in vicinity of Zembawk, Aizawl, 13°44'54"N, 62°45'27"
2183	<i>Schistura altipedunculata</i> (Bănărescu & Nalbant, 1968)	F	KA	(Bănărescu & Nalbant 1968)	Mandurli, northern Canara, Kati River drainage, 15°05'N, 74°25'E, northern Karnataka
2184	<i>Schistura andrewi</i> Solo, Lalramliana, Lalronunga & Lalnuntluanga, 2014	F	MZ	(Solo et al. 2014)	Mizoram, Mat River, tributary of Kaladan River
2185	<i>Schistura beavani</i> (Günther, 1868)	F	WB, OD, TN, UK, MP, AS, ML, AR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Bagra et al. 2009, Sharma 2007, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021)	Kossye River, Uttar Pradesh
2186	<i>Schistura bhimachari</i> (Hora, 1937)	F	KA	(Rema Devi et al. 2013)	Thunga River at Shimoga,

					Karnataka
2187	<i>Schistura carletoni</i> (Fowler, 1924)	F	HP, AS	(Fowler 1924, Kar & Sen 2007)	Kullu Valley
2188	<i>Schistura chindwinica</i> (Tilak & Husain, 1990)	F	MN	(Karmakar & Das 2005a)	Brahmaputra basin, Lanjha stream, Manipur
2189	<i>Schistura cincticauda</i> (Blyth, 1860)	F	AR	(Bagra et al. 2009)	
2190	<i>Schistura dayi</i> (Hora, 1935)	F	OD, AP, MH, TL	(Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman 1993, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Near Raniganj, Chota-Nagpur & Northwest Provinces
2191	<i>Schistura denisoni</i> (Day, 1867)	F	OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ, HP, RJ, MP, TL, CG	(Shaji et al. 2019, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sharma & Dhanze 2018, Kazi et al. 2018)	Bhawany River, base of Nilgiris
2192	<i>Schistura devdevi</i> (Hora, 1935)	F	WB, SK, ML, AR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1995, Bagra et al. 2009, Karmakar 2006)	Eastern Himalayas, small streams below Darjeeling & Sikkim
2193	<i>Schistura doonensis</i> (Tilak & Husain, 1977)	F	UK, UP	(Uniyal & Uniyal 2021)	Small stream near village of Kandholi, on way to Doonga District, Dehra Dun, Uttar Pradesh
2194	<i>Schistura fasciata</i> Lokeshwor & Vishwanath, 2011	F	WB, MN	(Chakraborty 2018)	Barak River at western side of Maram Hill, Senapati District, Manipur
2195	<i>Schistura ferruginea</i> Lokeshwor & Vishwanath, 2013	F	MN	(Lokeshwor & Vishwanath 2013)	Rivulet of Barak River at Don Bosco College campus, Maram, Manipur
2196	<i>Schistura gangetica</i> (Menon, 1987)	F	UK, UP	(Uniyal & Uniyal 2021)	Alaknanda River (Ganges River basin) at Srinagar, Garhwal, Uttar Pradesh
2197	<i>Schistura himachalensis</i> (Menon, 1987)	F	HP	(Sharma & Dhanze 2018)	Himachal Pradesh, Kangra
2198	<i>Schistura hiranyakeshi</i> Praveenraj, Thackeray & Balasubramanian, 2020	F	MH	(Praveenraj et al. 2020a)	Temple pond fed by a natural spring from a laterite cave system, origin of

					the Hiranyakeshi River, Sindhudurg district, Amboli, Maharashtra
2199	<i>Schistura horai</i> (Menon, 1952)	F	HP, PU	(Sharma & Dhanze 2018)	Bener Khand, south of Kangra, Kangra Valley, Punjab
2200	<i>Schistura kangrae</i> (Menon, 1952)	F	HP	(CoF 2023)	Kangra Valley, Baijnath, Kangra District, Himachal Pradesh
2201	<i>Schistura kangjupkhulensis</i> (Hora, 1921)	F	AS, AR, NL, MN	(Karmakar & Das 2005, 2005a, Bagra et al. 2009, Sen 1985)	Manipur valley
2202	<i>Schistura khugae</i> Vishwanath & Shanta, 2004	F	MN	(Vishwanath & Shanta 2004)	Khuga River, Churachandpur District, Manipur
2203	<i>Schistura kodaguensis</i> (Menon, 1987)	F	KA	(Rema Devi et al. 2013)	Kotu Hola, near Merkara, Karnataka
2204	<i>Schistura koladynensis</i> Lokeshwor & Vishwanath, 2012	F	MZ	(Lokeshwor & Vishwanath 2012c)	Mizoram, Lawntlai District, Koladyne River at Kolchaw, 22°23'45"N, 92°55'56"E
2205	<i>Schistura larketensis</i> Choudhury, Mukhim, Basumatary, Warbah & Sarma, 2017	F	ML	(Choudhury et al. 2017)	Krem Khung about 1.5 km from Larket village, East Jaintia Hills District, Meghalaya
2206	<i>Schistura liyaiensis</i> Lokeshwor & Vishwanath, 2014	F	MN	(Lokeshwor & Vishwanath 2014)	Barak River in the vicinity of Liyai village (Barak-Surma-Meghna basin), Senapati District, Manipur
2207	<i>Schistura maculosa</i> Lalronunga, Lalnuntluanga & Lalramliana, 2013	F	MZ	(Lalronunga et al. 2013a)	Mizoram, Pharsih River, a tributary of Tuivai River (Barak drainage) in the vicinity of Kawlbem, Champhai District
2208	<i>Schistura manipurensis</i> (Chaudhuri, 1912)	F	AS, AR, NL, MN	(Karmakar & Das 2005, 2005a, Bagra et al. 2009, Sen 1985)	Manipur

2209	<i>Schistura minuta</i> Vishwanath & Shanta Kumar, 2006	F	MN	(Vishwanath & Shanta Kumar 2006)	Lyei River, Noney, Tamenglong District, Manipur
2210	<i>Schistura mizoramensis</i> Lalramliana, Lalronunga, Vanramliana & Lalthanzara, 2014	F	MZ	(Lalramliana et al. 2014a)	Tuirivang River, tributary of Tuirial River, Barak drainage, Mizoram
2211	<i>Schistura mukambbikaensis</i> (Menon, 1987)	F	KA	(Rema Devi et al. 2013)	Kashi stream, Mujambbika [Mukambbika], Karnataka
2212	<i>Schistura multifasciata</i> (Day, 1878)	F	WB, MH, MP, SK, AS, ML, AR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Bagra et al. 2009, Karmakar 2006, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Darjeeling & Assam
2213	<i>Schistura nagaensis</i> (Menon, 1987)	F	NL	(Menon 1987)	Phodung River, tributary of Tizu River, Brahmaputra basin, Naga Hills, Nagaland
2214	<i>Schistura nagodiensis</i> Sreekantha, Gururaja, Rema Devi, Indra & Ramachandra, 2006	F	KA	(Rema Devi et al. 2013)	Sharavathi river, Algod, Shimoga, Karnataka
2215	<i>Schistura nebeshwari</i> Lokeshwor & Vishwanath, 2013	F	MZ	(Lokeshwor & Vishwanath 2013a)	Mizoram, Saiha District, from a stream at Phura village near Palak Lake (Koladyne basin)
2216	<i>Schistura nilgiriensis</i> (Menon, 1987)	F	TN, KL, KA	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013)	Wayanad, Kerala
2217	<i>Schistura obliquofascia</i> Lokeshwor, Barat, Sati, Darshan, Vishwanath & Mahanta, 2012	F	UK	(Lokeshwor et al. 2012a)	Uttarakhand State, Kalsa River at Chanfi, Ganga basin, 29°22'06" N, 79°34'44" E
2218	<i>Schistura papulifera</i> Kottelat, Harries & Proudlove, 2007	F	ML	(Kottelat et al. 2007)	Cave of Synrang Pamiang system, Maintia Hills, Krem Umsngat entrance, 25°11'14"N, 92°21'03"E, Meghalaya State
2219	<i>Schistura paucireticulata</i> Lokeshwor, Vishwanath & Kosygin, 2013	F	MZ	(Lokeshwor et al. 2013)	Mizoram: Aizawl District: Tuirial River near Aizawl (the Barak-Surma-Meghna river system)

2220	<i>Schistura phamhringi</i> Shangningam, Lokeshwor & Vishwanath, 2014	F	MN	(Lokeshwor & Vishwanath 2014)	Manipur, Chandel District: Dutah Stream, tributary of Yu River near Larong Village (Chindwin-Irrawaddy basin)
2221	<i>Schistura porocephala</i> Lokeshwor & Vishwanath, 2013	F	MZ	(Lokeshwor & Vishwanath 2013b)	Stream of Mat River near Thualthu, Lunglei district, Mizoram
2222	<i>Schistura rajasthanica</i> (Mathur & Yazdani, 1971)	F	RJ	(Mathur & Yazdani 1971)	Takhat Sagar, Kailana, Jodhpur, Rajasthan
2223	<i>Schistura rebuw</i> Choudhury, Dey, Bharali, Sarma & Vishwanath, 2019	F	AR	(Choudhury et al. 2019)	Pachai stream near Seppa, Kameng River drainage (Brahmaputra basin), East Kameng District, Arunachal Pradesh
2224	<i>Schistura reticulata</i> Vishwanath & Nebeshwar Sharma, 2004	F	MN	(Vishwanath & Nebeshwar Sharma 2004)	Maklang River, Ukhrul District, Manipur
2225	<i>Schistura reticulofasciata</i> (Singh & Bănărescu, 1982)	F	AS, ML	(Sen 1985, 1995)	Barani, near Shillong, Meghalaya
2226	<i>Schistura rosammai</i> (Sen, 2009)	F	AS	(Sen 2009)	Pabomukh, Subansiri River, Dhemaji District, Assam
2227	<i>Schistura rupecula</i> McClelland, 1838	F	WB, OD, MH, HP, UK, SK, AS, AR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Chanda & Jana 2021, Bagra et al. 2009, Sen 1985, Karmakar 2006, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sharma & Dhanze 2018, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021)	Simla, Himachal Pradesh
2228	<i>Schistura savona</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, MH, UK, MP, ML, AR, NL	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1995, Bagra et al. 2009, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021)	Kosi river of Nathpur, Uttar Pradesh
2229	<i>Schistura scaturigina</i> McClelland, 1839	F	WB, DL, ML, AR, MN, MZ, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1995, Bagra et al. 2009, Husain 1997, Barman 2002, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Kar & Sen 2007)	Assam
2230	<i>Schistura scyphovecteta</i> Lokeshwor & Vishwanath, 2013	F	MZ	(Lokeshwor & Vishwanath 2013a)	Ka-ao River near New Serkawr village (Koladyne basin), Saiha District, Mizoram

2231	<i>Schistura semiarmata</i> (Day, 1867)	F	TN, KL, KA, AS	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Sen 1985)	Bowany & Seegoor river at base of Nilgiri
2232	<i>Schistura sharavathiensis</i> Sreekantha, Gururaja, Rema Devi, Indra & Ramachandra, 2006	F	KA	(Rema Devi et al. 2013)	Sharavathi river, Kalkatte tributary, 1 kilometer above Dabbe Falls, Shimoga, Karnataka
2233	<i>Schistura sijuensis</i> (Menon, 1987)	F	ML	(Sen 1995)	Garo Hills, Meghalaya
2234	<i>Schistura sikmaiensis</i> (Hora, 1921)	F	MP, AS, ML, MN, MZ	(Sen 1995, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Sharma 2007, Kar & Sen 2007)	
2235	<i>Schistura singhi</i> (Menon, 1987)	F	NL	(Menon 1987)	Kiphire, Nagaland
2236	<i>Schistura striata</i> (Day, 1867)	F	OD, AP, KL, KA, MH, MP, TL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Wayanad, Kerala
2237	<i>Schistura syngkai</i> Choudhury, Mukhim, Dey, Warbah & Sarma, 2019	F	ML	(Choudhury et al. 2019a)	Twahdidoh Stream of Wahblei River near Seinduli village, Surma-Meghna basin, West Khasi Hills District, Meghalaya
2238	<i>Schistura tigrina</i> Vishwanath & Nebeshwar Sharma, 2005	F	MN	(Vishwanath & Nebeshwar Sharma 2005)	Barak River at Khunphung, Tami subdivision, Tamenglong District, Manipur
2239	<i>Schistura tirapensis</i> Kottelat, 1990	F	WB, AR, MZ	(Chakraborty 2018, Bagra et al. 2009, Kar & Sen 2007)	Arunachal Pradesh
2240	<i>Schistura vinciguerrae</i> (Hora, 1935)	F	MN, MZ, TR	(Vishwanath & Laisram 2001, Kar & Sen 2007)	
2241	<i>Schistura zonata</i> McClelland, 1839	F	AS	(McClelland 1839)	Upper Assam
2242	<i>Triplophysa drassensis</i> (Tilak, 1990)	F	LD	(Tilak 1990)	Stream near Drass, Ladakh
2243	<i>Triplophysa gracilis</i> (Day, 1877)	F	LD, SK	(Karmakar 2006, Tilak 1990)	
2244	<i>Triplophysa kashmirensis</i> (Hora, 1922)	F	J&K	(Bhat et al. 2020)	Verinag, Kukarnag & a small stream flowing from the Kashmir waterworks reservoir to the trout farm at Harwan
2245	<i>Triplophysa</i>	F	J&K	(Bhat et al. 2020)	Kashmir

	<i>marmorata</i> (Heckel, 1838)				
2246	<i>Triplophysa microps</i> (Steindachner, 1866)	F	LD, HP	(Sharma & Dhanze 2018, Tilak 1990)	Manechan in Rupshu, India, elevation about 16000 feet
2247	<i>Triplophysa panguri</i> (Hora, 1936)	F	LD, J&K	(Tilak 1990)	Pangur Tso & Tso Nyak [Upper Indus River], Kashmir
2248	<i>Triplophysa shehensis</i> Tilak, 1987	F	LD	(Menon 1987)	Ladakh
2249	<i>Triplophysa stewarti</i> (Hora,, 1922)	F	LD, SK	(Kapoor et al. 2002)	
2250	<i>Triplophysa stolickai</i> (Steindachner, 1866)	F	LD	(Tilak 1990)	Streams in Tsumureri Lake system, Ladakh
2251	<i>Triplophysa tenuicauda</i> (Steindachner, 1866)	F	LD	(Tilak 1990)	Hanle, Ladakh
2252	<i>Triplophysa yasinensis</i> (Alcock, 1898)	F	LD	(Tilak 1990)	Yasin River, Ladakh
Family: Psilorhynchidae Hora, 1926					
2253	<i>Psilorhynchus amplicephalus</i> Arunachalam, Muralidharan & Sivakumar, 2007	F	AS	(Arunachalam et al. 2007)	Balishwar river of Barak river basin at Malidor village, 24°14'24.1"N, 92°32'401"E, Silchar, Assam
2254	<i>Psilorhynchus arunachalensis</i> (Nebeshwar, Bagra & Das, 2007)	F	WB, AR	(Mogalekar et al. 2017)	Brahmaputra River system, Arunachal Pradesh
2255	<i>Psilorhynchus balitora</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, UK, DL, AS, ML, AR, NL, MZ, TR	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Vishwanath & Manojkumar 1995, Husain 1997, Barman 2002, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Kar & Sen 2007)	Rivers of north-east Bengal
2256	<i>Psilorhynchus breviminor</i> Conway & Mayden, 2008	F	MN	(Shangningam & Vishwanath 2014)	
2257	<i>Psilorhynchus bichomensis</i> Shangningam, Kosygin & Gopi, 2019	F	AR	(Shangningam et al. 2019b)	38 km from Seppa towards Ziro, East Kameng District, Arunachal Pradesh
2258	<i>Psilorhynchus chakpiensis</i> Shangningam & Vishwanath, 2013	F	MN	(Shangningam & Vishwanath 2013)	Manipur state, Chandel District, Chakpi River at Chakpikarong, 24°12'02.36"N, 93°54'50.36"E

2259	<i>Psilorhynchus hamiltoni</i> Conway, Dittmer, Jezisek & Ng, 2013	F	WB	(Conway et al. 2013)	West Bengal, Tista River at Trista Barrage, 26°45'1.0"N, 88°35'11.0"E, India, elevation 105 meters
2260	<i>Psilorhynchus homaloptera</i> Hora & Mukerji, 1935	F	AS, AR, MN	(Vishwanath & Manojkumar 1995, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985)	Brahmaputra drainage system, Naga Hills
2261	<i>Psilorhynchus kaladanensis</i> Lalramliana, Lalnuntluanga & Lalronunga, 2015	F	MZ	(Lalramliana et al. 2015)	Mizoram, Tuisi River, a tributary of Kaladan River in the vicinity of Khopai village
2262	<i>Psilorhynchus kamengensis</i> Dey, Choudhury, Mazumder, Bharali, Thaosen & Sarma, 2020	F	AR	(Dey et al. 2020a)	Tippi Naala stream at Tippi, Kameng River, Brahmaputra basin, West Kameng district, Arunachal Pradesh
2263	<i>Psilorhynchus khopai</i> Lalramliana, Solo, Lalronunga & Lalnuntluanga, 2014	F	MZ	(Lalramliana et al. 2014b)	Mizoram: Tuisi River, a tributary of Kaladan River in the vicinity of Khopai village, Saiha District
2264	<i>Psilorhynchus konemi</i> Shangningam & Vishwanath, 2016	F	MN	(Shangningam & Vishwanath 2016)	Chakpi River at Dujang, Chindwin River basin, Chandel district, Manipur
2265	<i>Psilorhynchus maculatus</i> Shangningam & Vishwanath, 2013	F	MN	(Shangningam & Vishwanath 2013a)	Challou River at Poi Village, Ukhrul District, Manipur
2266	<i>Psilorhynchus microphthalmus</i> Vishwanath & Manojkumar, 1995	F	AR	(Vishwanath & Manojkumar 1995)	85 kilometers south of Imphal, Manipur
2267	<i>Psilorhynchus nahlongthai</i> Dey, Choudhury, Mazumder, Thaosen & Sarma, 2020	F	AS	(Dey et al. 2020)	Dima Hasao district, Assam
2268	<i>Psilorhynchus nudithoracicus</i> Tilak & Husain, 1980	F	WB, UP, BR	(Conway et al. 2013, Arunachalam et al. 2018a)	Pilibhit District, western Uttar Pradesh
2269	<i>Psilorhynchus ngathanu</i> Shangningam & Vishwanath, 2013	F	MN	(Shangningam & Vishwanath 2014)	Dutah River at Larong Village, Chindwin basin, Chandel District, Manipur
2270	<i>Psilorhynchus pseudecheneis</i> Menon &	F	North eastern India	(Devi & Indra 2012)	

	Datta, 1964				
2271	<i>Psilorhynchus rowleyi</i> Hora & Misra, 1941	F	MN	(Shangningam & Vishwanath, 2014)	
2272	<i>Psilorhynchus sucatio</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, UP, AS, ML, AR, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Bagra et al. 2009, Barman 2002, Arunachalam et al. 2018a)	Northern Bengal
2273	<i>Psilorhynchus tenura</i> Arunachalam & Muralidharan, 2008	F	KA	(Arunachalam & Muralidharan 2008)	Tributary of Thunga River inside the Khudremukh National Park, 13°20'22.3"N, 75°10'19.4"E, Korkanhalla, Karnaaka
Family: Tincidae Jordan, 1878					
2274	<i>Tinca tinca</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	BF	TN	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	
Family: Xenocyprididae Günther, 1868					
2275	<i>Ctenopharyngodon idella</i> (Valenciennes, 1844)	BF	ANI, KL, NL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Shaji et al. 2019, Karmakar & Das 2005)	
2276	<i>Hypophthalmichthys molitrix</i> (Valenciennes, 1844)	BF	ANI, MP, NL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Karmakar & Das 2005, Sharma 2007)	
2277	<i>Hypophthalmichthys nobilis</i> (Richardson, 1845)	BF	ANI, MP, NL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Karmakar & Das 2005, Sharma 2007)	
Order: Elopiformes					
Family: Elopidae Valenciennes, 1847					
2278	<i>Elops machnata</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2279	<i>Elops saurus</i> Linnaeus, 1766	MB	OD, TN	(Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Megalopidae Jordan & Gilbert, 1883					
2280	<i>Megalops cyprinoides</i> (Broussonet, 1782)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Shaji et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Yennawar et al. 2015, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Nandi et al. 2008)	
Order: Gadiformes					
Family: Bregmacerotidae Gill, 1872					
2281	<i>Bregmaceros maclellandi</i> Thompson, 1840	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Ganges Delta, West Bengal
Family: Bathygadidae Jordan & Evermann, 1898					
2282	<i>Bathygadus furvescens</i> Alcock, 1894	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
2283	<i>Gadomus multifilis</i> (Günther, 1887)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
Family: Macrouridae Bonaparte, 1831					
2284	<i>Coelorinchus fasciatus</i> (Günther, 1878)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2285	<i>Coelorinchus flabellispinnis</i> (Alcock, 1894)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	

2286	<i>Coelorinchus macrolepis</i> Gilbert & Hubbs, 1920	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2287	<i>Coelorinchus parallelus</i> (Günther, 1877)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
2288	<i>Coelorinchus quadricristatus</i> (Alcock, 1891)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Andaman Sea, 11°31'40"N, 92°46'40"E
2289	<i>Coryphaenoides hextii</i> (Alcock, 1890)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	Laccadive Sea, 12°05'55"N, 71°33'30"E
2290	<i>Coryphaenoides hoskynii</i> (Alcock, 1890)	M	OD	(Pati et al. 2018)	Off Madras coast, India, 18°26'N, 85°24'E
2291	<i>Coryphaenoides macrolophus</i> (Alcock, 1889)	M	ANI, WB	(Rajan et al. 2013, Sanyal et al. 2012)	7 miles southeast by south of Ross Island, Port Blair, Andaman Islands
2292	<i>Coryphaenoides nasutus</i> Günther, 1877	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2293	<i>Coryphaenoides woodmasoni</i> (Alcock, 1890)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	Off Elicapeni Bank, Laccadive Sea, 11°12'47"N, 74°25'30"E
2294	<i>Hymenocephalus heterolepis</i> (Alcock, 1889)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Andaman Sea off Ross Island
2295	<i>Hymenocephalus italicus</i> Giglioli, 1884	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2296	<i>Malacocephalus laevis</i> (Lowe, 1843)	M	ANI, KA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Barman et al. 2012, 2013a)	
2297	<i>Nezumia brevirostris</i> (Alcock, 1889)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Andaman Sea, 7.5 miles east of North Cinque Island
2298	<i>Nezumia investigatoris</i> (Alcock, 1889)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Andaman Sea, all along andaman Chain
2299	<i>Nezumia propinqua</i> (Gilbert & Cramer, 1897)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2300	<i>Nezumia semiquincunciata</i> (Alcock, 1889)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Bay of Bengal, south by west of North Sentinel Island, Andaman Islands
2301	<i>Sphagemacrurus pumiliceps</i> (Alcock, 1894)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	Laccadive Sea, 7°05'45"N, 75°04'E
2302	<i>Ventrifossa petersonii</i> (Alcock, 1891)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Andaman Sea, 11°31'40"N, 92°46'06"E
Family: Moridae Moreau, 1881					
2303	<i>Lepidion inosimae</i> (Günther, 1887)	M	KL	(Vinu et al. 2017a)	

2304	<i>Physiculus argyropastus</i> Alcock, 1894	M	AP	(Alcock 1894)	Bay of Bengal, 43 kilometers southeast of Tangutur/Tanguturu, Andhra Pradesh State
2305	<i>Physiculus indicus</i> Babu, Ho, Mariyambi & Sivanpillai, 2022	M	LK	(Babu et al. 2022)	East coast of Kavaratti Island, Lakshadweep, India, 10°33'49.9"N, 72°39'4.0"E
2306	<i>Physiculus lakshadeepa</i> Babu, Ho, Mariyambi & Sivanpillai, 2022	M	LK	(Babu et al. 2022)	East coast of Kavaratti Island, Lakshadweep, India, 10°33'49.9"N, 72°39'4.0"E
2307	<i>Physiculus natalensis</i> Gilchrist, 1922	M	TN	(Kingston & Manikandavelu 2011)	
2308	<i>Physiculus roseus</i> Alcock, 1891	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Andaman Sea, 11°31'40"N, 92°46'40"E
Order: Gobiiformes					
Family: Eleotridae Bonaparte, 1835					
2309	<i>Belobranchus segura</i> Keith, Hadiaty & Lord, 2012	BF	ANI	(Rajan & Sreeraj 2014)	
2310	<i>Belobranchus belobranchus</i> (Valenciennes, 1837)	BF	ANI	(Rajan & Sreeraj 2014)	
2311	<i>Bostrychus sinensis</i> Lacepède, 1801	MBF	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2312	<i>Bunaka gyrinoides</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	MBF	ANI, AP, KL, KA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2019, Raghavan et al. 2020, Barman et al. 2012, 2013a)	
2313	<i>Butis amboinensis</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	MBF	ANI, GA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Barman et al. 2012, Talwar 1974)	
2314	<i>Butis butis</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2011, 2013a)	Botanical Garden of Calcutta, Ganges River estuary
2315	<i>Butis gymnopomus</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	BF	ANI, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Hariprakash et al. 2023)	
2316	<i>Butis humeralis</i> (Valenciennes, 1837)	MBF	WB, AP, TN	(Mishra et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Bay of Bengal
2317	<i>Butis koilomatodon</i> (Bleeker, 1849)	MBF	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mishra et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2012, Hariprakash et al. 2023)	
2318	<i>Eleotris feliceps</i> Blyth, 1960	F	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2319	<i>Eleotris fusca</i> (Forster, 1801)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA,	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2011, 2012, 2013a, Talwar 1974)	

			MH		
2320	<i>Eleotris lutea</i> Day, 1876	MB	ANI, WB, OD	(Rajan et al. 2013, Sanyal et al. 2012, Pati et al. 2018)	Andaman Islands, east of Bay of Bengal
2321	<i>Eleotris melanosoma</i> Bleeker, 1853	MBF	WB, OD, AP, TN	(Mishra et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2011, Pati et al. 2018)	
2322	<i>Eleotris oxycephala</i> Temminck & Schlegel, 1845	MBF	AP	(Padmavathi 2017)	
2323	<i>Giuris margaritaceus</i> (Valenciennes, 1837)	MBF	ANI, WB, AP, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2324	<i>Giuris tolsoni</i> (Bleeker, 1854)	MBF	ANI	(Mrinal & Sivaperuman 2023)	
2325	<i>Hypseleotris guentheri</i> (Bleeker, 1875)	MBF	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2326	<i>Incara multisquamatus</i> Rao, 1971	B	AP	(Mishra et al. 2019)	Godavari estuary, eastern India
2327	<i>Odonteleotris macrodon</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	BF	WB, AP	(Mishra et al. 2019)	Hooghly River at Calcutta
2328	<i>Ophiocara porocephalum</i> (Valenciennes, 1837)	MBF	ANI, WB, KA	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2013a)	
2329	<i>Oxyeleotris Urophthalmus</i> (Bleeker, 1851)	BF	WB	(Kumar et al. 2022)	
Family: Gobiidae Cuvier, 1816					
2330	<i>Acentrogobius caninus</i> (Valenciennes, 1837)	MBF	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mishra et al. 2019, Koumans 1941, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2331	<i>Acentrogobius dayi</i> Koumans, 1941	MBF	MH	(Mutsaddi & Bal 1974)	
2332	<i>Acentrogobius gracilis</i> (Bleeker, 1875)	MB	WB	(Sreeraj & Arya 2022)	
2333	<i>Acentrogobius griseus</i> (Day, 1876)	MBF	OD, TN, KL, KA, MH	(Mishra et al. 2019, Rao 1995, Barman et al. 2011, 2012, Biju et al. 2019)	Backwaters, Madras
2334	<i>Acentrogobius horai</i> (Fowler, 1925)	MBF	TN	(Parenti 2021)	Tuticorin, Madras
2335	<i>Acentrogobius janthinopterus</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	MBF	ANI, TN	(Rajan & Sreeraj 2014, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2336	<i>Acentrogobius madraspatensis</i> (Day, 1868)	MBF	ANI, OD, AP, TN, KL	(Mishra et al. 2019, Rao 1995, Rajan 2015, Biju et al. 2019)	
2337	<i>Acentrogobius moloanus</i> (Herre, 1927)	MB	WB	(Sreeraj & Arya 2022)	
2338	<i>Acentrogobius nebulosus</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	MBF	ANI, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2019, Roy et al. 2019)	
2339	<i>Acentrogobius viridipunctatus</i> (Valenciennes, 1837)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2019, Rao 1995, Barman et al. 2012, Sreeraj et al. 2023)	Mumbai
2340	<i>Amblyeleotris aurora</i> (Polunin & Lubbock, 1977)	M	ANI	(Allen & Erdmann 2012)	
2341	<i>Amblyeleotris diagonalis</i> Polunin &	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	

	Lubbock, 1979				
2342	<i>Amblyeleotris guttata</i> (Fowler, 1938)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2343	<i>Amblyeleotris downingi</i> Randall, 1994	M	ANI	(Rajan & Sreeraj 2015)	
2344	<i>Amblyeleotris fontanesii</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	M	ANI	(Allen & Erdmann 2012)	
2345	<i>Amblyeleotris gymnocephala</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	MB	ANI, WB, AP, TN	(Mishra et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2011, Allen & Erdmann 2012)	
2346	<i>Amblyeleotris latifasciata</i> Polunin & Lubbock, 1979	M	ANI	(Allen & Erdmann 2012)	
2347	<i>Amblyeleotris steinitzi</i> (Klausewitz, 1974)	M	ANI, TN	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2348	<i>Amblyeleotris wheeleri</i> (Polunin & Lubbock, 1977)	M	LK, TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Anto et al. 2024)	
2349	<i>Amblygobius albimaculatus</i> (Rüppell, 1830)	MB	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Barman et al. 2011)	
2350	<i>Amblygobius bynoensis</i> (Richardson, 1844)	MB	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2351	<i>Amblygobius decussatus</i> (Bleeker, 1855)	MB	ANI, TN	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2352	<i>Amblygobius nocturnus</i> (Herre, 1945)	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
2353	<i>Amblygobius phalaena</i> (Valenciennes, 1837)	M	ANI, TN	(Daniel et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2354	<i>Amblygobius semicinctus</i> (Bennett, 1833)	M	ANI, LK, GJ	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Babu et al. 2023, Vadher et al. 2024)	
2355	<i>Amblygobius sphynx</i> (Valenciennes, 1837)	MB	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2356	<i>Amblyotrypauchen arctocephalus</i> (Alcock, 1890)	M	WB, OD, AP	(Mishra et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018)	Off Máhánaddi Delta, Investigator station 69, depth 50 fathoms, off Visakhapatnam
2357	<i>Amoya dasi</i> (Talwar, Chatterjee & Dev Roy, 1982)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013, Parenti 2021)	Sippighat, South Andaman Island, Andaman Islands
2358	<i>Amoya veliensis</i> (Geevarghese & John, 1982)	B	KL	(Geevarghese & John 1982)	Veli estuary in Trivandrum, southwestern coast of Kerala
2359	<i>Apocryptes bato</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MBF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, TR	(Mishra et al. 2019, Sen & Dimos 2014, Barman et al. 2002, 2011, Biju et al. 2019)	Ganges River estuaries
2360	<i>Apocryptodon madurensis</i> (Bleeker, 1849)	MBF	WB, OD, AP, TN	(Mishra et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2011, Pati)	
2361	<i>Arcygobius baliurus</i> (Valenciennes, 1837)	MB	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2362	<i>Asterropteryx atripes</i> Shibukawa & Suzuki, 2002	M	ANI	(Allen & Erdmann 2012)	

2363	<i>Asterropteryx bipunctata</i> Allen & Munday, 1995	M	ANI	(Allen & Erdmann 2012)	
2364	<i>Asterropteryx ensifera</i> (Bleeker, 1874)	MB	ANI	(Allen & Erdmann 2012)	
2365	<i>Asterropteryx semipunctata</i> Rüppell, 1830	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Das & Mishra 2019, Rajan et al. 2021)	
2366	<i>Aulopareia cyanomos</i> (Bleeker, 1849)	MB	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, GJ	(Mishra et al. 2019, Koumans 1941, Barman et al. 2000, Sen et al. 2023)	
2367	<i>Aulopareia koumansii</i> (Herre, 1937)	M	ANI	(Rajan & Sreeraj 2014)	
2368	<i>Aulopareia ocellata</i> (Day, 1873)	M	MH, GJ	(Mishra et al. 2019, Parenti 2021, Koumans 1941)	Mumbai
2369	<i>Aulopareia unicolor</i> (Valenciennes, 1837)	MB	OD, AP, TN, MH	(Mishra et al. 2019, Rao 1995, Barman et al. 2011, Koumans 1941)	
2370	<i>Awaouichthys menoni</i> Chatterjee & Mishra, 2013	M	WB	(Chatterjee & Mishra 2013)	Patibonia Island, near Frasergunge, Gangetic delta
2371	<i>Awaous fluviatilis</i> (Rao, 1971)	MB	OD, AP, TN	(Mishra et al. 2019, Remadevi et al. 1996, Pati et al. 2018)	Gautami, Godavari estuary
2372	<i>Awaous grammepomus</i> (Bleeker, 1849)	BF	ANI, LK, WB, OD, TN, TL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Raghavan et al. 2020, Koumans 1941, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Pati et al. 2018, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016)	
2373	<i>Awaous guamensis</i> (Valenciennes, 1837)	MBF	ANI, OD, MZ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Sen & Dimos 2014, Pati et al. 2018)	
2374	<i>Awaous gutum</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MBF	WB, MH, GJ, UK	(Parenti 2021, Barman et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021)	
2375	<i>Awaous litturatus</i> (Steindachner, 1861)	MBF	TN	(Seth et al. 2023)	
2376	<i>Awaous melanocephalus</i> (Bleeker, 1849)	MBF	ANI, AP	(Rajan et al. 2013, Seth et al. 2023)	
2377	<i>Awaous motla</i> (Seth, Roy, Sura, Puval, Mishra & Mahapatra, 2023)	F	OD	(Seth et al. 2023)	Mahanadi River near Sonapur, Subarnapur district, Odisha
2378	<i>Awaous ocellaris</i> (Broussonet, 1782)	MBF	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2379	<i>Awaous personatus</i> (Bleeker, 1849)	F	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2380	<i>Awaous stamineus</i> (Valenciennes, 1842)	F	OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, MP	(Koumans 1941, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Sharma 2007)	
2381	<i>Bathygobius coalitus</i> (Bennett, 1832)	M	ANI, OD, AP	(Padmavathi 2017, Rajan et al. 2013, Pati et al. 2018)	
2382	<i>Bathygobius cocosensis</i> (Bleeker, 1854)	M	LK	(Sreeraj et al. 2022)	
2383	<i>Bathygobius cotticeps</i> (Steindachner, 1879)	M	LK, TN	(Sreeraj et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2384	<i>Bathygobius</i>	MB	KL	(Randall 1997)	Kovalam

	<i>cyclopterus</i> (Valenciennes, 1837)				
2385	<i>Bathygobius fuscus</i> (Rüppell, 1830)	MBF	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, GA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2011, 2012, Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Talwar 1974)	
2386	<i>Bathygobius niger</i> (Smith, 1960)	M	AP	(Parenti 2021)	
2387	<i>Bathygobius petrophilus</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	MB	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
2388	<i>Boleophthalmus birdsongi</i> Murdy, 1989	MB	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2389	<i>Boleophthalmus boddarti</i> (Pallas, 1770)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2019)	
2390	<i>Boleophthalmus dussumieri</i> Valenciennes, 1837	MBF	WB, OD, AP, TN, MH	(Mishra et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Mumbai
2391	<i>Brachyamblyopus brachysoma</i> (Bleeker, 1854)	BF	WB, OD	(Mishra et al. 2019, Sit et al. 2019)	
2392	<i>Brachygobius nunus</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	WB, OD, TN, KL, MH	(Mishra et al. 2019, Rao 1995, Barman et al. 2011, Biju et al. 2019)	Botanical Garden of Calcutta, Ganges River estuary
2393	<i>Bryaninops erythropros</i> (Jordan & Seale, 1906)	M	LK	(Babu et al. 2023)	
2394	<i>Bryaninops tigris</i> Larson, 1985	M	ANI	(Rajan & Sreeraj 2015)	
2395	<i>Bryaninops yongei</i> (Davis & Cohen, 1969)	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
2396	<i>Callogobius andamanensis</i> Menon & Chatterjee, 1974	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Curlow Island, Middle Andaman Island, Andaman Sea
2397	<i>Callogobius hasseltii</i> (Bleeker, 1851)	MBF	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Koumans 1941)	
2398	<i>Callogobius mannarensis</i> Rangarajan, 1968	M	ANI, TN	(Allen & Erdmann 2012)	Vedalai, Gulf of Mannar, 9°16'N, 79°08'E
2399	<i>Callogobius trifasciatus</i> Menon & Chatterjee, 1974	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Mayabunder, Middle Andaman Island, Andaman Islands
2400	<i>Caragobius urolepis</i> (Bleeker, 1852)	BF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2011, 2012, Biju et al. 2019)	
2401	<i>Cryptocentrus caeruleomaculatus</i> (Herre, 1933)	M	ANI	(Allen & Erdmann 2012)	
2402	<i>Cryptocentrus cinctus</i> (Herre, 1936)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2403	<i>Cryptocentrus cryptocentrus</i> (Valenciennes 1837)	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	

2404	<i>Cryptocentrus cyanotaenia</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	M	TN	(Ajith et al. 2015)	
2405	<i>Cryptocentrus fasciatus</i> (Playfair, 1867)	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
2406	<i>Cryptocentrus leptocephalus</i> Bleeker, 1876	M	Distribution details not available	(Koumans 1941)	
2407	<i>Cryptocentrus leucostictus</i> (Günther, 1872)	M	ANI	(Allen & Erdmann 2012)	
2408	<i>Cryptocentrus pavoninoides</i> (Bleeker, 1849)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2409	<i>Cryptocentrus sericus</i> Herre, 1932	M	ANI	(Allen & Erdmann 2012)	
2410	<i>Cryptocentrus strigilliceus</i> (Jordan & Seale, 1906)	M	ANI, LK	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Babu et al. 2023)	
2411	<i>Ctenogobiops crocineus</i> Smith, 1959	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
2412	<i>Ctenogobiops maculosus</i> (Fourmanoir, 1955)	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
2413	<i>Ctenogobiops mitodes</i> Randall, Shao & Chen, 2007	M	LK	(Babu et al. 2023)	
2414	<i>Ctenogobiops pomastictus</i> Lubbock & Polunin, 1977	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
2415	<i>Drombus bontii</i> (Bleeker, 1849)	MBF	ANI, AP, TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Rajan et al. 2013, Koumans 1941)	
2416	<i>Drombus dentifer</i> (Hora, 1923)	MB	OD	(Parenti 2021)	Rambha Bay, near Satpara & Barnikpaina
2417	<i>Drombus globiceps</i> (Hora, 1923)	MBF	WB, OD, TN, KL	(Mishra et al. 2019, Rao 1995, Barman et al. 2011, Biju et al. 2019)	Chilka Lake, Orissa
2418	<i>Drombus triangularis</i> (Weber, 1909)	MBF	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2419	<i>Egglestonichthys melanoptera</i> (Visweswara Rao, 1971)	MB	AP	(Mishra et al. 2019)	Godavari Estuary
2420	<i>Eugnathogobius kabilia</i> (Herre, 1940)	MB	AP	(Sreeraj & Arya 2023)	
2421	<i>Eugnathogobius mas</i> (Hora, 1923)	MB	OD	(Rao 1995)	Chilka Lake, off Samal Island, Rambha Bay, off Barkul, Orissa
2422	<i>Eugnathogobius mindora</i> (Herre, 1945)	B	TN, KL	(Nallathambi et al. 2023, Sreeraj et al. 2024)	
2423	<i>Eviota cometa</i> Jewett & Lachner, 1983	M	ANI	(Rajan & Sreeraj 2015)	
2424	<i>Eviota distigma</i> Jordan & Seale, 1906	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2425	<i>Eviota guttata</i> Lachner & Karnella, 1978	M	ANI	(Rajan & Sreeraj 2015)	
2426	<i>Eviota mikiae</i> Allen, 2001	M	ANI, LK	(Allen & Erdmann 2012, Babu et al. 2023)	
2427	<i>Eviota punyit</i> Tornabene, Valdez, Erdmann & Pezold,	M	LK	(Anto et al. 2024)	

	2016				
2428	<i>Eviota prasina</i> (Klunzinger, 1871)	M	ANI, LK	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
2429	<i>Eviota prasites</i> Jordan & Seale, 1906	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
2430	<i>Eviota queenslandica</i> Whitley, 1932	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
2431	<i>Eviota sebreei</i> Jordan & Seale, 1906	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
2432	<i>Eviota storthynx</i> (Rofen, 1959)	M	ANI	(Rajan & Sreeraj 2015)	
2433	<i>Eviota cf teresae</i> Greenfield & Randall, 2016	M	LK	(Anto et al. 2024)	
2434	<i>Eviota zonura</i> Jordan & Seale, 1906	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2435	<i>Exyrias puntang</i> (Bleeker, 1851)	MB	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2436	<i>Favonigobius gymnauchen</i> (Bleeker, 1860)	MBF	KL	(Mumthaz et al. 2023)	
2437	<i>Favonigobius reichei</i> (Bleeker, 1854)	MBF	ANI, OD, AP, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2011)	
2438	<i>Fusigobius infraculatus</i> (Randall, 1994)	M	ANI	(Rajan & Sreeraj 2015)	
2439	<i>Fusigobius melacron</i> (Randall, 2001)	M	ANI	(Allen & Erdmann 2012)	
2440	<i>Fusigobius neophytus</i> (Günther, 1877)	M	ANI, LK	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Rajan et al. 2021)	
2441	<i>Fusigobius signipinnis</i> Hoese & Obika, 1988	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
2442	<i>Glossogobius bicirrhosus</i> (Weber, 1894)	MBF	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2443	<i>Glossogobius celebicus</i> (Valenciennes, 1837)	MBF	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2444	<i>Glossogobius giuris</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ, HP, UK, HY, DL, UP, RJ, MP, TL, CG, BR, JH, AS, ML, AR, NL, MN, MZ, TR	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2019, Sen & Dimos 2014, Husain 1997, Barman 2002, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Yadav 2008, Sharma & Dhanze 2018, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a, Hembrom & Bodra 2021, Niraj & Singh 2013)	Ganges River
2445	<i>Glossogobius kokius</i> (Valenciennes, 1837)	MBF	TN, KL	(Parenti 2021)	Malabar
2446	<i>Glossogobius minutus</i> Geevarghese & John, 1983	B	KL	(Geevarghese & John 1983)	Veli Lake, Kerala
2447	<i>Gnatholepis anjerensis</i> (Bleeker, 1851)	M	LK	(Babu et al. 2023)	
2448	<i>Gnatholepis</i>	MB	ANI, LK,	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2019,	

	<i>cauerensis</i> (Bleeker, 1853)		WB	Rajan et al. 2021	
2449	<i>Gobiodon citrinus</i> (Rüppell, 1838)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Koumans 1941, Rajan et al. 2021)	
2450	<i>Gobiodon erythrospilus</i> Bleeker, 1875	M	ANI, TN	(Allen & Erdmann 2012, Koumans 1941)	
2451	<i>Gobiodon histrio</i> (Valenciennes, 1837)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2452	<i>Gobiodon quinquestrigatus</i> (Valenciennes, 1837)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Koumans 1941)	
2453	<i>Gobiodon rivulatus</i> (Rüppell, 1830)	MBF	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, Rajan et al. 2021)	
2454	<i>Gobiopsis arenaria</i> (Snyder, 1908)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2455	<i>Gobiopsis canalis</i> Lachner & McKinney, 1978	M	WB, KL, GJ	(Lachner & McKinney 1978, Kumar et al. 2022a)	
2456	<i>Gobiopsis liolepis</i> (Koumans, 1931)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
2457	<i>Gobiopsis macrostomus</i> Steindachner, 1861	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, MH, GJ	(Mishra et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2011, Allen & Erdmann 2012, Behera et al. 2024)	Mumbai
2458	<i>Gobiopsis quinquecineta</i> (Smith, 1931)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Lachner & McKinney 1978)	
2459	<i>Gobiopsis woodsii</i> Lachner & McKinney, 1978	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Allen & Erdmann 2012)	Musal Tivu, Manauli, Gulf of Mannar
2460	<i>Gobiopterus chuno</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	ANI, WB, OD, TN, KL	(Mishra et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2011, Biju et al., 2019)	Botanical Garden of Calcutta, Ganges River estuary
2461	<i>Gobiopterus smithi</i> (Menon & Talwar, 1973)	MB	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Shampen village, Dogma River, Great Nicobar Island
2462	<i>Hemigobius hoevenii</i> (Bleeker, 1851)	MBF	ANI, WB, AP, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Sreeraj & Sen 2022)	
2463	<i>Heteroleotris zonata</i> (Fowler, 1934)	M	No specific location	(Parenti 2021)	
2464	<i>Istigobius decoratus</i> (Herre, 1927)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2465	<i>Istigobius diadema</i> (Steindachner, 1876)	MBF	ANI, TN, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2019, Ajith et al. 2015, Vadher et al. 2024)	
2466	<i>Istigobius goldmanni</i> (Bleeker, 1852)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2467	<i>Istigobius ornatus</i> (Rüppell, 1830)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2019, Koumans 1941, Rajan et al. 2021, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, Sreeraj 2022)	
2468	<i>Istigobius spencei</i> (Smith, 1947)	MB	LK	(Jones & Kumaran 1980)	
2469	<i>Koumansetta hectori</i> (Smith, 1957)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, Sandra et al. 2022)	
2470	<i>Lentipes andamanicus</i> (Mukerji, 1935)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Andaman Islands
2471	<i>Mahidolia</i>	MB	ANI, AP,	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2019,	

	<i>mystacina</i> (Valenciennes, 1837)		TN	Barman et al. 2011)	
2472	<i>Mangarinus seshaiyai</i> (Jacob & Rangarajan 1960)	B	TN	(Barman et al. 2011)	Vellar estuary, Porto Novo
2473	<i>Mangarinus waterousi</i> Herre, 1943	MBF	TN	(Ragul et al. 2022)	
2474	<i>Mizogobius koladyne</i> Geetakumari & Vishwanath, 2012	F	MZ	(Geetakumari & Vishwanath, 2012)	Koladyne River, Kawlchaw, Mizoram
2475	<i>Mugilogobius chulae</i> (Smith 1932)	MBF	GA	(Talwar 1974)	
2476	<i>Mugilogobius mertoni</i> (Weber, 1911)	MBF	KL, MH	(Sreeraj et al. 2024)	
2477	<i>Mugilogobius rambaiae</i> (Smith, 1945)	BF	KL	(Sreeraj et al. 2024)	
2478	<i>Mugilogobius tigrinus</i> Larson, 2001	B	ANI, AP, TN, KL	(Praveenraj et al. 2017b, Sreeraj & Sen 2022, Sreeraj et al. 2023)	
2479	<i>Myersina filifer</i> (Valenciennes, 1837)	M	WB, OD, AP	(Roy et al. 2019, Silambarasan et al. 2022)	
2480	<i>Myersina yangii</i> (Chen, 1960)	M	TN	(Kodeeswaran et al. 2020)	
2481	<i>Obliquogobius cometes</i> (Alcock, 1890)	M	OD, TN, KL	(Koumans 1941)	Off Madras coast, India, 18°30'N, 84°46'E
2482	<i>Odontamblyopus roseus</i> (Valenciennes, 1837)	M	KL, MH	(Murdy & Shibukawa 2001)	Mumbai
2483	<i>Odontamblyopus rubicundus</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, KL, GA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2012, Talwar 1974)	Ganges River estuaries
2484	<i>Oligolepis acutipennis</i> (Valenciennes, 1837)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan & Sreeraj 2014a, Mishra et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2011)	Malabar
2485	<i>Oligolepis cylindriceps</i> (Hora, 1923)	B	OD, AP, TN, KL	(Rao 1995, Barman et al. 2011, Koumans 1941)	Chilka Lake, Orissa
2486	<i>Oligolepis formosanus</i> (Nichols 1958)	MB	AP, TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Mishra et al. 2019)	
2487	<i>Oligolepis nijsseni</i> (Menon & Govindan, 1977)	B	AP, TN	(Parenti 2021)	Ennore estuary, Tamil Nadu
2488	<i>Oplopomus caninoides</i> (Bleeker, 1852)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Barman et al. 2011)	
2489	<i>Oplopomus oplopomus</i> (Valenciennes, 1837)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2490	<i>Oxuderces dentatus</i> Eydoux & Souleyet, 1850	BF	ANI, WB, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2011)	
2491	<i>Oxuderces nexipinnis</i> (Cantor, 1849)	MB	WB	(Mukherjee 1995)	
2492	<i>Oxyurichthys auchenolepis</i> Bleeker, 1876	M	TN	(Pezold 1998)	
2493	<i>Oxyurichthys microlepis</i> (Bleeker, 1849)	MB	ANI, LK, OD, AP, TN, KA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2019, Pezold 1998, Rajan et al. 2021, Barman et al. 2013a)	
2494	<i>Oxyurichthys ophthalmonema</i> (Bleeker,	MBF	ANI, TN, KL	(Mishra et al. 2019, Pezold 1998, Sreeraj et al. 2024)	

	1856)				
2495	<i>Oxyurichthys papuensis</i> (Valenciennes, 1837)	MB	ANI, OD, AP, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2011, Behera et al. 2024)	
2496	<i>Oxyurichthys paulae</i> Pezold, 1998	M	KL, GA, MH	(Pezold 1998, Hegde et al. 2013)	Off Cochin, Kerala
2497	<i>Oxyurichthys tentacularis</i> (Valenciennes, 1837)	MB	ANI, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2011, 2012, 013a, Biju et al. 2019)	
2498	<i>Parachaeturichthys polynema</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2019, Koumans 1941, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, Hedge et al. 2013, Kumar et al. 2022a)	
2499	<i>Paragobiodon echinocephalus</i> (Rüppell, 1830)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
2500	<i>Paragobiopsis orbicularis</i> Visweswara Rao, 1971	B	AP	(Parenti 2021)	Brackish water canal, Kakinada
2501	<i>Paragobiopsis ostreicola</i> (Chaudhuri, 1916)	FB	OD, AP, TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Mishra et al. 2019, Rao 1995, Barman et al. 2011)	Oyster beds near Manikpur, Chilka Lake
2502	<i>Parapocryptes rictuosus</i> (Valenciennes, 1837)	MB	OD, AP, TN, KL	(Mishra et al. 2019)	Mouth of River of Arian, Puducherry
2503	<i>Parapocryptes serperaster</i> (Richardson, 1846)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2011, Das & Palita 2015, Biju et al. 2019)	
2504	<i>Paratrypauchen microcephalus</i> (Bleeker, 1860)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, GA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2011, 2012, Talwar 1974, Ruidas et al. 2020)	
2505	<i>Periophthalmodon schlosseri</i> (Pallas, 1770)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2019, Padmavathi 2017, Barman et al. 2012)	
2506	<i>Periophthalmodon septemradiatus</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	ANI, WB	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2019)	Ganges river estuary
2507	<i>Periophthalmus argentilineatus</i> Valenciennes, 1837	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2508	<i>Periophthalmus barbarus</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	MBF	OD, AP, TN, GJ	(Padmavathi 2017, Rao 1995, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000)	
2509	<i>Periophthalmus chrysospilos</i> Bleeker, 1853	MB	OD, AP, TN	(Mishra et al. 2019, Padmavathi 2017, Barman et al. 2011)	
2510	<i>Periophthalmus kalolo</i> Lesson, 1831	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2511	<i>Periophthalmus malaccensis</i> Eggert, 1935	MBF	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2512	<i>Periophthalmus novemradiatus</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2011, Das & Palita 2015)	Uttarbhag, Ganges River delta
2513	<i>Periophthalmus variabilis</i> Eggert, 1935	MB	WB, TN	(Mishra et al. 2019, Remadevi 1992)	
2514	<i>Periophthalmus walailakae</i> Darumas &	B	AP	(Padmavathi 2017)	

	Tantichodok, 2002				
2515	<i>Phyllogobius platycephalops</i> (Smith, 1964)	M	ANI	(Rajan & Sreeraj 2015)	
2516	<i>Pleurosicya annandalei</i> Hornell & Fowler, 1922	M	TN	(Allen & Erdmann 2012)	Tuticorin
2517	<i>Pleurosicya bilobata</i> (Koumans, 1941)	MB	ANI, TN	(Rajan & Sreeraj 2015, Allen & Erdmann 2012)	Muthivaratu Paar, Tamilnadu
2518	<i>Pleurosicya boldinghi</i> Weber, 1913	M	ANI	(Rajan & Sreeraj 2015)	
2519	<i>Priolepis compita</i> Winterbottom, 1985	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
2520	<i>Priolepis eugenius</i> (Jordan & Evermann, 1903)	M	ANI, LK	(Mishra et al. 2019, Rajan et al. 2021)	
2521	<i>Priolepis inhaca</i> (Smith, 1949)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
2522	<i>Priolepis profunda</i> (Weber, 1909)	M	ANI, KL	(Allen & Erdmann 2012, Ramachandran et al. 2020)	
2523	<i>Priolepis semidoliata</i> (Valenciennes, 1837)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Koumans 1941)	
2524	<i>Psammogobius biocellatus</i> (Valenciennes, 1837)	MBF	ANI, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, MZ, TR	(Rajan & Sreeraj 2014a, Mishra et al. 2019, Sen & Dimos 2014, Barman et al. 2011, 2012, 2013a)	Puducherry
2525	<i>Pseudapocryptes elongatus</i> (Cuvier, 1816)	BF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL	(Mishra et al. 2019, Padmavathi 2017)	Tharangambadi
2526	<i>Pseudogobiopsis oligactis</i> (Bleeker, 1875)	BF	ANI, MH	(Koumans 1941, Karmakar et al. 2012)	
2527	<i>Pseudogobius fulvicaudus</i> Huang, Shao & Chen, 2014	B	AP, TN	(Sreeraj & Arya 2023, Ragul et al. 2024b)	
2528	<i>Pseudogobius melanosticta</i> (Day, 1876)	MBF	ANI, TN, KL	(Larson 2001, Larson & Hammer 2021)	Backwaters of Madras
2529	<i>Pseudogobius minimus</i> (Hora, 1923)	B	WB, OD, AP, TN	(Padmavathi 2017, Rao 1995, Parenti 2021, Larson & Hammer 2021)	Chilka Lake, Orissa
2530	<i>Pseudogobius poicilosoma</i> (Bleeker, 1849)	BF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, MH	(Koumans 1941, Rao 1995, Barman et al. 2011, Koumans 1941, Padmavathi 2017, Sreeraj et al. 2024)	
2531	<i>Pseudotrypauchen multiradiatus</i> Hardenberg, 1931	BF	WB, OD, AP	(Mishra et al. 2019)	
2532	<i>Redigobius balteatus</i> (Herre, 1935)	MBF	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2533	<i>Redigobius bikolanus</i> (Herre, 1927)	MBF	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013, Remadevi 2005)	
2534	<i>Redigobius macrostoma</i> (Günther, 1861)	MB	WB, TN, MH	(Chatterjee et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
2535	<i>Redigobius oyensi</i> (de Beaufort, 1913)	F	ANI	(Praveenraj et al. 2017a)	
2536	<i>Redigobius tambujon</i> (Bleeker, 1854)	MBF	ANI, KA	(Rajan et al. 2013, Remadevi & Indhra 2005)	
2537	<i>Scartelaos cantoris</i> (Day, 1871)	M	ANI, TN, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Barman et al. 2011, Barman et al. 2000)	Andaman Islands

2538	<i>Scartelaos histophorus</i> (Valenciennes, 1837)	MB	WB, OD, AP, TN, MH, GJ	(Mishra et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012)	Mumbai
2539	<i>Scartelaos tenuis</i> (Day, 1876)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2540	<i>Schismatogobius deraniyagala</i> i Kottelat & Pethiyagoda, 1989	F	KL, KA	(Raghavan et al. 2020, Arunachalam et al. 2014)	
2541	<i>Sicyopterus garra</i> Hora, 1925	MBF	ANI	(Praveenraj et al. 2022)	Brichgunj, South Andaman Island, Andaman Islands
2542	<i>Sicyopterus griseus</i> (Day, 1877)	BF	TN, KL, KA, GA	(Mishra et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2011, Talwar 1974)	South Canara
2543	<i>Sicyopterus microcephalus</i> (Bleeker, 1855)	F	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2544	<i>Silhouettea indica</i> Visweswara Rao, 1971	MB	AP, TN	(Padmavathi 2017, Sreeraj 2022)	Godavari Estuary
2545	<i>Stenogobius gymnopomus</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	MBF	ANI, TN, KL, KA, GA	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2019, Koumans 1941, Barman et al. 2013a, Talwar 1974)	
2546	<i>Stenogobius laterisquamatus</i> (Weber, 1907)	F	OD	(Pati et al. 2018)	
2547	<i>Stigmatogobius sadanundio</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Botanical Garden of Calcutta, Ganges River estuary
2548	<i>Stigmatogobius yanamensis</i> Rao, 1971	B	WB, AP	(Larson & Hammer 2021, Sen et al. 2023)	Godavari Estuary
2549	<i>Sueviota lachneri</i> Winterbottom & Hoese, 1988	M	ANI	(Allen & Erdmann 2012)	
2550	<i>Taenioides anguillaris</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2551	<i>Taenioides buchanani</i> (Day, 1873)	MB	WB, OD, AP, TN	(Mishra et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2011)	Calcutta
2552	<i>Taenioides cirratus</i> (Blyth, 1860)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2019, Biju et al. 2019)	Calcutta
2553	<i>Taenioides gracilis</i> (Valenciennes, 1837)	MBF	TN	(Parenti 2021)	Puducherry
2554	<i>Tomiyamichthys russus</i> (Cantor, 1849)	M	ANI, TN	(Praveenraj et al. 2017, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2555	<i>Trimma annosum</i> Winterbottom, 2003	M	No specific location	(Allen & Erdmann 2012)	
2556	<i>Trimma griffithsi</i> Winterbottom, 1984	M	ANI	(Allen & Erdmann 2012)	
2557	<i>Trimma naudei</i> Smith, 1957	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
2558	<i>Trimma sanguinellus</i> Winterbottom & Southcott, 2007	M	ANI	(Rajan & Sreeraj 2015)	
2559	<i>Trimma striatum</i> (Herre, 1945)	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
2560	<i>Trimma winterbottomi</i> Randall	M	ANI, TN	(Allen & Erdmann 2012)	

	& Downing, 1994				
2561	<i>Trypauchen vagina</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Mishra et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2011, Thakkar et al. 2018, Rajan et al. 2021, Talwar 1974)	Tharangambadi
2562	<i>Trypauchenichthys sumatrensis</i> Hardenberg, 1931	B	WB, OD	(Mishra et al. 2019, Patra et al. 2023)	
2563	<i>Trypauchenichthys typus</i> Bleeker, 1860	F	WB	(Mukherjee 1995)	
2564	<i>Valenciennea decora</i> Hoese & Larson, 1994	M	ANI	(Rajan & Sreeraj 2015)	
2565	<i>Valenciennea helsdingenii</i> (Bleeker, 1858)	M	LK, TN	(Kannan et al. 2013, Rajan et al. 2021)	
2566	<i>Valenciennea limicola</i> Hoese & Larson, 1994	MB	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2567	<i>Valenciennea muralis</i> (Valenciennes, 1837)	M	ANI	(Allen & Erdmann 2012)	
2568	<i>Valenciennea puellaris</i> (Tomiyama, 1956)	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
2569	<i>Valenciennea randalli</i> Hoese & Larson, 1994	MB	ANI	(Allen & Erdmann 2012)	
2570	<i>Valenciennea sexguttata</i> (Valenciennes, 1837)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
2571	<i>Valenciennea strigata</i> (Broussonet, 1782)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
2572	<i>Valenciennea wardii</i> (Playfair, 1867)	M	ANI, LK	(Remadevi 1992, Allen & Erdmann 2012)	
2573	<i>Wuhanlinigobius polylepis</i> (Wu & Ni, 1985)	MB	WB	(Sreeraj & Arya 2021)	
2574	<i>Yongeichthys audax</i> (Smith, 1959)	MB	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2575	<i>Yongeichthys nebulosus</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	MBF	ANI, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Padmavathi 2017, Barman et al. 2011, 2013a, Roy et al. 2019, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Hedge et al. 2013, Vadher et al. 2024)	
2576	<i>Yongeichthys tuticorinensis</i> (Fowler, 1925)	F	TN	(Roy et al. 2019)	Tuticorin, Madras
2577	<i>Yongeichthys suluensis</i> (Herre, 1927)	MB	ANI	(Rajan 2015)	
2578	<i>Yongeichthys viganensis</i> (Steindachner, 1893)	FB	TN	(Nallathambi et al. 2023)	
Family: Kraemeriidae Whitley, 1935					
2579	<i>Kraemeria samoensis</i> Steindachner, 1906	MBF	LK, OD	(Rajan et al. 2021, Pati et al. 2018)	
Family: Microdesmidae Regan, 1912					
2580	<i>Gunnellichthys monostigma</i> Smith, 1958	M	LK	(Sandra et al. 2022)	
2581	<i>Gunnellichthys viridescens</i> Dawson, 1968	M	ANI	(Allen & Erdmann 2012)	
2582	<i>Nemateleotris decora</i> Randall & Allen, 1973	M	ANI	(Allen & Erdmann 2012)	

2583	<i>Nemateleotris magnifica</i> Fowler, 1938	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, Rajan et al. 2021)	
2584	<i>Oxymetopon compressus</i> Chan, 1966	M	TN	(Ragul et al. 2024)	
2585	<i>Parioglossus philippinus</i> (Herre, 1945)	MB	Exact location is missing	(Allen & Erdmann 2012)	
2586	<i>Parioglossus raoi</i> (Herre, 1939)	MB	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	West coast of Guitar Island, Middle Andaman Island, Andaman Islands
2587	<i>Parioglossus winterbottomi</i> Suzuki, Yonezawa & Sakaue, 2010	M	WB	(Suzuki et al. 2010)	Matla mudflats, Canning at South 24, Parganas District, West Benga
2588	<i>Ptereleotris caeruleomarginata</i> Allen, Erdmann & Cahyani, 2012	M	ANI	(Allen & Erdmann 2012)	Havelock Island, 12°03.297'N, 92°57.2525'E, Andaman Islands
2589	<i>Ptereleotris cyanops</i> Kodeeswaran & Praveenraj, 2020	M	TN	(Kodeeswaran & Praveenraj 2020)	Royapuram Fishing Harbour, Chennai Coast, Tamil Nadu
2590	<i>Ptereleotris evides</i> (Jordan & Hubbs, 1925)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
2591	<i>Ptereleotris hanae</i> (Jordan & Snyder, 1901)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2592	<i>Ptereleotris heteroptera</i> (Bleeker, 1855)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2593	<i>Ptereleotris microlepis</i> (Bleeker, 1856)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
Family: Schindleriidae Giltay, 1934					
2594	<i>Schindleria pietschmanni</i> (Schindler, 1931)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
2595	<i>Schindleria praematura</i> (Schindler, 1930)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
Order: Gonorynchiformes					
Family: Chanidae Günther, 1868					
2596	<i>Chanos chanos</i> (Forsskal, 1775)	MBF	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Khan 2002, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar et al. 2012, Nandi et al. 2008)	
Order: Holocentriformes					
Family: Holocentridae Bonaparte, 1833					
2597	<i>Myripristis adusta</i> Bleeker, 1853	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2598	<i>Myripristis berndti</i> Jordan & Evermann, 1903	M	ANI, LK, TN, AP	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Kumar et al. 2024)	
2599	<i>Myripristis botche</i> Cuvier, 1829	M	WB, AP, TN, MH	(Yennawar et al. 2015, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al.	Visakhapatnam

				2012)	
2600	<i>Myripristis formosa</i> Randall & Greenfield, 1996	M	AP, KL	(Silambarasan et al. 2022, Nair & Dineshkumar 2016)	
2601	<i>Myripristis greenfieldi</i> Randall & Yamakawa, 1996	M	KL	(Nair & Dineshkumar 2016)	
2602	<i>Myripristis hexagona</i> (Lacepède, 1802)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2603	<i>Myripristis kuntee</i> Valenciennes, 1831	M	AP	(Barman et al. 2004)	
2604	<i>Myripristis murdjan</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
2605	<i>Myripristis seychellensis</i> Cuvier, 1829	M	LK, KL, AP	(Rajan et al. 2021, Nair & Dineshkumar 2016, Kumar et al. 2024)	
2606	<i>Myripristis violacea</i> Bleeker, 1851	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2607	<i>Neoniphon argenteus</i> (Valenciennes, 1831)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
2608	<i>Neoniphon aurolineatus</i> (Liénard, 1839)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2609	<i>Neoniphon opercularis</i> (Valenciennes, 1831)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
2610	<i>Neoniphon sammara</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2611	<i>Ostichthys acanthorhinus</i> Randall, Shimizu & Yamakawa, 1982	M	OD, TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Mohanty et al. 2020)	
2612	<i>Ostichthys japonicus</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	ANI, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019)	
2613	<i>Ostichthys kaianus</i> (Günther, 1880)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2614	<i>Sargocentron caudimaculatum</i> (Rüppell, 1838)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2615	<i>Sargocentron diadema</i> (Lacepède, 1802)	M	ANI, LK, TN, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
2616	<i>Sargocentron dorsomaculatum</i> (Shimizu & Yamakawa, 1979)	M	AP	(Sneha Jha et al. 2023)	
2617	<i>Sargocentron ittodai</i> (Jordan & Fowler, 1902)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
2618	<i>Sargocentron melanospilos</i> (Bleeker, 1858)	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2619	<i>Sargocentron praslin</i> (Lacepède, 1802)	M	ANI, WB, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Yennawar et al. 2015, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2620	<i>Sargocentron punctatissimum</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	ANI, LK, TN, GA	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
2621	<i>Sargocentron rubrum</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	ANI, LK, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	

2622	<i>Sargocentron spiniferum</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2623	<i>Sargocentron violaceum</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
Order: Kurtiformes					
Family: Apogonidae Günther, 1859					
2624	<i>Apogon coccineus</i> Rüppell, 1838	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2625	<i>Apogon ceramensis</i> Bleeker, 1852	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2626	<i>Apogon semiornatus</i> Peters, 1876	M	TN	(Padate et al. 2014)	
2627	<i>Apogon quadrisquamatus</i> Longley, 1934	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2628	<i>Apogonichthyoides erdmanni</i> Fraser & Allen, 2011	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2629	<i>Apogonichthyoides heptastygma</i> (Cuvier, 1828)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2630	<i>Apogonichthyoides melas</i> (Bleeker, 1848)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2631	<i>Apogonichthyoides niger</i> (Döderlein, 1883)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2632	<i>Apogonichthyoides nigripinnis</i> (Cuvier, 1828)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Puducherry
2633	<i>Apogonichthyoides pseudotaeniatus</i> (Gon, 1986)	M	TN, KL, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Kumar et al. 2019)	
2634	<i>Apogonichthyoides sialis</i> (Jordan & Thompson, 1914)	M	OD, AP, TN	(Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Patra et al. 2023)	
2635	<i>Apogonichthyoides taeniatus</i> (Cuvier, 1828)	M	ANI, OD, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2636	<i>Apogonichthyoides umbratilis</i> Fraser & Allen, 2010	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2637	<i>Apogonichthys ocellatus</i> (Weber, 1913)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2638	<i>Apogonichthys perdix</i> Bleeker, 1854	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2639	<i>Archamia bleekeri</i> (Günther, 1859)	M	TN, GA	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Hedge et al. 2013)	
2640	<i>Cheilodipterus arabicus</i> (Gmelin, 1789)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2641	<i>Cheilodipterus artus</i> Smith, 1961	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2642	<i>Cheilodipterus lachneri</i> Klausewitz, 1959	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
2643	<i>Cheilodipterus macrodon</i> (Lacepède, 1802)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2644	<i>Cheilodipterus quinquelineatus</i> Cuvier, 1828	M	ANI, LK, TN, KA	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a)	
2645	<i>Fibramia amboinensis</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	MBF	ANI, WB	(Rajan et al. 2013, Sanyal et al. 2012)	

2646	<i>Fibramia lateralis</i> (Valenciennes, 1832)	MBF	WB, TN	(Misra 1959, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2647	<i>Fibramia thermalis</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	ANI, LK, KL, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2012)	
2648	<i>Foa brachygramma</i> (Jenkins, 1903)	MBF	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Sandra et al. 2022)	
2649	<i>Fowleria aurita</i> (Valenciennes, 1831)	M	ANI, LK, OD, TN, GA	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
2650	<i>Fowleria marmorata</i> (Alleyne & Macleay, 1877)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2651	<i>Fowleria variegata</i> (Valenciennes, 1832)	MB	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2652	<i>Gymnapogon africanus</i> Smith, 1954	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
2653	<i>Holapogon maximus</i> (Boulenger, 1888)	M	TN, KL	(Said Koya et al. 2011, Ranjith et al. 2016)	
2654	<i>Jaydia ellioti</i> (Day, 1875)	M	ANI, OD, TN, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	Chennai
2655	<i>Jaydia lineata</i> (Temminck & Schlegel, 1843)	M	TN, GJ	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Kumar et al. 2019)	
2656	<i>Jaydia novaeguineae</i> (Valenciennes, 1832)	M	OD, TN	(Mohanty et al. 2020)	
2657	<i>Jaydia poeciloptera</i> (Cuvier, 1828)	MB	ANI, OD, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2658	<i>Jaydia queketti</i> (Gilchrist, 1903)	M	WB, AP, TN, KL, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Pradhan et al. 2022, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Kumar et al. 2019)	
2659	<i>Jaydia smithi</i> Kotthaus, 1970	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2660	<i>Jaydia striata</i> (Smith & Radcliffe, 1912)	M	WB	(Pradhan et al. 2022)	
2661	<i>Jaydia truncata</i> (Bleeker, 1855)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2662	<i>Lepidamia kalosoma</i> (Bleeker, 1852)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2663	<i>Lepidamia multitaeniata</i> (Cuvier, 1828)	M	ANI, TN, KL, GA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, Talwar 1974)	
2664	<i>Neamia octospina</i> Smith & Radcliffe 1912	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2665	<i>Nectamia bandanensis</i> (Bleeker, 1854)	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2666	<i>Nectamia fusca</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1825)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2667	<i>Nectamia savayensis</i> (Günther, 1872)	M	ANI, LK, TN, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
2668	<i>Ostorhinchus angustatus</i> (Smith & Radcliffe, 1911)	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
2669	<i>Ostorhinchus endekataenia</i> (Bleeker, 1852)	M	KA	(Barman et al. 2013a)	
2670	<i>Ostorhinchus apogonoides</i> (Bleeker, 1856)	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	

2671	<i>Ostorhinchus aureus</i> (Lacepède, 1802)	M	ANI, OD, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2672	<i>Ostorhinchus bryx</i> (Fraser, 1998)	M	KL	(Fraser 2005)	
2673	<i>Ostorhinchus chrysotaenia</i> (Bleeker, 1851)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2674	<i>Ostorhinchus compressus</i> (Smith & Radcliffe, 1911)	M	ANI, TN	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2675	<i>Ostorhinchus cookii</i> (MacLeay, 1881)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2676	<i>Ostorhinchus cyanosoma</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2677	<i>Ostorhinchus dispar</i> (Fraser & Randall, 1976)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2678	<i>Ostorhinchus endekataenia</i> (Bleeker, 1852)	M	ANI, LK, OD, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2679	<i>Ostorhinchus fasciatus</i> (White, 1790)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, GA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Pradhan et al. 2022, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, Hedge et al. 2013)	
2680	<i>Ostorhinchus fleurieu</i> Lacepède, 1802	MB	ANI, WB, OD, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Pradhan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Patra et al. 2023)	
2681	<i>Ostorhinchus hoevenii</i> (Bleeker, 1854)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2682	<i>Ostorhinchus holotaenia</i> (Regan, 1905)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2683	<i>Ostorhinchus moluccensis</i> (Valenciennes, 1832)	M	ANI, LK	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Rajan et al. 2021)	
2684	<i>Ostorhinchus nanus</i> (Allen, Kuitert & Randall, 1994)	M	ANI	(Rajan & Vikas 2016)	
2685	<i>Ostorhinchus nigripes</i> (Playfair, 1867)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2686	<i>Ostorhinchus nigrofasciatus</i> (Lachner, 1953)	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2687	<i>Ostorhinchus novemfasciatus</i> (Cuvier, 1828)	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2688	<i>Ostorhinchus oxina</i> (Fraser, 1999)	M	TN	(Fraser 1999)	Madras
2689	<i>Ostorhinchus pleuron</i> (Fraser, 2005)	M	TN	(Fraser 2005)	
2690	<i>Ostorhinchus properuptus</i> (Whitley, 1964)	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
2691	<i>Ostorhinchus quadrifasciatus</i> (Cuvier, 1828)	M	AP	(Barman et al. 2004)	Puducherry
2692	<i>Ostorhinchus quinquestriatus</i> (Regan, 1908)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2693	<i>Ostorhinchus septemstriatus</i> (Günther, 1880)	M	ANI, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2694	<i>Ostorhinchus</i>	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	

	<i>taeniophorus</i> (Regan, 1908)				
2695	<i>Ostorhinchus wassinki</i> (Bleeker, 1861)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2696	<i>Pristicon trimaculatus</i> (Cuvier, 1828)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2697	<i>Pristiapogon exostigma</i> (Jordan & Starks, 1906)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
2698	<i>Pristiapogon fraenatus</i> (Valenciennes, 1832)	M	ANI, LK, TN, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
2699	<i>Pristiapogon kallopterus</i> (Bleeker, 1856)	MB	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2700	<i>Pseudamia gelatinosa</i> Smith, 1956	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Das et al. 2021)	
2701	<i>Rhabdamia gracilis</i> (Bleeker, 1856)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
2702	<i>Siphamia tubifer</i> Weber, 1909	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2703	<i>Sphaeramia orbicularis</i> (Cuvier, 1828)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2704	<i>Taeniamia ataenia</i> (Randall & Satapoomin, 1999)	M	ANI	(Goutham-Bharathi et al. 2020)	
2705	<i>Taeniamia buruensis</i> (Bleeker, 1856)	MB	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
2706	<i>Taeniamia fucata</i> (Cantor, 1849)	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Biswas et al. 2012b)	
2707	<i>Taeniamia lineolata</i> (Cuvier, 1828)	M	AP, TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2708	<i>Taeniamia macroptera</i> (Cuvier, 1828)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2709	<i>Taeniamia zosterophora</i> (Bleeker 1856)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2710	<i>Verulux cypselurus</i> (Weber, 1909)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
2711	<i>Yarica hyalosoma</i> (Bleeker, 1852)	MBF	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Sreeraj et al. 2023)	
2712	<i>Zoramia leptacanthus</i> (Bleeker 1856)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2713	<i>Zoramia fragilis</i> (Smith, 1961)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
2714	<i>Zoramia viridiventer</i> Greenfield, Langston & Randall, 2005	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
Family: Kurtidae Bleeker, 1859					
2715	<i>Kurtus indicus</i> Bloch, 1786	MBF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, MH	(Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Trichonotidae Günther, 1861					
2716	<i>Trichonotus cyclograptus</i> (Alcock, 1890)	M	WB, OD, TN	(Ray et al. 2018a, Pati et al. 2018, Roy et al. 2019b)	Ganjam Coast, Bay of Bengal
2717	<i>Trichonotus setiger</i> Bloch & Schneider, 1801	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	eastern India
Order: Lampriformes					
Family: Regalecidae Gill, 1884					

2718	<i>Regalecus glesne</i> Ascanius, 1772	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Trachipteridae Swainson, 1839					
2719	<i>Desmodema polystictum</i> (Ogilby, 1898)	M	ANI, TN	(Zacharia et al. 2012, Rajeeshkumar et al. 2022a)	
2720	<i>Zu elongatus</i> Heemstra & Kannemeyer, 1984	M	ANI	(Shrike et al. 2017)	
Order: Lepisosteidae					
Family: Lepisosteidae Agassiz, 1832					
2721	<i>Atractosteus spatula</i> (Lacepède, 1803)	MBF	WB	(Manna et al. 2021)	
Order: Lophiiformes					
Family: Antennariidae Jarocki, 1822					
2722	<i>Abantennarius coccineus</i> (Lesson, 1831)	M	LK	(Kapoor et al. 2002)	
2723	<i>Abantennarius nummifer</i> (Cuvier, 1817)	M	LK	(Kapoor et al. 2002)	
2724	<i>Antennarius biocellatus</i> (Cuvier, 1817)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2725	<i>Antennatus coccineus</i> (Lesson, 1831)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2726	<i>Antennarius commerson</i> (Lacepède, 1798)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2727	<i>Antennarius hispidus</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, MH	(Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, Goutham-Bharathi et al. 2021)	Coromandel coast
2728	<i>Antennarius indicus</i> Schultz, 1964	M	WB, OD, TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Bhakta et al. 2023a, Mohanty et al. 2020)	Vizakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh
2729	<i>Antennarius pictus</i> (Shaw, 1794)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2730	<i>Antennatus nummifer</i> (Cuvier, 1817)	M	LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2731	<i>Antennarius striatus</i> (Shaw, 1794)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2732	<i>Antennatus tuberosus</i> (Cuvier, 1817)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
2733	<i>Histrio histrio</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Ceratiidae Gill, 1861					
2734	<i>Ceratias uranoscopus</i> Murray, 1877	M	ANI	(Rajeeshkumar et al. 2021a)	
2735	<i>Cryptopsaras couesii</i> Gill, 1883	M	ANI	(Rajeeshkumar et al. 2021a)	
Family: Chaunacidae Gill, 1863					
2736	<i>Chaunax apus</i> Lloyd, 1909	M	ANI, KL	(Rajeeshkumar et al. 2021a)	
2737	<i>Chaunax multilepis</i> Ho, Meleppura & Bineesh, 2016	M	ANI, KL	(Biju et al. 2019)	off North Andaman Islands
2738	<i>Chaunax penicillatus</i> McCulloch, 1915	M	KL	(Ho & Last 2013)	
2739	<i>Chaunax pictus</i> Lowe, 1846	M	KL	(Biju et al. 2019)	
Family: Diceratiidae Regan & Trewavas, 1932					
2740	<i>Bufoceratias shaoi</i> Pietsch, Ho & Chen, 2004	M	Western Indian	(Rajeeshkumar et al. 2021a)	

			ocean, Arabian Sea		
2741	<i>Bufoceratias thele</i> (Uwate, 1979)	M	Western Indian ocean, Arabian Sea	(Rajeeshkumar et al. 2021a)	
2742	<i>Diceratias trilobus</i> Balushkin & Fedorov, 1986	M	KL	(Rajeeshkumar et al. 2021a)	
Family: Himantolophidae Gill, 1861					
2743	<i>Himantolophus kalami</i> Rajeeshkumar, Pietsch & Saravanane, 2022	M	ANI	(Rajeeshkumar et al. 2022)	Northern andaman, Andaman Nicobar Islands
Family: Lophiidae Rafinesque, 1810					
2744	<i>Lophiodes gracilimanus</i> (Alcock, 1899)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Off Malabar coast
2745	<i>Lophiodes insidiator</i> (Regan, 1921)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2746	<i>Lophiodes lugubris</i> (Alcock, 1894)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2747	<i>Lophiodes mutilus</i> (Alcock, 1894)	M	ANI, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Bay of Bengal
2748	<i>Lophiodes triradiatus</i> (Lloyd, 1909)	M	LK, KL	(Ho et al. 2014)	
2749	<i>Lophiomus setigerus</i> (Vahl, 1797)	M	ANI, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, , Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Ogocephalidae Gill, 1893					
2750	<i>Coelophrys micropus</i> (Alcock, 1891)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Bay of Bengal, 15°56'50"N, 81°30'30"E
2751	<i>Dibranchus hystrix</i> Garman, 1899	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2752	<i>Halieutaea coccinea</i> Alcock, 1889	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Bay of Bengal, off Orissa coast
2753	<i>Halieutaea fumosa</i> Alcock, 1894	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Bay of Bengal, 13°51'12"N, 80°28'12"E
2754	<i>Halieutaea indica</i> Annandale & Jenkins, 1910	M	OD, TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Bay of Bengal, off Orissa coast
2755	<i>Halieutaea nigra</i> Alcock, 1891	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Andaman Sea, 11°31'40"N, 92°46'06"E
2756	<i>Halieutaea stellata</i> (Vahl, 1797)	M	WB, OD, AP, TN	(Yennawar et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2757	<i>Halicmetus ruber</i> Alcock, 1891	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Andaman Sea, 11°31'40"N, 92°46'06"E
2758	<i>Halieutopsis nasuta</i> (Alcock, 1891)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Andaman Sea, 11°31'40"N, 92°46'40"E
2759	<i>Halieutopsis stellifera</i> (Smith & Radcliffe, 1912)	M	ANI	(Kumar et al. 2013)	

2760	<i>Malthopsis gigas</i> Ho & Shao, 2010	M	ANI	(Rajeeshkumar et al. 2021a)	
2761	<i>Malthopsis lutea</i> Alcock, 1891	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Andaman Sea, 11°31'40"N, 92°46'06"E
2762	<i>Malthopsis mitrigeria</i> Gilbert & Cramer, 1897	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2763	<i>Ogcocephalus nasutus</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
Family: Oneirodidae Gill, 1878					
2764	<i>Lophodolos indicus</i> Lloyd, 1909	M	KL	(Lloyd 1909)	Southwest of Cape Comorin, off Trevancore
Order: Mugiliformes					
Family: Mugilidae Jarocki, 1822					
2765	<i>Chelon melinopterus</i> (Valenciennes, 1836)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	
2766	<i>Chelon parsia</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ, MP	(Rajan et al. 2013, Shaji et al. 2019, Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman 1993, Barman et al. 2013a, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Nandi et al. 2008)	Freshwater rivers of Bengal
2767	<i>Crenimugil buchani</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Hooghly River, Calcutta
2768	<i>Crenimugil crenilabis</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	MB	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2769	<i>Crenimugil seheli</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	MBF	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2770	<i>Ellochelon vaigiensis</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1825)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Shaji et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2771	<i>Minimugil cascasia</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, TN, GA, GJ, HP, UK, DL, AS, ML, MN, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1995, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Husain 1997, Barman 2002, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Yadav 2008, Jagtap 2013, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021)	Rivers of northern Bengal
2772	<i>Moolgarda cunnesius</i> (Valenciennes, 1836)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Shaji et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Talwar 1974)	Malabar & Mumbai, Moluccas Island, Indonesia
2773	<i>Mugil cephalus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Shaji et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Pati et al. 2018, Barman 1993, Barman et al. 2013a, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000)	
2774	<i>Osteomugil engeli</i> (Bleeker, 1858)	MBF	KL	(Bhatt & Mankodi 2023)	
2775	<i>Osteomugil</i>	M	TN, KL	(Bhatt & Mankodi 2023)	

	<i>perusii</i> (Valenciennes, 1836)				
2776	<i>Osteomugil speigleri</i> (Bleeker, 1858)	MBF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2017, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2777	<i>Parachelon grandisquamis</i> (Valenciennes, 1836)	MBF	MH	(Bhatt & Mankodi 2023)	
2778	<i>Paramugil parmatus</i> (Cantor, 1849)	MBF	ANI, OD	(Rajan et al. 2013, Pati et al. 2018)	
2779	<i>Planiliza alata</i> (Steindachner, 1892)	MBF	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2780	<i>Planiliza carinata</i> (Valenciennes, 1836)	MB	ANI, TN, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 200, 2012, Talwar 1974)	
2781	<i>Planiliza klunzingeri</i> (Day, 1888)	M	TN, MH	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Hasan et al. 2022)	Mumbai
2782	<i>Planiliza macrolepis</i> (Smith, 1846)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Shaji et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
2783	<i>Planiliza mandapamensis</i> (Thomson, 1997)	BF	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Kilakarei, south of Mandapam
2784	<i>Planiliza planiceps</i> (Valenciennes, 1836)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, TN, KA	(Rajan et al. 2013, Danda et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a)	Bengal, eastern Indian Ocean
2785	<i>Planiliza subviridis</i> (Valenciennes, 1836)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a)	Ganges River, Malabar
2786	<i>Planiliza tade</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, GA, MH, GJ	(Shaji et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012, Talwar 1974)	
2787	<i>Plicomugil labiosus</i> (Valenciennes, 1836)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
2788	<i>Rhinomugil corsula</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KA, MH, GJ, UK, DL, UP, MP, TL, CG, JH, ML, TR	(Mishra et al. 2017, Sen 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Mishra et al. 2021a, Tudu et al. 2022)	Most rivers of the Gangetic provinces, & in southern parts of Bengal
Order: Myctophiformes					
Family: Myctophidae Gill, 1893					
2789	<i>Ceratospelus warmingii</i> (Lütken, 1892)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2790	<i>Centrobranchus andreae</i> (Lütken, 1892)	M	LK	(Kapoor et al. 2002)	
2791	<i>Benthoosema pterotum</i> (Alcock, 1890)	M	ANI, OD	(Rajan et al. 2013, Pati et al. 2018)	Madras coast, India, 18°30'N, 84°46'E
2792	<i>Bolinichthys pyrsobolus</i> (Alcock, 1890)	M	TN	(Alcock 1890)	Off Madras coast, India,

					15°38'N, 82°30'E
2793	<i>Centrobranchus andreae</i> (Lütken, 1892)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
2794	<i>Dasyscopelus obtusirostris</i> (Tåning, 1928)	M	TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2795	<i>Dasyscopelus spinosus</i> (Steindachner, 1867)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
2796	<i>Diaphus coeruleus</i> (Klunzinger, 1871)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2797	<i>Diaphus diademophilus</i> Nafpaktitis, 1978	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2798	<i>Diaphus dumerilii</i> (Bleeker, 1856)	M	KA	(Barman et al. 2013a)	
2799	<i>Diaphus effulgens</i> (Goode & Bean, 1896)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2800	<i>Diaphus fulgens</i> (Brauer, 1904)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
2801	<i>Diaphus garmani</i> Gilbert, 1906	M	TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2802	<i>Diaphus luetkeni</i> (Brauer 1904)	M	South Indian Coast	(Kapoor et al. 2002)	
2803	<i>Diaphus malayanus</i> Weber, 1913	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2804	<i>Diaphus nielseni</i> Nafpaktitis, 1978	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2805	<i>Diaphus perspicillatus</i> (Ogilby, 1898)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2806	<i>Diaphus splendidus</i> (Brauer, 1904)	M	KL	(Biju et al. 2019)	
2807	<i>Diaphus suborbitalis</i> Weber, 1913	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2808	<i>Diaphus thiollierei</i> Fowler, 1934	M	TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2809	<i>Diaphus watasei</i> Jordan & Starks, 1904	M	KL	(Biju et al. 2019)	
2810	<i>Hygophum reinhardtii</i> (Lütken, 1892)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
2811	<i>Myctophum affine</i> (Lütken, 1892)	MB	LK	(Rajan et al., 2021)	
2812	<i>Myctophum aurolaternatum</i> Garman, 1899	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
2813	<i>Myctophum fissunovi</i> Becker & Borodulina, 1971	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2814	<i>Myctophum indicum</i> (Day, 1877)	M	AP	(Day 1877)	Visakhapatnam
2815	<i>Symbolophorus evermanni</i> (Gilbert, 1905)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
Family: Neoscopelidae Jordan, 1901					
2816	<i>Neoscopelus macrolepidotus</i> Johnson, 1863	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2817	<i>Scopelengys tristis</i> Alcock, 1890	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	Off Elicapeni Bank, Laccadive Sea, 11°12'47"N, 74°25'30"E

	Order: Notacanthiformes				
	Family: Halosauridae Günther, 1868				
2818	<i>Aldrovandia affinis</i> (Günther, 1877)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
2819	<i>Aldrovandia mediorostris</i> (Günther, 1887)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
2820	<i>Aldrovandia phalacra</i> (Vaillant, 1888)	M	Off Indian Coast (southern India)	(CoF 2023, Fishbase 2023)	
2821	<i>Halosaurus carinicauda</i> (Alcock, 1889)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Andaman Sea, 7.5 miles east of North Cinque Island
	Family: Notacanthidae Rafinesque, 1810				
2822	<i>Notacanthus laccadiviensis</i> Konhamkakkada, Kinattumkara, Raghavan & Sivanpillai, 2023	M	LK	(Konhamkakkada et al. 2023)	Off Kavaratti Island, Lakshadweep Archipelago, Arabian Sea, depth about 350 meters
	Order: Ophidiiformes				
	Family: Bythitidae Gill, 1861				
2823	<i>Barathronus diaphanus</i> Brauer, 1906	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2824	<i>Diplacanthopoma brachysoma</i> Günther, 1887	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2825	<i>Diplacanthopoma raniceps</i> Alcock, 1898	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Andaman Sea, 13°27'N, 93°14'30"E
2826	<i>Hepthocara simum</i> Alcock, 1892	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Gulf of Manaar, 6°58'N, 77°26'50"E
	Family: Carapidae Poey, 1867				
2827	<i>Carapus mourlani</i> (Petit, 1934)	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2828	<i>Encheliophis boraborensis</i> (Kaup, 1856)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
2829	<i>Encheliophis gracilis</i> (Bleeker, 1856)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
2830	<i>Encheliophis homei</i> (Richardson, 1846)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2831	<i>Onuxodon margaritiferae</i> (Rendahl, 1921)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2832	<i>Pyramodon ventralis</i> Smith & Radcliffe, 1913	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2833	<i>Pyramodon lindas</i> Markle & Olney, 1990	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
	Family: Dinematichthyidae Whitley, 1928				
2834	<i>Alionematichthys piger</i> (Alcock, 1890)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2835	<i>Dinematichthys</i>	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	

	<i>iluocoeteoides</i> Bleeker, 1855				
2836	<i>Eusurculus andamanensis</i> Schwarzhans & Møller, 2007	M	ANI	(Schwarzhans & Møller 2007)	Aves Island, Andaman Islands
Family: Ophidiidae Rafinesque, 1810					
2837	<i>Bassozetus glutinosus</i> (Alcock, 1890)	M	OD	(Pati et al. 2018)	Off Madras coast, India, 18°26'N, 85°24'E
2838	<i>Brotula multibarбата</i> Temminck & Schlegel, 1846	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2839	<i>Dicrolene introniger</i> Goode & Bean, 1883	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
2840	<i>Dicrolene multifilis</i> (Alcock, 1889)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Bay of Bengal
2841	<i>Dicrolene nigricaudis</i> (Alcock, 1891)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Andaman Sea, 11°31'40"N, 92°46'40"E
2842	<i>Glyptophidium argenteum</i> Alcock, 1889	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Andaman Sea, off Ross Island
2843	<i>Holcomycteronus pterotus</i> (Alcock, 1890)	M	LK, OD, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Off Madras coast, India, 18°26'N, 85°24'E
2844	<i>Lamprogrammus niger</i> Alcock, 1891	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Bay of Bengal
2845	<i>Monomitopus conjugator</i> (Alcock, 1896)	M	South coast of India	(Kapoor et al. 2002)	
2846	<i>Monomitopus nigripinnis</i> (Alcock, 1889)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	Andaman Sea, 7.5 miles east of North Cingue Island
2847	<i>Neobythites macrops</i> Günther, 1887	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2848	<i>Neobythites malayanus</i> Weber, 1913	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2849	<i>Neobythites multistriatus</i> Nielsen & Quéro, 1991	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2850	<i>Neobythites steatiticus</i> Alcock, 1894	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Bay of Bengal, 15°04'07"N, 80°25'07"E
2851	<i>Neobythites stefanovi</i> Nielsen & Uiblein, 1993	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2852	<i>Neobythites unimaculatus</i> Smith & Radcliffe, 1913	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2853	<i>Ophidion smithi</i> (Fowler, 1934)	M	WB	(Ray & Mahapatra 2022a)	
2854	<i>Porogadus melanocephalus</i> (Alcock, 1891)	M	LK	(Alcock 1891)	Bay of Bengal, 12°50'N, 90°52'E
2855	<i>Porogadus trichiurus</i> (Alcock, 1890)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	Off Elicapeni Bank, Laccadive Sea, 11°12'47"N, 74°25'30"E

2856	<i>Pycnocraspedum squamipinne</i> Alcock, 1889	M	WB, TN	(Teena et al. 2021)	Bay of Bengal, 20°17'30"N, 88°50'E
2857	<i>Spottobrotula mahodadi</i> Cohen & Nielsen, 1978	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Near Baren Island, Andaman Islands, Andaman Sea
2858	<i>Tauredophidium hextii</i> Alcock, 1890	M	OD	(Pati et al. 2018)	Off Madras coast, India, 18°26'N, 85°24'E
Order: Osteoglossiformes					
Family: Notopteridae Bleeker, 1851					
2859	<i>Chitala chitala</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, MH, GJ, HP, PU, UK, DL, UP, MP, TL, CG, BR, JH, AS, ML, AR, TR	(Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Bagra et al. 2009, Husain 1997, Barman 2002, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Jagtap 2013, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Mishra et al. 2021a, Kaur et al. 2017, Hembrom & Bodra 2021, Murugan & Prabakaran 2012)	
2860	<i>Notopterus notopterus</i> (Pallas, 1769)	BF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ, HP, PU, UK, HY, DL, UP, RJ, MP, TL, CG, BR, JH, AS, ML, AR, NL, MN, MZ, TR	(Shaji et al. 2019, Karmakar & Das 2005, Mishra et al. 2017, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Yadav 2008, Jagtap 2013, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a, Braich & Saini 2019, Hembrom & Bodra 2021, Murugan & Prabakaran 2012)	India
Order: Perciformes					
Family: Ammodytidae Bonaparte, 1835					
2861	<i>Bleekeria kallelepis</i> Günther, 1862	M	TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Chennai
2862	<i>Bleekeria murtii</i> Joshi, Zacharia & Kanthan, 2012	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Tuticorin, Tamilnadu
2863	<i>Bleekeria nigrilinea</i> Psomadakis, Yoshinaga, Wah & Ida, 2021	M	WB	(Ray et al. 2024)	
Family: Anthiadidae Poey, 1861					
2864	<i>Caprodon longimanus</i> (Günther, 1859)	M	West Coast of India	(Akhilesh et al. 2021)	
2865	<i>Meganthias filiferus</i> Randall & Heemstra, 2008	M	KL	(Biju et al. 2019)	
2866	<i>Mirolabrichthys evansi</i> (Smith, 1954)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2021, Akhilesh et al. 2021)	
2867	<i>Nemanthias ignitus</i> (Randall & Lubbock, 1981)	M	ANI, LK	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Rajan et al. 2021)	
2868	<i>Odontanthias perumali</i> (Talwar, 1976)	M	TN, KL	(Akhilesh et al. 2021, Talwar 1976)	off Kollam, Kerala

2869	<i>Odontanthias rhodopeplus</i> (Günther, 1872)	M	TN, KL	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1976)	
2870	<i>Plectranthias alcocki</i> Bineesh, Gopalakrishnan & Jena, 2014	M	KL	(Biju et al. 2019)	off Kollam, Kerala
2871	<i>Pseudanthias bimaculatus</i> (Smith, 1955)	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
2872	<i>Pseudanthias cichlops</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
2873	<i>Pseudanthias conspicuus</i> (Heemstra, 1973)	M	MH, GJ, Diu	(Heemstra 1973)	Off Diu, India, Arabian Sea, 20°23'N, 70°00'E
2874	<i>Pseudanthias cooperi</i> (Regan, 1902)	M	ANI, LK	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Rajan et al. 2021)	
2875	<i>Pseudanthias fasciatus</i> (Kamohara, 1955)	M	KL	(Biju et al. 2019)	
2876	<i>Pseudanthias gibbosus</i> (Klunzinger, 1884)	M	ANI	(Akhilesh et al. 2021)	
2877	<i>Pseudanthias hypselosoma</i> Bleeker, 1878	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
2878	<i>Pseudanthias marcia</i> Randall & Hoover, 1993	M	AP, TN, KL	(Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2008, Biju et al. 2019)	
2879	<i>Pseudanthias pillai</i> Heemstra & Akhilesh, 2012	M	AP, TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2008, Krishna et al. 2017)	Off Charakkadu, 10°30'N, 75°24'E, Kerala
2880	<i>Pseudanthias pulcherrimus</i> (Heemstra & Randall, 1986)	M	ANI	(Akhilesh et al. 2021)	
2881	<i>Pseudanthias rubrizonatus</i> (Randall, 1983)	M	ANI	(Akhilesh et al. 2021)	
2882	<i>Pseudanthias squamipinnis</i> (Peters, 1855)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2008, Rajan et al. 2013, Rajan et al. 2021)	
2883	<i>Pseudanthias taeniatus</i> (Klunzinger, 1884)	M	TN	(Akhilesh et al. 2021)	
2884	<i>Pseudanthias townsendi</i> (Boulenger, 1897)	M	GJ	(Akhilesh et al. 2021)	
2885	<i>Sacura boulengeri</i> (Heemstra, 1973)	M	KL	(Biju et al. 2019)	
2886	<i>Sacura margaritacea</i> (Hilgendorf, 1879)	M	LK	(Akhilesh et al. 2021)	
Family: Bembropidae Regan, 1913					
2887	<i>Bembrops caudimacula</i> Steindachner, 1876	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2888	<i>Bembrops curvatura</i> Okada & Suzuki, 1952	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2889	<i>Bembrops platyrhynchus</i> (Alcock, 1894)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Bay of Bengal, 15°04'07"N, 80°25'07"E
2890	<i>Chironema chlorotaenia</i> McKay, 1971	M	TN, KL	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Centrogenyidae Fowler, 1907					
2891	<i>Centrogenys vaigiensis</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1824)	MB	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	

Family: Epinephelidae Bloch, 1793					
2892	<i>Aethaloperca rogae</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2893	<i>Anyperodon leucogrammicus</i> (Valenciennes, 1828)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2894	<i>Cephalopholis aurantia</i> (Valenciennes, 1828)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2895	<i>Cephalopholis argus</i> Schneider, 1801	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
2896	<i>Cephalopholis aurantia</i> (Valenciennes, 1828)	M	Along the coastline	(Kapoor et al. 2002)	
2897	<i>Cephalopholis boenak</i> (Bloch, 1790)	M	ANI, LK, TN, KA, GA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, 2013a, Ansari et al. 1995)	
2898	<i>Cephalopholis cyanostigma</i> (Valenciennes, 1828)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2899	<i>Cephalopholis formosa</i> (Shaw, 1812)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Ray & Mahapatra 2022)	Visakhapatnam
2900	<i>Cephalopholis leopardus</i> (Lacepède, 1801)	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
2901	<i>Cephalopholis microprion</i> (Bleeker, 1852)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2902	<i>Cephalopholis miniata</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL, GA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, Ansari et al. 1995)	
2903	<i>Cephalopholis nigripinnis</i> (Valenciennes, 1828)	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2904	<i>Cephalopholis oligosticta</i> Randall & Bentuvia, 1983	M	TN	(Akhilesh et al. 2021)	
2905	<i>Cephalopholis polleni</i> (Bleeker, 1868)	M	TN	(Akhilesh et al. 2021)	
2906	<i>Cephalopholis polypila</i> Randall & Satapoomin, 2000	M	ANI	(Akhilesh et al. 2021)	
2907	<i>Cephalopholis sexmaculata</i> (Rüppell, 1830)	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
2908	<i>Cephalopholis sonnerati</i> (Valenciennes, 1828)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, TN, KL, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Ray et al. 2023, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	Puducherry
2909	<i>Cephalopholis urodeta</i> (Forster, 1801)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2910	<i>Chromileptes altivelis</i> (Valenciennes, 1828)	M	ANI, WB, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Ray et al. 2023, Mogalekar et al. 2008)	
2911	<i>Epinephelus albomarginatus</i> Boulenger, 1903	M	TN	(Akhilesh et al. 2021)	
2912	<i>Epinephelus amblycephalus</i> (Bleeker, 1857)	M	ANI	(Akhilesh et al. 2021)	

2913	<i>Epinephelus andersoni</i> Boulenger, 1903	M	Western Coast of India	(Akhilesh et al. 2021)	
2914	<i>Epinephelus areolatus</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	ANI, LK, WB, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Ray & Mahapatra 2022, Silambarasan et al. 2022)	
2915	<i>Epinephelus bleekeri</i> (Vaillant, 1878)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Ray & Mahapatra 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2008)	
2916	<i>Epinephelus bontoides</i> (Bleeker, 1855)	M	TN	(Akhilesh et al. 2021)	
2917	<i>Epinephelus chlorostigma</i> (Valenciennes, 1828)	M	ANI, OD, TN, KA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2008, Barman et al. 2012, 2013a)	
2918	<i>Epinephelus coeruleopunctatus</i> (Bloch, 1790)	M	ANI, LK, WB, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Ray & Mahapatra 2022)	
2919	<i>Epinephelus coioides</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2008, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a, Hedge et al. 2013)	Large Gangetic estuaries
2920	<i>Epinephelus corallicola</i> (Valenciennes, 1828)	MB	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2008)	
2921	<i>Epinephelus diacanthus</i> (Valenciennes, 1828)	M	OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2008, Talwar 1974)	Coast of Malabar
2922	<i>Epinephelus epistictus</i> (Temminck & Schlegel, 1842)	M	WB, KL, KA, MH	(Biju et al. 2019, Ray et al. 2023, Barman et al. 2012, 2013a)	
2923	<i>Epinephelus erythrurus</i> (Valenciennes, 1828)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Ray & Mahapatra 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2008, Hedge et al. 2013, Behera et al. 2024)	Malabar region
2924	<i>Epinephelus fasciatus</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Ray & Mahapatra 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2008, Ansari et al. 1995)	
2925	<i>Epinephelus faveatus</i> (Valenciennes, 1828)	M	ANI, TN, KA	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2008, Barman et al. 2013a)	
2926	<i>Epinephelus fasciatomaculosus</i> (Peters, 1865)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2008)	
2927	<i>Epinephelus flavocaeruleus</i> (Lacepède, 1802)	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2008)	
2928	<i>Epinephelus fuscoguttatus</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2008, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	
2929	<i>Epinephelus</i>	M	TN	(Akhilesh et al. 2021)	

	<i>heniochus</i> Fowler, 1904				
2930	<i>Epinephelus hexagonatus</i> (Forster, 1801)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2008)	
2931	<i>Epinephelus lanceolatus</i> (Bloch, 1790)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2008)	
2932	<i>Epinephelus latifasciatus</i> (Temminck & Schlegel, 1842)	M	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2011a, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2008)	
2933	<i>Epinephelus lebretonianus</i> (Hombron & Jacquinot, 1853)	M	TN	(Akhilesh et al. 2021)	
2934	<i>Epinephelus longispinis</i> (Kner, 1864)	M	ANI, LK, WB, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Ray & Mahapatra 2022)	Chennai
2935	<i>Epinephelus macrospilos</i> (Bleeker, 1855)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2008)	
2936	<i>Epinephelus maculatus</i> (Bloch, 1790)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2008)	
2937	<i>Epinephelus magniscuttis</i> Postel, Fourmanoir & Guézé, 1963	M	WB, AP	(Ray & Mahapatra 2022)	
2938	<i>Epinephelus malabaricus</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2008, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	Tharangambadi
2939	<i>Epinephelus melanostigma</i> Schultz, 1953	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2008)	
2940	<i>Epinephelus merra</i> Bloch, 1793	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2008)	
2941	<i>Epinephelus miliaris</i> (Valenciennes, 1830)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2008)	
2942	<i>Epinephelus morrhua</i> (Valenciennes, 1833)	M	LK, OD, TN, MH	(Rajan et al. 2021, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2008, Barman et al. 2012)	
2943	<i>Epinephelus ongus</i> (Bloch, 1790)	MB	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2008)	
2944	<i>Epinephelus poecilonotus</i> (Temminck & Schlegel, 1843)	MB	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2008)	
2945	<i>Epinephelus polylepis</i> Randall & Heemstra, 1991	M	LK, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2021, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	
2946	<i>Epinephelus polyphkadion</i> (Bleeker, 1849)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2008)	
2947	<i>Epinephelus polystigma</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	BF	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2948	<i>Epinephelus quoyanus</i> (Valenciennes, 1830)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2008)	
2949	<i>Epinephelus radiatus</i> (Day, 1868)	M	ANI, WB, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Ray & Mahapatra 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2008)	Near Chennai
2950	<i>Epinephelus retouti</i> Bleeker, 1868	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2008)	
2951	<i>Epinephelus rivulatus</i> (Valenciennes, 1830)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2008)	

2952	<i>Epinephelus sexfasciatus</i> (Valenciennes, 1828)	M	ANI, WB, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Ray & Mahapatra 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2008)	
2953	<i>Epinephelus spilotoceps</i> Schultz, 1953	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2008)	
2954	<i>Epinephelus stoliczkae</i> (Day, 1875)	M	KA, MH	(Barman et al. 2012, 2013a, Sharma & Dhanze 2018)	
2955	<i>Epinephelus summana</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	M	ANI, LK	(Akhilesh et al. 2021)	
2956	<i>Epinephelus tauvina</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, GA	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2008, Talwar 1974)	
2957	<i>Epinephelus tukula</i> Morgans, 1959	M	KL	(Kapoor et al. 2002)	
2958	<i>Epinephelus undulosus</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1824)	M	ANI, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2008)	
2959	<i>Gracila albomarginata</i> (Fowler & Bean, 1930)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
2960	<i>Hyporthodus chabaudi</i> (Castelnau, 1861)	M	KA	(Barman et al. 2013a)	
2961	<i>Hyporthodus octofasciatus</i> (Griffin, 1926)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2008)	
2962	<i>Hyporthodus septemfasciatus</i> (Thunberg, 1793)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2008)	
2963	<i>Plectropomus areolatus</i> (Rüppell, 1830)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
2964	<i>Plectropomus laevis</i> (Lacepède, 1801)	M	ANI, LK, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Nair et al. 2013)	
2965	<i>Plectropomus leopardus</i> (Lacepède, 1802)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
2966	<i>Plectropomus maculatus</i> (Bloch, 1790)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
2967	<i>Plectropomus pessuliferus</i> (Fowler, 1904)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2968	<i>Variola albimarginata</i> Baissac, 1953	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2969	<i>Variola louti</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Grammistidae Bleeker, 1857					
2970	<i>Aporops bilinearis</i> Schultz, 1943	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
2971	<i>Grammistes sexlineatus</i> (Thunberg, 1792)	M	ANI, LK, TN, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
2972	<i>Pseudogramma cernunnos</i> Prokofiev, 2019	M	ANI	(Prokofiev 2019)	Bay of Bengal, 6°40'04"N, 93°52'06"E, depth 52 meters
2973	<i>Pseudogramma polyacanthus</i> (Bleeker, 1856)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
2974	<i>Pogonoperca ocellata</i> Günther, 1859	M	ANI, WB, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Ray et al. 2023, Mogalekar et al. 2008)	

2975	<i>Pogonoperca punctata</i> (Valenciennes, 1830)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2008)	
Family: Labridae Cuvier, 1816					
2976	<i>Anampses caeruleopunctatus</i> Rüppell, 1829	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
2977	<i>Anampses lineatus</i> Randall, 1972	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2978	<i>Anampses meleagrides</i> Valenciennes, 1840	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
2979	<i>Bodianus axillaris</i> (Bennett, 1832)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
2980	<i>Bodianus diana</i> (Lacepède, 1801)	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2981	<i>Bodianus leucosticticus</i> (Bennett, 1832)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2982	<i>Bodianus macrourus</i> (Lacepède, 1801)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2983	<i>Bodianus mesothorax</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2984	<i>Bodianus neilli</i> (Day, 1867)	M	AP, TN	(Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Chennai
2985	<i>Bolbometopon muricatum</i> (Valenciennes, 1840)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2986	<i>Calotomus carolinus</i> (Valenciennes, 1840)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2987	<i>Calotomus spinidens</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1824)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2988	<i>Calotomus viridescens</i> (Rüppell, 1835)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2989	<i>Cetoscarus bicolor</i> (Rüppell, 1829)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2990	<i>Cheilio inermis</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Rajan et al. 2013, Rajan et al. 2021)	
2991	<i>Cheilinus chlorourus</i> (Bloch, 1791)	M	ANI, LK, WB, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Pradhan et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2992	<i>Cheilinus fasciatus</i> (Bloch, 1791)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2993	<i>Cheilinus oxycephalus</i> Bleeker, 1853	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2994	<i>Cheilinus trilobatus</i> Lacepède, 1801	MB	ANI, LK, TN, KL, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al., 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
2995	<i>Cheilinus undulatus</i> Rüppell, 1835	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
2996	<i>Chlorurus atrilunula</i> (Randall & Bruce, 1983)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
2997	<i>Chlorurus bleekeri</i> (de Beaufort, 1940)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
2998	<i>Chlorurus enneacanthus</i> (Lacepède, 1802)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
2999	<i>Chlorurus gibbus</i> (Rüppell, 1835)	M	ANI, AP,	(Rajan et al. 2013, Silambarasan et al.	

	1829)		TN	2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3000	<i>Chlorurus japanensis</i> (Bloch, 1789)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3001	<i>Chlorurus sordidus</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	MB	ANI, LK, TN, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
3002	<i>Chlorurus strongylocephalus</i> (Bleeker, 1855)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
3003	<i>Chlorurus oedema</i> (Snyder, 1909)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3004	<i>Choerodon anchorago</i> (Bloch, 1791)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3005	<i>Choerodon robustus</i> (Günther, 1862)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3006	<i>Choerodon typus</i> (Bleeker, 1856)	M	ANI, TN	(Randall 1997, Nashad et al. 2023)	
3007	<i>Choerodon zamboangae</i> (Seale & Bean, 1907)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3008	<i>Cirrhilabrus exquisitus</i> Smith, 1957	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
3009	<i>Cirrhilabrus rubeus</i> Victor, 2016	M	TN	(Kodeeswaran et al. 2023b)	
3010	<i>Coris aygula</i> Lacepède, 1801	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3011	<i>Coris aurilineata</i> Randall & Kuitert, 1982	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
3012	<i>Coris batuensis</i> (Bleeker, 1856)	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
3013	<i>Coris caudimacula</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1834)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3014	<i>Coris cuvieri</i> (Bennett, 1831)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
3015	<i>Coris formosa</i> (Bennett, 1830)	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3016	<i>Coris gaimard</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1824)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3017	<i>Coris latifasciata</i> Randall, 2013	M	LK	(Anto et al. 2024)	
3018	<i>Cymolutes lecluse</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1824)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3019	<i>Cymolutes praetextatus</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1834)	M	ANI, AP, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3020	<i>Cymolutes torquatus</i> (Valenciennes, 1840)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3021	<i>Diproctacanthus xanthurus</i> (Bleeker, 1856)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
3022	<i>Epibulus insidiator</i> (Pallas, 1770)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3023	<i>Gomphosus caeruleus</i> Lacepède, 1801	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3024	<i>Gomphosus varius</i> Lacepède, 1801	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
3025	<i>Halichoeres argus</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	

3026	<i>Halichoeres bicolor</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3027	<i>Halichoeres chloropterus</i> (Bloch, 1791)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3028	<i>Halichoeres chrysurus</i> Randall, 1981	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3029	<i>Halichoeres cosmetus</i> Randall & Smith, 1982	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
3030	<i>Halichoeres hartzfeldii</i> (Bleeker, 1852)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3031	<i>Halichoeres hortulanus</i> (Lacepède, 1801)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3032	<i>Halichoeres leucurus</i> (Walbaum, 1792)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3033	<i>Halichoeres leucoxanthus</i> Randall & Smith, 1982	M	ANI, LK	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Anto et al. 2024)	
3034	<i>Halichoeres margaritaceus</i> (Valenciennes, 1839)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3035	<i>Halichoeres marginatus</i> Rüppell, 1835	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL, KA	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a)	
3036	<i>Halichoeres melanurus</i> (Bleeker, 1851)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3037	<i>Halichoeres melanochir</i> Fowler & Bean, 1928	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3038	<i>Halichoeres nebulosus</i> (Valenciennes, 1839)	M	ANI, LK, TN, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	Mumbai
3039	<i>Halichoeres nigrescens</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	M	ANI, TN, KL, GA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, Talwar 1974)	
3040	<i>Halichoeres scapularis</i> (Bennett, 1832)	M	ANI, LK, OD, TN, KL, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
3041	<i>Halichoeres timorensis</i> (Bleeker, 1852)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3042	<i>Halichoeres vrolikii</i> (Bleeker, 1855)	M	ANI, LK	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Rajan et al. 2021)	
3043	<i>Halichoeres zeylonicus</i> (Bennett, 1833)	M	LK, WB, AP, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Pradhan et al. 2019, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3044	<i>Hemigymnus fasciatus</i> (Bloch, 1792)	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3045	<i>Hemigymnus melapterus</i> (Bloch, 1791)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3046	<i>Hipposcarus harid</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3047	<i>Hologymnosus annulatus</i> (Lacepède, 1801)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3048	<i>Hologymnosus doliatus</i> (Lacepède, 1801)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	

3049	<i>Iniistius bimaculatus</i> (Rüppell, 1829)	M	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Pradhan & Mahapatra 2017, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Mohanty et al. 2021)	
3050	<i>Iniistius cyanifrons</i> (Valenciennes, 1840)	M	TN, KL, MH	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	Puducherry
3051	<i>Iniistius dea</i> (Temminck & Schlegel, 1845)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3052	<i>Iniistius pavo</i> (Valenciennes, 1840)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3053	<i>Iniistius pentadactylus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	M	ANI, TN, KL, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
3054	<i>Iniistius rajagopalani</i> (Venkataramanjam, Venkataramani & Ramanathan, 1987)	M	TN	(Venkataramanjam et al. 1987)	Tuticorin Bay, Tamil Nadu
3055	<i>Iniistius twistii</i> (Bleeker, 1856)	M	KL	(Biju et al. 2019)	
3056	<i>Labrichthys unilineatus</i> (Guichenot, 1847)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
3057	<i>Labroides bicolor</i> Fowler & Bean, 1928	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
3058	<i>Labroides dimidiatus</i> (Valenciennes, 1839)	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3059	<i>Leptojulius chrysotaenia</i> Randall & Ferraris, 1981	M	Southern India	(Allen & Erdmann 2012)	
3060	<i>Leptojulius cyanopleura</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	M	TN, KL	(Randall 1996, Padate et al. 2017)	
3061	<i>Leptojulius lambdastigma</i> Randall & Ferraris, 1981	M	ANI	(Jayakumar et al. 2020)	
3062	<i>Leptoscarus vaigiensis</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1824)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3063	<i>Macropharyngodon meleagris</i> (Valenciennes, 1839)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3064	<i>Macropharyngodon ornatus</i> Randall, 1978	M	TN	(Padate et al. 2014)	
3065	<i>Novaculichthys taeniourus</i> (Lacepède, 1801)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3066	<i>Novaculooides macrolepidotus</i> (Bloch, 1791)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
3067	<i>Oxycheilinus arenatus</i> (Valenciennes, 1840)	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Murugan et al. 2022)	
3068	<i>Oxycheilinus bimaculatus</i> (Valenciennes, 1840)	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3069	<i>Oxycheilinus digramma</i> (Lacepède, 1801)	MB	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3070	<i>Paracheilinus mccoskeri</i> Randall &	M	TN	(Kodeeswaran et al. 2023b)	

	Harmelin-Vivien 1977				
3071	<i>Pseudocheilinus evanidus</i> Jordan & Evermann, 1903	M	LK	(Anto et al. 2024)	
3072	<i>Pseudocheilinus hexataenia</i> (Bleeker, 1857)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3073	<i>Pseudodax moluccanus</i> (Valenciennes, 1840)	M	ANI, LK, OD	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Pati et al. 2018)	
3074	<i>Pteragogus flagellifer</i> (Valenciennes, 1839)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
3075	<i>Scarus altipinnis</i> (Steindachner, 1879)	M	LK	(Sandra et al. 2022)	
3076	<i>Scarus arabicus</i> (Steindachner, 1902)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3077	<i>Scarus dimidiatus</i> Bleeker, 1859	MB	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
3078	<i>Scarus dubius</i> Bennett, 1828	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3079	<i>Scarus falcipinnis</i> (Playfair, 1868)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
3080	<i>Scarus ferrugineus</i> Forsskål, 1775	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3081	<i>Scarus festivus</i> Valenciennes, 1840	MB	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3082	<i>Scarus flavipectoralis</i> Schultz, 1958	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3083	<i>Scarus frenatus</i> Lacepède, 1802	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3084	<i>Scarus ghobban</i> Forsskål, 1775	MB	ANI, LK, WB, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2013, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, 2013a)	
3085	<i>Scarus globiceps</i> Valenciennes, 1840	M	ANI, LK, TN, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
3086	<i>Scarus niger</i> Forsskål, 1775	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3087	<i>Scarus prasiognathos</i> Valenciennes, 1840	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3088	<i>Scarus psittacus</i> Forsskål, 1775	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3089	<i>Scarus quoyi</i> Valenciennes, 1840	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3090	<i>Scarus rivulatus</i> Valenciennes, 1840	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3091	<i>Scarus rubroviolaceus</i> Bleeker, 1847	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3092	<i>Scarus russelii</i> Valenciennes, 1840	M	LK, AP, TN, KL, KA	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Visakhapatnam
3093	<i>Scarus scaber</i> Valenciennes, 1840	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	

3094	<i>Scarus schlegeli</i> (Bleeker, 1861)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
3095	<i>Scarus tricolor</i> Bleeker, 1847	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3096	<i>Stethojulis albovittata</i> (Bonnaterre, 1788)	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3097	<i>Stethojulis balteata</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1824)	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3098	<i>Stethojulis interrupta</i> (Bleeker, 1851)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3099	<i>Stethojulis strigiventer</i> (Bennett, 1833)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3100	<i>Stethojulis trilineata</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Coromandel
3101	<i>Thalassoma amblycephalus</i> (Bleeker, 1856)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3102	<i>Thalassoma hardwicke</i> (Bennett, 1830)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3103	<i>Thalassoma hebraicum</i> (Lacepède, 1801)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
3104	<i>Thalassoma janseni</i> (Bleeker, 1856)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3105	<i>Thalassoma lunare</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL, AP	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Kumar et al. 2024)	
3106	<i>Thalassoma lutescens</i> (Lay & Bennett, 1839)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3107	<i>Thalassoma purpureum</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3108	<i>Thalassoma quinquevittatum</i> (Lay & Bennett, 1839)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3109	<i>Thalassoma trilobatum</i> (Lacepède, 1801)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Pinguipedidae Günther, 1860					
3110	<i>Parapercis annamalai</i> Yosuva, Ho, Jeyapragash & Saravanakuamr, 2020	M	TN	(Yosuva et al. 2020)	Off coast of Parangipettai, south-eastern India, Bay of Bengal
3111	<i>Parapercis alboguttata</i> (Gunther, 1872)	M	AP, TN, MH	(Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3112	<i>Parapercis clathrata</i> Ogilby, 1910	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3113	<i>Parapercis cylindrica</i> (Bloch, 1792)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3114	<i>Parapercis diplospilus</i> Gomon, 1981	M	WB	(Ray & Mohapatra 2016a)	
3115	<i>Parapercis hexoptalma</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3116	<i>Parapercis lineopunctata</i> Randall, 2003	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
3117	<i>Parapercis maculata</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	M	TN	(Bloch & Schneider 1801)	Tuticorin

3118	<i>Parapercis millepunctata</i> (Günther, 1860)	M	ANI, LK	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Rajan et al. 2021)	
3119	<i>Parapercis nebulosa</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1825)	M	AP, TN, GJ	(Barman et al. 2000, 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3120	<i>Parapercis ommatura</i> Jordan & Snyder, 1902	M	WB	(Ray & Mohapatra 2015a)	
3121	<i>Parapercis pulchella</i> (Temminck & Schlegel, 1843)	M	TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3122	<i>Parapercis punctulata</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3123	<i>Parapercis schauinslandii</i> (Steindachner, 1900)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3124	<i>Parapercis snyderi</i> Jordan & Starks, 1905	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3125	<i>Parapercis xanthozona</i> (Bleeker, 1849)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
Family: Plectrogeniidae Fowler, 1938					
3126	<i>Bembradium magnoculum</i> Kishimoto, Kawai, Tashiro & Aungtonya, 2019	M	ANI	(Aneesh Kumar et al. 2019)	
Family: Liopropomatidae Poey, 1867					
3127	<i>Aulacocephalus temminckii</i> Bleeker, 1855	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3128	<i>Diploprion bifasciatum</i> Cuvier, 1828	M	ANI, LK, OD, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
3129	<i>Liopropoma lunulatum</i> (Guichenot, 1863)	M	KL	(Nair et al. 2013)	
3130	<i>Liopropoma randalli</i> Akhilesh, Bineesh & White, 2012	M	KL	(Biju et al. 2019)	Cochin, Kerala
Family: Platycephalidae Swainson, 1839					
3131	<i>Cociella crocodilus</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Sanyal et al. 2012, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3132	<i>Cociella punctata</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3133	<i>Cymbacephalus beauforti</i> (Knapp, 1973)	M	ANI	(Rajan & Vikas 2016)	
3134	<i>Sunagocia carbunculus</i> (Valenciennes, 1833)	M	ANI, AP, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Barman et al. 2004, 2012)	Mumbai
3135	<i>Grammoplites scaber</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Khan 2002, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3136	<i>Grammoplites suppositus</i> (Troschel, 1840)	M	LK, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	Mumbai
3137	<i>Inegocia japonica</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	ANI, OD, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	

3138	<i>Insidiator macracanthus</i> (Bleeker, 1869)	M	TN, MH	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
3139	<i>Kumococius rodericensis</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Sanyal et al. 2012, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3140	<i>Onigocia oligolepis</i> (Regan, 1908)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3141	<i>Platycephalus indicus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Khan 2002, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	
3142	<i>Ratabulus melanopterus</i> (Knapp & Wongratana, 1987)	M	OD, TN, KA	(Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a)	3.2 kilometers off Cochin
3143	<i>Ratabulus tuberculatus</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Khan 2002, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Pati et al. 2018)	
3144	<i>Rogadius asper</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3145	<i>Rogadius pristiger</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	OD	(Pati et al. 2018)	
3146	<i>Rogadius serratus</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3147	<i>Rogadius welanderi</i> (Schultz, 1966)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3148	<i>Sunagocia carbunculus</i> (Valenciennes, 1833)	M	TN, KL, GA, MH	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, Hedge et al. 2013)	Mumbai
3149	<i>Sunagocia otaitensis</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3150	<i>Thysanophrys armata</i> (Fowler, 1938)	M	GA	(Hedge et al. 2013)	
3151	<i>Thysanophrys celebica</i> (Bleeker, 1855)	M	ANI, WB, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Chakraborty et a 2020a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3152	<i>Thysanophrys chiltonae</i> Schultz, 1966	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
Family: Scorpaenidae Risso, 1827					
3153	<i>Brachypterois serrulifer</i> Fowler, 1938	M	WB, OD, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Matsunuma & Motomura 2017)	
3154	<i>Caracanthus maculatus</i> (Gray, 1831)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
3155	<i>Caracanthus unipinna</i> (Gray, 1831)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
3156	<i>Dendrochirus bellus</i> (Jordan & Hubbs, 1925)	M	TN	(Padate et al. 2017)	
3157	<i>Dendrochirus biocellatus</i> (Fowler, 1938)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3158	<i>Dendrochirus brachypterus</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3159	<i>Dendrochirus zebra</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3160	<i>Ebosia falcata</i> Eschmeyer &	M	WB, AP	(Roy et al. 2022, Naranji & Sujatha 2016)	

	Rama-Rao, 1978				
3161	<i>Lythrichthys longimanus</i> (Alcock, 1894)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Andaman Sea
3162	<i>Neomerinthe amplisquamiceps</i> (Fowler, 1938)	M	AP	(Naranji et al. 2020)	
3163	<i>Neomerinthe erostris</i> (Alcock, 1896)	M	AP	(Mohapatra et al. 2016)	
3164	<i>Neomerinthe megalepis</i> (Fowler, 1938)	M	WB	(Ray & Mahapatra 2022c)	
3165	<i>Parapterois heterurus</i> (Bleeker, 1856)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3166	<i>Parapterois macrura</i> (Alcock, 1896)	M	KL	(Biju et al. 2019)	Malabar Coast off Calicut
3167	<i>Parascorpaena aurita</i> (Rüppell, 1838)	M	GA	(Talwar 1974)	
3168	<i>Parascorpaena picta</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3169	<i>Phenacoscorpius adenensis</i> Norman, 1939	M	LK	(Idreesbabu & Sivanpillai 2021)	
3170	<i>Pteroidichthys amboinensis</i> Bleeker, 1856	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3171	<i>Pterois antennata</i> (Bloch, 1787)	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3172	<i>Pterois lunulata</i> Temminck & Schlegel, 1843	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3173	<i>Pterois miles</i> (Bennett, 1828)	M	ANI, LK, OD, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3174	<i>Pterois mombasae</i> (Smith, 1957)	M	AP, TN	(Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3175	<i>Pterois paucispinula</i> Matsunuma & Motomura, 2014	M	AP	(Naranji et al. 2016)	
3176	<i>Pterois radiata</i> Cuvier, 1829	M	ANI, LK, OD, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3177	<i>Pterois russelii</i> Bennett, 1831	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	Coromandel coast
3178	<i>Pterois volitans</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	MB	ANI, WB, AP, TN, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Yennawar et al. 2015, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3179	<i>Rhinopias eschmeyeri</i> Condé, 1977	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3180	<i>Scorpaena neglecta</i> Temminck & Schlegel, 1843	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3181	<i>Scorpaenopsis cirrosa</i> (Thunberg, 1793)	M	ANI, LK, OD, TN, KL, GA	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
3182	<i>Scorpaenopsis diabolus</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2017)	
3183	<i>Scorpaenopsis gibbosa</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	

3184	<i>Scorpaenopsis macrochir</i> Ogilby, 1910	M	AP	(Naranji et al. 2017)	
3185	<i>Scorpaenopsis neglecta</i> Heckel, 1837	M	Eastern Indian Coast	(Allen & Erdmann 2012)	
3186	<i>Scorpaenopsis obtusa</i> Randall & Eschmeyer, 2002	M	TN	(Subburaman et al. 2023)	
3187	<i>Scorpaenopsis oxycephalus</i> (Bleeker, 1849)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3188	<i>Scorpaenopsis ramaraoi</i> Randall & Eschmeyer, 2002	M	WB, AP	(Ray et al. 2015b, Silambarasan et al. 2022)	
3189	<i>Scorpaenopsis venosa</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	ANI, AP, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Bay of Bengal
3190	<i>Scorpaenodes corallinus</i> Smith, 1957	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3191	<i>Scorpaenodes guamensis</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1824)	M	ANI, LK, OD, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Biswas et al. 2012, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3192	<i>Scorpaenodes muciparus</i> (Alcock, 1889)	M	OD	(Pati et al. 2018)	26 miles north by east of Gopalpur,
3193	<i>Scorpaenodes parvipinnis</i> (Garrett, 1864)	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3194	<i>Scorpaenodes smithi</i> Eschmeyer & Ramarao, 1972	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Andaman Sea, off western Malaya, Andaman Islands, 5°45'N, 98°20'E
3195	<i>Sebastapistes cyanostigma</i> (Bleeker, 1856)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
3196	<i>Sebastapistes strongia</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3197	<i>Setarches guentheri</i> Johnson, 1862	M	ANI, KL, KA	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2013a)	
3198	<i>Taenianotus triacanthus</i> Lacepède, 1802	M	ANI, LK	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Rajan et al. 2021)	
Family: Serranidae Swainson, 1839					
3199	<i>Chelidoperca investigatoris</i> (Alcock, 1890)	M	OD, TN	(Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Off Madras coast
3200	<i>Chelidoperca maculicauda</i> Bineesh & Akhilesh, 2013	M	KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Bineesh et al. 2013)	Off Kollam, Kerala coast
3201	<i>Chelidoperca occipitalis</i> Kottaus, 1973	M	AP, KL	(Bineesh et al. 2013, Rao & Naranji 2016)	
3202	<i>Chelidoperca pleurospilus</i> (Günther, 1880)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3203	<i>Chelidoperca stella</i> Matsunuma & Motomura, 2016	M	ANI	(Matsunuma & Motomura 2016)	Paratype collected from ANI
3204	<i>Serranus cabrilla</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	M	KL	(Parenti & Randall 2020)	
Family: Synanceiidae Swainson, 1839					
3205	<i>Ablabys binotatus</i> (Peters, 1855)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3206	<i>Ablabys macracanthus</i> (Bleeker, 1852)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Murugan et al. 2023)	

3207	<i>Ablabys taenianotus</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	ANI, OD	(Rajan et al. 2013, Pati et al. 2018)	
3208	<i>Acanthosphelex leuryynnis</i> (Jordan & Seale, 1905)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3209	<i>Apistus carinatus</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	M	OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	
3210	<i>Choridactylus multibarbus</i> Richardson, 1848	M	LK, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	
3211	<i>Cocotropus roseus</i> Day, 1875	M	WB, TN	(Ray & Mohapatra 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Coromandel coast
3212	<i>Cocotropus echinatus</i> (Cantor, 1849)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3213	<i>Cocotropus steinitzi</i> Eschmeyer & Dor, 1978	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3214	<i>Inimicus caledonicus</i> (Sauvage, 1878)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3215	<i>Inimicus cuvieri</i> (Gray, 1835)	M	Andaman Sea	(Allen & Erdmann 2012, Kodeeswaran et al. 2020a)	
3216	<i>Inimicus didactylus</i> (Pallas, 1769)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3217	<i>Inimicus filamentosus</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Kodeeswaran et al. 2020a)	
3218	<i>Inimicus sinensis</i> (Valenciennes, 1833)	M	Southern India	(Lieske & Myers 1994, Kodeeswaran et al. 2020a)	
3219	<i>Minous coccineus</i> Alcock, 1890	M	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL	(Eschmeyer et al. 1979)	off Ganjam, Odisha
3220	<i>Minous dempsterae</i> Eschmeyer, Hallacher & Rama-Rao, 1979	M	AP, TN, MH, GJ	(Eschmeyer et al. 1979, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Off Pobandar coast, Gujarat
3221	<i>Minous inermis</i> Alcock, 1889	M	LK, WB, AP, TN, KL, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2021, Eschmeyer et al., 1979)	Off Godavari Coast, Andhra Pradesh
3222	<i>Minous monodactylus</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	M	LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2021, Eschmeyer et al. 1979, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a, Talwar 1974)	
3223	<i>Minous pictus</i> Günther, 1880	M	WB, AP	(Ray et al. 2022a, Silambarasan et al. 2022)	
3224	<i>Minous trachycephalus</i> (Bleeker, 1855)	M	WB, OD, TN	(Eschmeyer et al. 1979, Ray et al. 2022a, Pati et al. 2018)	Reported from the GoM in between TN & Srilanka
3225	<i>Neovespicula depressifrons</i> (Richardson, 1848)	MBF	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3226	<i>Ocosia ramaraoi</i> Poss & Eschmeyer, 1975	M	KL	(Poss & Eschmeyer 1975)	Quilon coast
3227	<i>Paracentropogon longispinis</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	

3228	<i>Paraploactis taprobanensis</i> (Whitley, 1933)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3229	<i>Pseudovespicula dracaena</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	TN, KA	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a)	Malabar coast
3230	<i>Pseudosynanceia melanostigma</i> Day, 1875	M	GJ	(Day 1875)	
3231	<i>Richardsonichthys leucogaster</i> (Richardson, 1848)	M	TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3232	<i>Synanceia alula</i> Eschmeyer & Rama-Rao, 1973	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Nancowry Island, Nicobar
3233	<i>Synanceia horrida</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
3234	<i>Synanceia verrucosa</i> Bloch & Schneider, 1801	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	India
3235	<i>Snyderina guentheri</i> (Boulenger, 1889)	M	AP, TN	(Silambarasan et al. 2022, Padate et al. 2017)	
3236	<i>Tetraroge barbata</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3237	<i>Tetraroge nigra</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	MBF	ANI, OD, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Puducherry
3238	<i>Trachicephalus uranoscopus</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, TN, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Eschmeyer & Rama Rao 1973, Ray et al. 2022a, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	Tranquebar, India
3239	<i>Trichosomus trachinoides</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	MB	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3240	<i>Xenaploactis cautes</i> Poss & Eschmeyer, 1980	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
Family: Triglidae Rafinesque, 1815					
3241	<i>Heminodus philippinus</i> Smith, 1917	M	ANI	(Rajeeshkumar et al. 2018)	
3242	<i>Lepidotrigla bispinosa</i> Steindachner, 1898	M	AP, MH	(Silambarasan et al. 2022, Barman et al. 2012)	
3243	<i>Lepidotrigla faurei</i> Gilchrist & Thompson, 1914	M	TN, KL, KA, MH	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, 2013a)	
3244	<i>Lepidotrigla longipinnis</i> Alcock, 1890	M	ANI, OD, TN, KL, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	Bay of Bengal, off Ganjam Coast
3245	<i>Lepidotrigla omanensis</i> Regan, 1905	M	TN, KA, MH	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, 2013a)	
3246	<i>Lepidotrigla spiloptera</i> Günther, 1880	M	OD, TN	(Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3247	<i>Peristedion amblygenys</i> Fowler, 1938	M	ANI	(Rajeeshkumar et al. 2021)	
3248	<i>Peristedion liorhynchus</i> (Günther, 1872)	M	ANI, KL	(Rajeeshkumar et al. 2021)	
3249	<i>Pterygotrigla arabica</i> (Boulenger, 1888)	M	WB, TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Ray & Mohapatra 2016b, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3250	<i>Pterygotrigla hemisticta</i> (Temminck & Schlegel, 1843)	M	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Ray & Mohapatra 2016b, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3251	<i>Pterygotrigla intermedica</i> Roy, Ray, Mishra, Mishra & Mohapatra, 2023	M	WB	(Ray et al. 2023a)	Digha Mohana fishing harbour, West Bengal

3252	<i>Satyrichthys laticeps</i> (Schlegel, 1852)	M	TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3253	<i>Satyrichthys milleri</i> Kawai, 2013	M	GJ	(Kannan et al. 2017)	
3254	<i>Scalicus hians</i> (Gilbert & Cramer, 1897)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3255	<i>Scalicus serrulatus</i> (Alcock, 1898)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Andaman Sea, 13°17'15"N, 93°10'25"E
3256	<i>Paraheminodus murrayi</i> (Günther, 1880)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
Family: Uranoscopidae Bonaparte, 1831					
3257	<i>Ichthyscopus inermis</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Coromandel, Malabar, Puducherry
3258	<i>Ichthyscopus lebeck</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	M	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, MH	(Biju et al. 2019, Chakraborty et a 2020a, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, Velamala & Naranji 2018)	Tharangambadi
3259	<i>Uranoscopus crassiceps</i> Alcock, 1890	M	WB, OD, KL	(Pati et al. 2018, Pradhan et al. 2019a, Mullasserri et al. 2017a)	Off Madras coast
3260	<i>Uranoscopus cognatus</i> Cantor, 1849	M	WB, OD, TN	(Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3261	<i>Uranoscopus dollfusi</i> Brüß, 1987	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2019)	
3262	<i>Uranoscopus guttatus</i> Cuvier, 1829	M	OD, AP, TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Puducherry
Order: Polymixiiformes					
Family: Polymixiidae Bleeker, 1859					
3263	<i>Polymixia berndti</i> Gilbert, 1905	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3264	<i>Polymixia busakhini</i> Kotlyar, 1992	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3265	<i>Polymixia fusca</i> Kotthaus, 1970	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3266	<i>Polymixia japonica</i> Günther, 1877	M	LK, KL	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019)	
Order: Salmoniformes					
Family: Salmonidae Jarocki or Schinz, 1822					
3267	<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i> (Walbaum, 1792)	F	LD, J&K, UK	(Bhat et al. 2020, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021)	
3268	<i>Salmo trutta</i> Linnaeus, 1758	F	LD, J&K, UK	(Bhat et al. 2020, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021)	
Order: Scombriformes					
Family: Ariommatidae Haedrich, 1967					
3269	<i>Ariomma indica</i> (Day, 1871)	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Chennai
3270	<i>Ariomma brevimanus</i> (Klunzinger, 1884)	M	KL	(Roul et al. 2019)	
Family: Bramidae Bonaparte, 1831					
3271	<i>Brama brama</i> (Bonnaterre, 1785)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	

	1788)				
3272	<i>Brama myersi</i> Mead, 1972	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
3273	<i>Eumegistus illustris</i> Jordan & Jordan, 1922	M	LK	(Aju et al. 2023)	
3274	<i>Taractes rubescens</i> (Jordan & Evermann, 1887)	M	ANI, WB, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Ray et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Centrolophidae Bonaparte, 1846					
3275	<i>Psenopsis cyanea</i> (Alcock, 1890)	M	OD, TN, KL, KA, MH	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, 2013a)	Off Madras coast, India, 18°30'N, 84°46'E
3276	<i>Psenopsis intermedia</i> Piotrovsky, 1987	M	KA	(Thomas & Rohit 2007)	
3277	<i>Psenopsis obscura</i> Haedrich, 1967	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
Family: Chiasmodontidae Jordan & Gilbert, 1883					
3278	<i>Chiasmodon niger</i> Johnson, 1864	M	OD	(Pati et al. 2018)	
3279	<i>Champsodon atridorsalis</i> Ochiai & Nakamura, 1964	M	KL	(Chakraborty et al. 2023)	
3280	<i>Champsodon sagittus</i> Nemeth, 1994	M	TN	(Rahangdale et al. 2018)	
3281	<i>Champsodon vorax</i> Günther, 1867	M	OD	(Pati et al. 2018)	
3282	<i>Dysalotus alcocki</i> MacGilchrist, 1905	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Bay of Bengal, south of Andaman Islands
Family: Gempylidae Gill, 1862					
3283	<i>Gempylus serpens</i> Cuvier, 1829	M	LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3284	<i>Leionura atun</i> (Euphrasen, 1791)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3285	<i>Lepidocybium flavobrunneum</i> (Smith, 1843)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3286	<i>Nealotus tripes</i> Johnson, 1865	M	AP, TN, KL, KA	(Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3287	<i>Neoepinnula orientalis</i> (Gilchrist & von Bonde, 1924)	M	TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	
3288	<i>Promethichthys prometheus</i> (Cuvier, 1832)	M	LK, KL, KA	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2013a)	
3289	<i>Rexea prometheoides</i> (Bleeker, 1856)	M	KL, KA	(Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2013a)	
3290	<i>Rexea bengalensis</i> (Alcock, 1894)	MB	AP, TN, KL, KA	(Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Off Madras
3291	<i>Rexea prometheoides</i> (Bleeker, 1856)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3292	<i>Ruvettus pretiosus</i> Cocco, 1833	M	LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3293	<i>Thyrstitoides marleyi</i> Fowler, 1929	M	LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	

Family: Nomeidae Günther, 1860					
3294	<i>Cubiceps pauciradiatus</i> Günther, 1872	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3295	<i>Cubiceps whiteleggii</i> (Waite, 1894)	M	TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3296	<i>Psenes cyanophrys</i> Valenciennes, 1833	M	LK, OD, TN, MH	(Rajan et al. 2021, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
3297	<i>Psenes maculatus</i> Lütken, 1880	MB	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
Family: Pomatomidae Gill, 1863					
3298	<i>Pomatomus saltatrix</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	MB	KA	(Barman et al. 2013a)	
Family: Scombridae Rafinesque, 1815					
3299	<i>Acanthocybium solandri</i> (Cuvier, 1832)	M	LK, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	
3300	<i>Auxis rochei</i> (Risso, 1810)	MB	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3301	<i>Auxis thazard</i> (Lacepède, 1800)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3302	<i>Euthynnus affinis</i> (Cantor, 1849)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Kar et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3303	<i>Grammatorcynus bicarinatus</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1825)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3304	<i>Gymnosarda unicolor</i> (Rüppell, 1836)	M	ANI, LK, KL, KA	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2013a)	
3305	<i>Katsuwonus pelamis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3306	<i>Rastrelliger brachysoma</i> (Bleeker, 1851)	MB	ANI, OD	(Rajan et al. 2013, Pati et al. 2018)	
3307	<i>Rastrelliger faughni</i> Matsui, 1967	M	ANI, AP, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3308	<i>Rastrelliger kanagurta</i> (Cuvier, 1816)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al., 2013, Rajan et al., 2021, Biju et al., 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a, Barman et al. 2012, Barman et al. 2000, Talwar 1974)	
3309	<i>Sarda orientalis</i> (Temminck & Schlegel, 1844)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3310	<i>Scomber australasicus</i> Cuvier, 1832	M	KL	(Abdussamad et al. 2016)	
3311	<i>Scomberomorus avirostrus</i> Abdussamad, Toji, Margaret, Mini, Rajesh et al., 2023	M	KA	(Abdussamad et al. 2023)	Karwar, Arabian Sea, west coast of India, 14.81°N, 74.12°E

3312	<i>Scomberomorus commerson</i> (Lacepède, 1800)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3313	<i>Scomberomorus guttatus</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2008, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	Tharangambadi
3314	<i>Scomberomorus koreanus</i> (Kishinouye, 1915)	M	AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3315	<i>Scomberomorus leopardus</i> (Shaw, 1803)	M	TN	(Abdussamad et al. 2023)	Coromandel coast
3316	<i>Scomberomorus lineolatus</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Visakhapatnam
3317	<i>Thunnus alalunga</i> (Bonnaterre, 1788)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3318	<i>Thunnus albacares</i> (Bonnaterre, 1788)	MB	ANI, LK, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3319	<i>Thunnus obesus</i> (Lowe, 1839)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3320	<i>Thunnus orientalis</i> (Temminck & Schlegel, 1844)	M	OD	(Pati et al. 2018)	
3321	<i>Thunnus tonggol</i> (Bleeker, 1851)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Stromateidae Rafinesque, 1810					
3322	<i>Pampus argenteus</i> (Euphrasen, 1788)	M	ANI, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	
3323	<i>Pampus candidus</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	MB	LK, WB	(Rajan et al. 2021, Radhakrishnan et al. 2019)	Visakhapatnam
3324	<i>Pampus chinensis</i> (Euphrasen, 1788)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	
3325	<i>Pampus cinereus</i> (Bloch, 1795)	M	TN	(Liu et al. 2013)	Tranquebar from Bloch & Schneider 1801
Family: Trichiuridae Rafinesque, 1810					
3326	<i>Aphanopus microphthalmus</i> Norman, 1939	M	KL	(Rajeesh Kumar et al. 2014)	
3327	<i>Benthodesmus oligoradiatus</i> Parin & Becker, 1970	M	Indian Coastline	(Nair & Dinesh Kumar 2018)	
3328	<i>Benthodesmus tenuis</i> (Günther, 1877)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	

3329	<i>Eupleurogrammus glossodon</i> (Bleeker, 1860)	M	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2008, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3330	<i>Eupleurogrammus muticus</i> (Gray, 1831)	MB	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	India
3331	<i>Lepturacanthus pantului</i> (Gupta, 1966)	MB	WB, OD, AP, TN, MH	(Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Frasergunj, 24-Parganas District
3332	<i>Lepturacanthus savala</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	Puducherry
3333	<i>Tentoriceps cristatus</i> (Klunzinger, 1884)	M	ANI, GA	(Rajan et al. 2013, Anuraj et al. 2023)	
3334	<i>Trichiurus auriga</i> Klunzinger, 1884	M	TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	Deep waters off Kerala & Tamil Nadu, India
3335	<i>Trichiurus gangeticus</i> Gupta, 1966	MB	WB, OD, AP, TN	(Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Frasergunj, 24-Parganas District
3336	<i>Trichiurus lepturus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	
3337	<i>Trichiurus russelli</i> Dutt & Thankam, 1967	M	AP	(Dutt & Thankam 1967)	Vishakhapatnam
Order: Siluriformes					
Family: Ailiidae Bleeker, 1858					
3338	<i>Ailia coila</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, AP, MH, UK, DL, UP, MP, TL, CG, BR, AS, ML, AR, MN, MZ, TR	(Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Husain 1997, Sen 1985, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Mishra et al. 2021a, Gunasekar & Isaac 2017, Kar & Sen 2007)	Bengal
3339	<i>Ailiichthys punctata</i> Day, 1872	F	WB, OD, DL, MN	(Sengupta & Homechaudhuri 2015, Chanda & Jana 2021, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a)	Jumna at & below Delhi, also lower Punjab rivers
3340	<i>Clupisoma bastari</i> Datta & Karmakar, 1980	F	OD, MH, MP, CG	(Chanda & Jana 2021, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Indravati River, tributary of Godavari River, at Lohandigura, 33 kilometers west of Jagdalpur, Bastar District, Madhya Pradesh

3341	<i>Clupisoma garua</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	WB, OD, MH, GJ, HP, PU, UK, DL, UP, MP, CG, BR, JH, AS, ML, AR, MZ, TR	(Kar et al. 2017, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Bagra et al. 2009, Husain 1997, Barman 2002, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Jagtap 2013, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Mishra et al. 2021a, Kaur et al. 2017, Tudu et al. 2022, Gunasekar & Isaac 2017, Kar & Sen 2007)	Rivers of Gangetic provinces
3342	<i>Clupisoma montanum</i> Hora, 1937	F	WB, UK, MP, BR, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Barman 2002, Sharma 2007, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Gunasekar & Isaac 2017)	Teesta River, below Darjeeling
3343	<i>Clupisoma prateri</i> Hora, 1937	F	MP, MN	(Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sharma 2007)	
3344	<i>Eutropiichthys cetosus</i> Ng, Lalramliana, Lalronunga & Lalnuntluanga, 2014	F	MZ	(Ng et al. 2014)	Vicinity of Kawlchaw Village, Lawngtlai District, Mizoram
3345	<i>Eutropiichthys goongwaree</i> (Sykes, 1839)	F	AP, KA, MH, TL	(Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Mula Mutha River near Poona, Maharashtra
3346	<i>Eutropiichthys murius</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, UP, AS, ML, MZ, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman 2002, Mishra et al. 2021a, Kar & Sen 2007)	Bolahat, Mahananda River, West Bengal
3347	<i>Eutropiichthys vacha</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	WB, OD, KA, MH, GJ, UK, HY, DL, UP, MP, TL, CG, BR, AS, ML, MN, MZ, TR	(Kar et al. 2017, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Barman 2002, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a, Gunasekar & Isaac 2017, Kar & Sen 2007)	Larger fresh water rivers, Gangetic provinces
3348	<i>Proeutropiichthys buchani</i> (Valenciennes, 1840)	F	Distribution details not available	(Jacquemont 1835-44)	Hindustaan
3349	<i>Proeutropiichthys taakree</i> (Sykes, 1839)	F	AP, KA, MH, TL	(Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Deccan
3350	<i>Silonia childreni</i> (Sykes, 1839)	F	AP, TN, KA, MH, MP, TL	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Deccan
3351	<i>Silonia silondia</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, TN, MH, UK, DL, UP, RJ, MP, BR, TR	(Danda et al. 2017, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Husain 1997, Barman 2002, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Mishra et al. 2021a, Gunasekar & Isaac 2017)	Gangetic estuaries
Family: Akysidae Gill, 1861					
3352	<i>Akysis manipurensis</i> (Arunkumar, 2000)	F	MN	(Arunkumar 2000b)	Lairaoak Maru stream near Moreh, 110

					kilometers from Imphal City, Yu River System, Manipur
3353	<i>Akysis prashadi</i> Hora, 1936	F	MN	(Jayaram 2006)	
Family: Amblycipitidae Day, 1873					
3354	<i>Amblyceps accari</i> Dahanukar, Raghavan, Ali & Britz, 2016	F	KA	(Dahanukar et al. 2016)	Tunga River, Krishna River System, Kudremukh, Karnataka
3355	<i>Amblyceps apangi</i> Nath & Dey, 1989	F	WB, AR	(Ng 2005, Bagra et al. 2009)	Dikrong River, Arunachal Pradesh
3356	<i>Amblyceps arunachalense</i> Nath & Dey, 1989	F	WB, AR	(Mogalekar et al. 2017, Bagra et al. 2009)	Dikrong River, Arunachal Pradesh
3357	<i>Amblyceps cerinum</i> Ng & Wright, 2010	F	WB	(Ng 2010)	Raidak I River at Shipra, just outside Buxa Tiger Reserve, ca. 8 kilometers toward Barobisha on Siliguri-Guwahati road, 26°31'12"N, 89°43'25"E, West Bengal
3358	<i>Amblyceps crassioris</i> Vijayakrishnan & Praveenraj, 2024	F	OD	(Vijayakrishnan & Praveenraj 2024)	Dhanua River, Mahanadi River drainage, Bhubaneswar, Khordha District, Odisha, India, 20°14'42.5"N, 85°54'24.5"E
3359	<i>Amblyceps hmolaii</i> Singh, Lalronunga & Ramliana, 2022	F	MZ	(Singh et al. 2022)	Kawlchaw River in the vicinity of Kawlchaw Village, Mizoram
3360	<i>Amblyceps laticeps</i> (McClelland, 1842)	F	AS, MN	(Sen 1985)	Khasi Hills
3361	<i>Amblyceps mangois</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, KA, HP, UK, MP, CG, JH, AS, ML, AR, NL, MN, MZ, TR	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Barman 2002, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Sharma 2007, Sharma & Dhanze 2018, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Hembrom & Bodra 2021, Kar & Sen 2007)	Northern Bihar
3362	<i>Amblyceps motumensis</i> Abujam, Tamang, Nimasow & Das, 2022	F	AR	(Abujam et al. 2022)	Motum River, tributary of Siang River, upper Brahmaputra River basin at

					Motum village Pasighat, East Siang District, Arunachal Pradesh
3363	<i>Amblyceps tenuispinis</i> Blyth, 1860	F	UK	(Jayaram 2006)	Gola River in Kathgodam Nainital district, Uttarakhand
3364	<i>Amblyceps torrentis</i> Linthoingambi & Vishwanath, 2008	F	MN	(Linthoingambi & Vishwanath 2008)	Laniye River, Chadwin drainage, Jessami village, Manipur
3365	<i>Amblyceps tuberculatum</i> Linthoingambi & Vishwanath, 2008	F	WB, MN	(Mogalekar et al. 2017)	Chandel District, Manipur
3366	<i>Amblyceps waikhomi</i> Darshan, Kachari, Dutta, Ganguly & Das, 2016	F	AR	(Darshan et al. 2016)	Nongkon stream at Nongkon village draining into the Noa Dehing River, Brahmaputra River basin, Namsai District, Arunachal Pradesh
Family: Ariidae Bleeker, 1858					
3367	<i>Arius arius</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MB	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Shaji et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012, Talwar 1974)	Estuaries of Bengal
3368	<i>Arius gagora</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	WB, OD	(Yennawar et al. 2015, Chanda & Jana 2021)	Bengal estuaries
3369	<i>Arius jatius</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	WB, OD, GA	(Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	Bengal
3370	<i>Arius jella</i> Day, 1877	MB	OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	Chennai, Coromandel Coast
3371	<i>Arius macronotacanthus</i> Bleeker, 1846	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, TN, MH	(Barman et al. 2012, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Rajan et al. 2013)	
3372	<i>Arius maculatus</i> (Thunberg, 1792)	MBF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Shaji et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	
3373	<i>Arius malabaricus</i> Day, 1877	MB	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Coastal Karnataka
3374	<i>Arius subrostratus</i> Valenciennes, 1840	MB	ANI, OD, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a, Hedge et al. 2013)	Malabar
3375	<i>Arius venosus</i> Valenciennes, 1840	MB	Eastern Indian Coast	(Kapoor et al. 2002)	
3376	<i>Batrachocephalus mino</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MB	WB, AP, TN, KL,	(Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a,	Sundarbans, Ganges River

			KA, MH, GJ	Mogalekar et al. 2018)	estuary
3377	<i>Hemiaris sumatranus</i> (Anonymous [Bennett], 1830)	MB	WB, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Kar et al. 2017, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	
3378	<i>Hexanematichthys sagor</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MB	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	Estuaries of West Bengal
3379	<i>Ketengus typus</i> Bleeker, 1846	MBF	ANI, WB, OD	(Talwar & Jhingran 1991)	
3380	<i>Kyataphisa nenga</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MB	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Hedge et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2017)	Estuaries of Bengal
3381	<i>Netuma bilineata</i> (Valenciennes, 1840)	MB	GA	(Hedge et al. 2013)	Puducherry
3382	<i>Netuma thalassina</i> (Rüppell, 1837)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Kar et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	
3383	<i>Osteogeneiosus militaris</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	MBF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Khan 2002, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3384	<i>Plicofollis argyropleuron</i> (Valenciennes, 1840)	MB	OD, TN	(Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3385	<i>Plicofollis dussumieri</i> (Valenciennes, 1840)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	Malabar
3386	<i>Plicofollis layardi</i> (Günther, 1866)	MB	WB, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017)	
3387	<i>Plicofollis nella</i> (Valenciennes, 1840)	MB	OD	(Pati et al. 2018)	Visakhapatnam
3388	<i>Plicofollis platystomus</i> (Day, 1877)	MB	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Canara
3389	<i>Plicofollis tenuispinis</i> (Day, 1877)	MB	WB, OD, AP, TN, KA, MH, GJ	(Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Mumbai
3390	<i>Plicofollis tonggol</i> (Bleeker, 1846)	MB	OD, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	
3391	<i>Pseudosciades sona</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MB	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, GA, MH, GJ	(Yennawar et al. 2015, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018)	Bengal estuaries
Family: Bagridae Bleeker, 1858					
3392	<i>Batasio affinis</i> Blyth, 1860	F	MN	(Vishwanath & Darshan 2006)	
3393	<i>Batasio batasio</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, ML, AR, MZ, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1995, Bagra et al. 2009, Barman 2002, Kar & Sen 2007)	Jolpigory, Tista River, northern

					Bengal
3394	<i>Batasio convexirostrum</i> Darshan, Anganthoibi & Vishwanath, 2011	F	MZ	(Darshan et al. 2011a)	Koladyne basin, Mizoram
3395	<i>Batasio fasciolatus</i> Ng, 2006	F	WB, AR	(Ng 2006a, Bagra et al. 2009)	Market at Malbazar, 26°32'30"N, 88°44'17"E, West Bengal
3396	<i>Batasio flavus</i> Plamoottil, 2015	F	KL	(Plamoottil 2015a)	Kerala, Manimala River at Paduthode
3397	<i>Batasio merianiensis</i> (Chaudhuri, 1913)	F	WB	(Mogalekar et al. 2017)	Pond at Mariani Junction, Brahmaputra River drainage, northeastern Assam
3398	<i>Batasio sharavatiensis</i> Bhatt & Jayaram, 2004	F	KA	(Rema Devi et al. 2013)	River Sharavati, Joginmatha, Uttara Kannada District, Karnataka
3399	<i>Batasio sharavatiensis</i> Bhatt & Jayaram, 2004	F	KA	(Bhatt & Jayaram 2004)	River Sharavati, 14°14'N, 74°49'E, Joginmatha, Uttara Kannada District, Karnataka
3400	<i>Batasio spilurus</i> Ng, 2006	F	WB	(Ng 2006a)	Assam, Dibrugarh District, about 27°29'N, 94°54'E
3401	<i>Batasio tengana</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, AS, ML, AR, MN, MZ	(Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Bagra et al. 2009, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Kar & Sen 2007)	Tista River at Tista barrage, 26°45'10"N, 88°34'11"E
3402	<i>Batasio travancoria</i> Hora & Law, 1941	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Travancore, Kerala
3403	<i>Hemibagrus maydelli</i> (Rössel, 1964)	F	KA, MH, TL	(Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016)	Bhima River at Wadgaon, Maharashtra, India
3404	<i>Hemibagrus menoda</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, AP, KA, MH, UP, AS	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Sen 1985, Karmakar et al. 2012, Mishra et al. 2021a)	
3405	<i>Hemibagrus microphthalmus</i> (Day, 1877)	BF	TN, TL, MN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016)	
3406	<i>Hemibagrus punctatus</i> (Jerdon, 1849)	F	AP, TN, KL, KA, GJ, TL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Sen &	Cauvery River, Western Ghats

				Banerjee 2000)	
3407	<i>Hemibagrus peguensis</i> (Boulenger, 1894)	F	MN	(Jayaram 2006)	
3408	<i>Mystus armatus</i> (Day, 1865)	BF	AP, TN, KL, KA, NL, MN	(Shaji et al. 2019, Karmakar & Das 2005, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar & Das 2005a)	Cochin, Malabar
3409	<i>Mystus bleekeri</i> (Day, 1877)	F	WB, OD, AP, TN, KA, MH, GJ, HP, PU, UK, HY, DL, RJ, MP, TL, BR, AS, ML, AR, NL, MN, TR	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Jagtap 2013, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Kaur et al. 2017, Kumar et al. 2011)	Yamuna River, Bengal
3410	<i>Mystus canarensis</i> Grant, 1999	F	KA	(Grant 1999)	Canara
3411	<i>Mystus carcio</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB	(Buragohain 2018)	Ponds of northern Bengal
3412	<i>Mystus catapogon</i> Plamoottil, 2016	F	KL	(Plamoottil 2016c)	Small water stream at Mavelikkara, Kerala
3413	<i>Mystus cavasius</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ, UK, HY, DL, UP, RJ, MP, TL, CG, AS, ML, AR, NL, MZ, TR	(Shaji et al. 2019, Karmakar & Das 2005, Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Barman 2002, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a, Kar & Sen 2007)	Gangetic Provinces
3414	<i>Mystus dibrugarensis</i> (Chaudhuri, 1913)	F	WB	(Chanda & Jana 2021)	Dibrugarh, Assam
3415	<i>Mystus falcarius</i> Chakrabarty & Ng, 2005	F	MN	(Chakrabarty & Ng 2005)	
3416	<i>Mystus gulio</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, GA, MH, GJ, TL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Dubey et al. 2015, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Yadav 2008)	Gangetic Provinces
3417	<i>Mystus heoki</i> Plamoottil & Abraham, 2013	F	KL	(Plamoottil & Abraham 2013b)	Elankadu, Manimala River, Kerala
3418	<i>Mystus indicus</i> Plamoottil & Abraham, 2013	F	KL	(Plamoottil & Abraham 2013b)	Kuttoor, Manimala River, Kerala

3419	<i>Mystus irulu</i> Vijayakrishnan & Praveenraj, 2022	F	KA	(Vijayakrishnan & Praveenraj 2022)	Netravathi River near Uppinangady Town, Karnataka, India, 12°50.57'N, 75°18.29'E
3420	<i>Mystus keletius</i> (Valenciennes, 1840)	F	TN, KA, GA, MH	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar et al. 2012, Yadav 2008)	Puducherry
3421	<i>Mystus keralai</i> Plamoottil & Abraham, 2014	F	KL	(Plamoottil & Abraham 2014a)	Kerala, Manimala River at Chenappady
3422	<i>Mystus malabaricus</i> (Jerdon, 1849)	BF	AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, TL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar et al. 2012, Yadav 2008)	Mountain streams of Malabar
3423	<i>Mystus menoni</i> Plamoottil & Abraham, 2013	F	KL	(Plamoottil & Abraham 2013a)	Manimala River at Elankadu, Kerala
3424	<i>Mystus montanus</i> (Jerdon, 1849)	BF	AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ, MP, TL, AS, ML, AR	(Shaji et al. 2019, Sen 1985, 1995, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000)	River at Mananthavadi, Wayanad, Kerala
3425	<i>Mystus ngasep</i> Darshan, Vishwanath, Mahanta & Barat, 2011	F	MN	(Darshan et al. 2011)	Nambul River at Bijoygovinda-Polemleikai Bridge, Chindwin-Irrawaddy drainage, Manipur
3426	<i>Mystus oculatus</i> (Valenciennes, 1840)	BF	TN, KL, GA, MH	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012, Yadav 2008)	Malabar Coast
3427	<i>Mystus prabini</i> Darshan, Abujam, Kumar, Parhi, Singh, Vishwanath, Das & Pandey, 2019	F	AR	(Darshan et al. 2019)	Sinkin River (a tributary of the Siang River) at Anpum village, Lower Dibang district, Arunachal Pradesh
3428	<i>Mystus pulcher</i> (Chaudhuri, 1911)	F	MN	(Selim & Vishwanath 1999)	
3429	<i>Mystus seengtee</i> (Sykes, 1839)	BF	TN	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	Deccan
3430	<i>Mystus rubripinnis</i> Vanarajan & Arunachalam, 2018	F	TN	(Vanarajan & Arunachalam 2018)	Vaigai Dam, impoundment of the lower reach of Vaigai River, Periyakulam, Madurai, Tamil Nadu
3431	<i>Mystus</i>	F	MN	(Jayaram 2006)	

	<i>rufescens</i> (Vinciguerra, 1890)				
3432	<i>Mystus tengara</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	WB, OD, AP, J&K, UP, TL, CG, BR, JH, AS, MN, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman 1993, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Mishra et al. 2021a, Hembrom & Bodra 2021, Murugan & Prabakaran 2012, Nath 1996, Kar & Sen 2007)	Ponds of gangetic provinces
3433	<i>Mystus vittatus</i> (Bloch, 1794)	BF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ, HP, UK, HY, DL, UP, RJ, MP, TL, CG, BR, JH, AS, ML, AR, MZ, TR	(Shaji et al. 2019, Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Barman 2002, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Jagtap 2013, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a, Hembrom & Bodra 2021, Kumar et al. 2011)	Tranquebar, South India
3434	<i>Olyra astrifera</i> Arunachalam, Raja, Mayden & Chandran, 2013	F	KL	(Arunachalam et al. 2013)	Kerala, Manimalai River at Kottangal village, 20 km from Mundakayam
3435	<i>Olyra horae</i> (Prasad & Mukerji, 1929)	F	AS, ML	(Sen 1985, 1995)	
3436	<i>Olyra longicaudata</i> McClelland, 1842	F	WB, SK, AS, ML, AR, NL, TR	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Bagra et al. 2009, Barman 2002, Karmakar 2006)	Khasi hills, Meghalaya
3437	<i>Olyra parviocula</i> Kosygin, Shangningam & Gopi, 2018	F	AR	(Kosygin et al. 2018)	Kameng River at Bhallukpong, Brahmaputra River basin, West Kameng District, Arunachal Pradesh
3438	<i>Olyra praestigiosa</i> Ng & Ferraris, 2016	F	WB	(Ng & Ferraris 2016)	Chel River, approximately 1.25 km north of Gorubathan, Kalimpong Subdivision, Darjeeling District, West Bengal
3439	<i>Olyra saginata</i> Ng, Lalramliana & Lalthanzara, 2014	F	MZ	(Ng et al. 2014a)	Kolodyne River system, Palak River in the vicinity of Phurra Village, Mizoram
3440	<i>Rama chandramara</i> (Hamilton,	F	WB, AS, ML, AR	(Sen 1995, Sanyal et al. 2012, Bagra et al. 2009, Sen 1985)	Atrai River, North Bengal

	1822)				
3441	<i>Rama rama</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB	(Hamilton 1822)	Brahmaputra River
3442	<i>Sperata acicularis</i> Ferraris & Runge, 1999	F	India	(Jayaram 2006)	
3443	<i>Sperata aor</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, AP, TN, KA, MH, GJ, PU, DL, UP, MP, TL, CG, BR, JH, AS, AR, MN, MZ, TR	(Dubey et al. 2015, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Mishra et al. 2021a, Kaur et al. 2017, Tudu et al. 2022, Murugan & Prabaharan 2012, Kar & Sen 2007)	Rivers of Bengal & upper parts of Gangetic estuaries
3444	<i>Sperata aorella</i> (Blyth, 1858)	F	WB	(Blyth 1858)	Calcutta fish market
3445	<i>Sperata aorides</i> (Jerdon, 1849)	F	TN	(Kumar et al. 2020)	Cauvery River at Errode, Tamil Nadu, southern India
3446	<i>Sperata lamarrii</i> (Valenciennes, 1840)	F	WB	(Kumar et al. 2020)	Ganges River
3447	<i>Sperata seenghala</i> (Sykes, 1839)	BF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KA, GA, MH, GJ, HP, PU, UK, HY, DL, UP, RJ, MP, TL, CG, BR, JH, AS, ML, AR, MZ, TR	(Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Nandi et al. 2008, Jagtap 2013, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a, Kaur et al. 2017, Tudu et al. 2022, Murugan & Prabaharan 2012, Kar & Sen 2007)	Deccan
Family: Chacidae Bleeker, 1858					
3448	<i>Chaca chaca</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, AS, ML, AR, MZ, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Bagra et al. 2009, Barman 2002)	Northeastern Bengal
Family: Clariidae Bonaparte, 1845					
3449	<i>Clarias batrachus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	F	WB, OD, AP, TN, KA, MH, GJ, J&K, PU, UK, HY, DL, UP, MP, TL, CG, BR, JH, AS, ML, AR, MN, TR	(Kar et al. 2017, Sen 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a, Kaur et al. 2017, Hembrom & Bodra 2021, Murugan & Prabaharan 2012, Nath 1998)	
3450	<i>Clarias dayi</i> Hora, 1936	F	TN, KL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	Wayanad, Kerala

3451	<i>Clarias dussumieri</i> Valenciennes, 1840	F	TN, KL, KA, GA, MH	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar et al. 2012, Yadav 2008)	Pondicherry, Malabar
3452	<i>Clarias gariepinus</i> (Burchell, 1822)	F	TN, KL, HY, UP, CG	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a)	
3453	<i>Clarias magur</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	ANI, WB, OD, TN, JH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Dubey et al. 2015, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Tudu et al. 2022)	Ganges River
3454	<i>Heterobranchus bidorsalis</i> Geoffroy Saint-Hilaire, 1809	F	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
3455	<i>Horaglanis abdukkalami</i> Babu, 2012	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Irinjalakuda, Trichur District, Kerala
3456	<i>Horaglanis alikunhii</i> Subhash Babu & Nayar, 2004	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Water well at Parappukara, Thrissur district, Kerala
3457	<i>Horaglanis krishnai</i> Menon, 1950	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	well at Kottayam, Travancore, Kerala
3458	<i>Horaglanis populi</i> Raghavan, Sundar, Arjun, Britz & Dahanukar, 2023	F	KL	(Raghavan et al. 2023)	Dug-out well at Malapally
Family: Erethistidae Bleeker, 1862					
3459	<i>Hara koladynensis</i> Anganthoibi & Vishwanath, 2009	F	MZ	(Anganthoibi & Vishwanath, 2009)	Koladyne river, Mizoram
Family: Heteropneustidae Hora, 1936					
3460	<i>Heteropneustes fossilis</i> (Bloch, 1794)	BF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ, PU, UK, HY, DL, UP, RJ, MP, TL, CG, BR, JH, AS, ML, AR, NL, MN, TR	(Rajan et al. 2013, Shaji et al. 2019, Karmakar & Das 2005, Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Nandi et al. 2008, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a, Braich & Saini 2019, Hembrom & Bodra 2021, Murugan & Prabakaran 2012)	Tranquebar, Tamilnadu
3461	<i>Heteropneustes fuscus</i> Plamoottil, 2021	F	KL	(Plamoottil 2021)	Small stream at Pathanamthitta, Kerala
3462	<i>Heteropneustes longiptectoralis</i> Rema Devi & Raghunathan, 1999	F	TN	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	Thirumurthi Dam, Anamalai Hills, Western Ghats, Tamil Nadu
Family: Horabagridae Jayaram, 2006					
3463	<i>Horabagrus</i>	BF	KL, KA	(Shaji et al. 2019, Rema Devi et al. 2013)	Cochin, Kerala

	<i>brachysoma</i> (Günther, 1864)				
3464	<i>Horabagrus nigricollaris</i> Pethiyagoda & Kottelat, 1994	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Chalakydy River, near Vettilappara, Kerala
3465	<i>Pachypterus atherinoides</i> (Bloch, 1794)	F	WB, OD, AP, TN, MH, UK, MP, TL, CG, AS, ML, AR, TR	(Mishra et al. 2017, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021)	Tharangambadi
3466	<i>Pachypterus khavalchor</i> (Kulkarni, 1952)	F	KA, MH, TL	(Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016)	Panchaganga River, near Kolhapur, Mumbai
3467	<i>Pseudeutropius mitchelli</i> Günther, 1864	F	KL, GA	(Shaji et al. 2019, Yadav 2008)	Madras Presidency
Family: Kryptoglanidae Britz, Kakkassery & Raghavan, 2014					
3468	<i>Kryptoglanis shajii</i> Vincent & Thomas, 2011	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	A water well at Thrissur district, Kerala
Family: Loricariidae Rafinesque, 1815					
3469	<i>Pterygoplichthys ambrosettii</i> (Holmberg, 1893)	F	BR	(Sinha et al. 2010)	
3470	<i>Pterygoplichthys disjunctivus</i> (Weber, 1991)	F	WB, TN	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	
3471	<i>Pterygoplichthys multiradiatus</i> (Hancock, 1828)	F	KL	(Radhakrishnan et al. 2012)	
3472	<i>Pterygoplichthys pardalis</i> (Castelnau, 1855)	F	WB, TN, KL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	
Family: Pangasiidae Bleeker, 1858					
3473	<i>Helicophagus typus</i> Bleeker, 1857	F	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3474	<i>Pangasius bocourti</i> Sauvage, 1880	F	OD	(Chanda & Jana 2021)	
3475	<i>Pangasius icaria</i> Ayyathurai, Kodeeswaran, Mohindra, Singh, Ravi, Kumar, Valaparambil et al., 2022	F	TN	(Ayyathurai et al. 2022)	Mettur Dam, Mettur Dam village, Salem district, Tamil Nadu
3476	<i>Pangasius pangasius</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KA, MH, HY, UP, MP, TL, CG, BR, JH, AS, TR	(Rajan et al. 2013, Dubey et al. 2015, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Sen 1985, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a, Hembrom & Bodra 2021, Gunasekar & Isaac 2017)	Ganges River, Calcutta
3477	<i>Pangasius silasi</i> Dwivedi, Gupta, Singh, Mohindra, Chandra, Easawarn, Jena & Lal 2017	F	AP, TL	(Prasad & Srinivasulu 2021)	Krishna River at Nagarjuna Sagar Dam, Guntur District, Andhra Pradesh

Family: Plotosidae Bleeker, 1858					
3478	<i>Plotosus abbreviatus</i> Boulenger, 1895	BF	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3479	<i>Plotosus canius</i> Hamilton, 1822	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Ansari et al. 1995)	Southern Bengal
3480	<i>Plotosus limbatus</i> Valenciennes, 1840	MBF	OD, TN, KL, KA	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a)	Malabar
3481	<i>Plotosus lineatus</i> (Thunberg, 1787)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a, Ansari et al. 1995)	
Family: Ritidae Bleeker, 1862					
3482	<i>Rita bakalu</i> Lal, Dwivedi & Singh, 2017	F	AP, TL	(Lal et al. 2017)	Pranhita River, Bejjur, Godavari river system, Telangana
3483	<i>Rita chrysea</i> Day, 1877	F	OD, MP, TL, CG	(Chanda & Jana 2021, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Sharma 2007)	Orissa
3484	<i>Rita gogra</i> (Sykes, 1839)	F	WB, AP, KA, GA, MH, GJ, MP, TL	(Mogalekar et al. 2017, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Yadav 2008)	Deccan
3485	<i>Rita kuturnee</i> (Sykes, 1839)	F	OD, AP, KA, GA, MH, MP, TL	(Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Yadav 2008)	Deccan
3486	<i>Rita macracanthus</i> Ng, 2004	F	Northwestern India	(Jayaram 2006)	
3487	<i>Rita rita</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	WB, OD, MH, GJ, HP, PU, HY, DL, UP, MP, CG, BR, AR, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Chanda & Jana 2021, Bagra et al. 2009, Husain 1997, Barman 2002, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Jagtap 2013, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a, Kaur et al. 2017, Murugan & Prabakaran 2012)	Bengal estuaries
Family: Schilbeidae Bleeker, 1858					
3488	<i>Eutropiichthys cetosus</i> Ng, Lalramliana, Lalronunga & Lalnuntluanga, 2014	F	MZ	(Ng et al. 2014)	Kaladan River drainage in Mizoram
Family: Siluridae Rafinesque, 1815					
3489	<i>Ompok bimaculatus</i> (Bloch, 1794)	BF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ, HP, PU, UK, DL, UP, RJ, MP, f, CG, BR, JH, AS,	(Shaji et al. 2019, Karmakar & Das 2005, Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007,	Malabar

			ML, AR, NL, MN, TR	Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Yadav 2008, Jagtap 2013, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Mishra et al. 2021a, Brraich & Saini 2019, Tudu et al. 2022, Murugan & Prabakaran 2012)	
3490	<i>Ompok karunkodu</i> Ng, 2013	F	TN	(Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	Tamil Nadu, Amaravathi River in the vicinity of Amaravathi Dam
3491	<i>Ompok malabaricus</i> (Valenciennes, 1840)	F	TN, KL, KA, GA, MH	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar et al. 2012, Yadav 2008)	Malabar
3492	<i>Ompok pabda</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, AP, KA, GJ, J&K, PU, UK, MP, TL, AS, ML, AR, TR	(Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Sharma 2007, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Brraich & Saini 2019, Hussain et al. 2016)	Ponds & rivers of Bengal
3493	<i>Ompok pabo</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, AP, MH, TL, AS, ML, AR, MZ	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman 1993, Bagra et al. 2009, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar et al. 2012, Kar & Sen 2007)	Brahmaputra River at Goalpara, Assam
3494	<i>Pinniwallago kanpurensis</i> Gupta, Jayaram & Hajela, 1981	F	UP	(Gupta et al. 1981)	'Bara Tal' near village of Bhitargaon, Tehsil, Ghatampur, Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh
3495	<i>Pterocryptis barakensis</i> Vishwanath & Nebeshwar Sharma, 2006	F	MN	(Jayaram 2006)	Barak River at Vanchengphai village, Tamenglong District, Manipur
3496	<i>Pterocryptis berdmorei</i> (Blyth, 1860)	F	WB, AR, MN	(Dey et al. 2015, Bagra et al. 2009, Karmakar & Das 2005a)	
3497	<i>Pterocryptis cochinchinensis</i> (Valenciennes, 1840)	F	SK, AS	(Sen 1985, Karmakar 2006)	
3498	<i>Pterocryptis gangelica</i> Peters, 1861	F	WB, AS, AR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Bagra et al. 2009, Günther 1864)	Ganges River
3499	<i>Pterocryptis indica</i> (Datta, Barman & Jayaram, 1987)	F	AR, NL	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Bagra et al. 2009)	Namdapha river, Arunachal Pradesh
3500	<i>Pterocryptis subrisa</i> Ng, Lalramliana & Lalronunga, 2018	F	MZ	(Ng et al. 2018)	Maisa River in the vicinity of Maisa, Saiha District, Mizoram
3501	<i>Pterocryptis wynaadensis</i> (Day, 1873)	F	TN, KL, MH,	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Wayanad, Kerala

3502	<i>Wallago attu</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	BF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ, HP, PU, UK, HY, DL, UP, RJ, MP, TL, CG, BR, JH, AS, ML, AR, MN, TR	(Shaji et al. 2019, Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Chandan & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Jagtap 2013, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a, Kaur et al. 2017, Hembrom & Bodra 2021, Kumar et al. 2011)	Malabar
Family: Sisoridae Bleeker, 1858					
3503	<i>Bagarius bagarius</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, AP, KA, MH, GJ, PU, UK, HY, DL, UP, RJ, MP, TL, CG, BR, JH, SK, AS, ML, AR, MN, TR	(Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar 2006, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016, Mishra et al. 2021a, Kaur et al. 2017, Tudu et al. 2022, Murugan & Prabakaran 2012)	Ganges River
3504	<i>Chimarrichthys davidi</i> Sauvage, 1874	F	No specific location	(Devi & Indra 2012)	
3505	<i>Chimarrichthys kishinouyei</i> (Kimura, 1934)	F	Eastern himalaya & Bramhaputra Drainage	(Thomson & Page 2006)	
3506	<i>Conta conta</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, MP, AS, ML, AR, MN	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Bagra et al. 2009, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sharma 2007)	Sanashygotta, Mahananda River, northeastern Bengal
3507	<i>Conta pectinata</i> Ng, 2005	F	WB, OD	(Dey et al. 2015, Chanda & Jana 2021)	Dibrugarh, Assam
3508	<i>Creteuchiloglanis arunachalensis</i> Sinha & Tamang, 2014	F	AR	(Sinha & Tamang 2014)	Pange River at Aro-Lenching, a tributary of Brahmaputra River, Ziro, Lower Subansiri District, Arunachal Pradesh
3509	<i>Creteuchiloglanis kamengensis</i> (Jayaram, 1966)	F	AR	(Bagra et al. 2009)	Norgum River at Kalaktang, Arunachal Pradesh
3510	<i>Creteuchiloglanis payjab</i> Darshan, Dutta, Kachari, Gogoi, Aran & Das, 2014	F	AR	(Darshan et al. 2014)	Arunachal Pradesh state, West Siang District, Yomgo

					River at Mechuka, a tributary of Siang River, Brahmaputra River basin
3511	<i>Creteuchiloglanis tawangensis</i> Darshan, Abujam, Wangchu, Kumar, Das & Kumar Imotomba, 2019	F	AR	(Darshan et al. 2019a)	Tawangchu River at Granger village, headwater of Manas drainage, Brahmaputra River basin, Tawang District, Arunachal Pradesh
3512	<i>Erethistes hara</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, CG, AS, ML, AR, MZ, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Bagra et al. 2009, Barman 2002, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Kar & Sen 2007)	Hooghly River south of Ranaghat
3513	<i>Erethistes horai</i> (Misra, 1976)	F	WB, OD	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Chandan & Jana 2021)	Terai & Duars, West Bengal
3514	<i>Erethistes jerdoni</i> (Day, 1870)	F	WB, BR, AS, AR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Bagra et al. 2009, Sen 1985, Gunasekar & Isaac 2017)	
3515	<i>Erethistes koladynensis</i> (Anganthoibi & Vishwanath, 2009)	F	WB	(Dey & Barat 2015)	Koladyne River at Kolchaw, 22°23'N, 92°57'E, Lawntlai District, Mizoram
3516	<i>Erethistes nareshi</i> (Mahapatra & Kar, 2015)	F	AS	(Mahapatra & Kar 2015)	Katakhal & Barak River, Haolakandi [Hailakandi] District, Assam
3517	<i>Erethistes pusillus</i> Müller & Troschel, 1849	F	WB, OD, AS, AR, NL, MN, MZ, TR	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Sanyal et al. 2012, Chanda & Jana 2021, Bagra et al. 2009, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985, Kar & Sen 2007)	Assam
3518	<i>Erethistoides infuscatus</i> Ng, 2006	F	WB, ML	(Mogalekar et al. 2017)	East Khasi Hills, Umsing River, Meghalaya
3519	<i>Erethistoides montana</i> Hora, 1950	F	WB, AS	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985)	Streamlets near Tangla, Darrang District, Assam
3520	<i>Erethistoides pipri</i> Hora, 1950	F	UP	(Hora 1950)	Rihand River at Pipri, Mirzapur District, Uttar Pradesh
3521	<i>Erethistoides senkhiensis</i> Tamang, Chaudhry & Choudhury, 2008	F	AR	(Tamang et al. 2008)	Senkhi stream, Arunachal Pradesh
3522	<i>Erethistoides sricula</i> Ng, 2005	F	WB	(Ng 2005)	Schutunga River, tributary of Mansai River, at Ansole,

					26°22'24"N, 89°11'17"E, West Bengal
3523	<i>Exostoma barakense</i> Vishwanath & Joyshree, 2007	F	MN	(Vishwanath & Joyshree 2007)	Iyei River, Barak River drainage, Tamenglong district, Manipur
3524	<i>Exostoma bermorei</i> Blyth, 1860	F	AR, TR	(Bagra et al. 2009, Kar & Sen 2007)	
3525	<i>Exostoma dhritiae</i> Singh, Kosygin, Gurumayum & Rath, 2022	F	AR	(Singh et al. 2022a)	Siking stream, a tributary of Siang River near Yingkiong, Brahmaputra River drainage, Upper Siang District, Arunachal Pradesh
3526	<i>Exostoma dujangense</i> Shangningam & Kosygin, 2020	F	MN	(Shangningam & Kosygin 2020)	Dujang stream flowing into the Chakpi River at Dutuwl near Khubung Khullen Village, Chandel District, Manipur
3527	<i>Exostoma kottelati</i> Darshan, Vishwanath, Abujam & Das, 2019	F	AR	(Darshan et al. 2019b)	Stream flowing into Ranga River at Yazali village, Brahmaputra River basin, Lower Subansiri district, Arunachal Pradesh
3528	<i>Exostoma labiatum</i> (McClelland, 1842)	F	AS, AR, MN	(Bagra et al. 2009, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985)	Arunachal Pradesh
3529	<i>Exostoma laticaudatum</i> Arunkumar, 2020	F	MN	(Arunkumar 2020)	Namthilok stream of Leimatak River, 8.5 km from Moirang Bazar, Henglep Kendra, Churachandpur district, Barak River basin, Manipur
3530	<i>Exostoma stuarti</i> (Hora, 1923)	F	AR	(Bagra et al. 2009)	

3531	<i>Exostoma sawmteai</i> Lalramliana, Lalronunga, Lalnuntluanga & Ng, 2015	F	MZ	(Lalramliana et al. 2015a)	Mizoram, Champhai District, Pharsih River, a tributary of Tuivai River, Barak River drainage, in the vicinity of Kawlbem, 23°51'58"N, 93°17'20"E
3532	<i>Exostoma tenuicaudatum</i> Tamang, Sinha & Gurumayum, 2015	F	AR	(Tamang et al. 2015)	Siang River, about 3 km from Bomdo village on main road to Tuting, Upper Siang district, Arunachal Pradesh
3533	<i>Exostoma vinciguerrae</i> Regan, 1905	F	MN	(Jayaram 2006)	
3534	<i>Gagata cenia</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, UK, DL, MP, CG, JH, AS, ML, AR, MN, MZ, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985a, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Bagra et al. 2009, Husain 1997, Barman 2002, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Sharma 2007, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Tudu et al. 2022, Kar & Sen 2007)	Northern Bengal rivers
3535	<i>Gagata dolichonema</i> He, 1996	F	WB	(Dey et al. 2015)	
3536	<i>Gagata gagata</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, MH, MN	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Chanda & Jana 2021, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Fresh water rivers & estuaries of Bengal
3537	<i>Gagata itchkeea</i> (Sykes, 1839)	F	AP, KA, MH, GJ, MP, TL	(Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Prasad & Srinivasulu 2021, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000)	Deccan, India
3538	<i>Gagata rhodobarbus</i> Bhakat & Sinha, 2019	F	WB	(Bhakat & Sinha 2019)	Tilbara Barrage, Mayurakshi River, Suri, Birbhum district, West Bengal
3539	<i>Gagata sexualis</i> Tilak, 1970	F	WB, DL, BR, MZ	(Mogalekar et al. 2017, Husain 1997, Kar & Sen 2007)	North Koel River at Daltonganj, Chotanagpur, southern Bihar
3540	<i>Glaridoglanis andersonii</i> (Day, 1870)	F	AR	(Sen & Khyriam 2010)	
3541	<i>Glyptosternon maculatum</i> (Regan, 1905)	F	SK	(Karmakar 2006)	
3542	<i>Glyptosternon reticulatum</i> McClelland, 1842	F	LD, J&K	(Bhat et al. 2020, Tilak 1990)	
3543	<i>Glyptothorax alaknandi</i> Tilak, 1969	F	UK, UP	(Uniyal & Uniyal 2021)	Alaknanda River, near Srinagar, District Pauri Garhwal, Uttar Pradesh

3544	<i>Glyptothorax anamalaiensis</i> Silas, 1952	F	TN, KL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	Anamalai Hills, Western Ghats
3545	<i>Glyptothorax annandalei</i> Hora, 1923	F	TN, KL, MH, AR	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Bagra et al. 2009, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Bhavani River at the base of Nilgiri hills, Tamil Nadu
3546	<i>Glyptothorax ater</i> Anganθοibi & Vishwanath, 2011	F	MZ	(Anganθοibi & Vishwanath 2011)	Koladyne River at Kolchaw, 22°23'N, 92°57'E, Lawntlai District, Mizoram
3547	<i>Glyptothorax botius</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB	(Hamilton 1822)	Hoogly River at Kalna, 23°13'30.0"N, 88°22'39.0"E, West Bengal
3548	<i>Glyptothorax brevipinnis</i> Hora, 1923	F	HP, AR	(Bagra et al. 2009, Sharma & Dhanze 2018)	India
3549	<i>Glyptothorax burmanicus</i> Prashad & Mukerji, 1929	F	MN	(Vishwanath & Linthoingambi 2007)	
3550	<i>Glyptothorax caudimaculatus</i> Anganθοibi & Vishwanath, 2011	F	MZ	(Anganθοibi & Vishwanath 2011)	Koladyne River at Kolchaw, 22°23'N, 92°57'E, Lawntlai District, Mizoram
3551	<i>Glyptothorax cavia</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, UK, AS, ML, AR, NL, MN, MZ, TR	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Vishwanath & Linthoingambi 2007, Bagra et al. 2009, Barman 2002, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Kar & Sen 2007)	Patgong, northern Bengal
3552	<i>Glyptothorax chimtuipuiensis</i> Anganθοibi & Vishwanath, 2010	F	MZ	(Anganθοibi & Vishwanath 2010)	Koladyne River at Kolchaw, Lawntlai District, 22°23'N, 92°57'E, Mizoram
3553	<i>Glyptothorax churamanii</i> Rameshori & Vishwanath, 2012	F	MZ	(Rameshori & Vishwanath 2012)	Lawntlai, Kaladan River at Kolchaw, 22°23'N, 92°57'E, Mizoram
3554	<i>Glyptothorax clavatus</i> Rameshori & Vishwanath, 2014	F	MN	(Rameshori & Vishwanath 2014)	Headwaters of Barak River at Maram Khullen, 25°23'N, 94°04'E, Manipur
3555	<i>Glyptothorax conirostris</i> (Steindachner, 1867)	F	WB, MH, GJ, HP, UK, AR, MZ, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Bagra et al. 2009, Barman 2002, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Sharma & Dhanze 2018, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Kar & Sen 2007)	Shimla, Himachal Pradesh

3556	<i>Glyptothorax davissinghi</i> Manimekalan & Das, 1998	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Nilambur, Nilgiri Biosphere Reserve, Kerala
3557	<i>Glyptothorax dikrongensis</i> Tamang & Chaudhry, 2011	F	WB	(Mogalekar et al. 2017)	Midpu, Arunachal Pradesh
3558	<i>Glyptothorax distichus</i> Kosygin, Singh & Gurumayum, 2020	F	MZ	(Kosygin et al. 2020)	Tlawng River near Sairang, Barak-Meghna-Surma drainage, Aizawl district, Mizoram
3559	<i>Glyptothorax dorsalis</i> Vinciguerra, 1890	F	MN	(Menon 1999)	
3560	<i>Glyptothorax elankadensis</i> Plamoottil & Abraham, 2013	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Elankadu, Manimala River, Kerala
3561	<i>Glyptothorax garhwali</i> Tilak, 1969	F	UK, UP	(Uniyal & Uniyal 2021)	Alaknanda River, near Srinagar, District Pauri Garhwal District, Uttar Pradesh
3562	<i>Glyptothorax gopii</i> Kosygin, Das, Singh & Chowdhury, 2019	F	MZ	(Kosygin et al. 2019a)	Tuipui River near Champhai, Kaladan River basin, Champhai district, Mizoram
3563	<i>Glyptothorax gracilis</i> (Günther, 1864)	F	WB, UK, SK, AR	(Mogalekar et al. 2017, Bagra et al. 2009, Karmakar 2006, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021)	Nepal
3564	<i>Glyptothorax granulus</i> Vishwanath & Linthoingambi, 2007	F	MN	(Vishwanath & Linthoingambi 2007)	Iril River, Phungdhar, Ukhrul District, Manipur
3565	<i>Glyptothorax giudikyensis</i> Kosygin, Singh & Gurumayum, 2020	F	MN	(Kosygin et al. 2020a)	Giudiky stream near Langpram village, Barak-Meghna-Surma River drainage, Tamenglong District, Manipur
3566	<i>Glyptothorax heokheei</i> Singh, Chowdhury, Gurumayum & Kosygin, 2023	F	AR	(Singh et al. 2023)	Siku stream near Mebo, Siang River drainage, Brahmaputra River basin, East Siang District, Arunachal Pradesh
3567	<i>Glyptothorax horai</i> (Fowler, 1934)	F	WB, UK	(Mogalekar et al. 2017, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021)	
3568	<i>Glyptothorax housei</i> Herre, 1942	F	TN, KL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	Valpari, Pollachi district, Tamilnadu
3569	<i>Glyptothorax igniculus</i> Ng & Kullander, 2013	F	MN	(Ng & Kullander 2013)	

3570	<i>Glyptothorax indicus</i> Talwar, 1991	F	WB, AR	(Dey et al. 2015, Bagra et al. 2009)	Streams of Terai, northern Bengal
3571	<i>Glyptothorax jayarami</i> Rameshori & Vishwanath, 2012	F	MZ	(Rameshori & Vishwanath 2012a)	Kaladan River at Kolchaw, 22°23'N, 92°57'E, Lawntlai District, Mizoram
3572	<i>Glyptothorax kailashi</i> Kosygin, Singh & Mitra, 2020	F	MZ	(Kosygin et al. 2020b)	Tuipui River near Champhai, Kaladan River drainage, Champhai district, Mizoram
3573	<i>Glyptothorax kashmirensis</i> Hora, 1923	F	J&K	(Bhat et al. 2020)	Kashmir Valley
3574	<i>Glyptothorax kudremukhensis</i> Gopi, 2007	F	KA	(Gopi 2007)	Stream in headwaters of the Thunga River, Muduba, 13°19.420'N, 75°08.635'E, Kudremukh National Park, Karnataka
3575	<i>Glyptothorax lairamkhullensis</i> Devi, Linthoingambi & Singh, 2023	F	MN	(Devi et al. 2023)	Taretlok River at Lairam Khullen, Kasom Khullen, Kamjong District, Manipur
3576	<i>Glyptothorax lonah</i> (Sykes, 1839)	F	OD, AP, KA, MH, MP, TL	(Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman 1993, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Prasad & Srinivasulu 2021, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Deccan
3577	<i>Glyptothorax maceriatius</i> Ng & Lalramliana, 2012	F	MZ	(Ng & Lalramliana 2012)	Tlawng River at Sairang, 23°48'36.0"N, 92°39'14.4"E, Meghna-Surma River system, Mizoram
3578	<i>Glyptothorax madraspatanus</i> (Day, 1873)	F	TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000)	Bhavani River, Nilgiris
3579	<i>Glyptothorax malabarensis</i> Gopi, 2010	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Valappattanam River, Kannur district, Kerala
3580	<i>Glyptothorax manipurensis</i> Menon, 1955	F	MN	(Vishwanath & Linthoingambi 2007)	Barak River at Karong, Naga Hills, Manipur State
3581	<i>Glyptothorax mibangi</i> Darshan, Dutta, Kachari, Gogoi & Das, 2015	F	AR	(Darshan et al. 2015)	Arunachal Pradesh State, Tisa River near Longding,

					Brahmaputra River basin
3582	<i>Glyptothorax nelsoni</i> Ganguly, Datta & Sen, 1972	F	BR, JH	(Tudu et al. 2022)	Subarnarekha River, Chotanagpur Plateau, Bihar
3583	<i>Glyptothorax ngapang</i> Vishwanath & Linthoingambi, 2007	F	MN	(Vishwanath & Linthoingambi 2007)	Iril River, Bamonkampu, Manipur
3584	<i>Glyptothorax pantherinus</i> Anganthoibi & Vishwanath, 2013	F	AR	(Anganthoibi & Vishwanath 2013)	Noa Dehing River, Brahmaputra River basin, Deban-Namdapha, Changlang district, Arunachal Pradesh
3585	<i>Glyptothorax pasighatensis</i> Arunkumar, 2016	F	AR	(Arunkumar 2016)	Siang River at Pasighat, East Siang district, Arunachal Pradesh
3586	<i>Glyptothorax pectinopterus</i> (McClelland, 1842)	F	HP, UK, AR, MN	(Bagra et al. 2009, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sharma & Dhanze 2018, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021)	Simla
3587	<i>Glyptothorax poonaensis</i> Hora, 1938	F	MH	(Hora 1938)	Mula-Mutha River at Poona, tributary of Bhima River, Maharashtra
3588	<i>Glyptothorax punjabensis</i> Mirza & Kashmiri, 1971	F	J&K, PU	(Bbraich & Saini 2019, Hussain et al. 2016)	
3589	<i>Glyptothorax platypogonides</i> (Bleeker, 1855)	F	AS, AR, MN	(Bagra et al. 2009, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985)	
3590	<i>Glyptothorax radiolus</i> Ng & L alramliana, 2013	F	WB	(Ng 2013)	West Bengal, Jayanti area
3591	<i>Glyptothorax rupiri</i> Kosygin, Singh & Rath, 2021	F	AR	(Kosygin et al. 2021a)	Jambung stream, a tributary of Siang River near Hawa Camp, Brahmaputra River basin, Upper Siang District, Arunachal Pradesh
3592	<i>Glyptothorax saisii</i> (Jenkins, 1910)	F	UK, BR, JH, AR	(Bagra et al. 2009, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Tudu et al. 2022)	Subarnarekha River, Chotanagpur Plateau, Bihar

3593	<i>Glyptothorax scrobiculus</i> Ng & Lalramliana, 2012	F	MZ	(Ng & Lalramliana 2012a)	Mausam River in the vicinity of NE Khawdungsei village, 23°57'33.0"N, 93°12'34.0"E, Tuivai River drainage, Mizoram
3594	<i>Glyptothorax senapatiensis</i> Premananda, Kosygin & Saidullah, 2015	F	MN	(Premananda et al. 2015)	Sinapati District, Imphal River at Motbung, Chindwin River drainage, Manipur
3595	<i>Glyptothorax siangensis</i> Singh, Kosygin, Rath & Gurumayum, 2023	F	AR	(Singh et al. 2023a)	Siking stream, a tributary of Siang River near Yingkiong, Brahmaputra River drainage, Upper Siang District, Arunachal Pradesh
3596	<i>Glyptothorax sinensis</i> (Regan, 1908)	F	AS, AR, MN	(Bagra et al. 2009, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sen 1985)	
3597	<i>Glyptothorax stolicka</i> (Steindachner, 1867)	F	HP	(Sharma & Dhanze 2018)	Simla, Himachal Pradesh, northwestern India
3598	<i>Glyptothorax striatus</i> (McClelland, 1842)	F	WB, SK, AS, ML, AR	(Ng 2013, Sen 1995, Bagra et al. 2009, Sen 1985, Karmakar 2006)	Khasi Hills, Meghalaya
3599	<i>Glyptothorax sykesi</i> (Day, 1873)	F	No specific location	(Day 1873)	Deccan
3600	<i>Glyptothorax telchitta</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, UK, DL, MP, JH, ML, AR, MN, MZ, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1995, Bagra et al. 2009, Husain 1997, Barman 2002, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sharma 2007, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Hembrom & Bodra 2021, Kar & Sen 2007)	Hoogly River at Kalna, 23°13'30.0"N, 88°22'39.0"E, west Bengal
3601	<i>Glyptothorax trewavasae</i> Hora, 1938	F	KA, MH	(Rema Devi et al. 2013, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Yenna Valley, Satara District, Maharashtra
3602	<i>Glyptothorax trilineatus</i> Blyth, 1860	F	AS, NL, MN, MZ	(Karmakar & Das 2005, 2005a, Sen 1985, Kar & Sen 2007)	
3603	<i>Glyptothorax ventrolineatus</i> Vishwanath & Linthoingambi, 2006	F	MN	(Vishwanath & Linthoingambi 2007)	Irilk River, Ukhruk District, Manipur
3604	<i>Glyptothorax verrucosus</i> Rameshori & Vishwanath, 2012	F	MZ	(Rameshori & Vishwanath 2012b)	Mizoram, Lawntlai District, Koladyne River at Kolchaw, 22°23'N, 92°47'E

3605	<i>Glyptothorax viridis</i> Shangningam & Kosygin, 2023	F	MN	(Shangningam & Kosygin 2023a)	Dujang River at Dutuwl below Khubung Khullen, a tributary of the Chakpi River, Chindwin basin, Chandel District, Manipur
3606	<i>Glyptothorax waikhomi</i> Shangningam & Kosygin, 2022	F	MN	(Shangningam & Kosygin 2022)	Chakpi River near Chakpikarong, headwaters of Chindwin drainage, Chandel District, Manipur
3607	<i>Gogangra viridescens</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, AP, KA, MH, GJ, DL, MP, AS, ML, AR, MN, MZ, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Kar & Sen 2007)	Ganges river
3608	<i>Myersglanis jayarami</i> Vishwanath & Kosygin, 1999	F	MN	(Vishwanath & Kosygin 1999)	Laniye River at Jessami, Manipur
3609	<i>Oreoglanis majuscula</i> Linthoingambi & Vishwanath, 2011	F	AR	(Linthoingambi & Vishwanath 2011)	Kameng River, at Rupa, 27°12'38"N, 92°24'06"E, Brahmaputra basin, Arunachal Pradesh
3610	<i>Oreoglanis pangenensis</i> Sinha & Tamang, 2015	F	AR	(Sinha & Tamang 2015)	Pange River, upper Brahmaputra River basin, Lower Sunansiri district, Ziro Valley, Aro-Lenching, Apatani plateau, Arunachal Pradesh
3611	<i>Oreoglanis setigera</i> Ng & Rainboth, 2001	F	AR	(Bagra et al. 2009)	
3612	<i>Nangra assamensis</i> Sen & Biswas, 1994	F	WB, AR	(Dey et al. 2015, Bagra et al. 2009)	Brahmaputra River at Neematighat, 14 kilometers from Jorhat, Assam
3613	<i>Nangra nangra</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, MH, DL, BR, AS, MN, MZ,	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Husain 1997, Karmakar et al. 2012, Kar & Sen 2007)	Ganges River at Patna

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3614	<i>Nangra robusta</i> Mirza & Awan, 1973	F	AS, MN, TR	(Kar & Sen 2007)	
3615	<i>Parachiloganis hodgarti</i> (Horsfield, 1923)	F	WB, UK, SK, AS, AR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Bagra et al. 2009, Sen 1985, Karmakar 2006, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021)	Nepal
3616	<i>Parachiloganis paliziensis</i> Abujam, Mahato, Bushi, Nimasow, Nimasow & Das, 2022	F	AR	(Abujam et al. 2022a)	Bichom River at Palizi Village, Brahmaputra River basin, West kameng District, Arunachal Pradesh
3617	<i>Pseudecheneis koladynae</i> Anganthoibi & Vishwanath, 2010	F	MZ	(Anganthoibi & Vishwanath 2010a)	Koladyne River, 33°23'N, 92°57'E, Lawntlai District, Mizoram State
3618	<i>Pseudecheneis nagalandensis</i> Shangningam & Kosygin, 2020	F	NL	(Shangningam & Kosygin 2020a)	Tizu River at Sohomi, Chindwin River basin, Phek District, Nagaland
3619	<i>Pseudecheneis sirenica</i> Vishwanath & Darshan, 2007	F	AR	(Bagra et al. 2009)	Siren River, Upper Siang District, Brahmaputra River drainage, Arunachal Pradesh
3620	<i>Pseudecheneis sulcata</i> (McClelland, 1842)	F	WB, UK, SK, AS, ML, AR, MN, MZ	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Sen 1985, 1995, Bagra et al. 2009, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Karmakar 2006, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Kar & Sen 2007)	Khasi Hills, Meghalaya
3621	<i>Pseudecheneis suppaetula</i> Ng, 2006	F	HP	(Ng 2006b)	Upper reaches of Giri River, in Chhaila area, vicinity of Kotkhai, 31°06'05"N, 77°25'56"E, Ganges River drainage, Himachal Pradesh
3622	<i>Pseudecheneis ukhrulensis</i> Vishwanath & Darshan, 2007	F	MN	(Vishwanath & Darshan 2007)	Momo stream, Tusom Christian Village, Ukhrul District, Manipur
3623	<i>Pseudolaguvia austrina</i> Radhakrishnan, Sureshkumar & Ng, 2011	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Kunthi river, Mannarkkad, Kerala

3624	<i>Pseudolaguvia ferruginea</i> Ng, 2009	F	WB	(Ng 2009)	West Bengal
3625	<i>Pseudolaguvia ferula</i> Ng, 2006	F	WB	(Ng 2006)	Tista River at Tista Barrage, 26°45'10"N, 88°34'11"E, West Bengal
3626	<i>Pseudolaguvia flavida</i> Ng, 2009	F	WB	(Ng 2009)	Hooghly River at Kalna, 23°13'30"N, 88°22'39"E, West Bengal
3627	<i>Pseudolaguvia flavipinna</i> Bhakat, 2019	F	WB	(Bhakat 2019)	Mayurakshi River, Tilpara Barrage, Suri, Birbhum district, West Bengal
3628	<i>Pseudolaguvia foveolata</i> Ng, 2005	F	WB	(Ng 2006)	Tista River at Tista barrage, 26°45'10"N, 88°34'11"E, West Bengal
3629	<i>Pseudolaguvia fucosa</i> Ng, Lalramliana & Lalronunga, 2016	F	MZ	(Ng et al. 2016)	Mizoram, Lawngtlai District, Tuichawng River in the vicinity of Bandukbanga village, Karnaphuli drainage
3630	<i>Pseudolaguvia jiyaensis</i> Tamang & Sinha, 2014	F	AS, AR	(Tamang & Sinha 2014)	Arunachal Pradesh, Lower Dibang Valley District, Jiya stream, near Bolik village, approx. 14 km from Roing towards Shantipur, Assam
3631	<i>Pseudolaguvia kapuri</i> (Tilak & Husain, 1975)	F	UP	(Tilak & Husain 1975)	Padhoi River near Kalsia Ghat, Saharanpur, Uttar Pradesh
3632	<i>Pseudolaguvia lapillicola</i> Britz, Ali & Raghavan, 2013	F	KA	(Britz et al. 2013)	Subramanya, Kumaradhara river, 12°40'N, 75°37'E. Karnataka
3633	<i>Pseudolaguvia magna</i> Tamang & Sinha, 2014	F	AS, AR	(Tamang & Sinha 2014)	Arunachal Pradesh, Lower Dibang Valley District, Jiya stream, near

					Bolik village, approx. 14 km from Roing towards Shantipur, Assam
3634	<i>Pseudolaguvia meghalayaensis</i> Lokeshwor & Marak, 2022	F	ML	(Lokeshwor & Marak 2022)	Confluence of Rongkil & Rongdal stream at Rajasimla, Brahmaputra River basin, North Garo Hill, Meghalaya
3635	<i>Pseudolaguvia nubila</i> Ng, Lalramliana, Lalronunga & Lalnuntluanga, 2013	F	MZ	(Ng et al. 2013)	Sala River, a tributary of the Kaladan River in the vicinity of Lungpug Village, 22°03'36.11"N, 92°55'15.37", Saiha District, Mizoram
3636	<i>Pseudolaguvia permaris</i> Vijaykrishnan, Praveenraj & Mishra, 2023	F	OD	(Vijaykrishnan et al. 2023)	Kuakhai River, Mahanadi River basin, Bhubaneswar, Khordha district, Odisha
3637	<i>Pseudolaguvia ribeiroi</i> (Hora, 1921)	F	WB, UK, MP, AR, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Bagra et al. 2009, Barman 2002, Sharma 2007, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021)	Khoila River, tributary of Tista at Jalpaiguri, Darjeeling District, Himalayas, West Bengal
3638	<i>Pseudolaguvia shawi</i> (Hora, 1921)	F	WB, SK, ML, AR, MZ	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Bagra et al. 2009, Sen 1995, Karmakar 2006, Kar & Sen 2007)	Mahanadi River below Darjeeling, West Bengal
3639	<i>Pseudolaguvia vespa</i> Praveenraj, Vijaykrishnan, Lima & Gurumayum, 2021	F	NL	(Praveenraj et al. 2021)	Tsücha River, Khar village, Mokokchung district, Nagaland
3640	<i>Pseudolaguvia spicula</i> Ng & Lalramliana, 2010	F	MZ	(Ng & Lalramliana 2010)	Bawrai River, a tributary of Langkaih River in the vicinity of Zawinuam, 24°07'37.2"N, 92°20'42.0"E, Mizoram

3641	<i>Pseudolaguvia viriosa</i> Ng & Tamang, 2012	F	AR	(Ng & Tamang 2012)	Sile River, approximately 1 km upstream from RCC bridge, about 10 km from Ruksin & about 26 km before Pasighat, 27°52'37.6"N 95°18'18.0"E, East Siang District, Arunachal Pradesh
3642	<i>Pseudolaguvia virgulata</i> Ng & Lalramliana, 2010	F	MZ	(Ng & Lalramliana 2010a)	Sihthiang River, a tributary of the Teirei River in the vicinity of Sihthiang, 24°04'12.0"N, 92°27'25.2"E, Mizoram
3643	<i>Sisor barakensis</i> Vishwanath & Darshan, 2005	F	WB	(Dey et al. 2015)	River Barak, Brahmaputra drainage, Jiri, Manipur
3644	<i>Sisor chenuah</i> Ng & Lahkar, 2003	F	AS	(Ng 2003)	Brahmaputra River drainage, Dibrugarh, from Aquarium trade, Assam
3645	<i>Sisor rabdophorus</i> Hamilton, 1822	F	WB, DL, AR, NL	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Sanyal et al. 2012, Bagra et al. 2009, Husain 1997)	Northern rivers of Bengal & Bihar
3646	<i>Sisor rheophilus</i> Ng, 2003	F	UP	(Ng 2003)	Kali Nadi River, near Muzaffarnagar, Uttar Pradesh State
3647	<i>Sisor torosus</i> Ng, 2003	F	BR	(Ng 2003)	Ganges River at Patna, Bihar
3648	<i>Tremeuchiloglanis macrotrema</i> (Norman, 1925)	F	AR	(Talwar & Jhingran 1991)	
Order: Syngnathiformes					
Family: Aulostomidae Rafinesque, 1815					
3649	<i>Aulostomus chinensis</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL, KA	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a)	
Family: Callionymidae Bonaparte, 1831					
3650	<i>Callionymus belcheri</i> Richardson, 1844	M	WB	(Danda et al. 2017)	
3651	<i>Callionymus carebares</i> Alcock, 1890	M	WB, OD, TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Off Madras coast
3652	<i>Callionymus erythraeus</i> Ninni, 1934	M	TN	(Fricke 2002)	

3653	<i>Callionymus filamentosus</i> Valenciennes, 1837	M	ANI, OD, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Roy et al. 2021a)	
3654	<i>Callionymus fluviatilis</i> Day, 1876	MB	WB, OD, TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Hooghly River at Calcutta
3655	<i>Callionymus hindsii</i> Richardson, 1844	M	OD	(Roy et al. 2021a)	
3656	<i>Callionymus japonicus</i> Houttuyn, 1782	M	ANI, TN, KA	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a)	
3657	<i>Callionymus kaianus</i> Günther, 1880	M	KL	(Fricke 1981)	
3658	<i>Callionymus kotthausi</i> Fricke, 1981	M	KL	(Biju et al. 2019)	About 40 kilometers west-southwest of Cochin
3659	<i>Callionymus margaretae</i> Regan, 1905	M	OD, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Roy et al. 2021a)	
3660	<i>Callionymus marleyi</i> Regan, 1919	M	TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3661	<i>Callionymus megastomus</i> Fricke, 1982	M	WB	(Mishra et al. 2017)	India
3662	<i>Callionymus melanopterus</i> Bleeker, 1850	MB	OD	(Pati et al. 2018)	
3663	<i>Callionymus recurvispinnis</i> (Li, 1966)	M	OD	(Roy et al. 2021a)	
3664	<i>Callionymus sagitta</i> Pallas, 1770	M	WB, OD, TN, KL, GA, MH	(Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, Hedge et al. 2013)	Mouth of Hooghly River, Sundarbans, Bengal Province
3665	<i>Callionymus schaapii</i> Bleeker, 1852	M	TN	(Fricke 2002)	
3666	<i>Callionymus sublaevis</i> McCulloch, 1926	M	GA	(Hedge et al. 2013)	
3667	<i>Eleutherochir opercularis</i> (Valenciennes, 1837)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Mouth of Arian-Coupan River at Puducherry
3668	<i>Dactylopus kuiteri</i> (Fricke, 1992)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3669	<i>Synchiropus lineolatus</i> (Valenciennes, 1837)	M	OD, TN	(Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Puducherry
3670	<i>Synchiropus splendidus</i> (Herre, 1927)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3671	<i>Synchiropus stellatus</i> Smith, 1963	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
Family: Centriscidae Bonaparte, 1831					
3672	<i>Aeoliscus strigatus</i> (Günther, 1861)	M	ANI, WB, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Sanyal et al. 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3673	<i>Centriscops humerosus</i> (Richardson, 1846)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3674	<i>Centriscus scutatus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	MB	ANI, OD, AP, TN, KL, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
3675	<i>Macroramphosus</i>	M	KA	(Barman et al. 2013a)	

	<i>gracilis</i> (Lowe, 1839)			
Family: Dactylopteridae Gill, 1861				
3676	<i>Dactyloptena gilberti</i> Snyder, 1909	M	TN	(Eschmeyer 1997)
3677	<i>Dactyloptena macracantha</i> (Bleeker, 1855)	M	LK, OD, TN, KL, KA	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a)
3678	<i>Dactyloptena orientalis</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	ANI, LK, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)
3679	<i>Dactyloptena papilio</i> Ogilby, 1910	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)
3680	<i>Dactyloptena peterseni</i> (Nyström, 1887)	M	TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)
3681	<i>Dactyloptena tiltoni</i> Eschmeyer, 1997	M	KL	(Nihal et al. 2024)
Family: Fistulariidae Stark, 1828				
3682	<i>Fistularia commersonii</i> Rüppell, 1838	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018)
3683	<i>Fistularia petimba</i> Lacepède, 1803	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)
Family: Mullidae Rafinesque, 1815				
3684	<i>Mulloidichthys flavolineatus</i> (Lacepède, 1801)	M	ANI, LK, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)
3685	<i>Mulloidichthys ayliffe</i> Uiblein, 2011	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, Vishnupriya & Nair 2023)
3686	<i>Mulloidichthys vanicolensis</i> (Valenciennes, 1831)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)
3687	<i>Parupeneus barberinus</i> (Lacepède, 1801)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)
3688	<i>Parupeneus ciliatus</i> (Lacepède, 1802)	M	OD, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018)
3689	<i>Parupeneus chrysopleuron</i> (Temminck & Schlegel, 1843)	M	TN, KA	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Vishnupriya & Nair 2023)
3690	<i>Parupeneus cyclostomus</i> (Lacepède, 1801)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)
3691	<i>Parupeneus forsskali</i> (Fourmanoir & Guézé, 1976)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)
3692	<i>Parupeneus heptacantha</i> (Lacepède, 1802)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)

3693	<i>Parupeneus indicus</i> (Shaw, 1803)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	Vishakhapatnam
3694	<i>Parupeneus macronemus</i> (Lacepède, 1801)	M	ANI, LK, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3695	<i>Parupeneus minys</i> Randall & Heemstra, 2009	M	KL	(Randall & Heemstra 2009)	
3696	<i>Parupeneus multifasciatus</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1825)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
3697	<i>Parupeneus pleurostigma</i> (Bennett, 1831)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3698	<i>Parupeneus rubescens</i> (Lacepède, 1801)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3699	<i>Parupeneus spilurus</i> (Bleeker, 1854)	MB	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3700	<i>Parupeneus trifasciatus</i> (Lacepède, 1801)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3701	<i>Upeneus guttatus</i> (Day, 1868)	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, 2013a, Vishnupriya & Nair 2023)	Chennai
3702	<i>Upeneus heemstra</i> Uiblein & Gouws, 2014	M	TN, KL	(Uiblein & Gouws 2014)	
3703	<i>Upeneus indicus</i> Uiblein & Heemstra, 2010	M	KL	(Uiblein & Heemstra 2010)	Cochin
3704	<i>Upeneus japonicus</i> (Houttuyn, 1782)	M	AP, TN, GJ	(Barman et al. 2000, 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3705	<i>Upeneus luzonius</i> Jordan & Seale, 1907	M	WB, TN	(Yennawar et al. 2015, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3706	<i>Upeneus madras</i> Uiblein & Maclaine, 2022	M	TN	(Uiblein & Maclaine 2022)	Off Chennai (Madras)
3707	<i>Upeneus margarethae</i> Uiblein & Heemstra, 2010	M	TN, KL	(Kannan et al. 2023, Vishnupriya & Nair 2023)	
3708	<i>Upeneus moluccensis</i> (Bleeker, 1855)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	
3709	<i>Upeneus oligospilus</i> Lachner, 1954	MB	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3710	<i>Upeneus sulphureus</i> Cuvier, 1829	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3711	<i>Upeneus sundaicus</i> (Bleeker, 1855)	MB	LK, WB, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3712	<i>Upeneus supravittatus</i> Uiblein & Heemstra, 2010	M	TN, KL	(Uiblein & Heemstra 2010)	
3713	<i>Upeneus taeniopterus</i> Cuvier, 1829	M	LK, WB, OD, AP,	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018,	

			TN, KL, MH	Barman et al. 2004, 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3714	<i>Upeneus tragula</i> Richardson, 1846	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a, Hedge et al. 2013)	
3715	<i>Upeneus vittatus</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a, Talwar 1974)	
Family: Pegasidae Bonaparte, 1831					
3716	<i>Eurypegasus draconis</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	MB	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3717	<i>Pegasus laternarius</i> Cuvier, 1829	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3718	<i>Pegasus volitans</i> Linnaeus, 1758	MB	ANI, OD, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Solenostomidae Nardo, 1843					
3719	<i>Solenostomus cyanopterus</i> Bleeker, 1854	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
3720	<i>Solenostomus paradoxus</i> (Pallas, 1770)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Syngnathidae Bonaparte, 1831					
3721	<i>Acentronura gracilissima</i> (Temminck & Schlegel, 1850)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3722	<i>Bhanotia fasciolata</i> (Duméril, 1870)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3723	<i>Bryx analicarens</i> (Duncker, 1915)	M	GJ	(Chandran et al. 2020)	
3724	<i>Choeroichthys brachysoma</i> (Bleeker, 1855)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
3725	<i>Choeroichthys sculptus</i> (Günther, 1870)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3726	<i>Corythoichthys amplexus</i> Dawson & Randall, 1975	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
3727	<i>Corythoichthys benedetto</i> Allen & Erdmann, 2008	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3728	<i>Corythoichthys flavofasciatus</i> (Rüppell, 1838)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3729	<i>Corythoichthys haematopterus</i> (Bleeker, 1851)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
3730	<i>Corythoichthys intestinalis</i> (Ramsay, 1881)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3731	<i>Corythoichthys ocellatus</i> Herald, 1953	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
3732	<i>Corythoichthys schultzi</i> Herald, 1953	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
3733	<i>Doryrhamphus excisus</i> Kaup, 1856	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	

3734	<i>Dunckerocampus dactyliophorus</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3735	<i>Halicampus macrorhynchus</i> Bamber, 1915	M	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
3736	<i>Halicampus mataafae</i> (Jordan & Seale, 1906)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3737	<i>Hippichthys cyanospilos</i> (Bleeker, 1854)	MBF	LK, OD, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3738	<i>Hippichthys heptagonus</i> Bleeker, 1849	BF	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3739	<i>Hippichthys penicillus</i> (Cantor, 1849)	MBF	GA	(Talwar 1974)	
3740	<i>Hippichthys spicifer</i> (Rüppell, 1838)	MBF	ANI, LK, WB, TN, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mishra et al. 2017, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
3741	<i>Hippocampus fuscus</i> Rüppell, 1838	M	OD, TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3742	<i>Hippocampus histrix</i> Kaup, 1856	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Kar et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3743	<i>Hippocampus kelloggi</i> Jordan & Snyder, 1901	M	OD, TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Behera et al. 2023)	
3744	<i>Hippocampus kuda</i> Bleeker, 1852	MB	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Hedge et al. 2013)	
3745	<i>Hippocampus spinosissimus</i> Weber, 1913	MB	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3746	<i>Hippocampus trimaculatus</i> Leach, 1814	M	ANI, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3747	<i>Hippocampus zebra</i> Whitley, 1964	M	TN	(Kumar & Geetha 2012)	
3748	<i>Ichthyocampus carce</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MBF	WB, OD, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018)	Botanical Garden of Colcata, Ganges River system
3749	<i>Microphis brachyurus</i> (Bleeker, 1854)	MBF	ANI, OD, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3750	<i>Microphis cuncalus</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	WB, OD, KL, GA, MH	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Karmakar et al. 2012, Nandi et al. 2008)	Estuaries near Calcutta
3751	<i>Microphis deocata</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	F	WB, OD, BR, AR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Pati et al. 2018, Bagra et al. 2009)	Baruni, Ganges River sytem
3752	<i>Microphis insularis</i> (Hora, 1925)	F	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Birchgunge, southern ANdaman Islands
3753	<i>Microphis martensii</i> (Peters, 1868)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3754	<i>Phoxocampus belcheri</i> (Kaup, 1856)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
3755	<i>Phoxocampus tetrophthalmus</i> (Bleeker, 1858)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	

3756	<i>Syngnathoides biaculeatus</i> (Bloch, 1785)	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL, GA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
3757	<i>Trachyrhamphus bicoarctatus</i> (Bleeker, 1857)	M	KL	(Biju et al. 2019)	
3758	<i>Trachyrhamphus serratus</i> (Temminck & Schlegel, 1850)	M	AP, TN, KL, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3759	<i>Trachyrhamphus longirostris</i> Kaup, 1856	M	OD, TN	(Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Order: Stomiiformes					
Family: Gonostomatidae Cocco, 1838					
3760	<i>Cyclothone microdon</i> (Günther, 1878)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
3761	<i>Cyclothone signata</i> Garman, 1899	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
3762	<i>Diplophos taenia</i> Günther, 1873	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3763	<i>Sigmops elongatus</i> (Günther, 1878)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
Family: Phosichthyidae Weitzman, 1974					
3764	<i>Ichthyococcus parini</i> Mukhacheva, 1980	M	LK	(Rajakrishnan et al. 2023)	
3765	<i>Polymetme corythaeola</i> (Alcock, 1898)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Andaman Sea
3766	<i>Vinciguerria lucetia</i> (Garman, 1899)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
3767	<i>Vinciguerria nimbaria</i> (Jordan & Williams, 1895)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
Family: Sternoptychidae Duméril, 1805					
3768	<i>Argyropelecus affinis</i> Garman, 1899	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3769	<i>Argyropelecus sladeni</i> Regan, 1908	M	LK	(Rajakrishnan et al. 2023)	
3770	<i>Polyipnus asper</i> Harold, 1994	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3771	<i>Polyipnus limatulus</i> Harold & Wessel, 1998	M	KL	(Rajakrishnan et al. 2023)	
3772	<i>Polyipnus omphus</i> Baird, 1971	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3773	<i>Polyipnus spinosus</i> Günther, 1887	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3774	<i>Sternoptyx obscura</i> Garman, 1899	M	LK	(Rajakrishnan et al. 2023)	
Family: Stomiidae Bleeker, 1859					
3775	<i>Astronesthes formosana</i> Liao, Chen & Shao, 2006	M	KL	(Rajeev et al. 2022)	Arabian Sea (21°45'N to 10°58' N)
3776	<i>Astronesthes indopacificus</i> Parin & Borodulina, 1997	M	KL	(Rajeev et al. 2022)	Arabian Sea (21°45'N to 10°58' N)
3777	<i>Astronesthes trifibulatus</i> Gibbs, Amaoka & Haruta, 1984	M	KL	(Biju et al. 2019)	
3778	<i>Borostomias elucens</i> (Brauer, 1906)	M	MH	(Rajakrishnan et al. 2023)	

3779	<i>Chauliodus pammelas</i> Alcock, 1892	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Laccadive Sea, 8°49'N, 73°18'45"E
3780	<i>Chauliodus sloani</i> Bloch & Schneider, 1801	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3781	<i>Grammatostomias dentatus</i> Goode & Bean, 1896	M	KL	(Rajakrishnan et al. 2023)	
3782	<i>Malacosteus niger</i> Ayres, 1848	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3783	<i>Melanostomias valdiviae</i> Brauer, 1902	M	LK	(Rajakrishnan et al. 2023)	
3784	<i>Photonectes barnetti</i> Klepadlo, 2011	M	ANI	(Rajakrishnan et al. 2023)	
3785	<i>Photonectes paxtoni</i> Flynn & Klepadlo, 2012	M	LK	(Rajakrishnan et al. 2023)	
3786	<i>Stomias affinis</i> Günther, 1887	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, Rajan et al. 2021)	
3787	<i>Stomias nebulosus</i> Alcock, 1889	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Gulf of Manaar, 6°29'N, 79°34'E
3788	<i>Photostomias atrox</i> (Alcock, 1890)	M	OD	(Pati et al. 2018)	
3789	<i>Photostomias guernei</i> Collett, 1889	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3790	<i>Chauliodus sloani</i> Bloch & Schneider, 1801	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
Order: Synbranchiformes					
Family: Chaudhuriidae Annandale, 1918					
3791	<i>Garo khajuriae</i> (Talwar, Yazdani & Kundu, 1977)	F	AS, ML	(Sen 1985, 1995)	Paddy field at Rongrengiri, Garo Hills District, Meghalaya
3792	<i>Pillaia indica</i> Yazdani, 1972	F	WB, AS, ML	(Arunachalam et al. 2014a, Sen 1985, 1995)	Sumer stream, about 22 kilometers north of Shillong, Khasi & Jaintia Hills, Meghalaya
Family: Mastacembelidae Swainson, 1839					
3793	<i>Macrogathus aculeatus</i> (Bloch, 1786)	F	WB, OD, AP, TN, KA, GJ, UP, MP, CG, BR, AS, TR	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Sen 1985, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Sharma 2007, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Mishra et al. 2021a, Niraj & Singh 2013)	
3794	<i>Macrogathus albus</i> Plamoottil & Abraham, 2014	F	KL	(Plamoottil & Abraham 2014)	Chenappady, Manimala River, Kerala
3795	<i>Macrogathus aral</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	F	WB, OD, TN, KA, MH, DL, TL, BR, JH, ML, AR, MN	(Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar et al. 2012, Tudu et al. 2022, Niraj & Singh 2013)	Tharangambadi, Tamilnadu

3796	<i>Macrogathus caudocellatus</i> (Boulenger, 1893)	F	MN	(Karmakar & Das 2005a)	
3797	<i>Macrogathus fasciatus</i> Plamoottil & Abraham, 2014	F	KL	(Plamoottil & Abraham 2014b)	Karuthavadasseri kvara, Manimala River, Kerala
3798	<i>Macrogathus guentheri</i> (Day, 1865)	F	TN, KL, MH, TL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar et al. 2012)	Cochin, Kerala
3799	<i>Macrogathus lineatamaculatus</i> Britz, 2010	F	WB	(Britz 2010)	Jorau River, a tributary of the Sankosh at Laskapara, Barobisha town outskirts, 26°28'52"N, 89°49'30"E, Jalpaiguri district, West Bengal
3800	<i>Macrogathus malabaricus</i> (Jerdon, 1849)	F	TN, KL	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018)	Malabar
3801	<i>Macrogathus morehensis</i> Arunkumar & Tombi Singh, 2000	F	WB	(Dey et al. 2015)	Maklang River near Moreh Bazar, Chandel district, Manipur
3802	<i>Macrogathus pancalus</i> Hamilton, 1822	BF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KA, MH, GJ, PU, UK, DL, RJ, MP, TL, CG, BR, JH, AS, ML, AR, NL, MN, MZ, TR	(Karmakar & Das 2005, Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Kaur et al. 2017, Tudu et al. 2022, Gunasekar & Isaac 2017, Kar & Sen 2007)	Ganges River drainage
3803	<i>Macrogathus siangensis</i> Arunkumar, 2016	F	AR	(Arunkumar 2016a)	Siang river at Pasighat, East Siang district, Brahmaputra river basin, Arunachal Pradesh
3804	<i>Mastacembelus armatus</i> (Lacepède, 1800)	BF	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ, HP, PU, UK, HY, DL, UP, RJ, MP, TL, CG, BR, JH, SK, AS, ML, AR, MN, MZ,	(Shaji et al. 2019, Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar & Canciyal 2018, Barman 1993, 2002, Bagra et al. 2009, Rema Devi et al. 2013, Husain 1997, Karmakar & Das 2005a, Laxmappa & Bakshi 2016, Karmakar 2006, Raghav & Dixit 2009, Datta & Majumdar 1964, Sharma 2007, Karmakar et al. 2012, Sen & Banerjee 2000, Yadav 2008, Jagtap 2013, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Bhatnagar et al. 2016,	

			TR	Mishra et al. 2021a, Brraich & Saini 2019, Tudu et al. 2022, Kumar et al. 2011, Kar & Sen 2007)	
Family: Synbranchidae Bonaparte, 1835					
3805	<i>Monopterus albus</i> (Zuiew, 1793)	BF	WB, MN	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Karmakar & Das 2005a)	
3806	<i>Monopterus ichthyophoides</i> Britz, Lalremsanga, Lalrotluanga & Lalramliana, 2011	F	MZ	(Britz et al. 2011)	Sawlung River & Barak River drainage in Mizoram
3807	<i>Ophisternon bengalense</i> McClelland, 1844	F	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, SK	(Shaji et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Chanda & Jana 2021, Barman 1993, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Karmakar 2006)	Hooghly river, Bengal
3808	<i>Ophichthys cuchia</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	WB, OD, PU, UK, DL, MP, BR, JH, AS, ML, AR, TR	(Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Bagra et al. 2009, Husain 1997, Barman 2002, Sharma 2007, Uniyal & Uniyal 2021, Kaur et al. 2017, Hembrom & Bodra 2021, Niraj & Singh 2013)	Southeastern Bengal
3809	<i>Ophichthys fossorius</i> (Nair, 1952)	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Karamanai river, Trivandrum, Kerala
3810	<i>Ophichthys hodgarti</i> (Chaudhuri, 1913)	F	AS	(Chaudhuri 1913)	Upper Rotung, Abor Hills, Assam
3811	<i>Ophichthys ichthyophoides</i> (Britz, Lalremsanga, Lalrotluanga & Lalramliana, 2011)	F	MZ	(Britz et al. 2011)	Sawlung River, a tributary of Tuirial River in the vicinity of Sawlung, 23°58'52"N, 92°55'14"E, Barak River drainage, Mizoram
3812	<i>Ophichthys indicus</i> (Silas & Dawson, 1961)	F	MH	(Silas & Dawson 1961)	Robbers Cave, Satara District, Maharashtra State
3813	<i>Ophichthys terricolus</i> Britz, Standing, Gower & Kamei, 2023	F	AS	(Britz et al. 2023)	Merua Grant Village, Prakashpur Division, Bajrangpur Tea Estate, Silchar, Cachar District
3814	<i>Rakthamichthys digressus</i> (Gopi, 2002)	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Calicut, Kerala, India
3815	<i>Rakthamichthys indicus</i> (Eapen, 1963)	F	KL, MH	(Karmakar et al. 2012)	Kottayam, Kerala

3816	<i>Rakthamichthys mumba</i> Praveenraj, Thackeray, Mohapatra & Pavan-Kumar, 2021	F	MH	(Praveenraj et al. 2021a)	industrial home for the Blind, S V Road, Jogeshwari West, Mumbai City, Maharashtra
3817	<i>Rakthamichthys rongsaw</i> (Britz, Sykes, Gower & Kamei, 2018)	F	ML	(Britz et al. 2018)	Nongriat Village, Khasi Hills, Meghalaya
3818	<i>Rakthamichthys roseni</i> (Bailey & Gans, 1998)	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	From a well, Periyam village, Kerala
Order: Tetraodontiformes					
Family: Balistidae Rafinesque, 1810					
3819	<i>Abalistes stellatus</i> (Anonymous, 1798)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Ray & Mohapatra 2022b, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a, Biju et al. 2019)	
3820	<i>Balistapus undulatus</i> (Park, 1797)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, TN, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Ray & Mohapatra 2022b, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
3821	<i>Balistes vetula</i> Linnaeus, 1758	M	AP	(Padmavathi et al. 2017a)	
3822	<i>Balistoides conspicillum</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3823	<i>Balistoides viridescens</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	M	ANI, LK, WB, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Ray & Mohapatra 2022b, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3824	<i>Canthidermis maculata</i> (Bloch, 1786)	M	ANI, WB, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Ray & Mohapatra 2022b, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Devi et al. 2023a)	Tharangambadi
3825	<i>Canthidermis rotundata</i> (Marion de Procé, 1822)	M	LK, WB, TN, MH	(Rajan et al. 2021, Yennawar et al. 2015, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
3826	<i>Melichthys indicus</i> Randall & Klausewitz, 1973	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
3827	<i>Melichthys niger</i> (Bloch, 1786)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3828	<i>Melichthys vidua</i> (Richardson, 1845)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3829	<i>Odonus niger</i> (Rüppell, 1836)	M	ANI, LK, WB, AP, TN, KL, GA	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Ray & Mohapatra 2022b, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Hedge et al. 2013)	
3830	<i>Pseudobalistes flavimarginatus</i> (Rüppell, 1829)	MB	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3831	<i>Pseudobalistes fuscus</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3832	<i>Rhinecanthus aculeatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	M	ANI, LK, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019)	
3833	<i>Rhinecanthus rectangulus</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3834	<i>Rhinecanthus</i>	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	India

	<i>verrucosus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)				
3835	<i>Sufflamen bursa</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3836	<i>Sufflamen chrysopterum</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Devi et al. 2023a, Padmavathi et al. 2017a)	Coromandel Coast
3837	<i>Sufflamen fraenatum</i> (Latreille, 1804)	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Ray & Mohapatra 2022b, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Mohanty et al. 2024)	
3838	<i>Xanthichthys lineopunctatus</i> (Hollard, 1854)	M	AP, TN, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3839	<i>Xanthichthys mento</i> (Jordan & Gilbert, 1882)	M	ANI	(Patankar et al. 2018)	
3840	<i>Xanthichthys ringens</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Diodontidae Bonaparte, 1835					
3841	<i>Cylichthys orbicularis</i> (Bloch, 1785)	M	OD, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	
3842	<i>Cylichthys spilostylus</i> (Leis & Randall, 1982)	M	AP, TN	(Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3843	<i>Chilomycterus reticulatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	M	ANI, LK	(Sandra et al. 2022, Patankar et al. 2018)	
3844	<i>Diodon holocanthus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	India
3845	<i>Diodon hystrix</i> Linnaeus, 1758	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, 2013a, Hedge et al. 2013)	India
3846	<i>Diodon liturosus</i> Shaw, 1804	M	ANI, LK, WB	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Sanyal et al. 2012)	
3847	<i>Lophodiodon calori</i> (Bianconi, 1854)	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3848	<i>Tragulichthys jaculiferus</i> (Cuvier, 1818)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Molidae Bonaparte, 1835					
3849	<i>Masturus lanceolatus</i> (Liénard, 1840)	M	TN, MH	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
3850	<i>Mola alexandrini</i> (Ranzani, 1834)	M	KL	(Devi et al. 2023a)	
3851	<i>Mola mola</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	M	ANI, WB, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Ray et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3852	<i>Ranzania laevis</i> (Pennant, 1776)	M	WB, TN, KL, MH	(Biju et al. 2019, Sanyal et al. 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	
Family: Monacanthidae Nardo, 1843					
3853	<i>Acanthaluteres spilomelanurus</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1824)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3854	<i>Acreichthys hajam</i> (Bleeker, 1851)	M	GA	(Hedge et al. 2013)	
3855	<i>Acreichthys</i>	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	

	<i>tomentosus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)				
3856	<i>Aluterus monoceros</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	M	ANI, WB, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawaret al. 2017, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	
3857	<i>Aluterus scriptus</i> (Osbeck, 1765)	M	ANI, LK, AP, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3858	<i>Amanses scopas</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3859	<i>Anacanthus barbatus</i> Gray, 1830	M	ANI, LK, OD, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3860	<i>Cantherhines dumerilii</i> (Hollard, 1854)	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3861	<i>Cantherhines fronticinctus</i> (Günther, 1867)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3862	<i>Cantherhines pardalis</i> (Rüppell, 1837)	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3863	<i>Cantherhines sandwichiensis</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1824)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
3864	<i>Cantherhines verecundus</i> Jordan, 1925	MB	ANI	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010)	
3865	<i>Chaetodermis penicilligerus</i> (Cuvier 1816)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3866	<i>Lalmohania velutina</i> Hutchins, 1994	M	AP, TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018, Padmavathi et al. 2017a)	Kilakkarai, about 9°16'N, 78°48'E, Gulf of Mannar
3867	<i>Monacanthus chinensis</i> (Osbeck, 1765)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3868	<i>Oxymonacanthus longirostris</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3869	<i>Paraluteres arqat</i> Clark & Gohar, 1953	M	ANI	(Patankar et al. 2018)	
3870	<i>Paraluteres prionurus</i> (Bleeker, 1851)	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3871	<i>Paramonacanthus choirocephalus</i> (Bleeker, 1851)	M	ANI, LK, OD, AP, TN, GA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, Talwar 1974, Padmavathi et al. 2017a)	
3872	<i>Paramonacanthus curtiorhynchus</i> (Bleeker, 1855)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3873	<i>Paramonacanthus frenatus</i> (Peters, 1855)	M	TN, KL, GJ	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Sureandiran 2024)	
3874	<i>Paramonacanthus japonicus</i> (Tilesius, 1809)	M	ANI, AP, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Padmavathi et al. 2017a)	
3875	<i>Paramonacanthus nematophorus</i> (Günther, 1870)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3876	<i>Paramonacanthus oblongus</i> (Temminck & Schlegel, 1850)	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3877	<i>Paramonacanthus pusillus</i> (Rüppell, 1829)	M	ANI, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Padmavathi et al. 2017)	

3878	<i>Paramonacanthus sulcatus</i> (Hollard, 1854)	M	Pondicherry	(Mary et al. 2021)	
3879	<i>Paramonacanthus tricuspis</i> (Hollard, 1854)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3880	<i>Pervagor melanocephalus</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	M	ANI, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Devi et al. 2023a)	
3881	<i>Pseudalutarius nasicornis</i> (Temminck & Schlegel, 1850)	M	TN	(Padate et al. 2017)	
3882	<i>Pseudomonacanthus peroni</i> (Hollard, 1854)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3883	<i>Stephanolepis aurata</i> (Castelnau, 1861)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3884	<i>Stephanolepis diaspros</i> Fraser-Brunner, 1940	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3885	<i>Thamnaconus modestoides</i> (Barnard, 1927)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3886	<i>Thamnaconus multilineatus</i> (Tanaka, 1918)	M	ANI	(Nashad et al. 2023)	
3887	<i>Thamnaconus striatus</i> (Kotthaus, 1979)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Ostraciidae Rafinesque, 1810					
3888	<i>Lactoria cornuta</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	MB	ANI, LK, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a, Hedge et al. 2013)	India
3889	<i>Lactoria fornasini</i> (Bianconi, 1846)	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3890	<i>Ostracion cubicum</i> Linnaeus, 1758	M	ANI, LK, WB, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	India
3891	<i>Ostracion meleagris</i> Shaw, 1796	M	ANI, LK, TN, KA	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2013a)	
3892	<i>Ostracion rhinorhynchos</i> Bleeker, 1851	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3893	<i>Ostracion nasus</i> Bloch, 1785	M	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Danda et al. 2017, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3894	<i>Tetrosomus concatenatus</i> (Bloch, 1785)	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3895	<i>Tetrosomus gibbosus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	M	ANI, OD, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2012, 2013a)	India
3896	<i>Tetrosomus reipublicae</i> (Whitley, 1930)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
Family: Tetraodontidae Bonaparte, 1831					
3897	<i>Amblyrhynchote honckenii</i> (Bloch, 1785)	MB	GA	(Talwar 1974)	
3898	<i>Arothron hispidus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2021, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	India
3899	<i>Arothron immaculatus</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, TN, KL, GA	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Hedge et al. 2013)	

3900	<i>Arothron mappa</i> (Lesson, 1831)	M	ANI, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3901	<i>Arothron meleagris</i> (Anonymous, 1798)	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3902	<i>Arothron nigropunctatus</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	M	ANI, LK, WB, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Tharangambadi
3903	<i>Arothron reticularis</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	MB	ANI, OD, AP, TN, KL, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Malabar sea
3904	<i>Arothron stellatus</i> (Anonymous, 1798)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Danda et al. 2017, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3905	<i>Canthigaster amboinensis</i> (Bleeker, 1864)	M	ANI, LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Patankar et al. 2018)	
3906	<i>Canthigaster bennetti</i> (Bleeker, 1854)	M	ANI, LK, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3907	<i>Canthigaster coronata</i> (Vaillant & Sauvage, 1875)	M	ANI, KL	(Ramakrishna et al. 2010, Biju et al. 2019)	
3908	<i>Canthigaster cyanospilota</i> Randall, Williams & Rocha, 2008	M	ANI, LK	(Kapoor et al. 2002)	
3909	<i>Canthigaster investigatoris</i> (Annandale & Jenkins, 1910)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Andaman Islands, 11°49'30"N, 92°55'E
3910	<i>Canthigaster janthinoptera</i> (Bleeker, 1855)	M	LK	(Rajan et al. 2021)	
3911	<i>Canthigaster margaritata</i> (Rüppell, 1829)	M	LK, OD, AP, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3912	<i>Canthigaster papua</i> (Bleeker, 1848)	M	ANI, AP	(Rajan et al. 2013, Kumar et al. 2024)	
3913	<i>Canthigaster petersii</i> (Bianconi, 1854)	M	ANI, LK, KL	(Rajan et al. 2021, Devi et al. 2023a, Patankar et al. 2018)	
3914	<i>Canthigaster solandri</i> (Richardson, 1845)	M	ANI, AP, TN	(Rajan et al. 2013, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Biswas et al. 2012)	
3915	<i>Canthigaster smithae</i> Allen & Randall, 1977	M	ANI	(Mishra et al. 2019)	
3916	<i>Canthigaster valentini</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	M	ANI, LK	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021)	
3917	<i>Carinotetraodon imitator</i> Britz & Kottelat, 1999	F	KL	(Shaji et al. 2019)	Cochin District, in small rivers
3918	<i>Carinotetraodon travancoricus</i> (Hora & Nair, 1941)	F	KL, KA	(Shaji et al. 2019, Rema Devi et al. 2013)	Pamba river, central Travancore, Kerala
3919	<i>Chelonodontops patoca</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	MBF	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, GA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Silambarasan et al. 2022, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, Talwar 1974)	Ganges River estuaries
3920	<i>Chelonodontops bengalensis</i> Habib, Neogi, Oh,	M	WB, OD	(Mohapatra et al. 2020b, Roul et al. 2022a)	

	Lee & Kim, 2018				
3921	<i>Chelonodontops leopardus</i> (Day, 1878)	MB	TN, KL, KA	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Chakraborty et al. 2020a)	Seas of India
3922	<i>Dichotomyctere fluviatilis</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	ANI, WB, OD, TN, KL, GA, MH, UP, BR	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Dubey et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, Hedge et al. 2013, Kumar et al. 2011)	Ganges River at Allahabad, Uttar Pradesh
3923	<i>Lagocephalus cheesemanii</i> (Clarke, 1897)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3924	<i>Lagocephalus guentheri</i> Miranda Ribeiro, 1915	M	ANI, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3925	<i>Lagocephalus inermis</i> (Temminck & Schlegel, 1850)	M	ANI, WB, OD, TN, KL, KA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, 2013a)	
3926	<i>Lagocephalus lagocephalus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	M	LK, OD, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Mohanty et al. 2021d)	India
3927	<i>Lagocephalus lunaris</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	M	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	Tharangambadi
3928	<i>Lagocephalus sceleratus</i> (Gmelin, 1789)	M	ANI, LK, WB, TN, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Yennawar et al. 2015, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3929	<i>Lagocephalus spadiceus</i> (Richardson, 1845)	M	WB, OD, TN, KA, GA, MH	(Chakraborty et al. 2020a, Pati et al. 2018, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, 2013a, Talwar 1974)	
3930	<i>Lagocephalus suezensis</i> Clark, & Gohar 1953	M	TN	(Padate et al. 2017)	
3931	<i>Leiodon cutcutia</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	BF	WB, OD, TN, MH, BR, AS, ML, AR, TR	(Dubey et al. 2015, Sen 1985, 1995, Chanda & Jana 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Bagra et al. 2009, Barman 2002, Barman et al. 2012, Murugan & Prabakaran 2012)	Ganges River
3932	<i>Leiodon viridipunctatus</i> Day, 1865	M	OD	(Pati et al. 2018)	Cochin
3933	<i>Pao palembangensis</i> (Bleeker, 1851)	F	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
3934	<i>Sphoeroides pachygaster</i> (Müller & Troschel, 1848)	M	KL	(Ramachandran et al. 2022)	
3935	<i>Takifugu oblongus</i> (Bloch, 1786)	MB	WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, GA, MH	(Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2004, 2012, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Hedge et al. 2013)	Coromandel
3936	<i>Torquigener brevipinnis</i> (Regan, 1903)	M	ANI, OD, AP, KL	(Silambarasan et al. 2022, Devi et al. 2023a, Nashad et al. 2023, Mohanty et al. 2024)	
3937	<i>Torquigener florealis</i> (Cope, 1871)	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3938	<i>Torquigener hypselogeneion</i> (Bleeker, 1852)	MB	ANI, LK, TN, MH	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012)	

3939	<i>Tylerius spinosissimus</i> (Regan, 1908)	MB	AP	(Anonymous 2003)	
Family: Triacanthidae Bleeker, 1859					
3940	<i>Pseudotriacanthus strigilifer</i> (Cantor, 1849)	MB	ANI, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, GA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Talwar 1974)	
3941	<i>Triacanthus biaculeatus</i> (Bloch, 1786)	MB	ANI, LK, WB, OD, AP, TN, KL, KA, MH, GJ	(Rajan et al. 2013, 2021, Biju et al. 2019, Mishra et al. 2017, Pati et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2000, 2004, 2012, 2013a, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3942	<i>Triacanthus nieuhoftii</i> Bleeker, 1852	M	LK, WB, TN, GA, MH	(Rajan et al. 2021, Sen et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Hedge et al. 2013, Shivakrishna et al. 2021)	
3943	<i>Tripodichthys blochii</i> (Bleeker, 1852)	MB	GA	(Talwar 1974)	
3944	<i>Tripodichthys oxycephalus</i> (Bleeker, 1851)	M	OD	(Pati et al. 2018)	
3945	<i>Triphichthys weberi</i> (Chaudhuri, 1910)	M	WB, OD	(Sanyal et al. 2012, Pati et al. 2018)	Gopalur, Orissa
Family: Triacanthodidae Gill, 1862					
3946	<i>Halimochirurgus alcocki</i> Weber, 1913	M	KL	(Devi et al. 2023a)	
3947	<i>Halimochirurgus centriscooides</i> Alcock, 1899	M	TN, KL	(Devi et al. 2023a)	
3948	<i>Macrorhamphosodes platycheilus</i> Fowler, 1934	M	ANI, KL	(Rajan et al. 2013, Biju et al. 2019)	
3949	<i>Mephisto fraserbrunneri</i> Tyler, 1966	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	Bay of Bengal, 10°39'N, 97°06'E
3950	<i>Paratriacanthodes retrospinis</i> Fowler, 1934	M	ANI, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Mullasserri et al. 2017)	
3951	<i>Triacanthodes ethiops</i> Alcock, 1894	M	LK, TN	(Rajan et al. 2021, Mogalekar et al. 2018)	Bay of Bengal, 13°51'12"N, 80°12'12"E
Order: Trachichthyiformes					
Family: Diretmidae Gill, 1893					
3952	<i>Diretmichthys parini</i> (Post & Quéro, 1981)	M	KL	(Ramachandran et al. 20210)	
Family: Monocentridae Gill, 1859					
3953	<i>Monocentris japonica</i> (Houttuyn, 1782)	M	ANI	(Rajan et al. 2013)	
Family: Trachichthyidae Bleeker, 1856					
3954	<i>Gephyroberyx darwinii</i> (Johnson, 1866)	M	LK, KL	(Biju et al. 2019, Kar et al. 2023)	
3955	<i>Hoplostethus mediterraneus</i> Cuvier, 1829	M	TN	(Mogalekar et al. 2018)	
3956	<i>Hoplostethus melanopus</i> (Weber, 1913)	M	TN, KL	(Vinu et al. 2017)	
3957	<i>Hoplostethus rubellopterus</i> Kotlyar, 1980	M	ANI, AP, TN, KL, KA	(Vinu et al. 2017)	
Order: Zeiformes					
Family: Parazenidae McAllister, 1968					
3958	<i>Cyttopsis rosea</i> (Lowe, 1843)	M	LK, KL,	(Rajan et al. 2021, Biju et al. 2019,	

			KA, MH	Barman et al. 2012, 2013a)	
Family: Zeidae Rafinesque, 1815					
3959	<i>Zenopsis conchifer</i> (Lowe, 1852)	M	TN, KL, KA, MH	(Biju et al. 2019, Mogalekar et al. 2018, Barman et al. 2012, 2013a)	
3960	<i>Zenopsis nebulosa</i> (Temminck & Schlegel, 1845)	M	Coasts of India	(Kapoor et al. 2002)	
Family: Zeniontidae Myers, 1960					
3961	<i>Zenion hololepis</i> (Goode & Bean, 1896)	M	ANI	(Rufus et al. 2021)	

Sl No	Species Name	Habitat	Distribution	Reference	Type Locality
3962	<i>Entomacrodus thalassinus</i> (Jordan & Seale, 1906) Family: Blenniidae	M	AP	(Kumar et al. 2024)	
3963	<i>Ophichthus suryai</i> Behera, Acharya, Mishra & Mohapatra, 2024 Family: Ophichthidae	B	OD	(Behera et al. 2024b)	Three different estuarine ecosystems in Odisha
3964	<i>Ariosoma Thoothukudiense</i> Kodeeswaran, Kathirvelpandian, Mohapatra & Kumar, 2024 Family: Congridae	M	TN	(Kodeeswaran et al. 2024b)	From trawl by-catch landings at Thoothukudi, Tamilnadu
3965	<i>Acentrogobius vanderloosi</i> Allen, 2015 Family: Gobiidae	M	TN	(Ragul et al. 2024b)	
3966	<i>Creteuchiloglanis nuthemuensis</i> Sarkar, Tenali, Chandran & Singh, 2024 Family: Sisoridae	F	AR	(Sarkar et al. 2024)	Duphlokho River in West Kameng district, Arunachal Pradesh
3967	<i>Opsarius siangi</i> Kumari, Borah, Nair & Suresh, 2024 Family: Danionidae	F	AR	(Kumari et al. 2024)	Siang River, Pasighat, Arunachal Pradesh